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D3.2 ENTRUST Risk Assessment & Collective Threat Intelligence Framework – Initial Release

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Abstract	<p>Towards providing operational assurance to organizations belonging to the medical domain, ENTRUST aims to ensure that the trustworthiness level of Connected Medical Devices (CMDs) remains at an acceptable level throughout their operational lifecycle. In this regard, this deliverable is dedicated to the detailed description of all components participating in the Trust Assessment process of ENTRUST throughout all three core phases of the ENTRUST action workflow, i.e., the Manufacturing Phase, the Pre-deployment Phase, and the Runtime Phase. First, we focus on the Formal Verification component, which is responsible for formally verifying the security processes of ENTRUST. Next, we describe the Threat Modeling and Software Verification component, which aggregates information from existing databases and formulates the attack vector for the device. This is forwarded to the Risk Assessment component, which evaluates the risk level for the device and calculates its Required Trust Level (RTL). We then describe the Trust Assessment Framework of ENTRUST (TAF) which is able to evaluate the Actual Trust Level (ATL) of the device. Next, the Digital Twin (DT) is able to emulate any incidents that led to a failed attestation process and identify new threats or vulnerabilities. The Secure Software Update module is then able to securely deploy updates as mitigation measures to patch such vulnerabilities. This document positions all aforementioned components within the overall ENTRUST framework and documents all interactions between them.</p>		
Keywords	Connected Medical Devices, Threat Modelling, Trust Assessment, Formal Verification, Risk Assessment, Digital Twin, Secure Software Update, Manufacturer Usage Description, Conformity Certificate, Trust Assessment		

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- * R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
- DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
- DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
- OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.
- DMP: Data Management Plan

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Term	Description
AAA	Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting
ABAC	Attribute-based Access Control
ABE	Attribute-based Encryption
ABS	Attribute-based Signatures
ACL	Access Control List
AK	Attestation Key
AOO	Actions on Objectives
APT	Advanced Persistent Threat
ATL	Actual Level of Trust
ATL	Actual Level of Trust
ATT&CK	Adversarial Tactics, techniques & Common Knowledge
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
C2	Command and Control
CA	Certification Authority
CEGAR	Counterexample-Guided Abstraction Refinement
CFA	Control-Flow Attestation
CIV	Code Integrity Validation
CMD	Connected Medical Device
CPSs	Cyber-Physical Systems
CVE	Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures
DDoS	Distributed Denial-of-Service attacks
DDRV	Distributed and Decentralized Runtime Verification
DFG	Data Flow Diagram
DID	Domain Identifier
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DoS	Denial of Service
DT	Digital Twin
EMTs	Emergency Medical Technicians
ENISA	European Network and Information Security Agency
FES	Feel Emotion Sensor
FL	Federated Learning
FV	Formal Verification
FW	Firmware
HDOs	Healthcare Delivery Organizations
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
HRV	Hardware-supported Runtime Verification
ICT	Information and Communications Technology

IDS	Intrusion Detection System
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IoC	Indicator of Compromise
IoT	Internet of Things
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LTL	Linear Temporal Logic
MD	Medical Device
MDR	Medical Devices Regulation
MDSW	Medical Device Software
mHealth	Mobile health
MISP	Malware Information Sharing Platform
MITM	Man-In-The-Middle
ML	Machine Learning
MUD	Manufacturer Usage Descriptions
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
OSN	Online Social Networks
PACS	Picture Archiving and Communication System
PHG	Tellu Personal Health Gateway
PMS	Patient Monitoring Systems
PUF	Physical Unclonable Function
QMS	Quality Management System
QoS	Quality of Service
RA	Risk Assessment
ReLU	Rectified Linear Unit
RoT	Root-of-Trust
RPMS	Remote Patient Monitoring Systems
RTL	Required Level of Trustworthiness
SA	Static Analysis
SBOM	Software Bill of Material
SDL	Secure Development Lifecycle
SL	Subjective Logic
SMT	Satisfiability Modulo Theories
SoS	System of Systems
SPLC	Secure Product Life Cycle
SSI	Self-Sovereign Identity
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
STRIDE	Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Denial of Service and Elevation of Privilege
SUT	System Under Test
SW	Software

SWaP	Size, Weight, and Power
TAR	Trust Assessment Request
TARA	Threat Agent Risk Assessment
TC	Trusted Component
TDE	Trust Decision Engine
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TI	Threat Intelligence
TLEE	Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine
TM	Threat Modelling
TMM	Trust Model Manager
TOE	Target of Evaluation
TSM	Trust Sources Manager
TTP	Tactics, Techniques and Procedures
UID	Unique Initial Identification
UML	Unified Modelling Language
VC	Verifiable Credential
VP	Verifiable Presentation
YANG	Yet Another Next Generation

Executive Summary

One of the core tenets of ENTRUST is the design and implementation of a complete security framework that provides operational assurance to **Connected Medical Devices (CMDs)**, in order to ensure that they are in a trustworthy state throughout their operational lifecycle. The end goal of this approach is *to enhance the capability of medical organizations to provide reliable healthcare services by ensuring that the trustworthiness of the CMDs, as well as the domain infrastructure as a whole, remain at a satisfactory level*. Thus, the ENTRUST framework covers the entire lifecycle of medical devices, including (i) the **Manufacturing (Design) Phase**, which includes all actions performed at the side of the Manufacturer before its deployment to the target medical domain, (ii) the **Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase**, which includes all actions performed after the deployment of the device to the medical domain before its actual operation, and (iii) the **Runtime Phase**, which entails all actions performed during the normal operation of the device. In this context, ENTRUST provides a **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)**, which aims to ensure that CMDs are at a trustworthy state throughout their operational lifecycle. In this deliverable, we provide details on the design and implementation of all components participating in the Trust Assessment process, as well as their positioning within the overall ENTRUST framework, and we expand upon the initial descriptions of these components provided in D3.1 [26].

The **Formal Verification** component, which is analyzed in Chapter 3, utilizes state-of-the-art security protocol verification tools in order to ensure that the security protocols implemented and executed as part of the ENTRUST framework fulfil all **security requirements**, both at a device level and at a domain level. These requirements may be defined either by the Manufacturer during the Manufacturing (Design) Phase, or by the security administrator of the medical domain where the device is deployed during the Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase. Note that this component aims to verify the correctness of security processes, while the verification of the correctness of properties (trust attributes) is the responsibility of the remote attestation schemes of ENTRUST, described in detail in D4.2 [27]. Thus, this component aims to monitor and attest only those properties that cannot be attested during runtime. In the context of the Trust Assessment process of ENTRUST, the Formal Verification component may provide information to the TAF in case the aforementioned requirements cannot be fulfilled.

The **Threat Modeling** component, which is described in detail in Chapter 4, aims to collect information regarding the threats and vulnerabilities associated with the considered type of device, and utilizes **generative AI** and **fuzzing methods** in order to provide a comprehensive description of the threat landscape that needs to be considered in the context of the Trust Assessment process of the device. The use of AI-based techniques presents a variety of advantages in this regard, such as the capability to consume diverse types of data, to process and unify large amounts of data, to produce context-aware text in a readable format, and to identify possible attack scenarios. The information generated by this component is provided to the **Risk Assessment** component which, as analyzed in detail in Chapter 5, is responsible for performing a risk analysis based on the identified threats and vulnerabilities in order to calculate the **Required Trust Level (RTL)** of the device. Note that this is initially performed during the Manufacturing (Design) Phase considering the device in isolation, and is updated after its deployment to the medical organization by considering domain-specific threats. In addition, the identified threats, as well as the appropriate mitigation measures, are contained in the **extended Manufacturer Usage Description**

(eMUD) files of the device, analyzed in detail in Chapter 6. Note that, in the context of ENTRUST, we define both a Device-level Manufacturer Usage Description (eMUD) and a Domain-level extended Manufacturer Usage Description (eMUD), which consider the device in isolation and as part of the (Medical) Domain, respectively.

In Chapter 9, we outline the **Digital Twin (DT)** component of ENTRUST, which aims to create a digital representation of a CMD in order to mirror its real-time dynamics within a controlled environment, thus enabling the emulation of potential attacks targeting the device in a safe and controlled manner, leading to the identification of **new threats and zero-day vulnerabilities**. In addition, the Digital Twin provides the basis for the **Secure Software/Firmware Update** mechanisms of ENTRUST, analyzed in Chapter 10. Specifically, in case any threat or vulnerability is identified by the Digital Twin, it is possible to deploy a software or firmware update in a secure manner, in order to address and mitigate the identified issue. Thus, ENTRUST follows a **reactive approach** with regard to the update process, which is triggered in case of an **Indication of Risk** that points towards a change in the trustworthiness level of the device.

All aforementioned components participate in the **Trust Assessment** process of ENTRUST, which aims to verify whether the device is in a trustworthy state or not. The component responsible for handling this process is the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)**, which is analyzed in Chapter 7 and aims to calculate the **Actual Trust Level (ATL)** of the device based on the available **trustworthiness evidence**, collected in the context of attestation processes for attesting to the correctness of a set of specified **trust properties**. The ATL is then compared to the **Required Trust Level (RTL)** of the device, which is calculated by the Risk Assessment component based on the identified threats and vulnerabilities for the specific type of device.

Throughout this deliverable, we provide details regarding the design and implementation of all aforementioned components, as well as their positioning within the overall ENTRUST framework. We also provide a detailed overview of the action workflow of the entire ENTRUST framework, with particular focus on the Trust Assessment process.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

One core target of ENTRUST is the implementation of a holistic security framework for enabling medical organizations to ensure the secure, reliable, and uninterrupted provision of medical services. In this regard, ENTRUST needs to provide mechanisms to ensure that the **Connected Medical Devices (CMDs)** belonging to the medical domain, as well as the system infrastructure as a whole, remain at an acceptable **trustworthiness level**. Thus, we need to consider that the types of medical organizations targeted by ENTRUST may be distributed and cooperative, and the different entities belonging to such systems may depend on the correct provisioning of services or input data from other system entities. Such dependencies constitute **Trust Relationships**, wherein a **trustor** needs to rely on a **trustee** in order to ensure the reliable provision of medical services. Based on the **zero-trust paradigm**, this trust cannot be assumed by default, but instead needs to be based on **trustworthiness evidence and analysis**. This deliverable is dedicated to the design and implementation of all components of the ENTRUST framework that participate in the **Trust Assessment** process, as well as their role and positioning within the overall framework.

As previously outlined in D3.1 [26], for ensuring that the trustworthiness level of a CMD remains at an acceptable level throughout its operational lifecycle, ENTRUST follows a Trust Assessment approach that entails the calculation of its **Required Trust Level (RTL)** based on the information available for this type of device, such as the identified threats and vulnerabilities, as well as the likelihood and impact associated with each of them. Then, during runtime, the **Actual Trust Level (ATL)** of the device is calculated by the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)** of ENTRUST based on **trustworthiness evidence**, collected by the available tracing mechanisms of the device (described in D5.1 [28]) in order to attest to the correctness of a set of **trustworthiness properties** of the device. Then, a **Trust Decision** is made depending on whether the ATL exceeds the RTL. If yes, the device is considered trustworthy. Otherwise, mitigation measures may need to be applied for addressing any identified vulnerabilities (e.g., in the form of a **secure update**).

Recall that, as outlined throughout several deliverables, the action workflow of ENTRUST covers the entire lifecycle of the medical device, beginning from its initial conception by the Manufacturer and including all stages of its actual operation. Specifically, the action workflow of ENTRUST can be split into three distinct phases: (i) the **Manufacturing (Design) Phase**, which include all actions taken at the side of the device Manufacturer until the device leaves the manufacturing floor, (ii) the **Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase**, which includes actions taken at the side of the medical domain before the actual operation of the device within the domain infrastructure, and (iii) the **Runtime Phase**, which includes all actions taken during the normal operation of the device. In this regard, **the Trust Assessment process entails a variety of actions that take place in all three phases of the ENTRUST action workflow**, and pertain to various aspects of the calculation of the RTL and ATL, as well as the identification of the appropriate mitigation measures in case the device is found to be in an untrustworthy state.

Specifically, during the **Manufacturing (Design) Phase**, after the initial conceptualization and implementation of the medical device, the Manufacturer specifies an initial set of known threats and vulnerabilities, as well as known mitigation measures to address them. In addition, the **Threat Modeling** component (Chapter 4) is responsible for gathering known threats and vulnerabilities for the specific type of device from online databases, such as the **NIST National Vulnerability Database (NVD)** and the **MITRE Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE)**, and uses a Large Language Model (LLM) approach for their aggregation and processing. The **Formal Verification** component (Chapter 3) mathematically verifies the software stack of the device in order to ensure that the requirements set forth by the Manufacturer are fulfilled, and in case this is unsuccessful, any identified threats or vulnerabilities are forwarded to the Threat Modeling component. Based on all the above, the **Risk Assessment** component (Chapter 5) performs an initial calculation of the RTL of the device. In addition, the **Device-level MUD** is constructed (Chapter 6), containing information that can be used in order to execute the specified security (attestation) measures for addressing the identified vulnerabilities.

During the **Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase**, the device is connected to the infrastructure of the domain where it is intended to operate, and is henceforth referred to as a **Connected Medical Device (CMD)**. During this phase, the device is **authenticated, onboarded, and enrolled** into the domain, following processes which are detailed in D4.2 [27]. In the context of the Trust Assessment process, this phase entails **updating the RTL of the device** based on domain-specific information. Specifically, the Risk Assessment component updates the risk calculation for the CMD considering interdependencies with other entities. The Formal Verification component is also able to perform an updated verification process considering domain-specific requirements as constraints, and potentially identify new vulnerabilities based on these new requirements. In addition, the Digital Twin emulates the domain-specific threats, which may have been identified by the System Administrator. Finally, a **Domain-level eMUD** is created for the CMD as an extension of the Device-level MUD, containing the domain-specific threat vector, associated with the appropriate mitigation measures.

The **Runtime Phase** entails the normal operation of the CMD as part of the (Medical) Domain, as well as all actions taken by the ENTRUST framework in order to ensure that its trustworthiness level remains at an acceptable level. Specifically, the ENTRUST framework provides a set of **Remote Attestation (RA)** schemes (described in D4.2 [27]), whose execution requires the collection of **trust evidence** on a set of **trust properties**, leveraging the tracing capabilities of the CMD. This evidence is forwarded to the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)** of ENTRUST (Chapter 7), which uses it in order to calculate the ATL of the device. If the ATL exceeds the RTL, the device is considered to be trustworthy. Otherwise, this constitutes an **Indication of Risk** that signifies the need for further action. Specifically, the **Digital Twin** receives the trust evidence (traces) in order to emulate the attack that led to the failed attestation, and the **Secure Software/Firmware Update** component (Chapter 10) is responsible for deploying an update or patch in a secure manner, in order to mitigate any identified vulnerabilities.

Throughout the remainder of this deliverable, we will expand upon all aforementioned components, their design and their implementation, as well as their positioning and role within the ENTRUST framework. In Chapter 2, we first provide a comprehensive high-level overview of the entire action workflow of the ENTRUST framework focused on these components, and in each subsequent Chapter we focus on each component, building upon the initial descriptions provided in D3.1 [26].

1.1 Towards Defining Trustworthiness Claims and Policies

As previously outlined, the components and methodologies described in this deliverable are centered around the **Trust Assessment** process of ENTRUST and formulate a holistic action workflow that aims

to evaluate the level of *trustworthiness* of a CMD belonging to a medical domain. In this context, trustworthiness is defined as *the degree of confidence users can have that a system performs as expected*. This definition is in accordance with the ISO/IEC 30141:2018 international standard [65], whose scope includes the definition of a universal IoT Reference Architecture, and provides the basis for the definition of a **conceptual model of trustworthiness** for conveying the abstractions that need to be expressed through the Trust Assessment process of ENTRUST.

In order to identify the trust abstractions that need to be modelled in the context of ENTRUST, we first need to identify the aspects that impact the **level of trust**, which is evaluated based on the appropriate set of **trustworthiness evidence**. Therefore, we need to build upon the aforementioned definition of trustworthiness in order to identify the **trust objectives** that need to be achieved through the available evidence. These objectives can be defined through the following set of questions that need to be answered by the Trust Assessment process adopted by ENTRUST:

- **What needs to be done about trust?** This means that we need to identify the trust properties that need to be evaluated through the collected trustworthiness evidence. Note that the attestation enablers offered by ENTRUST are able to verify the *integrity* of the specified trust properties, but the Trust Assessment approach of ENTRUST aims to go beyond this, and offer a Trust Assessment framework that is able to consider different types of properties, as outlined in Section 7.1.4. These may include *accountability, trust evidence privacy, reliability, accuracy, usability*, and other properties that may be relevant for the medical domain. This question also entails the identification of the **security controls** that need to be deployed for the collection and extraction of the trustworthiness evidence, based on which the ENTRUST TAF will evaluate the aforementioned properties.
- **Where is the security control required?** In this regard, we need to identify the entities where a trust decision needs to be made, and to express the types of security controls to be deployed in these entities, as well as their positioning within the entire ENTRUST ecosystem. This is dependent on the type of medical organization where the CMD is operating, which is represented in the context of ENTRUST by four different use case demonstrators. For instance, in the *Tellu Remote Patient Monitoring* use case, the Tellu PHG gateway device may wish to verify the integrity of one or more of the connected medical sensor devices, in order to ensure that the devices can be considered trustworthy, and thus reliable healthcare services can be provided.
- **Between which nodes in the chain does a security control need to be executed?** As an extension of the previous point, the endmost goal of the Trust Assessment approach of ENTRUST is the *establishment and management of trust between entities*, starting from bilateral interactions between two individual components, and expanding to the entire medical domain infrastructure. This may depend on the different types of **Trust Relationships** established between entities, which may be categorized based on whether they are direct or indirect, or depending on the type of entities that form a relationship, as outlined in Section 7.1. These entities, in tandem with the Trust Relationships between them, formulate the **Trust Network** based on which the Trust Assessment process is performed.
- **When is the security control required?** This refers to the temporal relation of the execution of a security control with the correspondence of the corresponding security event, i.e., before or after. Specifically, as will be outlined in Chapter 2, the security (attestation) controls to be applied by a device are contained in the Protection Profile of the device- or domain-level extended MUD (eMUD) of the device and may need to be executed either periodically, or reactively (after the occurrence of a security event). In general, in ENTRUST we consider a reactive approach to the execution of security controls, but we offer the possibility for the adoption of different temporal approaches.

- **What additional elements are needed to complement the specification of a security objective?** Beyond the trustworthiness evidence, it may be possible to include other information within the data model in order to enable Trust Assessment. This may refer to additional information that may be required for the proper execution of a security control for achieving a security objective.

Based on all the above, we need to define a **conceptual model of trustworthiness** that can be used in order to exchange and share the information required for the assessment of the level of trust, based on the evidence collected from the available trust sources. Thus, answering the above questions will enable us to identify the elements to be included in the model that will serve the entire lifecycle for the Trust Assessment process. Essentially, this model will convey the **level of abstraction that needs to be conveyed** through the propositions that need to be evaluated, the interactions between the information and the properties per asset, and how the interactions between assets translate to the level of trustworthiness that we need to achieve through the execution of security enablers. A graphical representation of this model is presented in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1: Conceptual Model of Trustworthiness.

This model is in line with the ISO/IEC 30141:2018 [65], thus ensuring the compliance of the Trust Assessment process of ENTRUST with the latest international standards. In this model, user **Trust** on the **Behavior** of a healthcare provision system is a measure of **Confidence** on the overall system. Thus, the degree to which such a system fulfils a set of **Characteristics** can be considered as a measure of the confidence of users in the entire system. Conversely, Characteristics are the aspects of such a system that enable the expression of Trust-enabling behaviors.

In the context of ENTRUST, **Trustworthiness** is based on the concept of **Assurance** on the overall system, which includes the asset cartography and the interdependencies between the assets. Assurance is determined based on **Attestation**, which is performed on the **Trust properties to be attested** using the attestation enablers of ENTRUST (described in detail in D4.2 [27]). In order to perform an attestation process, we need to consider our **Assumptions** on the **Capabilities of the CMDs**, which are defined as *basic features that can be configured to enforce a security policy*, and may refer to any functionality that can be provided by a security enabler.

Throughout the remainder of this deliverable, we will provide detailed descriptions of all the components participating in the Trust Assessment approach of ENTRUST. Note that in Chapter 7 we will expand upon

the concepts outlined in this section, by providing a detailed description of the TAF of ENTRUST, as well as the role of all relevant components of the ENTRUST work in the overall action workflow of the Trust Assessment process.

1.2 Relation to Other WPs and Deliverables

Figure 1.2 depicts the relationship of this deliverable with other Work Packages (WPs), as well as other tasks in the same WP(3). As aforementioned, the main purpose of this deliverable is to provide information on the design and implementation of the components of the ENTRUST framework that participate in the Trust Assessment process of ENTRUST, and builds upon the initial versions of these components presented in D3.1 [26]. This deliverable takes input from the initial version of the reference architecture provided in D2.1 [25] and provides a version of the architecture focused on the aforementioned components, while presenting the necessary refinements following the progress of the implementation process of the participating components.

D4.2 [27] provides details on the Remote Attestation schemes of ENTRUST, whose execution entails the collection of the required trust evidence for attesting to the correctness of the specified set of trust properties. Thus, these schemes provide input to the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) of ENTRUST analyzed in this deliverable for the evaluation of the trustworthiness level of a CMD. The tracing mechanisms implemented in the CMDs for the collection of the aforementioned evidence are detailed in D5.1 [28], which also provides information on the Blockchain Infrastructure where relevant information is stored (Conformity Certificates, Trust Policies). The evaluation of the components designed and developed as part of WP3 will be performed in the context of WP6, and will be outlined in the corresponding deliverables.

1.3 Deliverable Structure

The remainder of this deliverable is organized as follows:

- **Chapter 2** provides a high-level architecture of the entire ENTRUST action workflow with particular focus on the components analyzed in this deliverable, which participate in the Trust Assessment process of ENTRUST. The action workflow is split into three distinct phases (Manufacturing (Design) Phase, Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase, Runtime Phase).
- **Chapter 3** details the Formal Verification component using the specified verification tools. It also includes details on the formal verification of the onboarding scheme using the Extensible Authentication Protocol (EAP) for delegated authentication with the Manufacturer.
- **Chapter 4** provides information on the Threat Modeling and Software Verification components of ENTRUST, including detailed action workflows for both components. It also includes information on the Large Language Model (LLM) and fuzzing methods used in the context of these components.
- **Chapter 5** provides details on the Risk Assessment component of ENTRUST, which is responsible for performing risk calculation on medical devices. This is performed on the device in isolation during the Manufacturing (Design) Phase, and considers the interdependencies with other components of the domain infrastructure in subsequent phases. It also describes the process for the calculation of the RTL of the device.

Figure 1.2: Relations of D3.2 with other WPs and deliverables.

- **Chapter 6** provides details on both the Device-level MUD and the Domain-level eMUD, including a list of fields included in both these types of eMUDs, and details on the differences between the two types of eMUDs.
- **Chapter 7** describes the Trust Assessment Framework (TAF) of ENTRUST, including its positioning within the overall ENTRUST framework, the interactions with all components described in the previous chapters, as well as detailed descriptions of the internal components of the TAF and the interfaces between them.
- **Chapter 9** provides details on the Digital Twins, their positioning within the ENTRUST framework, and their use in the emulation of identified attacks and threats in order to identify new vulnerabilities.
- **Chapter 10** describes the Secure Software/Firmware Update component, which operates through the Digital Twin and is responsible for deploying updates or patches in a secure manner, in order to mitigate the identified types of vulnerabilities.
- **Chapter 11** concludes the deliverable.

Chapter 2

Updated Architectural Flows

One of the core tenets of ENTRUST is the **monitoring and maintenance of the level of trust and trust-worthiness of medical devices** throughout their operational lifecycle, starting from their manufacturing phase and including their deployment to the network infrastructure of a medical organization. Thus, the ENTRUST framework aims to ensure that the trustworthiness level of **Connected Medical Device (CMD)s** belonging to such organizations, as well as the entire **Service Graph Chains (SGCs)** consisting of such CMDs, is at an adequate level. Recall that, in D3.1 [26], we provided a high-level overview of the approach followed in this regard, which entails (i) the calculation of the **Required Trust Level (RTL)** of the device based on the existing identified threats and vulnerabilities corresponding to the type of device and the available countermeasures for each, and (ii) the calculation of the **Actual Trust Level (ATL)** during runtime, i.e., the normal operational phase of the device after it has been deployed to the target medical organization. Afterwards, the ATL of the device is compared to the RTL in order to determine if it can be considered to be in a trustworthy state, and whether any additional mitigation measures are needed (e.g., secure software or firmware updates, attestation actions, etc.).

In D3.1, we also provided an overview of the positioning of all ENTRUST components participating in this process (namely **Formal Verification, Threat Modeling (TM)** and **Software Verification, Digital Twin, Protection Profiles, Risk Assessment (RA)**, and **TAF**) within the overall architecture of ENTRUST. Here, we expand on this analysis by providing further design and implementation details for each of the aforementioned components, as well as an updated action workflow considering the refined versions of those components.

2.1 High-Level Flow for the ENTRUST Ecosystem

In D3.1, we provided a high-level overview of the overall action workflow of the ENTRUST framework. Here, we provide an updated action workflow, considering the updates in each of the core artefacts of ENTRUST, as well as their positioning within the overall framework. Figure 2.1 provides a high-level depiction of the ENTRUST action workflow, as well as the types of cryptographic keys used by the CMDs in the context of the security processes offered by ENTRUST. Considering all the above, the individual steps can be summarized as follows:

1. Based on the threats and vulnerabilities known for the device, the **Risk Assessment** component performs risk calculation, which quantifies the level of risk for the aforementioned threats and vulnerabilities. During the Manufacturing (Design) Phase, the device-level risks are given by the Manufacturer to the Risk Assessment component through the Device-level MUD, which is stored on the

Figure 2.1: High-level overview of the architecture and action workflow of the ENTRUST framework.

MUD server. Conversely, during the Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase, the Risk Assess-

ment component receives information about the asset topology and domain-specific threats and vulnerabilities from the **System Administrator**. Thus, the Risk Assessment component calculates the RTL, which is then sent to the **Trust Policy** for the formulation of the **Trust Model Templates**.

2. The **Threat Modelling** component (Chapter 4) retrieves information on the threats and vulnerabilities from various online databases (such as NVD and MITRE CWE). Then, through a **Large Language Model (LLM)**, it creates attack scenarios that go through the Threat Model builder, who in turn provides the attack path vectors to the Risk Assessment component.
3. The **Formal Verification** component receives the security requirements from the Manufacturer (during the Manufacturing (Design) Phase) and the Security Administrator or Use Case demonstrators (during the Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase and Runtime Phase). The Formal Verification component also receives the ENTRUST security protocols to be formally verified as input. If the device has already been deployed to the domain, the CMD Asset Topology is also considered. Considering the above, the schemes to be verified are passed through the Formal Verification Toolchain (ProVerif, Tamarin, Verifpal, as will be analyzed in Chapter 3). Consider that any requirement or aspect that cannot be formally verified needs to be attested during runtime using the remote attestation schemes of ENTRUST (to be analyzed in detail in D4.2 [27]). Thus, with the support of the Security Administrator, the types of properties that cannot be formally verified are sent by the Formal Verification component to be added to the Trust Policy on the ledger.
4. The **Software Verification** component receives input from the **Software Service Provider**, who provides the software binaries running on the device, so that **Malware Scanning** and **Fuzzing** processes can be performed (analyzed in Chapter 4). Then, the Software Verification component provides any newly identified threats or vulnerabilities as output to the Risk Assessment Engine, so that it can update the risk calculation and risk graph.
5. When a new device needs to be onboarded to the domain infrastructure, it is enrolled into the domain through the **Domain Manager** using the **Zero-Touch Onboarding process**, which is described in detail in D4.2 [27]. Note that, in the context of ENTRUST, we consider both **High-end devices** and **Low-end devices**, depending on their available computational capabilities. High-end devices are authenticated directly through the Domain Manager, while Low-end devices are authenticated through their respective parent High-end device through their **Secure Communication Extension** components using Merkle Trees. This process falls outside the scope of this deliverable and is described in detail in D4.2 [27].
6. The set of **Verifiable Credentials (VCs)** of the enrolled device are issued by the Domain Manager, in collaboration with the **Privacy Certification Authority (CA)**. These are issued for both High-end and Low-end devices, and they contain the set of attributes of the device that can be used in order to provide trustworthiness evidence during runtime in a verifiable manner. More details on this process are provided in deliverable D4.2 [27].
7. When a device is enrolled into the domain, the Security Administrator may extend the Device-level MUD into the Domain-level eMUD in order to contain domain-level threats and vulnerabilities, which is then stored in the ledger.
8. In order to execute an attestation process on a CMD for verifying the correctness of one or more of its Trust Properties, the Domain Manager retrieves the Domain-level eMUD of the device (Chapter 6) dictating the attestation challenges corresponding to the device. For the execution of the attestation process, the **Trust Model Manager** component of the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)** (Chapter 7) retrieves the Trust Policy Template from the DLT. Then, the **Trust Source Manager** of the TAF retrieves the **Trust Policy**, which dictates the **Trust Sources** from which trustworthiness

evidence will be received. Such sources are the **remote attestation**, the **AI-based Misbehaviour Detection**, etc.

9. For the execution of the attestation action, as attestation evidence, the **Device Tracer** for the High-end device or the **Static tracer** for the low-end device collect the raw data required as attestation evidence. After an attestation action is executed, the result is sent to the **Trust Source Manager** of the TAF, as it constitutes a Trust Source, as aforementioned. Note that, when a low-end device wants to provide a Trust Source, this is performed through the high-end device, which receives its Trust Appraisal through the Secure Communication Extension and sends it to the Trust Source Manager.
10. The Trust Source Manager forwards the attestation evidence to the **Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine** of the TAF, which calculates the ATL of the device based on the use of Subjective Logic (as analyzed in Chapter 7) and provides it to the **Trust Decision Engine** of the TAF. There, the ATL is compared to the RTL, as calculated by the Risk Assessment component, and a decision is made on the trustworthiness of the device. The Trust Decision Engine also pushes the history of the ATLs of the device to the Trust Policy on the ledger.
11. In case of a failed attestation (i.e., $ATL < RTL$), the evidence is sent from the High-end device (or from the Low-end device through the corresponding high-end device) to the **Attack Emulation** component of the **Digital Twin** (Chapter 9), so that it can perform an analysis and generate the attack execution paths that led to the failed attestation. These paths are provided as input to the Software Verification component, so that it is able to create the **Fuzzing test cases** (Chapter 4).
12. The output of the Software Verification component also feeds the **Software Update** component (Chapter 10), which gives a clean software update version to be pushed to the **Digital Twin** through the **Update Server**. Note that the Digital Twin component possesses the **subfleet Manager**, which contains the virtual representations of the assets of the topology (both High-end and Low-end devices), as well as the topology itself. The Subfleet Manager is responsible for pushing the updates to their respective components.
13. After a failed attestation, the raw traces used as attestation evidence is sent to the **AI-based Misbehaviour Detection** (Chapter 9) so that they can be analyzed for potential anomalies. Then, the attestation report is sent to the Trust Source Manager, along with the output of the AI-based anomaly detection. These, as aforementioned, constitute the Trust Sources that are used for calculating the ATL of the device.
14. When a new threat or vulnerability is identified following the aforementioned process, the Risk Assessment Engine is notified, in order to update the risk calculation and the risk graph. Then, the output of the Risk Assessment pertaining to this threat or vulnerability is pushed to the **Threat Intelligence Database** in the form of **STIX-formulated threat intelligence information**.
15. The attestation evidence is also sent to the **Security Context Broker**, who pushes them to the **Off-Chain Storage Facility**, so that they can become available to any responsible auditing or certification parties that possess the appropriate permissions. Afterwards, a location pointer to this data is recorded to the ledger, for enabling the retrieval of the data from the Off-chain Storage.

As outlined in D3.1 [26], the ENTRUST action workflow can be split into three core phases. In the following, the three phases will be referred to as follows:

1. **Manufacturing (Design) Phase:** Entails the manufacturing process of the device and the creation of the device-level extended MUD (eMUD).

2. **Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase:** Entails the deployment and secure enrolment of the device into the Service Graph Chain (SGC) of the target medical organization. Includes the creation of the domain-specific eMUD of the CMD as an extension of the device-level eMUD.
3. **Runtime Phase:** Entails actions taken during the normal operation of the CMD, aiming towards the evaluation of the level of trust in the CMD and the system as a whole.

In the following, we will expand on these three phases, while also updating and expanding upon the high-level action workflows provided in D3.1, and outlining the updates that will be put forth in the context of this deliverable. In Figure 2.1, we provide a high-level overview of the entire ENTRUST architecture and action workflow, focused on the components and flows related to the calculation of the trust level of the device. Specifically, in the Figure, the **Manufacturer** frame contains the components running at the backend at the Manufacturer side, before the device is actually deployed to the medical domain infrastructure. Conversely, the **Domain** frame contains the components running at the backend at the Domain side, after the device has been deployed to the medical domain.

Note that, while Figure 2.1 provides a high-level overview of all three aforementioned phases of the ENTRUST framework, in the following sections we provide individual figures for each of the three phases with a higher level of granularity regarding the description of the action workflows, as well as detailed descriptions of the actions taken as part of each phase.

2.1.1 Manufacturing (Design) Phase

The first phase of the ENTRUST workflow is the **Manufacturing (Design) Phase**, which entails the actions taken at the side of the Manufacturer of the device, before it is deployed to the actual medical organization where it will operate. Note that, while the term **CMDs** is used throughout this document to refer to the devices considered in the context of ENTRUST, it is not applicable to the Manufacturing phase, as it requires that the device is connected to the domain infrastructure. Thus, the term CMD only applies to the Pre-deployment and Runtime phases, where the domain infrastructure is actually considered.

In the context of ENTRUST, as outlined in D3.1, the **extended Manufacturer Usage Description (eMUD)** of the device defines its *foundational security requirements, outlining the necessary operational characteristics to mitigate threats and ensure safe interactions within a network*. Here, we expand upon this by providing further details on its definition and implementation. Specifically, we now consider that each device is characterized by **two types of eMUDs**: (i) The **Device-level MUD**, which includes the device characteristics that do not consider its placement within its operational domain, and (ii) the **Domain-level eMUD**, which is created as an extension of the Device-level MUD and includes the device characteristics pertaining to its operation within the medical domain. Since this section is dedicated to the Manufacturing phase, here we focus on the definition of the Device-level eMUD, which is essentially the core outcome of the Manufacturing phase.

In this regard, one of the main updates outlined in this deliverable is the definition of the fields present within the aforementioned eMUDs. Note that this definition applies to both types of eMUDs:

- The **Protection Profile** of the device, which refers to the set of information required in order to apply the appropriate actions for the protection of the device based on the identified threats and vulnerabilities, and contains the following:
 - ✓ The **list of threats defined by the Manufacturer**, which are the threats and vulnerabilities which are provided directly by the Manufacturer based on existing knowledge on the type of

device constructed, and are connected to **types of security enablers that can be used in order to mitigate them.**

- ✓ The **list of threats identified by the Threat Modeling component.** As outlined in D3.1 and will be expanded in Chapter 4, the Threat Modeling component is responsible for collecting, fuzzing, and aggregating types of threats and vulnerabilities for the considered type of device based on existing databases, as will be outlined in the following. These threats are also connected to the **types of security enablers** employed for their mitigation.
- The **list of Policy Hashes.** These are values that can verify the operational correctness of the device. For example, in case a *secure boot* mechanism is available, this may refer to the correct and expected value for the output of the secure boot that can be used in order to verify that the process has been performed correctly. In addition, depending on the type of secure element used (e.g., PUF), this may refer to evidence related to the correctness of the output provided by this element. These Policy Hashes can also be used in the context of a *Key Restriction Usage Policy*, which specifies that a cryptographic key can only be used if the device is known to be in a correct state. Note that this field is initially empty during the Manufacturing phase, and is populated during the Pre-deployment (domain-specific) phase.
- The pointer to the **Trust Policy** for the particular device in the Blockchain infrastructure, which is essentially a smart contract deployed to the private ledger, and dictates the types of evidence that need to be collected by the device in order to verify its trustworthiness level. This will be further analyzed in the following.
- The type of **Trusted Computing Base (TCB)** of the device, which is specified by the manufacturer, and will provide the basis for the execution of all security operations that require the provision of trustworthiness guarantees.

The construction of these eMUDs is in line with the specification of the **Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD)**, as aligned in the relevant standards [9]. In the following sections, we will describe the process for the creation of these eMUDs, as well as their storage and updating process, throughout all three operational phases of the ENTRUST framework.

Considering all the above, in the following we provide an updated high-level action workflow for the Manufacturing Phase in the context of ENTRUST, which is also depicted in Figure 2.2:

1. The Manufacturing phase begins with the conceptualization of the device by the Manufacturer, focusing on the medical scope of the device where the device is intended to be used, including the specifications, essential security and requirements, and compliance with the latest medical safety protocols [25]. Note that the definition of these requirements *do not consider the positioning of the device within the network infrastructure of a specific medical organization, since this phase is only concerned with the device in isolation.*
2. The Manufacturer provides an initial set of known threats and vulnerabilities for the device to the **Risk Assessment** component, which performs an initial risk calculation based on these threats. Note that, at this point, no risk graph is created, since the device is considered in isolation. Thus, the risk calculation entails the quantification of the *Individual Risk Level (IRL)*, which takes into consideration all the associated threats vulnerabilities and the security controls that are able to address these vulnerabilities. We expand upon this process in Chapter 5.
3. In parallel, the **Threat Modeling** component identified **Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVEs)** by gathering data using a web scraper from online databases, such as the **NIST National**

Figure 2.2: Architecture and flow of the Manufacturing (Design) phase of the ENTRUST framework.

Vulnerability Database (NVD) and the **MITRE Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE)**, which are known databases containing vulnerabilities and attack methods. Afterwards, a **Large Language Model (LLM)** is used in order to convert and organize this information that enables it to be provided to the Risk Assessment component.

- The risk calculation is performed based on the threats and vulnerabilities originating from both aforementioned sources. Note that *the innovation of ENTRUST in this regard is the use of the Risk Assessment component for the calculation of the RTL of the device*. Specifically, leveraging the methods that will be outlined in Chapter 7, an initial calculation of the RTL for the device is performed. This is performed through the identification of the threats, originating either from the Manufacturer or the relevant databases, and the evaluation of their impact on the trustworthiness of the device. Afterwards, the security controls which can be deployed against these threats are identified, as well as **the reduction of the impact of each attack that can be achieved by each security control**. Note that, as part of this process, each security control needs to be associated with the **types of trust evidence that need to be monitored or we have access to** in order to calculate the **ATL** of the device, which will eventually be used in order to evaluate the trustworthiness level of the device during runtime.
- The **Software Verification** module, based on the identified threat landscape, creates a testing plan based on various intelligence sources, using **Indices of Compromise (IOC)**. This component consists of a binary code analyser and a source code analyser which are used in order to identify whether the files or binaries related to the target device demonstrate vulnerabilities or malicious patterns.

6. Independently, the **Formal Verification component** performs a formal verification of the software stack, i.e., the binaries running in each device, as will be detailed in Chapter 3. Note that the Threat Modeling component provides the identified CVEs to the Formal Verification component, so that they can be used in order to determine the type of fuzzing that will be made in the verification process. If any new vulnerabilities are found with this process, they are sent to the Threat Modeling component, which forwards them to the Risk Assessment component in order to update the risk calculation accordingly.
7. After the device is constructed, it is possible to create a digital representation of the device, referred to as the **Digital Twin**. In the context of ENTRUST, this is used in order to perform an emulation of the identified types of attacks, as will be described in Chapter 9. Specifically, the required input in order to emulate the attack is provided to the DT, and the behavior of the device is monitored using probes that collect various types of information (e.g., bandwidth or energy consumption). This information is essentially an enriched version of the information that can be taken from the physical device, and can be used in order to identify deviations from the expected behavior of the device. Note that, at this point, *this process is only performed considering the device in isolation. However, when it is deployed to the target medical domain, this will provide the basis for the operation of the **AI-based Intrusion Detection** process, which aims to identify deviations from the expected behavior of the device during runtime.*
8. After the execution of all the above methods, if any new exploit or zero-day vulnerability is identified, it is provided to a **Threat Intelligence Database**, which is essentially a ledger that can be accessed by other manufacturers towards sharing threat intelligence knowledge. This constitutes a **threat hygiene market**, which aims to increase the security posture of devices operating within the medical domain. They are also sent to the Risk Assessment component so that it is able to calculate the updated RTL, based on the newly identified threats and vulnerabilities.
9. Considering all the above, the **Device-level MUD** is created and sent to the **MUD Server**. Note that Protection Profiles in the context of ENTRUST extend the definition of the MUD profile, as standardised by the IETF in RFC 8520. In addition, the information on the identified threats, vulnerabilities, as well as associated security controls are included into the device-level MUD. Note that the calculated RTL, as well as the types of trust evidence to be collected in order to verify the correctness of the trust attributes, are added to the **Trust Policy**, which is a smart contract that is deployed to the private ledger. Note that, in the device-level MUD, there will be a **pointer to the Trust Policy in the ledger** that enables the collection of the required evidence and the execution of the appropriate mitigation measures in case any of the identified threats or vulnerabilities are detected during runtime.

2.1.2 Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase

After the Manufacturing phase of the device is complete, the next phase entails the deployment of the device into the network infrastructure of the target medical organization. Thus, the main consideration of this phase compared to the Manufacturing phase outlined in the previous section is the **consideration of all the assets belonging to the SGC of the medical domain** in order to assess the level of trust of the device, rather than considering the device in isolation as in the previous phase. In addition, one core update in this phase compared to the one described in D3.1 is the **distinction between the low-end and high-end devices**, which are equipped with different computational capabilities, and whose deployment process differs depending on the types of crypto operations they are able to perform. While the onboarding and enrolment phases are described in D4.2 [27] in further detail, here we provide a

high-level description of these processes and their positioning within the actions performed in the pre-deployment phase.

Figure 2.3: Architecture and flow of the Pre-Deployment (Domain-specific) phase of the ENTRUST framework.

Thus, considering the above, in the following we provide an updated high-level action workflow for the Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase in the context of ENTRUST, which is also depicted in Figure 2.3:

1. When a device wishes to be enrolled into the domain (i.e., the SGC of the medical organization where the device needs to be deployed), it notifies the **Domain Manager**, who afterwards initiates the pre-deployment process. This can be essentially split into two sub-phases: (i) The **Authentication, Onboarding, and Enrolment** of the device into the domain, and (ii) the **updating of the RTL of the device** considering the domain infrastructure. In the following, we provide a high-level overview of the actions taken as part of both these sub-phases.
2. The cryptographic underpinnings and detailed action workflows of the authentication, onboarding, and enrolment phase are provided in D4.2. However, for the sake of completeness, here we also provide a high-level overview of the actions contained in this phase:
 - (a) In order to initiate the **Authentication** process, the Domain Manager notifies the **Authentication Server** of the Manufacturing domain. Afterwards, the Authentication Server sends a challenge, which is signed by the device with its pre-established **Root ID Key**. This process ensures the authenticity of the device, and when complete, enables the device to be onboarded and enrolled into the actual domain.
 - (b) After the authentication of the device is complete, the **Onboarding** process is performed, which entails the issuance of the device credentials by the **Privacy Certification Authority (CA)**. These credentials contain device attributes or characteristics based on which **Trust Assessment** is performed, i.e., a trust property is verified based on the presence and correctness of a set of attributes, as will be outlined in Chapter 7. These refer to any attributes

that denote the trust characteristics of the device and are related to the trust properties of interest (e.g., secure boot, PUF, the device TCB, the authentic tracer, OP-TEE). The purpose of these credentials is *the provision of the ability of the device to share trust evidence during runtime in the form of a **Verifiable Presentation (VP)**, which enables sharing evidence in a privacy-preserving manner.* As will be detailed in D4.2, VPs in the context of ENTRUST offer two types of privacy: (i) **attribute anonymity**, which enables the device to demonstrate the possession of a set of attributes without disclosing the attributes themselves, and (ii) **attribute value anonymity**, which enables the device to disclose a set of attributes without revealing their exact values.

- (c) After the onboarding process is complete, the device sends a request to the Domain Manager to initiate its **Enrolment** into the domain. To this end, the Domain Manager possesses a set of policies that dictate a set of attributes that the device needs to prove ownership of in order to be enrolled into the medical domain SGC. Thus, the Domain Manager sends a request to the device for the creation of a VP containing the required attributes. Upon successful verification of the VP provided by the device, its enrolment into the domain is complete. Note that the aforementioned enrolment process applies to **high-end devices**, while the enrolment of a **low-end device** is performed through its parent high-end device, following the process that is outlined in D4.2.
3. The second phase, i.e., the updating of the RTL, falls within the scope of this deliverable, and will be described in detail in the following Chapters. Specifically, this phase consists of the following steps:
- (a) First, the Domain Manager notifies the **Risk Assessment** component about the addition of the new device. This triggers a re-quantification of risk, as well as the creation of the **risk graph**, considering the assets belonging to the domain infrastructure and the interconnectivity between them. Thus, the Risk Assessment component performs **attack path calculation** considering the asset topology of the domain, and calculates the **updated risk score** considering the specific domain characteristics, the **impact per vulnerability**, and the identified **attack paths**, as will be detailed in Chapter 5. This leads to an update in the RTL against which the ATL of the device will be compared during runtime in the context of the trust assessment of the device.
 - (b) Next, the **Formal Verification** component verifies, in offline mode, the protocols that are executed by the device as part of each security service, such as attestation processes, secure communication, secure update processes, and any other process that can be formally verified offline. Note that the output of the Formal Verification component constitutes the **trust boundary** of the device, which contains all processes, binaries, and software which are known to be correct and trustworthy. Any other element or process that cannot be verified is considered to be outside the trust boundary, and needs to be attested during runtime through the verification of the correctness of the required trust properties or attributes.
 - (c) Afterwards, the addition of a new device triggers the **Digital Twin** component to create a new virtual representation of the device, and performs the emulation of the identified types of attacks, as outlined in the Manufacturing (Design) Phase in the previous section. However, the difference here is that emulation is also performed on domain-specific threats, i.e., threats and vulnerabilities that have been identified either by the System Administrator or the Threat Modeling component.
 - (d) After the aforementioned processes are complete, the newly identified threats and vulnerabilities based on the domain-specific information provided by the System Administrator, or identified by the Formal Verification and/or Digital Twin components, are sent back to the Risk Assessment in order to calculate the updated RTL for the device.

- (e) Recall that, during the Design phase, a Device-level MUD of the device has been created and stored into the MUD server. Here, we extend this into a **Domain-level eMUD**, which also contains the threat vector identified at the domain by the Threat Modeling component and the System Administrator, i.e., the domain-specific threats and vulnerabilities, associated with the security controls that can be used in order to mitigate those threats. In addition, the **Policy Hashes** field of the eMUD (which was initially empty) is populated with the Key Restriction Usage Policies specific to the domain, in order to verify the correctness of the device during runtime. Afterwards, the **Trust Policy** specifying the types of evidence that needs to be collected by the newly specified security controls is updated accordingly.

2.1.3 Runtime Phase

After the Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase is complete, the CMD is considered to be part of the medical domain infrastructure, and it is able to begin its normal operation as part of the medical organization. The Runtime Phase entails all actions taken during the normal operation of the device in order to ensure its trustworthiness. This process is centered around the **TAF** of ENTRUST, which is responsible for calculating the **ATL** of the device during runtime and comparing it with the **RTL**, computed as outlined in the previous sections, in order to determine the actions that need to be taken in order to bring the CMD into a trustworthy state.

Figure 2.4: Architecture and flow of the Runtime phase of the ENTRUST framework.

Thus, considering the above, in the following we provide an updated high-level action workflow for the Runtime Phase in the context of ENTRUST, also shown in Figure 2.4:

1. After the CMD has been successfully onboarded and enrolled into the ENTRUST framework and the SGC of the medical domain has been constructed as outlined in the previous section, the TAF is considered to be running in the backend. During runtime, a trust assessment may need to be performed based on the **Trust Policies** that have been constructed, dictating the actions that need to be taken. Such actions may be **Remote Attestation (RA)** processes, such as **Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV)** to verify the correctness of the configuration state of the device during runtime, or **Swarm Attestation (SA)** to verify the correctness of several devices simultaneously. The triggering of these policies may be (i) **synchronous**, meaning that the calculation of the ATL of the device is requested at fixed time intervals, or (ii) **asynchronous**, meaning that a security control needs to be deployed on demand, for instance in case a change has been detected in the system.
2. If a device is notified that a security control needs to be deployed, either synchronously or asynchronously, the device needs to start collecting the required **trust evidence**. Recall that, in the context of ENTRUST, devices are categorized as **high-end** or **low-end** devices (CMDs), depending on their computational capabilities. For each of these types, this process is differentiated as follows:
 - (a) In the case of **high-end devices (CMDs)**, the MUD URL is sent to the Domain Manager by the CMD. If the corresponding Domain-level eMUD is available on the MUD Server, it is retrieved by the Domain Manager. Recall that this eMUD also contains the pointer to the location of the Trust Policy on the ledger, which contains the types of evidence that need to be collected in the context of the specified security control(s).
 - (b) In the case of a **low-end devices (CMD)**, these may not be directly exposed to the network, as it is possible that they are connected to the network through a parent high-end device. Thus, communication with the Domain Manager for the retrieval of the eMUD and the collection of trust evidence is performed through the parent high-end device.
3. Based on the content of the retrieved Device-level MUD, the appropriate security enabler is initiated by the Verifier, which issues an attestation challenge to the (Prover) CMD in order to initiate the attestation process, specifying the type of trust evidence that needs to be collected by the Prover device. Note that, in the context of ENTRUST, the Verifier may either be the Domain Manager or a different entity (e.g., another device). If the Verifier is different than the Domain Manager, the required information is forwarded to the Verifier so that it can issue the attestation challenge to the Prover. A high-level overview of the attestation process in the context of ENTRUST is provided in D2.1 [25], and further information on the attestation schemes of ENTRUST is provided in D4.2 [27].
4. The trust evidence collected by the Prover CMD during the attestation process is forwarded to the TAF, which then *starts calculating the ATL, both for the device and the service being attested*. Further details on the trust assessment process are provided in Chapter 7. At a high level, the TAF consists of the **Trust Model Manager (TMM)** for expressing and specifying the information required to perform trust assessment based on the available templates, the **Trust Source Manager (TSM)** which enables the management of the available trust sources, the **Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine (TLEE)** for performing the calculation of the ATL of the device or service, the **Trust Decision Engine (TDE)** for deciding whether the ATL is at an adequate level considering the calculated RTL, and the **Trust Assessment Manager (TAM)** which acts as the orchestrator between all aforementioned components.
5. After the ATL is calculated, the TAF provides an **up-to-date view of the ATL both per device and per service**. If $ATL > RTL$, the device or service is considered to be in a trustworthy state. In this case, the device creates a **Conformity Certificate** using **Privacy Attribute-Based Credentials (PABCs)**, which enable the sharing of device attributes related to the collected trust evidence in a

privacy-preserving manner. This is based on the use of **harmonized attributes**, that enable the device to share a set of attributes without sharing the values of the attributes themselves. The Conformity Certificate is then sent to be stored on the Blockchain Infrastructure, in order to enable auditing the trustworthiness level of the device in a privacy-preserving manner.

6. In case of a failed attestation (i.e., if $ATL < RTL$), this constitutes an **indication of risk**, and signifies the possibility that mitigation measures may be needed in order to achieve the required trust level of the device. In this case, the raw traces collected as trust evidence as part of the attestation process are sent to the **Digital Twin**, so that it can have a synchronized view with the corresponding data on the physical device and it can emulate the attack path that led to the failed attestation. Thus, the Digital Twin is able to perform **AI-based Intrusion/Misbehavior Detection** based on the received traces in order to identify any behavior that may deviate from what is known and expected. In addition, in case there is an indication of risk, ENTRUST specifies a **Secure Software Update** process that goes through the Digital Twin, and is subsequently sent to the concerned devices so that the required patches or updates can be installed. These operations are described in detail in Chapters 9 and 10.
7. Recall that the **Formal Verification** component follows a model-based approach in order to formally verify the fulfilment of the security requirements, as they have been defined either by the Manufacturer at a device level, or by the System Administrator at a domain level. In some cases, the trust evidence collected by the Device Tracer may be used in order to formally verify the fulfilment of these security requirements during runtime. Thus, the trust evidence is also forwarded to the Formal Verification component. The runtime operation of the Formal Verification is described in detail in Chapter 3.
8. In case a new threat or vulnerability is identified, either by the Digital Twin or the Formal Verification component, it is sent to the **Threat Modeling** component, which forwards it to the **Risk Assessment** graph in order to update the risk quantification and risk graph accordingly.
9. Based on all the above, if additional threats or vulnerabilities are identified, the RTL of the device may need to be recalculated. Thus, after the Risk Assessment calculates the updated RTL, the Domain-level eMUD of the device needs to be updated in order to reflect the newly identified attack vector, including the types of security controls that can be applied to mitigate those attacks. In addition, the **Trust Policy** of the device on the ledger is updated, specifying any additional trust evidence that needs to be monitored.

Chapter 3

ENTRUST Formal Verification Toolchain & Operation

The role of the Formal Verification component within the ENTRUST architecture is to apply the 'secure-by-design' approach and to support the concept of zero-trust (i.e. 'never trust, always verify') by applying formal verification techniques for all the phases in the CMD lifecycle starting with its onboarding. The properties that are verified reflect the envisioned security and functional correctness requirements as defined in D2.1 and D3.1. We recognize that applying formal verification for all internal operations might be unfeasible due to their inherent complex nature. To address this complexity, proper abstractions might be needed to achieve effective verification process that converges and produces an outcome. These abstractions enable granular definition of trust policies that need to be attested at runtime. Thus, attestation at runtime is needed only for those system and domain properties that cannot be formally verified at design time.

This component specifies and uses formal models of the critical security protocols and schemes of ENTRUST and checks if the security properties formulated explicitly in the formal language of the used verification tools hold for the given models. To accomplish this, the formal verification component utilizes state-of-the-art security protocol verification tools such as ProVerif and Tamarin, as well as other formal verification tools where needed (such as general purpose model checkers and theorem provers).

The envisaged requirements that will be verified capture on one hand the underlying needs of the designed protocols and on the other hand the needs of the applications and services where they are used. For a given model and a set of formally given requirements, there are three possible results that determine the output of this component. The first one is a positive outcome of the verification. This outcome increases the confidence in the design and also the implementation of the verified protocols and schemes. The successfully verified requirements establish the trust boundary of the system's operation and show that it exhibits the expected behavior captured in the MUD trustworthiness profiles. The second possible result is that the verification process does not terminate in a reasonable time for a given requirement. This outcome is due to the fact that in general the protocol verification problem is undecidable for unbounded number of protocol runs and unbounded size of the terms. This outcome is usually observed in case of complex system internals, complex protocols and/or requirements. In this case, the requirement will be subject to monitoring and checking at runtime by defining suitable monitoring hooks. The third possible result is that the requirement does not hold. The verification tools typically provide an attack scenario as an additional outcome. It can be used to fix the protocol being verified and repeat the verification process on the new version. This iterative approach performed at design time manifests the 'security-by-design' principle and is one of the core innovations of ENTRUST. It is therefore important to perform the formal verification at an early stage of the design of the CMD's software since finding a vulnerability in a software that is already deployed leads to a costly process of updates.

Deliverable D3.1 [26] outlined the overall vision for the formal verification component. The goal is to model and formally verify both the onboarding phase (that prepares the device for trust establishment) and the runtime mechanisms for establishing and re-establishing the required trust level. D3.1 presented an initial version of the device onboarding model expressed in the language of the tool VerifPal. The experience showed that the VerifPal tool does not scale well for non-trivial models and properties and it was decided that the more mature tools ProVerif and Tamarin will be used for formal modeling and verification.

This chapter refines the vision behind the formal verification component of ENTRUST by defining a roadmap that outlines the protocols to be verified and a strategy for doing this. Furthermore, the chapter presents the models of two protocols that prepare the device for trust establishment: the device authentication and credential issuance, and the first step of the device onboarding protocol [27], namely the device authentication step based on the EAP-PSK (already covered in D3.1 [26]).

3.1 ENTRUST's Vision & RoadMap for Design-Time Compositional Security

The overall goal of the component is to provide models along with their security properties for the most important security protocols and crypto schemes of ENTRUST. The verification of the properties will be done using two state of the art protocol verification tools: ProVerif and Tamarin. It should be noted that for properties like secrecy and authentication (checked later on in the chapter) both tools are equally applicable. In general, each tool has its own strengths and weaknesses that make one or the other tool more suitable for a specific scenario. For example, ProVerif provides a very succinct syntax for basic properties whereas Tamarin comes with a more complex but very powerful property specification language based on a fragment of first-order logic. Therefore, we will be using both tools whenever possible and utilizing the one that has a better fit for the more complex scenarios. As an additional outcome, this will enable a comparison between the tools.

The following protocols and crypto schemes are expected to be modeled and verified.

Protocols that prepare the CMD for trust establishment:

- device authentication and verifiable credential issuance
- device onboarding

Protocols that enable the CMD to establish trust during operation:

- remote attestation mechanism
- secure device communication
- attribute-based encryption and signcryption schemes

Protocols that allow the CMD to re-establish its trust level:

- secure software update

In addition, if needed, we will address any other relevant and non-trivial protocol or scheme that contributes significantly to the ENTRUST vision.

A major component in achieving trusted computing services is a secure anchor that acts as Root-of-Trust (RoT) providing cryptographic functions, secure storage and measured boot among others. In the context of the project, the ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base recommends using Trusted Execution Enviroments (TEE) for high-end devices and PUFs for low-end devices. They can be considered inherently secure and all their internal operations handling cryptographic data and functions can be idealized assuming perfect cryptography [37]. However, this does not neccessarily mean that the applications and services using these functions are secure as well. Consequently, formal verification process is needed when complex interacting applications are developed and when their security must be ensured. If the RoT internal operations are not idealized and are modeled explicitly (e.g. handling secure internal storage) along with the application/service logic, the resulting model may become too complex leading to the risk that the verification process may not converge.

In order to address this challenge, a two-step approach to verification will be followed that separates the logic of the interaction in the protocol (or application) from the logic of the device internal operations thus achieving compositional verification. As a first step (taken in this deliverable) the focus will be on modeling and verifying the overall flow of events in the application/protocols pertaining to the domain assuming perfect secrecy of the underlying crypto schemes.

The second step will focus on modeling and verification at device level (in contrast to the first step that focuses at the interaction among the participants in the domain) by looking at the device internals. This step will also explicitly differentiate between low-end and high-end CMDs that may lead to refinement of the initial protocols.

This approach aims to break the main goal of modeling of the ENTRUST framework and formally verifying the security requirements defined in D2.1 into two distinct phases. In essence this is a top-down approach in which the first phase starts at the domain-level where a device is enrolled in the CMD domain. We are modeling the interactions among the participants by simplifying and abstracting their internal functions. This aims to give an overview of the security requirements of the designed framework before implementing the components. Each component is considered as an actor of the interaction and only the interface (input and the output) of the components are modeled and verified using protocol verification tools. This will help map the dependencies between components, identify how they rely on each other, and discover vulnerabilities. Therefore, potential security vulnerabilities can be detected in the early design phase. Since each component is treated as an independent actor, the focus is on the inputs and outputs of each component, ensuring that the components are encapsulated and isolated to prevent unauthorized access or interference. Furthermore, this phase is an iterative process for verifying and improving the designed framework from the security context. The models generated from this phase serve as the foundation for the second step, where the complete interaction, including the internal components, is modeled and verified. The second step of our approach aims to model the full interaction including the behavior of the internal components.

A final element of the roadmap (if the time permits) aims at capitalizing on our experience gained from applying the security protocol verification tools. As already mentioned in D3.1, their highly specialized languages are a significant hurdle for the practitioners that want to easily specify and verify their protocols at the design phase. We propose to define a domain-specific language (DSL) for specifying security protocols and their properties equipped with an automatic generation of the tool-specific representation in tools like ProVerif and Tamarin. To realize this goal we plan to gather information from literature and identify modeling patterns for how common security properties are specified. This input can then be generalized and integrated into a DSL.

3.1.1 Focus of this Deliverable: Device Onboarding

The main goal of the formal verification task of this deliverable is to model and verify the security properties of the onboarding process of the CMD in the protocol verification tools ProVerif and Tamarin. First, we use a tool-independent notation to model the protocols used as input for creating models using security verification tools. An overview of the security properties that need to be verified is described in Section 3.2.2.

The onboarding process consists of authentication of the device based on its root identification key, the issuance of verifiable credentials that attribute to the device the characteristics that will be used to conduct the trust assessment, enrolment of the device in the target domain, and establishment of the necessary crypto material (keys) for provisioning the runtime evidence in a verifiable manner based on the information defined in the extended MUD. In deliverable D3.1 we verified the authentication protocol using ProVerif and Verifpal. Section 3.3.2.5 describes the improved ProVerif model of the EAP-PSK protocol (delegated authentication), while in Section 3.3.2.6 we modeled and verified the authentication protocol in Tamarin. Section 3.3 describes the modeling and verification process of the verifiable credential issuance, first modeling the protocol in a tool-independent notation and then translating it to ProVerif and Tamarin to verify the required security properties.

Deliverable D4.2 [27] presents the enrolment protocol that aims to verify the attribute keys and enroll the device to the domain manager. The first step of this protocol is to authenticate the device using the root identity key provided by the manufacturer. This authentication process is based on the EAP protocol verified in D3.1, therefore this part of the enrolment protocol is already verified using ProVerif and Tamarin.

3.2 Threat Model

This section aims to define the adversarial model used for verifying the security properties during the onboarding process, including the definition of the security properties and the assumptions used to model the onboarding process and the cryptographic schemes.

3.2.1 The Anticipated Actions of an Attacker

To verify the security properties of the proposed onboarding process, a threat model needs to be defined, that is used in the verification process of the automated verification tools. We define a threat model based on the well-known Dolev-Yao model [23]. This approach considers an active attacker who intercepts all communication between the actors of the security protocol and tries everything to obtain relevant information. Therefore, we use the behavior defined for the Dolev-Yao model where the attacker can obtain any message from the network, the attacker can initiate a conversation since it is a legitimate user of the network, and can be a receiver to any actor of the protocol. Thus, the Dolev-Yao model is only applicable at the network level, as the attacker cannot access the data or keys at the device level.

The Dolev-Yao model admits a number of well known attack scenarios when verifying the security properties of a protocol. Some notable examples are the replay and MITM attacks being some of the most common threats in typical attack scenarios, both being part of the Dolev-Yao threat model. These scenarios can be verified using automated verification tools such as ProVerif and Tamarin. A replay attack involves an attacker recording and retransmitting data to exploit system vulnerabilities to obtain sensitive information or gain unauthorized access. Furthermore, an MITM attack is represented by an attacker intercepting and manipulating the communication between two parties.

Another scenario is the attempt of the adversary to onboard a malicious CMD to an honest domain manager to exploit vulnerabilities, bypass security protocols, attempt to disrupt normal operations on the domain, or be used as a vector to distribute malware to other devices from the network. Conversely, the attacker may try to onboard an honest CMD to a malicious domain manager to reveal the inner workings of the domain or perform unauthorized actions to collect sensitive information from the device.

We explicitly do not consider scenarios that involve colluding devices where two or more communicating parties collaborate to achieve a malicious goal. Techniques that prevent such attacks usually require significant computational power that may not be available at constraint devices.

3.2.2 Verified Properties

Before starting the verification process we need to define what needs to be protected. Some of the relevant security properties that can be verified using protocol verification tools are secrecy of information, e.g. keys, authentication, anonymity, and temporal order verification. The secrecy of the keys property ensures that the keys cannot be computed or retrieved by an attacker using the information intercepted through the open communication channel, while the authentication property ensures that two actors of a security protocol authenticate to each other. Furthermore, the temporal order verification implies that some steps of the protocol need to take place in a certain order. A more detailed description of the exact keys and steps that need to be protected is given in Section 3.3 for each scheme of the onboarding process.

Besides secrecy, authentication, and temporal order, security requirements have been defined for cryptographic protocols in deliverable D4.2 [27]. A short description of these requirements is described in Table 3.1. These security requirements are achieved through cryptographic operations that are considered perfectly secure throughout the formal verification task of this deliverable.

Security Requirement	Description
Unforgeability	An adversary cannot construct a forgery VC that can be accepted by a verifier.
Selective Disclosure	High-end devices can generate a VP showing that it contains the required attributes without disclosing further information about the attributes' values.
Integrity	Only authenticated and non-compromised high and low-end devices can access the required attestation keys to successfully create attestations.
Device Root Key Binding	Issued VCs need to be bound to the TC key embedded in the device, ensuring that no other device shares the same attribute keys
Confidentiality	Legitimate access control to sensitive encrypted data is ensured by the ABSC protocol.
Continuous authentication and authorization	Achieved through Attribute-based Access Control performed as a chain code after receiving VCs including the list of attributes required to access specific services or information.

Table 3.1: Security requirements based on Deliverable D4.2 [27]

3.2.3 Assumptions

As described in Section 3.2, we use the Dolev-Yao model that assumes an active attacker who can intercept all communication between the actors of the protocol and can initiate a conversation since it is considered a legitimate user of the network. In deliverable D3.1, we presented the EAP authentication protocol which we verified using Verifpal and ProVerif and assumed that an attacker could not obtain the PSK provided to the CMD on the manufacturer side.

Following the same approach for the Device Authentication and Verifiable Credential Issuance protocol, we assume that the attacker cannot obtain the root identity key installed on the device during the manufacturing phase. We assume that the MUD file has not been tampered with, and the integrity of the MUD is to be checked in the next iterations of the formal verification task. Furthermore, as mentioned in Section 3.3, symbolic security analysis assumes perfect cryptography such that an attacker can perform cryptographic operations only if relevant keys are leaked.

3.3 Modeling and Verification

This section describes the models used to verify the onboarding process and cryptographic schemes. Furthermore, it also presents the verification results, discusses required changes (if necessary) for the onboarding protocol based on the results, and describes runtime verification requirements.

We use automatic analysis tools for verifying the security protocols within the ENTRUST context. These tools are based on formal verification techniques such as model checking and theorem proving, taking into consideration security properties. The tools are classified into symbolic and computational security analysis. Towards this direction, the tools used for this task are ProVerif and Tamarin, both based on symbolic security analysis. They are based on the consideration of a Dolev-Yao threat model, as described in Section 3.2. The actors of the protocol are modeled as processes that can exchange messages (algebraic terms) whereas cryptographic primitives are modeled based on equational theories. **This model assumes perfect cryptography.** An attacker may perform cryptographic operations only if relevant cryptographic keys are leaked.

ProVerif uses applied pi-calculus to specify the behaviour of the participants, communicating through messages consisting of algebraic terms. Security properties such as **reachability for checking secrecy, correspondence used for checking authenticity, and behaviour equivalence are the most common properties that are checked using ProVerif.** In this deliverable we are verifying only the first two properties while the third one (behavioral equivalence) may be relevant for proving anonymity. This is a subject of future work. The pi-calculus processes are translated into Horn clauses that are used as input by the tool's algorithm to prove the properties assuming an unbounded number of sessions. The verification process can have three outcomes: *the property is Proven; Does Not Hold; or the Process Does Not Finish (unknown result)*. If a property does not hold, ProVerif generates a trace that describes a possible attack. The main reason for a verification process not to terminate is the complexity of the protocol and underlying proof procedure that is undecidable on an unbounded number of sessions.

3.3.1 Modeling and Verification of the Onboarding Process

To model the onboarding process, we first need to model the security protocols used during this phase. Therefore, we model the schemes presented in deliverable D4.2 as a sequence chart in a tool-independent way. The goal is to use this tool-independent model to support the modeling process in various verification tools such as ProVerif and Tamarin. An overview of the notations used in our model is present in Table 3.2.

Symbol	Description
Privacy CA	Privacy Certificate Authority
DM	Domain Manager
sk_R	Root identity key
(sk_M, pk_M)	The Manufacturer's private and public key pair
(SK_CA, PK_CA)	The Privacy CA private and public key pair
KDF	Key Derivation Function

sign()	The signing operation
CMD	Connected Medical Device
HMAC	Hashed Message Authentication Code
MAC	Message Authentication Code

Table 3.2: Notation Summary

3.3.2 Description of the Verified Models and Results

3.3.2.1 Device Authentication and Credential Issuance

Figure 3.1: Device Authentication and Credential Issuance

The goal of this phase is to authenticate the medical device to the manufacturer and generate Verifiable

Credentials on the device's attributes where the Privacy CA is the issuer that creates and signs the credential. At the end of this step, any verifier can cryptographically verify the authenticity and integrity of the credentials which are represented by a crypto structure according to W3C standard, containing a conformity certificate associated to a signature.

Various keys are known before the generation of verifiable credentials begins by the actors. The device knows the root identity key sk_R , the Privacy CA knows the secret key sk_{CA} , public keys pk_{CA} and pk_M , while the manufacturer knows the public key pk_M , and secret keys sk_M and sk_R .

In the first step, the device requests the verifiable credential on attribute a_i from the Privacy CA, which responds with a random challenge c . A verifiable credential is used for all attributes, but we only consider one attribute in our model because we cannot model a set of attributes using ProVerif or Tamarin, so we decided to abstract this by using only one attribute. Next, the device generates the secret key sk_{VC} and the public key pk_{VC} for the verifiable credential. This is a simplification used to represent the secret part of the attribute key, which is used by the device to read the attribute and the public part of the attribute key generated by the Privacy CA. In the third step, the device initializes the authorization with the manufacturer by sending the challenge c and public key pk_{VC} . In the fourth step, the manufacturer responds with a random challenge c' that is used by the device to generate the signatures $sig_{R,D}$ (encrypting the concatenation of the challenges c and c' using the HMAC function on the secret key sk_R) and $sig_{VC,D}$ (signing the concatenation of the challenges c and c' using the secret key sk_{VC}). Next, the signatures are sent to the manufacturer where they are verified and a new signature sig_M is generated by signing the concatenation of the challenge c and public key with the secret key sk_M . In the sixth step, the signature is sent to the device where it is forwarded to the Privacy CA with the public key pk_{VC} . The Privacy CA verifies signature sig_M on c and pk_{VC} with pk_M and then replies to the device a set of attributes S that are signed by the device and sent back to the Privacy CA to generate the attribute keys. Finally, the Privacy CA verifies each signature of the attributes under pk_{CA} and generates the attribute keys using a key derivation function and signing it.

3.3.2.2 ProVerif Model for Device Authentication and Verifiable Credential Issuance

The full ProVerif model defined for the device authentication and verifiable credentials issuance is presented in Appendix B.1. The model represents the device authentication and credential issuance that is modeled in a tool-independent notation. As described in Section 3.3.2.1, the goal of this protocol is to authenticate a CMD to the privacy CA and create verifiable credentials over its attributes.

Listing 3.1 shows the types of the variables defined for the ProVerif model. The $skey$ and $pkey$ represent the key pair secret, public keys used for symmetric encryption. Next, the communication channels are defined, where one channel is used for the communication between the CMD and the privacy CA, while the other channel is used for the communication between the CMD and the manufacturer. The root key of the CMD is defined as a free private variable sk_R which is known only by the CMD.

```

1 type skey .
2 type pkey .
3 type attribute .
4
5 free c1: channel .
6 free c2: channel .
7 free sk_R: skey [private] .

```

Listing 3.1: ProVerif Variables

Listing 3.2 presents the functions used to model the cryptographic functions employed for generating verifiable credentials. First, the function for computing the HMAC using a bitstring and a secret key as input is defined. Next, we define the public key generation function used to create the public key based on a secret key. Then, two functions are used to compute the attribute key based on an attribute and a secret key and to convert an attribute to a bitstring. The *sign* function is used to sign a message of type bitstring using a secret key, while the *kdf* function is used to compute the attribute key using a secret key.

The reduction rules are used to retrieve the content from signed messages, verify the signature of a message using the public key of the sender, and check the signature of a message containing an HMAC.

```

1
2 (* Function for creating a HMAC using a secret key and a message *)
3 fun hmac(bitstring, skey): bitstring.
4 (* Function for deriving a public key from a given secret key *)
5 fun pk(skey): pkey.
6
7 (* Function for signing a message with a secret key *)
8 fun sign(bitstring, skey): bitstring.
9
10 (* Function for converting a variable of type attribute to bitstring
    *)
11 fun attributeToBitstring(attribute): bitstring.
12
13 (* Function for computing the attribute key *)
14 fun kdf(bitstring, skey): bitstring.
15
16 (* Reduction rule that the original message can be recovered from its
    signature *)
17 reduc forall m: bitstring, sk: skey; getmess(sign(m, sk)) = m.
18 (* Reduction rule that a signature can be verified with the
    corresponding
19 public key *)
20 reduc forall m: bitstring, sk: skey; checksign(sign(m, sk), pk(sk)) =
    m.
21 (* Reduction rule that a signature can be verified with the
    corresponding public key *)
22 reduc forall m: bitstring, sk: skey; checksignhmac(hmac(m, sk), sk) =
    m.
23

```

Listing 3.2: ProVerif Functions

Listing 3.3 shows the queries defined for our ProVerif model to verify the security requirements. The secrecy of the secret keys *sk_R*, *sk_VC*, and *sk_CA* is verified to ensure that these keys are not leaked to the attacker. Another query is used to verify if the attacker can compute the key *sk_R* using free variables. Events are defined to check whether an attacker cannot skip the protocol steps to authenticate or solve a challenge such that for every authentication process finished there needs to be a starting event with the same parameter before. Finally, an event *check_reachability* is used to verify that at least one path in the protocol reaches successfully the end of the protocol.

```

1
2 (* Verify the secrecy of the variables *)
3 query secret sk_R.

```

```

4 query secret sk_VC.
5 query secret sk_CA.
6 query secret sk_M.
7
8 (* Verify the attacker cannot compute keys using from free names *)
9 query attacker(sk_R).
10
11 event beginAuth(bitstring).
12 event endAuth(bitstring).
13 event beginChallengeCA(bitstring).
14 event endChallengeCA(bitstring).
15 event check_reachability().
16
17 (* Query that the endAuth event follows the beginAuth event *)
18 query x: bitstring; inj-event(endAuth(x)) ==> inj-event(beginAuth(x)).
19 query x: bitstring; inj-event(endChallengeCA(x)) ==> inj-event(
    beginChallengeCA(x)).
20 query event(check_reachability()).

```

Listing 3.3: ProVerif Queries

In ProVerif each actor of the protocol needs to be modeled separately, thus, the behavior of each actor is defined in a process. Each message of an actor is defined as presented in the diagram from Figure 3.1. The full ProVerif model containing the behavior of each actor of the protocol is presented in Appendix B.1

3.3.2.3 Tamarin Model for Device Authentication and Verifiable Credential Issuance

Tamarin along with ProVerif is one of the most mature tools for automatic verification of security protocols. Similarly to ProVerif, it works in the symbolic model, i.e. assumes perfect cryptography and uses algebraic terms in the bodies of the exchanged messages.

Tamarin specifies the protocol in terms of multi-set rewriting rules and as such belongs to the larger family of tools based on rewriting logic. The properties to be verified are specified as formulas in a fragment of First-Order Logic (FOL) and are checked on the traces derived from the protocol runs. Cryptographic primitives are specified in equational theories. Internally Tamarin uses a constraints-solving algorithm for falsification and verification of properties assuming unbounded number of sessions. Like in ProVerif, non-termination is a possible outcome. In this section we will explain the Tamarin model of the device authentication and verifiable credential issuance protocol of ENTRUST along with an explanation of the language constructs. The full model is given in Appendix B.1

```

1 theory VCI
2 begin
3
4 builtins: symmetric-encryption, signing
5 functions: hmac/2, vc/1, kdf/2
6
7 //pre-shared keys infra
8 rule Register_psk:
9   [Fr(~skr)]
10 -->
11   [!Psk_skr('d', 'm', ~skr)]

```



```

12
13 //public keys infra
14 rule Register_pk:
15   [Fr(~skCA)]
16 -->
17   [!Ltk('ca', ~skCA), !Pk('ca', pk(~skCA)), Out(pk(~skCA))]

```

Listing 3.4: Definition of a Tamarin theory and public-private key infrastructure

A Taming model is defined as a theory (see listing 3.4) that contains declarations of the used builtin crypto primitives, declarations of functions and the rules for modeling the protocol. Our theory uses the predefined primitives of symmetric encryption and signing. In addition to these builtins, users can define their own primitives by using equational theories (not used in this model).

Three functions are declared by giving their names and arities (number of arguments): for calculation of Message Authentication Codes (MAC), for creation of verifiable credentials and for key derivation (*kdf*). The function *vc* abstracts the cryptographic details for calculating the verifiable credentials for a set of attributes.

Each theory consists of a number of rewriting rules. Each rule has a name, a left-hand side called premis and a right-hand side called consequence. The left-hand and right-hand sides are sequences of terms. At any stage of the execution of the protocol the state of the protocol consists of a number of possibly repeated terms called facts. A rule is executed if its left-hand side matches the facts in the current state. Upon the rule execution, the matched facts are consumed (deleted from the state) and the terms of the rule's right-hand side are included in the state. The effect is rewriting of some of the facts in the state with new facts.

Rules may also have trace actions, exemplified later in this section. Every time a rule is executed, the trace actions of the rule are added to the trace. In this way the result of a protocol execution is a sequence of sets of trace actions called trace. The protocol properties are expressed as formulas over the traces (also exemplified later).

Listing 3.4 has two rules that establish the shared key and public/private keys infrastructure. Rule *Register_psk*s creates a random (fresh) value *skr* via the left-hand side term *Fr* that will serve as a shared key between the device and the manufacturer. The fact about this shared key will be included in the protocol state by the right-hand side term *!Psk_skr*. The exclamation mark indicates this fact as persistent, that is, it will not be deleted from the state if matched by a rule.

Rule *Register_pk* creates a pair of private and public keys for the certification authority (CA). The private key *skCA* is created as a random fresh value and stored as a long term key via the term *!Ltk*. The public key is obtained by the builtin function *pk* applied over the private key and stored via the persistent term *!Pk*. Finally, the public key is made known to everyone by the term *Out* which is the reserved term for sending a message over the open channel. The pair of public/private keys for the manufacturer are created in a similar way (please consult the full model in the appendix).

```

1 rule D_1:
2   [Fr(~a)]
3 -->
4   [Out(<'ca', ~a>), D_1(~a)]

```

Listing 3.5: First step in the protocol

The first step of the protocol is taken by the device that sends a set of attributes to the CA. Sets can't be directly modeled in Tamarin. We can model it as a single attribute or as a tuple of fixed number of

attributes. For the sake of simplicity and without limiting the generality we model just a single attribute being sent as shown in listing 3.5. The attribute is obtained as a fresh value. For convenience we assign an identifier to each role to indicate the intended recipient of the messages. In this rule the message that is sent via *Out* is the tuple consisting of *ca* and the attribute. The value of the generated attribute is also included in the protocol state for usage in the later steps via the term *D_1*.

```

1 rule CA_1:
2   [In(<'ca', a>), Fr(~c)]
3 -->
4   [Out(<'d', ~c>), CA_1(a, ~c)]

```

Listing 3.6: Second step of the protocol

In the second protocol step the CA reads the message from the open channel via the predefined term *In* and assigns the value of the received attribute to the variable *a* (see listing 3.6). It generates a challenge (fresh value *c*) and sends it to the device *d*. The received attribute and the challenge are stored for the following protocol steps as fact *CA_1*.

The following protocol steps are modeled in a similar way. The only difference is step 5 modeled with a rule that includes a trace action (3.7).

```

1 rule D_3:
2   [In(<'d', c1>), D_2(a, c), !Psk_skr('d', 'm', skr), !Ltk('d', skVC)]
3 --[Initiate('d', 'm', <c, c1>)]->
4   [Out(<'m', hmac(<c, c1>, skr), sign(<c, c1>, skVC)>), D_3(a, c, c1)]

```

Listing 3.7: Example of trace action

This step marks the initiation of the authentication of a device by the manufacturer on the values of the two challenges *c* and *c1*. The execution of this rule will result in including the trace action *Initiate* in the protocol trace. The device sends the MAC of the concatenated challenges to the manufacturer along with the signature of the challenges using previously created secret key *skVC*. Here *sign* is a function defined in the builtin theory *signing*.

```

1 rule M_2:
2   [In(<'m', hmac(<c, c1>, skr), sig>), M_1(c, pkVC, c1), !Psk_skr('d',
3     'm', skr), !Ltk('m', skM)]
4 --[Eq(verify(sig, <c, c1>, pkVC), true), Auth('d', 'm', <c, c1>),
5   Initiate_M('m', 'ca', <c, pkVC>)]->
6   [Out(<'d', sign(<c, pkVC>, skM)>)]

```

Listing 3.8: Authentication of a device by the manufacturer

The next rule shows how the manufacturer authenticates the device by checking the MAC and by verifying the signature. The check of the MAC is done by the matching of the values in the term *In* which is only possible if the manufacturer knows the shared key *skr*. In Tamarin the verification of the signature is done as a trace action *Eq* and the *verify* function part of the builtin theory *signing*. In order to verify the signature, the function *verify* has to return *true*. If the rule is successfully executed the trace action *Auth* will be included in the trace indicating a successful authentication of the device by the manufacturer over the two challenges. At the same time, the manufacturer initiates its authentication by the CA over the challenge *c* and the public key for the verifiable credentials *pkVC*.

```

1 //step10
2 rule CA_3:
3   [In(<'ca', sig>), CA_2(a, vc, pkVC), !Ltk('ca', skCA)]

```



```

4 --[Eq(verify(sig, a, pkVC), true)]->
5   [Out(<'d', kdf(a, skCA), sign(kdf(a, skCA), skCA)>), CA_3(a, vc,
6     pkVC, kdf(a, skCA))]
7 //step11
8 rule D_6:
9   [In(<'d', ak, sig>), !Psk_skr('d', 'm', skr), !Pk('ca', pkCA)]
10 --[Eq(verify(sig, ak, pkCA), true), Success(skr)]->
11  []

```

Listing 3.9: The last steps of the protocol

In the last two steps of the protocol (listing 3.9), the CA verifies the signed attribute a and creates an attribute key using a key derivation function kdf . Recall that this function acts as an abstraction over the cryptographic details of the key generation. The key then is signed and both the key and the signature are sent to the device. The device verifies the signature and this is the last step in the protocol model. Rule D_6 adds the trace action $Success$ with parameter the shared key between the device and manufacturer. This trace action will serve two purposes when various properties are checked: to mark the end of the protocol run and to indicate which key can be checked for secrecy.

We will now describe which protocol properties are checked and how they are expressed in Tamarin. The first property is a sanity check if the complete protocol can be run. As already mentioned, the properties are expressed as FOL formulas over traces. In terms of traces, we are interested in the existence of at least one trace that contains the trace action $Success$ which is the indication of reaching the end of the protocol. The following listing shows how this property is expressed in Tamarin.

```

1 lemma honest: // the protocol can run to the end
2 exists-trace 'Ex k #i. Success(k) @ #i'

```

Listing 3.10: Sanity check for non-empty set of protocol traces

The trace is a sequence of trace actions ordered in the time of adding them to the trace. The time of observing $Success$ is denoted as the variable $\#i$. The property simply checks if there exists a trace that contains a moment $\#i$ at which $Success$ is observed in the trace.

We will check mainly two kinds of properties: secrecy and authentication. The secrecy properties check if the adversary can know certain values, usually keys. We will illustrate this by checking if the adversary can learn the shared key between the device and the manufacturer. This key is kept as a parameter of $Success$ action. The property is specified as follows:

```

1 lemma shared_key_secretcy: // shared secret between device and
2   manufacturer is not revealed during protocol execution
3 'not(Ex k #i #j. Success(k) @ #i & K(k) @ #j)'

```

Listing 3.11: Key secrecy property

In the Tamarin syntax $K(k)$ denotes the knowledge of the adversary K of some value, in this case the shared key k . The property is a negation of the fact that the adversary knows the key at some moment during the protocol run.

Apart from the shown property, other properties that check for the secrecy of the involved private keys can be formulated as well in a similar manner.

We also formulated two properties that check for authentication. An example of a check if the device is successfully authenticated by the manufacturer is shown below.


```

1 lemma device_auth: // device is authenticated by the manufacturer
2 '(All d m data #i. Auth(d, m, data) @ #i ==> (Ex #j. Initiate(d, m,
   data) @ #j & (#j < #i)))'
```

Listing 3.12: Checking of authentication property

The property states that in every trace in which action *Auth* is observed for the device and the manufacturer on some data, it has been preceded by the action *Initiate* for the same pair of device and manufacturer and on the same data.

All the formulated properties are successfully verified by the Tamarin prover. It usually takes 1-2 seconds to verify them. This result shows the correctness of the protocol with regards to the specified properties.

3.3.2.4 Device Onboarding - Device Authentication by EAP-PSK

In this deliverable we will present and verify only the initial step in the device onboarding protocol. The entire onboarding protocol is described in deliverable D4.2 [27].

The step that will be modeled and verified here is the delegated device authentication when the device attempts to join a domain (e.g. when the device is deployed in the hospital premises). This step is by itself a separate protocol which was already described in deliverable D3.1. Again in D3.1 a formal model in VerifPal was presented but due to the inefficient verification process we decided to switch to ProVerif and Tamarin as formal verification tools.

The delegated authentication is based on the EAP-PSK protocol. We model the protocol in ProVerif and Tamarin.

3.3.2.5 ProVerif Model of EAP-PSK

In deliverable D3.1 [26], the EAP-PSK protocol was modeled and verified using both Verifpal and Proverif. Although we did not go into much detail regarding the ProVerif syntax, we explained in Section 3.3 how ProVerif works and its syntax. Furthermore, Appendix B.1 contains an improved version of the ProVerif model for the EAP-PSK. A more detailed description of the EAP-PSK protocol is present in deliverable D3.1.

```

1
2 (* Verify the attacker cannot compute keys using from free names *)
3 query attacker(msk_aaa).
4 query attacker(eap_session_key_cmd).
5 query attacker(eap_session_key_aaa).
6
7 (* Verify the secrecy of the variables *)
8 query secret msk_aaa.
9 query secret eap_session_key_cmd.
10 query secret eap_session_key_aaa.
11 query secret kdk.
12 query secret ak.
13 query secret k.
14
15 event beginAuthAaa(mac).
16 event endAuthAaa(mac).
```



```

17 event beginAuthCmd(mac).
18 event endAuthCmd(mac).
19
20 event beginMskProvisioning(bitstring).
21 event endMskProvisioning(bitstring).
22
23 (* Authenticate AAA to CMD using MAC_P*)
24 query x: mac; inj-event(endAuthAaa(x)) ==> inj-event(beginAuthAaa(x)).
25 (* Authenticate CMD to AAA using MAC_S *)
26 query x: mac; inj-event(endAuthCmd(x)) ==> inj-event(beginAuthCmd(x)).
27 (* For every decrypted MSK key by the DM there is a provisioning phase
    for the MSK *)
28 query x: bitstring; event(endMskProvisioning(x)) ==> event(
    beginMskProvisioning(x)).

```

Listing 3.13: Queries EAP-PSK ProVerif Model

Listing 3.13 shows the queries used to verify that an attacker cannot compute the master session key generated by the successful authentication, EAP session keys and that these keys are not leaked. Furthermore, the authentication process of the CMD and AAA server is verified through events along with the provisioning process of the master session key to the CMD.

3.3.2.6 Tamarin Model of EAP-PSK

The model was already described in abstract terms in D3.1 and a VerifPal model was discussed. Here we explain the most important fragments of the Tamarin model. The syntax and the meaning of the Tamarin constructs were explained in a previous section.

Recall that the participants in the protocol are the device, the domain manager (DM) and the manufacturer represented by its authentication and authorization authority (AAA). The authentication is performed between the device and the AAA while the DM only forwards/delegates messages among them.

```

1 theory Onboarding
2 begin
3
4 builtins: symmetric-encryption
5 functions: mac/2, hkdf1/2, hkdf2/2
6
7 //pre-shared keys infra
8 rule Register_psk:
9   [Fr(~ak), Fr(~kdk), Fr(~k)]
10 -->
11   [!Psk_ak('id_s', 'id_p', ~ak), !Psk_kdk('id_s', 'id_p', ~kdk), !
    Psk_k('id_s', 'dm', ~k)]

```

Listing 3.14: Shared keys infrastructure of EAP-PSK

The shared keys (authentication key, key derivation key, and the assumed key k for secure communication between the AAA and DM) are created as fresh values and registered as facts by the rule *Register_psk*.

```

1 //step1
2 rule Aaa_1:

```



```

3  [Fr(~rand_s)]
4  -->
5  [Aaa_1(~rand_s), Out(<'dm', 'id_s', ~rand_s>)]

```

Listing 3.15: Step 1 in the delegated EAP-PSK

In the first step, the AAA generates a random number and sends it to the device along with its identity using the DM as intermediary.

```

1  //step3
2  rule Cmd_1:
3    [In(<'cmd', id_s, rand_s>), Fr(~rand_p), !Psk_ak(id_s, 'id_p', ak)]
4  --[CmdAuthReq('id_p', ak)]->
5    [Cmd_1(~rand_p, id_s, rand_s), Out(<'dm', ~rand_p, 'id_p', mac(ak,
    <'id_p', ~rand_p, id_s, rand_s>))]

```

Listing 3.16: Device receives the challenge and the identity of the AAA

The device receives the challenge and the AAA's identity and in turn creates a new random challenge, then forms the MAC of the four values according to the EAP-PSK using the authentication key and sends it to the AAA. The action fact *CmdAuthReq* marks the initiation of the authentication.

The next listing shows that AAA verifies the MAC based on the pattern matching in the message.

```

1  //step5
2  rule Aaa_2:
3    [Aaa_1(rand_s), !Psk_ak('id_s', id_p, ak), !Psk_kdk('id_s', id_p,
    kdk), Fr(~payload), In(<'aaa', rand_p, id_p, mac(ak, <id_p, rand_p,
    'id_s', rand_s>))] //pattern match checks the mac
4  --[AuthAaa(id_p, ak)]->
5    [Aaa_2(rand_s, hkdf1(rand_p, kdk), hkdf2(rand_p, kdk)), Out(<'dm',
    mac(ak, <'id_s', rand_p>), ~payload, mac(hkdf1(rand_p, kdk), <~
    payload, rand_s>))] //computes session and msk keys, stores them

```

Listing 3.17: AAA authenticates the device

The action fact *AuthAaa* marks that the device has been authenticated by successfully checking the MAC using the shared authentication key. We will not explain the next steps in the protocol, the reader is referred to the appendix to check the remaining steps in the model.

The properties that are verified are the sanity check if the protocol can be run until its end (a standard idiom for Tamarin), the secrecy of the three shared keys, and the mutual authentication of the device and the AAA. The following listing shows the specifications of some of these properties.

```

1  lemma secrecy1:
2  'not(Ex Id k #i #j. AuthAaa(Id, k) @ #i & K(k) @ #j)'
3  .....
4  lemma secrecy3:
5  'not(Ex k #i #j. Msk_Dm(k) @ #i & K(k) @ #j)'
6
7  lemma cmd_auth:
8  '(All id k #i. AuthAaa(id, k) @ #i ==> (Ex #j. CmdAuthReq(id, k) @ #j)
    )'
9
10 lemma honest:

```



```
11 exists -trace 'Ex k #i. Msk_Dm(k) @ #i'
```

Listing 3.18: Some of the verified properties of EAP-PSK

All the properties were successfully verified in a few seconds.

3.3.3 Results and Discussion

As described in the introduction of Section 3.3, ProVerif is used to check the secrecy of keys, correspondence, and behaviour equivalence. We used ProVerif to check for the secrecy of the secret key of the Privacy CA, Manufacturer, and the root identity key provided to the device. Furthermore, we defined events for the beginning of the authentication process of the device to the manufacturer and one for finishing the process. Another set of events is used to check that the challenge generated by the Privacy CA is solved. For both verifications, every *end* event must be preceded by exactly one **begin** event. To ensure the completion of the protocol, we defined an event *check_reachability* to verify that at least one path reaches the end of the protocol successfully. This is a safety check to ensure that the model does not have a step that does not allow to finish the protocol.

Using ProVerif, we ensure the secrecy of the secret keys provided to the Privacy CA, verifiable credential private key, and root identity key of the device. Also, the device's authentication to the manufacturer is verified along with solving the challenge generated by the Privacy CA. The output of the ProVerif model is presented in Listing 3.19.

```
1 Query secret sk_R_2,sk_R_1 is true.
2
3 Query secret sk_VC is true.
4
5 Query secret sk_CA_1,sk_CA is true.
6
7 Query secret sk_M_1,sk_M is true.
8
9 Query not attacker(sk_R[]) is true.
10
11 Query inj-event(endAuth(x)) ==> inj-event(beginAuth(x)) is true.
12
13 Query inj-event(endChallengeCA(x)) ==> inj-event(beginChallengeCA(x))
    is true.
14
15 Query not event(check_reachability) is false.
```

Listing 3.19: Device Authentication and Credential Issuance ProVerif Results

Chapter 4

Software Verification and Threat Modeling

This chapter provides information with regards to the **Threat Modeling** and **Software Verification** modules of ENTRUST.

The Threat Modeling module is used in order to collect the relevant threat landscape of a specific device during the design phase. This is achieved by getting vulnerability data from established databases, such as NIST NVD. Then, based on this information, it creates attack scenarios that are tailored to match the characteristics of a device. These attack scenarios are generated using Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI), in order to generate a human readable attack vector that is based on data from multiple data sources, with the possibility of supporting different data formats.

The Software Verification module is responsible for checking if the software that is going to be deployed on medical devices is vulnerable. This is done by scanning the modules that are going to be used, in order to ensure that malicious patterns are not deployed, and fuzzing, in order to verify if hidden vulnerabilities can be found.

This section begins by presenting the information flows of both modules, and how they are integrated into ENTRUST. It then offers an overview regarding the adoption of technologies, focusing on the reasoning of using generative AI in the context of ENTRUST of generating a threat landscape tailored for a specific device, based on intelligence from public databases. Another issue that is going to be tackled is the fuzzing methods that are used during the software verification, with the roles of finding hidden vulnerabilities in medical devices. Afterwards, the current status of the components is provided, referring to the current implementation of the modules, as well as their deployment method. The chapter ends with the definition of the interface between the Software Verification and Threat Modeling modules and their clients, specifically the Risk Assessment and Digital Twin modules. In this section, the output of the modules is presented, as well as the main documentation method of the APIs.

4.1 GenAI assisted threat modeling

In this section, the core of ENTRUST Threat Modeling module. Specifically, the **Large Language Model (LLM)** is presented, whose role is to process the information collected from existing databases, such as NIST NVD, in order to create threat landscapes that are tailored to a specific device. Our goal is to showcase and investigate the appropriate format of the output of an LLM be in order to enable the Digital Twin component to perform an attack emulation path analysis.

This section begins with the reasoning of using genAI techniques in the threat modeling component. It then proceeds with descriptions of the underlying technical details, such as using pretrained models and

using a context-based approach. It then tackles the problem of hallucinations, that LLMs are prone to. Later the generation of the output is presented. The section concludes with the implementation in the context of ENTRUST using LLama2 [72].

4.1.1 Reasoning behind the usage of generative AI techniques

Connected medical devices (CMDs) are integral to modern healthcare, enabling remote monitoring and real-time interventions. However, their widespread adoption introduces significant security risks. CMDs vary widely in terms of communication protocols, hardware, and software, making it challenging to create a unified security framework. Additionally, legacy systems and the need for secure interoperability further complicate the landscape. Ensuring patient safety and addressing adversarial threats are critical considerations.

Given the complexity of CMDs, the ENTRUST project team explored the potential benefits of the use of generative AI techniques for threat modeling. Traditional methods struggle to handle the intricacies of CMD ecosystems. AI, on the other hand, can analyze large datasets, identify patterns, and model complex interactions effectively. In dynamic environments with evolving threats, AI models adapt and learn from real-world data, improving threat assessments over time. By automating diverse attack scenarios, AI helps identify vulnerabilities and optimizes resource efficiency for security experts.

The ENTRUST project views this exploration as a research initiative. Integrating AI into threat modeling aims to enhance CMD security, minimize risks, and foster trust in connected healthcare. Ongoing work involves developing AI-driven threat models, evaluating their effectiveness, and refining the followed approach. Ultimately, this initiative goes beyond technology, and extends to safeguarding patients, healthcare providers, and the entire CMD ecosystem based on:

- Ability to consume diverse data: Generative AI models have the capability to process and understand data in various formats, communication styles, and languages. This is essential for threat modeling as it involves analyzing a wide range of information sources, including technical documents, security reports, vulnerability databases, and even informal discussions or forum threads. Generative AI can effectively handle the diversity of these data sources.
- Capacity to ingest large amounts of data: Threat modeling requires processing large volumes of data to identify potential threats and vulnerabilities. Generative AI models excel at handling large datasets, allowing for comprehensive analysis and identification of patterns and trends. By ingesting significant amounts of data, the models can capture a broader and more accurate representation of the threat landscape.
- Production of context-aware text in a human-friendly format: Generative AI models, especially language models, can generate text that is contextually aware and understandable to humans. This is crucial for threat modeling as the goal is to provide users, such as security administrators, with an overview of the threat landscape in a format they can easily comprehend. By generating human-friendly descriptions and explanations, generative AI techniques facilitate better understanding and help create more effective defense strategies.
- Production of attack scenarios: Generative AI can be used to create attack scenarios by applying known threat vectors on specific devices or modules within an infrastructure. By simulating these attack scenarios, the security administrator gains a deeper awareness of the possible attack vectors and can better prioritize and strategize their defense measures. Generative AI enables the generation of realistic attack scenarios by leveraging its understanding of diverse data sources and context.

- Experimentation and unification of data: Generative AI techniques, particularly with the use of context-aware large language models (LLMs), enable experimentation and unification of data from different sources. This means that diverse data can be combined, unified, and analyzed together, allowing for a comprehensive understanding of the threat landscape. The power of context-aware LLMs helps in leveraging the combined knowledge from various sources, enhancing the accuracy and effectiveness of the threat modeling component.

These capabilities ultimately contribute to providing a clear and easily understandable overview of the threat landscape, empowering security administrators to create better defense strategies.

4.1.2 Pretrained Models

In this section, the concept of a pretrained model will be presented. Concrete examples of tools that allow the usage of this type of model will also be given.

Pretrained models in Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks offer substantial advantages, particularly the ability to bypass the need for training models from scratch. These models are already trained on extensive and diverse datasets, capturing a wide array of linguistic patterns and world knowledge. This pretraining equips them with a strong foundational understanding, enabling them to perform various NLP tasks with high accuracy and efficiency. By leveraging these pretrained models, developers can significantly reduce the time, computational resources, and data required for training. This approach is particularly beneficial for tasks like text classification, translation, summarization, and conversational AI, where rapid deployment and high-quality results are paramount.

CMDs often operate in resource-constrained environments, and by utilizing pretrained models, we tap into their existing knowledge and linguistic patterns. This efficiency is crucial for real-time threat assessment and decision-making. Additionally, pretrained models allow us to skip time-consuming training phases, accelerating development timelines. We can focus on fine-tuning specific tasks rather than starting from scratch. Ultimately, using pretrained models aligns perfectly with ENTRUST's mission—to secure CMDs effectively, efficiently, and with a focus on patient well-being.

Some tools that provides such models are HuggingFace [43] and Ollama [66]. These allow the developers to use pretrained models in order to develop applications using LLMs at a much faster rate.

HuggingFace provides Python libraries, particularly for the Transformers. These supports a wide range of NLP tasks, such as text classification, question answering, and text generation, using models like BERT, Llama2, and Phi3. It is designed for ease of use, offering simple APIs that allow users to quickly implement and fine-tune models. Additionally, Hugging Face provides the Datasets library, which simplifies the process of loading and processing large datasets, and the Tokenizers library, which offers efficient and fast tokenization for various languages.

Ollama is a standalone LLM manager. It allows one to download, manage and expose LLM as APIs. Some of their supported models include Meta's Llama2 [72], and Microsoft's Phi3 [12]. The application also provides a way to customize these models by providing specific parameters such as *Temperature* that can modify the behaviour of the model.

4.1.3 Context Window

In this section, the concept of a context window, which is used by a LLM, is going to be presented. This will represent the foundation for the next subsection in which the Retrieval-Augmented Generation method will be presented.

The context window in large language models (LLMs) is technically defined by the model's architecture and its capacity to process and retain information over a span of tokens. This capability is primarily facilitated by the self-attention mechanism in transformer models, which allows each token in the input sequence to attend to every other token. The size of the context window is determined by the maximum number of tokens that can be simultaneously fed into the model's encoder-decoder architecture. For instance, in models like LLaMA2, a context window of 4096 tokens [72] means that during each forward pass, the model can consider up to 4096 tokens to generate its output. This involves maintaining a memory of token embeddings and their positional encodings to ensure that the relationships between tokens are accurately represented. As the context window size increases, the computational and memory requirements also scale, often requiring more advanced hardware or optimization techniques to handle larger windows efficiently. Additionally, the design of attention mechanisms, such as using sparse attention or efficient transformers, can significantly impact how effectively a model utilizes its context window without incurring prohibitive computational costs.

4.1.4 Retrieval-Augmented Generation

Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) is an advanced approach in natural language processing that combines the strengths of retrieval-based models with generative models to enhance the quality and relevance of generated text [47]. In RAG, the process begins by using a retrieval system to fetch relevant documents or information from a large corpus based on the input query. This retrieved information is then fed into a generative model, such as a transformer-based language model, which uses this context to generate more informed and accurate responses. The integration of retrieval mechanisms allows RAG models to access a vast amount of external knowledge, enabling them to produce outputs that are not only coherent but also factually grounded. This hybrid approach is particularly useful in scenarios requiring up-to-date or domain-specific information. By leveraging both retrieval and generation, RAG models effectively bridge the gap between static knowledge embedded in model parameters and dynamic, external information, leading to more robust and versatile language understanding and generation capabilities.

4.1.5 Context Switching vs Fine-Tuning

RAG and fine-tuning are two distinct strategies used to enhance the performance of large language models, each with its own strengths and applications. In this subsection a comparison between these two techniques is going to be presented.

Fine-tuning involves taking a pre-trained model and training it further on a specific dataset to adapt its parameters to the nuances of a particular task or domain. This method can yield highly specialized models with improved accuracy for the targeted applications but requires significant computational resources and can be time-consuming. In contrast, RAG combines retrieval mechanisms with generative models to dynamically incorporate external, up-to-date information during inference. This approach does not alter the underlying model parameters but enhances its ability to produce relevant and accurate responses by leveraging a vast external corpus. While fine-tuning excels in scenarios where domain-specific knowledge and deep understanding are paramount, RAG offers greater flexibility and scalability, particularly for applications requiring real-time access to diverse and evolving information. RAG is also more efficient in terms of computational resources since it avoids the need for extensive retraining. Thus, the choice between RAG and fine-tuning depends on the specific requirements of the task, with RAG being preferable for dynamic information retrieval and fine-tuning for deep, domain-specific adaptations.

4.1.6 Hallucinations

LLMs are powerful tools for generating text, but they are prone to a phenomenon known as hallucinations. Hallucinations occur when the model produces text that is coherent and plausible-sounding but factually incorrect or nonsensical [74]. This issue arises because LLMs generate responses based on patterns and correlations in the training data rather than true understanding or verification of facts. Hallucinations can be particularly problematic in applications requiring high accuracy and reliability, such as medical information dissemination, legal advice, or customer support. Addressing hallucinations involves strategies like refining the training data, incorporating RAG to provide grounded information, and enhancing model interpretability to allow users to discern the reliability of generated content. Despite these efforts, completely eliminating hallucinations remains a challenge, highlighting the importance of human oversight and the development of more robust mechanisms for fact-checking and validation in the deployment of LLMs.

4.1.7 Output consumption

In this subsection starts with describing how the process of encoding and decoding works. After, an example of an output from a LLM is going to be presented.

Output consumption involves interpreting and utilizing the generated text based on the model's decoded embeddings. These embeddings are high-dimensional vectors that represent the semantic meaning of the input tokens processed by the model. During decoding, the model transforms these embeddings back into human-readable text. The quality and relevance of the generated output depend on how well the embeddings capture the context and nuances of the input.

In the context of ENTRUST, once the LLM has received data of a specific device and a specific vulnerability it will start to generate attack scenarios. Even if this task can be time consuming, since this is not going to be performed in a real-time manner, this won't impact the performance of the ENTRUST framework as a whole. The LLM sends back the generated attack scenarios only after the entire output has finished being generated.

This has been tested using various IoT and networking devices. For example, if we want to get attack scenarios for a Cisco router that can be described with the Common Platform Enumeration (CPE) scheme *cpe:2.3:o:cisco:ios_xe:16.12.*.*.*.*.**, a vulnerability description, namely for *CVE-2023-20273* is *A vulnerability in the web UI feature of Cisco IOS XE Software could allow an authenticated, remote attacker to inject commands with the privileges of root. This vulnerability is due to insufficient input validation. An attacker could exploit this vulnerability by sending crafted input to the web UI. A successful exploit could allow the attacker to inject commands to the underlying operating system with root privileges.*, and the attack type, *Improper Neutralization of Special Elements used in an OS Command ('OS Command Injection')* the model is going to generate the following attack scenarios:

1. **Remote Authenticated Attack:** An attacker could exploit this vulnerability by sending crafted input to the web UI, potentially leading to injection of malicious commands with root privileges. This could allow the attacker to gain unauthorized access to sensitive information or disrupt system operations.
2. **Local Privilege Escalation:** An attacker with low-privileged access to the system could exploit this vulnerability to inject malicious commands, potentially leading to elevation of their privileges to root level. This could allow the attacker to perform malicious actions with increased access and control over the system.

3. **Denial of Service (DoS):** An attacker could exploit this vulnerability to inject malicious commands that consume excessive system resources, potentially leading to a denial of service attack. This could cause the system to become unavailable or slow, disrupting critical operations and services.
4. **Command Injection with Persistence:** An attacker could exploit this vulnerability to inject malicious commands with persistence, allowing them to maintain access to the system even after a reboot or system update. This could provide the attacker with long-term access and control over the system.
5. **Combination with Other Vulnerabilities:** An attacker could combine this vulnerability with other known vulnerabilities in the system, potentially leading to more severe attacks and exploitation. For example, an attacker could use this vulnerability in conjunction with a command injection vulnerability in another component of the system, allowing them to inject malicious commands with increased effectiveness.

This output has been generated with a **Llama2-13b** model that has not been fine-tuned. Other alternatives include other versions of Llama2, such as 7b, but also other model such as Microsoft Phi3 [12].

4.1.8 ENTRUST Implementation

This section aims to present the implementation of the system that uses LLM for the Threat Modeling task, including the data sources that are going to be used for RAG. Examples of prompts will also be given. This section ends by describing how this output can be consumed in an supervised manner in order to minimize the impact of possible hallucinations.

To implement a LLM solution that is able to assist in the process of threat modeling, we have used a **Llama2-13b** pretrained model that has not been fine-tuned that is exposed as an API using Ollama [66].

LLaMA2 operates as a transformer-based language model, utilizing vast amounts of text data to learn patterns and structures in human language. During training, it processes large datasets to develop an understanding of syntax, semantics, and context. The input to LLaMA2 consists of text prompts, which the model encodes into high-dimensional vectors. These vectors are then processed through multiple layers of attention mechanisms and neural networks to generate coherent and contextually relevant output. The output is typically a sequence of text that continues or responds to the input, making it suitable for tasks like text generation, translation, summarization, and conversational AI.

In order to create the LLM that has been trained using general knowledge, in order to process security data, we have used a context-switching approach based on RAG. This is done by querying vulnerability and attack databases such as MITRE CWE [18] and NIST NVD [64].

The choice of using context switching and not fine-tuning is motivated by the heavy resource usage that fine-tuning would require. The time cost of fine-tuning represents another reason for using a RAG approach. This way, the LLM has access to the current threat landscape faster, without the resource consumption or the delay that the fine-tuning would induce.

MITRE CWE is a comprehensive list of software and hardware weaknesses that are known to cause security vulnerabilities, managed by MITRE Corporation. The CWE list categorizes weaknesses into a structured format, allowing for easier identification, assessment, and mitigation of potential risks. It comes as a XML file that offers intelligence regarding attack types, such as their category and possible mitigations.

NIST NVD is a repository of standards-based vulnerability management data represented using the Security Content Automation Protocol. NVD provides detailed information about various vulnerabilities, including their impact, severity, and potential mitigation strategies. The database is continuously updated with new vulnerabilities, ensuring that security professionals have access to the latest information. It provides an API [61] that allows a user to query vulnerabilities after specific characteristics, such as the impacted devices via CPE identifier, severity via CVSS vector, or attack method via CWE identifier. In Python-based projects, developers are able to use NVDLib, a library that provides an API wrapper in order to ease the querying and the ingestion of information from the database.

The Threat Modeling Module initially queries the NIST NVD through their API by using the *NVDLib* library to obtain CVEs. These CVEs include CWE and CPE identifiers. Utilizing these identifiers, the module processes the CWE database file from MITRE to gather information on attack methods and Common Attack Pattern Enumeration and Classification (CAPEC) identifiers. This data is used in order to create the context for LLM, in order to make the LLM give security-oriented results. This process is illustrated in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: RAG implementation for Threat Modeling

After, to generate attack scenarios, a prompt is generated using data from NIST NVD and MITRE CWE in the format described in Listing 4.1.

```
prompt = 'Device: {device}; Vulnerability: {attack_description}; Focus on {attack_type}'
```

Listing 4.1: Prompt format for threat modeling

Device, represents device characteristics that are received from Risk Assessment module. This includes the CPE and the name of the device. *Attack_description* represents vulnerability description from NIST NVD. *Attack_type* is the attack identifier from MITRE CWE, used in order to generate scenarios that are specific for an attack method.

For example, for the previously example of a Cisco Router, the prompt used to generate attack scenarios can be found in Listing 4.2


```

1 prompt = 'Device: cpe:2.3:o:cisco:ios\_xe:16.12:*:*:*:*:*:*
2 ; Vulnerability: A vulnerability in the web UI feature of Cisco IOS XE
  Software could allow an authenticated, remote attacker to inject
  commands with the privileges of root. This vulnerability is due to
  insufficient input validation. An attacker could exploit this
  vulnerability by sending crafted input to the web UI. A successful
  exploit could allow the attacker to inject commands to the
  underlying operating system with root privileges. ; Focus on Improper
  Neutralization of Special Elements used in an OS Command ('OS
  Command Injection')'

```

Listing 4.2: Prompt used to generate attack scenarios for Cisco router

These scenarios will then be stored in a structure that is described in Table 4.2, alongside vulnerability identifiers.

The output will be consumed in a supervised manner, manually by a human administrator, that is going to be passed to the Digital Twin module in order to verify if the attack is plausible. If the attack proves to be a hallucination, the only downside will be the resources consumed during the process of verification. This means that critical processes won't be affected by a possible hallucination of the LLM.

4.2 Threat Modeling information flow

The goal of this section is to describe the information flow that the Threat Modeling module is using in the context of the whole ENTRUST project.

In the realm of connected medical devices (CMDs), robust cybersecurity practices are not just theoretical principles, but they directly impact patient safety, data integrity, and healthcare delivery. CMDs, ranging from wearable health trackers to implantable devices, form a critical part of modern healthcare. These devices collect sensitive patient data, facilitate remote monitoring, and enable life-saving interventions. However, their interconnected nature exposes them to various threats. Data privacy, device integrity, secure interoperability, and protection against adversarial threats are all essential considerations.

The ENTRUST framework recognizes these challenges. By integrating AI-based threat modeling and leveraging pretrained models, ENTRUST aims to enhance CMD security efficiently. Robust cybersecurity practices aren't abstract ideals; they're the foundation for safeguarding lives and ensuring trust in connected healthcare.

Figure 4.2 illustrates how user-provided information undergoes Risk Assessment and Threat Modeling before being applied to Digital Twins.

1. The process begins with the User sending device data to the Risk Assessment module. The Risk Assessment entity then forwards this data to the Threat Modeling.
2. In the Threat Modeling module, the process begins by gathering the threat landscape. NIST National Vulnerability Database (NIST NVD) [64] serves as the knowledge base for vulnerabilities and MITRE Common Weakness Enumeration (MITRE CWE) [18] serves as the knowledge base for attacks techniques.

3. After being processed, the relevant information is then send to both threat model builder and the LLM. For each vulnerability, the LLM generates scenarios that are specific to the given device. To do this, the model is leveraging the power of Attention layers [73] in order to assist in the creation of contextual embeddings for each word in a sentence. These embeddings take into account the entire string that was provided, providing a richer and more nuanced understanding of each word based on its context. Attention layers are combined with Transformers [50] in order to process large datasets. Transformers also help in NLP tasks, by making the model have a more effective contextualization, by capturing long-range dependencies in text. This makes the model to maintain the context over longer sequences of text.
4. Attack vectors are then sent to the threat model builder that forwards the threat model to the JSON processor.
5. Finally, the JSON Threat Model is sent to the Risk Assessment phase for further analysis and is also shared with the Digital Twins entity.

Figure 4.2: Information Flow within the ENTRUST Framework for Threat Modeling

4.3 Software Verification information flow

This section is describing the information flow between the Software verification module and the other ENTRUST components, represented graphically in figure 4.3.

The first flow represents the software verification during the pre-deployment phase, in which the manufacturer sends the binary to the Trust Manager to check if the binary requires any updates. The binary

that is going to be deployed is then sent to the Software Verification module in order to detect problems before the software is being deployed. This is done by performing two main checks: malware scanning and fuzzing.

In malware scanning phase, the binary is verified if it contains known malicious patterns via a YARA [13] based solution. This allows a developer to also scan 3rd party modules, such as used libraries, in order to ensure that the final product is not being delivered with malware.

During the fuzzing, the binary is tested either a blackbox or a greybox way depending on the given binary. The goal of fuzzing is to discover inputs that lead to unintended states, by generating test cases based on existing ones in order to verify how the binary reacts to malformed input. During the fuzzing, the test cases that lead to an error, such as a buffer overflow, are saved so that specific test can be executed again.

Once these analyses are complete, the Software Verification results are generated in JSON format, representing a report with the found issues. These results are then sent to the Risk Assessment stage for further evaluation. The JSONs can be sent both separately in case only one verification is required, or they can be aggregated in case a full verification is needed.

The second flow represents software verification during runtime based on real time traces. This process starts with the device that is sending trust evidence to TAF to compute the ATL and comparing it with the RTL. In case there is a change in the trust level of the device, the TAF signals the device to send the raw system traces to the Digital Twin for identifying the exact misbehavior. This is forwarded to the Attack Simulation component for possibly identifying the exact attack execution path. If such a path has been identified, a security administrator can create additional fuzzing test cases to be fed to the Fuzzer in a supervised manner.

Figure 4.3: Information Flow within the ENTRUST Framework for Software Verification

4.4 Fuzzing

This section begins with a short introduction of fuzzing and our aim of applying it in ENTRUST. Following this a presentation of the current state-of-the art of fuzzing is given. It then proceeds with what kind of threats can be identified using fuzzers. After, it presents American Fuzzing Lop (AFL), the tool that we've chose to integrate in ENTRUST, alongside the reasoning of doing so.

Fuzzing, also known as fuzz testing, is an automated software testing technique used to identify vulnerabilities and bugs in software applications [75]. It involves providing invalid, unexpected, or random data,

known as fuzz, to the input interfaces of a program. The goal is to observe the program's behavior and identify potential issues such as crashes, memory leaks, or security vulnerabilities.

The primary goal of fuzzing in the ENTRUST is to enhance software robustness by uncovering vulnerabilities in the software that is running on medical devices. This is done by providing inputs that can be complex or that can be overlooked by engineers in the development process. This leads to finding vulnerabilities, such as buffer overflows, that need to be patched. Later, based on these vulnerabilities, the Risk Assessment will generate a new risk graph and the Digital Twin component will validate the attack via attack simulation.

4.4.1 Types of Fuzzing

In this section, the state-of-the-art regarding fuzzing will be presented, including methods and tools that can be used in order to implement a specific type of fuzzing.

One of the primary challenges in firmware fuzzing is the limited computational resources of IoT devices [75]. These constraints make it difficult to implement and run fuzzing techniques effectively. Additionally, many firmware binaries are closed-source, which complicates the process of fuzzing without access to the original source code. The diverse hardware architectures and platforms used in IoT devices further increase the complexity of developing universal fuzzing tools.

Symbolic execution is highlighted as a powerful method for exploring the state space of firmware, although it is resource-intensive. Emulation-based fuzzing, which involves running firmware in a controlled environment using emulators, is another common approach. However, accurately emulating diverse hardware remains a significant challenge.

These tests can be conducted into three main ways: blackbox, whitebox and greybox.

In blackbox fuzzing, the system under test is treated as a black box, meaning that the fuzzer has no knowledge of the internal workings of the program. It relies solely on the input/output behavior of the system. Black-box fuzzers generate inputs based on simple heuristics or random data and observe the system's responses to detect crashes or unexpected behaviors. This method is widely used for its simplicity and ease of implementation. One tool that implements this type of fuzzing is Snipuzz [35], which introduces a method called message snippet inference, which identifies and mutates segments of messages exchanged between the client and the IoT device. This technique allows Snipuzz to infer relationships between message snippets and the corresponding code execution paths in the firmware, enabling efficient mutation without needing predefined syntax rules.

Whitebox fuzzing involves an understanding of the internal logic of the application. This type of fuzzing uses techniques like symbolic execution to systematically explore the paths through the program by solving constraints on the inputs. White-box fuzzers can achieve higher code coverage and uncover deeper bugs, but they require more computational resources and detailed knowledge of the system's code. Such a method has been described in [76], that presents an approach of fuzzing modern RPC-based APIs. This method involves extracting RPC schema specifications from the source code of any JVM-based RPC APIs. The extracted schema is then used to generate test cases aimed at maximizing code coverage through search-based techniques.

Greybox fuzzing is a hybrid approach that combines aspects of both black-box and white-box fuzzing. It uses some knowledge about the program's internals, typically through instrumentation, to guide the fuzzing process. This allows grey-box fuzzers to achieve a balance between the efficiency of black-box fuzzing and the thoroughness of white-box fuzzing.

Currently, one of the most used tools is American Fuzzy Lop (AFL) [36], considered to be a de-facto standard for fuzzing. AFL uses a novel form of compile-time instrumentation and genetic algorithms to systematically and intelligently mutate input data while monitoring the program's execution for unexpected behavior, such as crashes or hangs. The tool's effectiveness stems from its ability to maintain a balance between random input generation and feedback-driven mutation strategies, which guide the fuzzer to explore previously untested code paths.

Our proposed solution is leveraging AFL as the main way of fuzzing. The reason of choosing this technique is that it can offer more comprehensive results. Another important factor is that, in the context of ENTRUST, the devices can be very different, thus a solution that can be integrated into the verification of multiple types of devices is required.

The AFL is used as the foundation of our tool, mainly because of its capacity to run in both a fully blackbox mode (in which the user provides only the binary) and in a greybox mode (that injects, during the compilation phase, new code that helps AFL to generate better input).

Furthermore, we want to investigate if GenAI can be used in conjunction with AFL, in order to generate results that take multiple data sources into account, such as previous failed tests.

For an easier integration with current workflows, including DevOps pipelines, fuzzers will be exposed as REST APIs.

4.4.2 Threats identified by fuzzers

In this section, the threats that can be identified by fuzzers are going to be presented alongside their impact. This subsection also contains information regarding how fuzzing can detect such threats. One of the main goals of a fuzzer is to identify memory corruption bugs [48]. These are bugs that allow an attacker to manipulate the memory of a program, potentially leading to arbitrary code execution.

The most prominent attacks that target memory are stack and heap overflows. A stack overflow occurs when a program writes more data to a stack-based buffer than it can hold, causing the excess data to overwrite adjacent memory locations on the stack. This can lead to the corruption of critical data, such as return addresses, enabling attackers to execute arbitrary code. In contrast, a heap overflow happens when excessive data is written to a buffer allocated on the heap, corrupting the dynamic memory allocation structures or adjacent memory regions. This can disrupt the program's normal execution, potentially allowing the attacker to manipulate the program's behavior or gain unauthorized access.

Another attack that uses memory corruption bugs is Use-After-Free (UAF). UAF is a critical memory corruption vulnerability that arises when a program continues to use a memory pointer after the memory it references has been freed. This can lead to unpredictable behavior, including program crashes, data corruption, and security breaches. Attackers can exploit UAF vulnerabilities by reallocating the freed memory space, inserting malicious data, and causing the program to execute this malicious code. This type of vulnerability is particularly dangerous because it can be challenging to detect and exploit consistently, yet it can lead to arbitrary code execution and full system compromise.

A fuzzer is also able to find Format String Vulnerabilities that occur when user input is unsafely included in format strings. These vulnerabilities arise when the program does not properly validate or sanitize the input before incorporating it into a format string. Attackers can exploit this flaw to manipulate the format string syntax, potentially reading or writing arbitrary memory locations. This can lead to information disclosure, memory corruption, and arbitrary code execution. Format String Vulnerabilities are particularly dangerous because they can bypass security mechanisms and lead to full system compromise.

A fuzzer can help a developer to identify these vulnerabilities, by systematically generating and injecting a wide range of malformed or unexpected inputs into the program being tested. During this procedure, the fuzzer is monitoring the application in order to check if the input leads to an unintended state.

Based on the identified vulnerabilities, the Risk Assessment module generates a risk graph that finally updates the policy with the required attributes.

4.4.3 American Fuzzing Lop

In this section, we will present the internal workings of AFL, such as the methods used to generate tests and instrumentation methods. Among the myriad of fuzzing tools available, AFL stands out as one of the most influential and widely adopted. Developed by Michał Zalewski, AFL is renowned for its effectiveness in identifying security flaws through its innovative coverage-guided fuzzing approach. By mutating test cases and leveraging feedback from the program's execution, AFL systematically explores program paths, making it possible to uncover elusive bugs and vulnerabilities that might otherwise remain hidden.

The fuzzer is the core component of AFL, responsible for generating test cases and executing the target program with these inputs. It operates in a loop, continuously feeding the target program with mutated inputs derived from initial seed files or previously discovered interesting test cases.

Instrumentation is crucial for AFL as it provides the necessary feedback on the execution paths taken by the target program. AFL supports two primary types of instrumentation: compile-time and QEMU-based.

- **Compile-time instrumentation** involves inserting instrumentation code during the compilation of the target program. AFL provides patches for compilers like GCC and LLVM to add this instrumentation.
- **QEMU-based instrumentation** is used for binary-only targets where source code is not available. AFL uses QEMU to instrument the binary at runtime. This allows AFL to collect coverage information without needing to modify the source code.

AFL generates new test cases through various mutation strategies applied to existing inputs. Key methods include:

- **Bit Flips:** Flipping single or multiple bits in the input data.
- **Arithmetic Operations:** Adding or subtracting values from parts of the input.
- **Interesting Values:** Replacing parts of the input with common boundary values, e.g., 0, 255, -1.
- **Dictionary-based Fuzzing:** Using predefined or user-specified dictionaries of known input patterns relevant to the target program.

When AFL detects a crash, it logs the input that caused the crash and provides tools for analyzing and minimizing the test case. This helps developers quickly identify and understand the root cause of the vulnerability.

4.4.4 Fuzzing tools comparison

In this section, a comparison of multiple tools is provided. It also presents the reasoning of choosing AFL as the core of our fuzzing solution.

In Table 4.1, we provide a comparison of multiple fuzzing tools.

Feature	AFL	LibFuzzer	OSS-Fuzz	Snipuzz	EvoMaster
Integration	Standalone	LLVM	CI/CD systems	Standalone	Standalone
Scope	General	Libraries	General	General	Java APIs
Ease of Use	High	High	Medium	Low	Medium

Table 4.1: Comparison between multiple fuzzing tools

The *Ease of Use* factor refers to the ease of setting up the environment and using it in different projects. For example, AFL requires very little setup, needing a user only to install the required dependencies, while Snipuzz requires more setup regarding the environment.

Another factor that was analyzed is the performance of these tools. AFL and LibFuzzer have the advantage of being able to enhance the speed of finding test cases that lead to unintended states via instrumentation. This is adding additional instructions to the binary that is helping the fuzzer to find cases that can crash the program. The other tools don't allow for such an enhancement.

The main requirement for the fuzzer is that it should be able to fuzz different types of binaries. This requirement is given by the fact that the software used on medical devices can be very different, thus a tool that can handle diverse executables is needed.

The main reason of choosing AFL is its versatility of being able to fuzz different types of binaries, while also having a high performance and being easy to integrate in other existing workflows. This includes using AFL to test binaries written in different programming languages, as a standalone tool that can be integrated into APIs or CI/CD systems and being able to enhance the performance of the fuzzing process via instrumentation.

4.5 Current status of the Components

In this section the current status of the Threat Modeling and Software Verification components is presented. This section ends with a description regarding the docker compose that can be used in order to deploy these services. As shown in Figure 4.4, the main functionalities of both Threat Modeling and Software Verification are implemented.

As of this moment, Threat Modeling module is using data from MITRE ATT&CK, NIST National Vulnerability Database (NIST NVD) and from Common Weakness Enumeration, that is sent to the LLM in order to generate attack scenarios.

The Software Verification module allows for the verification of binaries using both static analysis and fuzzing. For static analysis Software Verification module is using a YARA-based malware analyzer that scans for malicious patterns. The AFL fuzzer allows for the fuzzing of binaries, enabling a user to find inputs that lead to unintended states.

In order to protect both APIs, we have added Keycloak for identity and access management. This is a temporary solution until the ENTRUST framework will be mature enough to be used for this aspect.

Figure 4.4: Current status of Threat Modeling and Software Verification

As shown in Figure 4.5, both APIs, including their dependencies, are included in a Docker Compose in order to facilitate faster deployment. By having also dependencies included into Docker Compose, we ensure that sensitive data won't leave local network.

Figure 4.5: Docker compose for Threat Modeling and Software Verification

4.6 Definition of the Interface between Thread Modeling, Risk Assessment, and Digital Twin

This section will present the interface between the Threat Modeling module and its clients, namely Risk Assessment and Digital Twin modules. This section will also present the documentation of the API.

4.6.1 Output ingestion

This subsection will present the output structure that the Threat Modeling module is going to provide to the Risk Assessment and Digital Twins modules. Currently, the output of the Threat Modeling module is

a JSON with a structure similar to the one presented in Table 4.2.

This approach ensures that each component of the threat model is clearly defined, enabling efficient identification and management of potential security issues. The device-related fields allow for the identification of a specific device. The Vulnerability fields offer information on each security flaw, including its description, affected devices, and associated CVSS vectors. The threats section offers insights into potential attack vectors and mitigations, enhancing the overall security posture by addressing specific threats with defined scenarios and mitigation strategies.

As shown in 4.2 this output is ingested by the Risk Assessment and Digital Twins module.

Field	Description
Device CPE	Device CPE
Device ID	Device ID
Device Name	Device Name
Vulnerabilities	
Vulnerability CPEs	List of affected by this vulnerability
CVSS Vectors	List of CVSS Vectors
Description	Description of the vulnerability
CVE ID	CVE ID
Vulnerability Name	Vulnerability Name
Threats	
CAPEC	List of CAPEC IDs
Mitigations	List of possible mitigations
Attack Scenarios	List of attack scenarios
Threat ID	Threat ID
Threat Name	Threat Name

Table 4.2: Threat Modeling JSON output ingested by the RA and DT module

An example of such a threat model can be seen in Listing E, in which a Cisco router running Cisco IOS XE 16.12 was analyzed.

4.6.2 Documentation

This subsection presents the current implementation of the Threat Modeling and Software Verification APIs from a consumer perspective.

In order to facilitate an easier adoption of developed APIs, both Threat Modeling and Software Verification modules, provide a Swagger [24] documentation.

Documenting an API using Swagger offers a streamlined and interactive approach to presenting API documentation. The reason of choosing this tool is that it displays API endpoints, request parameters, and response formats, enhancing the understanding and usability of the API for developers. Each endpoint is clearly listed, along with the HTTP methods (GET, POST, PUT, DELETE) that can be used. Detailed descriptions of each endpoint, including the required parameters, optional parameters, and potential responses, are also provided.

The documentation page for Threat Modeling API can be seen in Figure 4.6 and the one for Software Verification in Figure 4.7.

A developer can access Swagger by accessing `/apidocs` page. This allows the software engineer to see the description of each end-point, what input it requires, and the output it provides. This allows for an easier adoption of the intended API.

Figure 4.6: Threat Modeling API specifications with Swagger

For example, in the Threat Modeling Swagger page, one can find the main end-point, */analyze-device*, its description, telling the user that it is the end-point that will provide the threat model, its requirements, a JSON with device data, and its output, the threat model in JSON format.

Figure 4.7: Software Verification API specifications with Swagger

In a similar method, one can find the documentation of Software Verification API, in which the scanning and fuzzing end-points are presented.

Chapter 5

Risk Assessment

5.1 Risk assessment for supporting CMD secure and trustworthy lifecycle management

Maintaining an up-to-date view of the security posture of a system is essential to deem a device or asset trustworthy. Risk Assessment (RA) is a critical component in managing the lifecycle of secure medical devices, enabling trusted services such as patch management and software updates. Despite the abundance of risk assessment methodologies specified by different entities, there are still challenges and limitations in making RA a dynamic, core enabler of an overarching trust assessment framework.

On the one hand, in connected systems, RA is crucial for identifying potential mitigation strategies. Traditional RA methodologies often fail to adequately identify dependencies between risks and their impact on trust. On the other hand, the goal of ENTRUST RA Engine is to maintain an up-to-date risk graph of the connected medical device (CMD) ecosystem. But most importantly, ENTRUST's core innovation lies in its ability to leverage this information so as to specify a baseline trust level - namely the Required Trust Level. As highlighted in Chapter 7, RTL constitutes one of the two core tenets that activate the trust assessment process, ensuring a more comprehensive and dynamic risk management strategy.

On the other hand, coping with unclassified, zero-day vulnerabilities poses significant challenges for risk assessment. Being able to update the RA knowledge base dynamically, enables the ENTRUST RA Engine to keep an up-to-date view of the security posture of the CMD ecosystem. At the same time, it is equivalently crucial for the dynamic recalculation of the RTL value so as to make accurate trust decisions in the context of the Trust Assessment Framework. The capabilities of such real-time risk indicators are offered by components such as the AI-based anomaly detection (9). Hence, ENTRUST ensures a robust and adaptive risk management framework capable of responding to emerging threats in near real-time.

The remainder of this chapter provides a detailed overview of how the ENTRUST RA Engine is specified so as to address the aforementioned limitations and challenges. To this extent, this chapter presents the positioning of the RA Engine in the overall ENTRUST architecture along with the internal structure and behaviour of the risk assessment framework.

5.2 Information flow for Risk Assessment

The provision of the risk overview of the entire Connected Medical Devices topology constitutes one of the main enablers towards their trustworthiness assessment. Starting from the design-phase - even in

the manufacturing phase -, it is essential to adequately maintain the security posture of CMD devices. Subsequently, when the CMD ecosystem reaches the domain infrastructure, it is equivalently crucial to dynamically adopt the risk assessment processes. This implies the capturing of the entire risk graph of the topology, including the interconnectivity of the devices with the rest of the domain components. That being said, in the context of the ENTRUST framework, a robust Risk Assessment Engine sits in the center of the architecture communicating with core ENTRUST components so as to collect the latest information concerning the underlying CMD topology. At the same time, the Risk Assessment Engine shares the risk results across the ENTRUST architecture in a continuous manner so as to ensure the latest view on the security posture of the CMD infrastructure throughout the lifecycle of the devices (i.e., from design, to pre-deployment and runtime phase).

Figure 5.1: Risk assessment framework in ENTRUST

Figure 5.1 positions the Risk Assessment Engine (RA) in the frame of the entire ENTRUST framework. As described in Section 5.4, one key element of a risk assessment process is a thorough threat analysis. This includes the identification of the most prominent threats and vulnerabilities characterizing the monitoring environment. Complemented with the domain information - e.g., asset catalogue, CMD asset topology - provided by the security administrator (i.e., domain manager), the threat analysis enables the risk identification and quantification across the CMD topology. To this extent, the Threat Modeling component provides with essential threat analysis information that is persisted in the RA Engine. As presented in Section 4, the Threat Modeling gathers well-known vulnerabilities - i.e., reported by external sources, repositories etc. - and associates them with possible threats tailored to the assets as well as the related domain. This information leads to the identification of concrete attack scenarios along with associated information pertaining to the explicit vulnerability impact and the probability of a specific threat taking place (see Section 5.3). The Threat Modeling tool provides with valuable insight across the lifecycle of the CMD topology: mainly in initialization phase but also during the runtime phase in case a new vulnerability is identified. In the context of the runtime phase, the Digital Twin is responsible for collecting raw traces (e.g., attestation evidence) from the underlying CMD devices and fleshing out explicit attack

emulations based on the state configuration of each CMD asset (Section 9). These attack emulations enhance the RA knowledge base, possibly detailing the exact attack execution path justifying concrete attacks associated with the retrieved raw traces (e.g., failed attestation) from the CMD topology. A final key information related the CMD device level stems from the Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD) profiles. Based on the asset catalogue and during the pre-deployment phase, the RA Engine is able to access the Device-level eMUD profiles provided by the Manufacturer to the eMUD Server. This information is available to the RA Engine through the ENTRUST DLT. These profiles contain vulnerabilities and recommended security controls which are associated to a specific product (i.e., device and firmware), thus contributing to the in-depth threat analysis carried out in the ENTRUST RA Engine. Finally, moving to the application layer, it is essential to expand the threat analysis process over and beyond the device level. To ensure the secure lifecycle of the applications running on top of the CMD infrastructure, the Software Verification component (Chapter 4) analyzes the software artefacts to be deployed in the monitored topology and identifies possible vulnerabilities (e.g., due to bugs, implementation flaws) in the effort of providing vulnerability-free applications. This may introduce attack vectors that have not been identified by the community (i.e., external sources), facilitating the immediate reaction to new, probably zero-day, vulnerabilities.

The aforementioned detailed threat analysis enablers in ENTRUST provide the means to carry out the risk assessment process over the CMD topology. The risk results constitute a valuable input to multiple workflows across the ENTRUST architecture. First, the risk outcome contains not only the risk quantification pertaining to a CMD asset, but also the possible security controls that could be enforced to remediate (i.e., reduce or eliminate) a specific risk. This insight is essential for deriving the required trust level (RTL) that each CMD asset should attain during the runtime phase. Working in tandem with the ENTRUST Trust Assessment Framework 7, the calculation of RTL allows the implementation of an overarching framework where the trustworthiness of the topology can be evaluated during runtime. In parallel, the risk results provide essential input to the Software Verification component, by allowing the fine-tuning of the fuzzy techniques in the context of identifying new vulnerabilities from the software binaries running in the CMD topology. Finally, by processing the RA knowledge base (i.e., threat analysis and risk results) it is possible to contribute to the overall secure lifecycle management across the CMD continuum. The collective threat analysis results allow the RA Engine to contribute to the extension of the threat vectors to be included in the Domain-level eMUD profiles. Eventually, to strengthen the security posture of CMD ecosystems across multiple domains, the RA Engine is able to provide harmonized cyber-threat intelligence (CTI) data through the ENTRUST DLT, without disclosing anything about the underlying topology.

5.3 CVSS-based Risk Assessment methodology

The ENTRUST Risk Assessment Engine envisions to provide a transparent framework enabling the adoption of various risk assessment methodologies. Specifically, it adopts a CVSS-based methodology as a baseline risk assessment methodology based on widely adopted standards and specifications. It is a comprehensive risk assessment methodology that enables the modelling of vulnerabilities at various levels of a system, ranging from hardware vulnerabilities to firmware and application vulnerabilities, thus making it suitable for the context of embedded systems and the complex Systems-of-Systems landscape. While domain agnostic, the methodology is capable of capturing the risk of complex System-of-Systems environments. It is based on a well-adopted specification for conducting risk assessment, namely the NIST Special Publication 800-39, *Managing Information Security Risk: Organization, Mission, and Information System View* [59], that identifies the four main steps of the risk management process as well as the communication interfaces to enable the process to work effectively. According to the specification, the lifecycle consists of the following four steps.

- **Risk Framing:** Establishing a context for risk management, outlining strategies for assessing, responding to, and monitoring risks transparently and explicitly within organizational boundaries.
- **Risk Assessment:** Identifying threats, both internal and external, vulnerabilities, potential harm, and the likelihood of occurrence, resulting in a determination of risk level.
- **Risk Response:** Developing, evaluating, and implementing consistent organizational responses to identified risks in alignment with organizational risk tolerance.
- **Risk Monitoring:** Continuously evaluating the effectiveness of risk responses, identifying changes in organizational systems and environments, and ensuring implementation of planned risk responses to meet security requirements.

In addition, this methodology is also aligned with the EU Risk Management (RM) toolbox and processes as specified in [34] in an effort to provide an interoperable . The risk assessment methodology of ENTRUST will be based on the calculation of two risk score variants, namely the *Individual Risk Level* and the *Attack Path Risk Level*. The former represents the magnitude of a risk which is entailed on a distinct asset considering the vulnerabilities and threat applied to it. The latter refers to the magnitude of risk, as a result an attack path that may lead an attack to the specific asset, considering potential vulnerability and threat chains that can be exploited by an adversary. These two risk variation scores are further explained in the next section.

5.3.1 Risk Quantification

The NIST SP 800-30 specification [60] focuses on the second step of the risk management lifecycle - i.e., the Risk Assessment. It comprehensively outlines the various risk factors pivotal in determining the magnitude of a risk. Among these factors are threat, vulnerability, impact, and likelihood. These elements collectively serve as the foundation for establishing a robust risk quantification methodology. The remainder of this subsection introduces a risk quantification methodology that combines a subjective threat likelihood parameter with a systematic vulnerability impact measurement based on the Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) methodology.

Threat Probability

According to [60], a *threat* is any circumstance or event with the potential to adversely impact organizational operations and assets, individuals, other organizations, or the Nation through an information system via unauthorized access, destruction, disclosure, or modification of information, and/or denial of service. The **likelihood** that a threat may materialize is a variable that depends on a number of parameters, as for example the infrastructure’s inherent characteristics. As a result, defining a threat likelihood is an inherently subjective process, per individual infrastructure, threats and needs, that can be carried out by the OEM security administrator. Table 5.1 presents a qualitative and semi-quantitative classification of the threat likelihood.

Qualitative Values	Semi-Quantitative Values		Description
Very High	96-100	10	Adversary is almost certain to initiate the threat event.
High	80-95	8	Adversary is highly likely to initiate the threat event.
Moderate	21-79	5	Adversary is somewhat likely to initiate the threat event.
Low	5-20	2	Adversary is unlikely to initiate the threat event.

Very Low	0-4	0	Adversary is highly unlikely to initiate the threat event.
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Table 5.1: Likelihood of a threat occurring

Vulnerability Impact

In addition, NIST defines the term *vulnerability* as a weakness in an information system, system security procedures, internal controls, or implementation that could be exploited by a threat source. Associating vulnerabilities with specific assets enables security administrators to evaluate their impact in a systematic manner. Specifically, the Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) [71] developed by the Forum of Incident Response and Security Teams (FIRST) [6] is a globally recognised standard for assessing and rating the severity of software vulnerabilities. CVSS provides a structured framework for security professionals to objectively evaluate the potential impact and exploitability of vulnerabilities, aiding in prioritising remediation efforts and allocating resources effectively. Annex C summarises the CVSS attributes as defined in the 3.1 version of the specification. According to the CVSS v3.1 specification, there are three core metrics, namely the Base, the Temporal and the Environmental metrics.

The Base group (Mandatory Metric) represents the fundamental features of vulnerabilities that remain consistent over time and across user environments. It is further analysed to two sub-metrics the exploitability and the impact metric. The exploitability metric describes the technical feasibility of the vulnerability, while the impact reflects the results that a successful exploit will have and depicts the influence on the affected component.

The exploitability metric is further described by:

1. the *Attack Vector (AV)*, which indicates the level of access of the attacker, hence it can take four values: Physical (P), Local (L), Adjacent (A) and Network (N), moving to the one with the most requirements needed, to the one that can be achieved even remotely.
2. the *Attack Complexity (AC)*, this metric receives values Low (L) and High (H), depending on the preparation needed by the attacker in order to exploit.
3. the *Privileges Required (PR)*, which accepts values None (N), Low (L) and High (H), depending on the level of privileges required by the attacker to launch the attack, with low signifying basic user capabilities and high administrative privileges.
4. the *User Interaction (UI)*, referring to the interaction with a human user, receiving values None (N) and Required (R) if a user is needed.

On the other hand, the impact metric is further described by the CIA triad:

1. Confidentiality,
2. Integrity,
3. Availability.

Each of the CIA requirements received a score among the values High (H), Low (L) and None (N), depending on the level of intrusion that the attacker can successfully reach.

$$ISS = 1 - [(1 - Confidentiality) \times (1 - Integrity) \times (1 - Availability)]$$

The Temporal class (Optional Metric) reflects vulnerability characteristics that may alter over the course of time. Temporal metrics are further described by three metrics:

1. the *Exploit Code Maturity (E)*, which describes the feasibility to exploit, defined by Not Defined (X) due to lack of information, High (H) maturity with automated tools available, Functional (F), Proof-of-Concept (P) and Unproven (U).

2. the *Remediation Level (RL)*: which considers the possible patches for the identified vulnerability, defined by Not Defined (X), Unavailable (U), Workaround (W), Temporary Fix (T) and Official Fix (O).
3. the *Report Confidence (RC)*: which illustrates the certainty over the technical details and existence of vulnerability, described by Not Defined (X), Confirmed (C), Reasonable (R) and Unknown (U).

$$TemporalScore = \{mathitRoundup}(BaseScore \times E \times RL \times RC)$$

The Environmental category (Optional Metric) demonstrates vulnerability characteristics that are unique to a user’s environment. Environmental metrics are further described by the Security Requirements (SR) and adapt the CIA triad per the specific IT environment requirements (hence CR, IR and AR). Their score ranges among the values High (H), Low (L), Medium (M) and Not Defined (X), depending on the level of intrusion that the attacker can successfully reach.

$$MISS = Minimum(1 - [(1 - ConfidentialityRequirement \times ModifiedConfidentiality) \times (1 - IntegrityRequirement \times ModifiedIntegrity) \times (1 - AvailabilityRequirement \times ModifiedAvailability)], 0.915)$$

The Basic metric generates a score ranging from 0 to 10, which can then be revised by the Temporal and Environmental metrics. A compressed textual representation of the values utilized to calculate a CVSS score is also known as a CVSS vector string. A vulnerability, apart from the CVSS score can be described as a vector, e.g., CVSS:3.1/AV:N/AC:L/PR:H/UI:N/S:U/C:L/I:L/A:N.

Currently the NVD repository provides vulnerability scores for all vulnerabilities with respect to the scoring systems specified in versions 3.1 and below. However, a new version - namely 4.0 - has been defined with the aim to provide finer granularity in the attributes that characterise the quantifiable impact of a vulnerability, moving beyond the mere base score. Given the fact that the new version of the CVSS scoring system is not fully integrated in well known repositories such as NVD, it is expected that the ENTRUST RA Engine supports the new version by its second release.

5.3.2 Individual Risk Level

Based on the aforementioned risk factors it is possible to provide a host-based risk assessment. Each asset is linked to a series of vulnerabilities, with each vulnerability corresponding to a distinct threat. Based on the threat likelihood and vulnerability impact modeling presented above, it is possible to calculate the individual risk level for each tuple (*Asset, Vulnerability, Threat*) as follows - qualitative and quantitative scales are listed in Table 5.2:

$$IRL(Asset_i, Vulnerability_j, Threat_k) = ThreatLevel \times VulnerabilityImpact$$

Note: Computing an aggregated risk value for an asset is inherently context-dependent, emphasizing that there is no one-size-fits-all approach. Different approaches consist of taking the maximum IRL value, computing a weighted average or maintaining risk matrices, categorizing threats or vulnerabilities based on their likelihood and impact. It is up to the security administrator to determine what is the best approach for their application domain or scenario.

IRL Qualitative Values	IRL Quantitative Values
Very High	96-100
High	80-95

Medium	21-79
Low	5-20
Very Low	0-4

Table 5.2: Risk values in CVSS-based methodology

5.3.3 Attack Path Risk Level

This type of risk assessment methodologies measure the risk of an asset without taking into consideration the dependencies and the risks introduced by neighbouring assets. A holistic risk assessment framework should be to take into consideration the attack paths that an adversary may leverage to cause harm in a system. In this methodology, the interdependency graph of an asset topology is adopted. This allows security administrators to express any type of interconnection (e.g., physical, logical, network, flow of data) within the monitored infrastructure. Consequently, any cyber-physical ecosystem can be modelled and visualised as a Direct Acyclic Graph (DAG), based on the notion of interdependency graphs [31]. Based on this data model, it is possible to define an attack path starting from an entry point and through a set of pivoting steps are able to reach the target asset, thus forming a chain of assets. Each pivoting step allows an adversary to exploit a single vulnerability in an asset. This can result in multiple attack paths targeting the same set of assets, with adversaries exploiting different combinations of vulnerabilities. The realization of the attack path risk quantification can be also supported by the information coming from the attack emulation process run in the Digital Twin (Chapter 9). The detailed steps that an adversary may follow to carry out a combined attack in an asset provides meaningful information to further enhance the attack paths but also to evaluate the likelihood of a specific attack to occur depending on specific factors such as the difficulty of each step or the expertise required by an adversary. The details for the design and development of the attack path analysis are presented in D3.3. This will eventually lead to the realisation of the Attack Path Risk Level (APRL) that captures not only the individual risk level of an asset, but also the incoming risk imposed by neighbouring assets in the topology. The quantification of the risk level is critical to trust calculations. To this extent, it is essential to identify and fine-tune the risk assessment framework so that the imposed required trust level can be attained by all related assets in a model.

5.4 Internal Architecture

Figure 5.2 illustrates the internal architecture of the ENTRUST RA Engine, including the required input interfaces. The execution of a new risk assessment task is achieved through a new request at the OLISTIC backend. This can be triggered either manually (e.g., through an action performed by a security administrator) or automatically (e.g., through a periodic, scheduled task). The result is a representation of the risk report (e.g., in the form of a risk graph, or a table of results) shared with the intended entities, namely the security administrator and/or other authorized users (e.g., Domain Managers). The ENTRUST RA Engine mainly supports the CVSS-based methodology presented in 5.3.

To enable the execution of these risk methodologies, it is assumed that a thorough threat analysis is performed over the monitored CMD infrastructure. This includes information about vulnerabilities and threats coming from ENTRUST (e.g., Threat Modeling, MUD Server, AI-based anomaly detection), externa sources (e.g., NVD) or from the Domain Manager. The realization of the asset cartography - i.e., list of CMD assets comprising the monitored topology - is also required to depict all the assets (i.e., hardware, software and data) and their interdependencies (i.e., physical, logical, data flows). Finally, either manually or through the device - level eMUD profiles - it is essential to define mitigation strategies

Figure 5.2: Risk assessment internal architecture

that enable the ENTRUST RA Engine to assess the effectiveness of specific security measures that can be enforced in the asset topology. All of these functionalities enable the derivation of mechanisms to assess the required level of trustworthiness that each CMD asset needs to attain during runtime so as to be considered trusted. The remainder of this section briefly presents each of the internal RA Engine components.

5.4.1 OLISTIC backend

The OLISTIC backend offers the necessary APIs to orchestrate all the backend operations of the engine and works in synergy with the frontend to offer the necessary functionalities to the security analyst. The backend component is also responsible for performing the access control rules that allow only authorized users to use the available API. Finally, it provides the necessary interface for establishing asynchronous communication with the rest of the ENTRUST ecosystem through publish/subscribe protocols such as Kafka. This is essential for the real-time receipt of risk indicators that may trigger the recalculation of the overall risk graph of the monitored topology.

5.4.2 OLISTIC frontend

The OLISTIC frontend offers an interactive dashboard which is used for visualizing the digital representation of the cyber-physical environment. Of course, this dashboard offers a plethora of operations that can be performed, ranging from simple asset addition/editing/deletion to the creation of attack scenarios, management of vulnerability and threat profiles of assets, consideration of controls and mitigation actions, the execution of the risk assessment and many others.

5.4.3 Asset modeling and visualisation component

This component is responsible for modelling the list of assets that comprise the monitored ecosystem. In fact, this component is crucial for the realization of the ENTRUST RA Engine. We consider an asset any entity, tangible or intangible, that participates in the ecosystem and carries a level of risk. To address the first functional requirement, an abstract notion of the term asset is adopted to represent hardware assets (e.g., in-vehicle sensors and devices), services running on top of them (e.g., image processing, obstacle detection system) or even data flowing across the in-vehicle topology (e.g., camera data). Apart from a uniquely identifiable name in the topology, security administrators can provide additional information such as the level of criticality of each asset in the domain (i.e., business value). In addition, it is possible to provide the Common Product Enumeration identifier, if applicable. This facilitates the seamless and

automated association of the assets with vulnerabilities and threats. The ENTRUST RA Engine also allows for an arbitrary set of attributes in a key-value format.

Moreover, following the conceptual model of ISO/IEC 3041:2018, assets consist of capabilities that allow them to participate in various functions/services. Each of these functions is modeled as an asset cartography comprising of a set of assets and a set of interdependencies between them. The relationships among assets can express various types of interdependencies ranging from network/physical connections, software dependencies or even data flows. An initial, yet not definitive, list of asset relationships is presented below:

- *IsConnectedTo*: to express network connections between hardware assets (e.g.,),
- *IsUsedBy*: to express logical dependency among assets (e.g.,),
- *IsProcessedBy*: to express the fact that a piece of data is accessed by an asset (e.g.,),
- *isLocatedIn*: to express geospatial dependency among assets (e.g.,),
- *isStoredOn*: to express the fact that a piece of data is stored on an asset (e.g.,),
- *isInstalledOn*: to express a dependency between software and hardware assets (e.g.,).

The ENTRUST RA Engine offers a graphical user interface based on which the security administrator is able to manage the asset cartography. Firstly, the tool supports the visualisation of the data flow diagram for each function and the inspection of the list of assets defined in the monitored infrastructure. Finally, to support the CVSS-based methodology, the Asset modelling and visualisation component also, accommodates for the association of assets with specific damage scenarios and their impact in the context of specific trust properties.

5.4.4 Vulnerability and threat modelling component

The association of assets with their vulnerabilities is crucial for conducting a risk analysis and determining the required risk level for a given function. To enable this process, the Vulnerability and threat Modelling component provides the means to store and manage a knowledge base comprising of well-known vulnerabilities. On the one hand the component supports the automated and periodic synchronisation with publicly available repositories such as the National Vulnerability Database (NVD) [58]. These repositories provide additional information that enables the calculation of the impact of a vulnerability based on the Common Vulnerability Score System specification (CVSS) [71]. In addition, this component leverages other cybersecurity awareness initiatives that focus on the association of specific vulnerabilities with common attack patterns (CAPEC [2]), weakness (CWE [4]), and product catalogues (CPE [3]) that enable the seamless association of vulnerabilities with specific product identifiers. To enrich this knowledge base, the component takes into consideration vulnerabilities and controls reported in the MUD server for each type of asset.

In parallel, towards meeting the final functional requirement related to the harmonisation of the risk results of various methodologies, the Vulnerability and threat modelling component adopts the STRIDE modelling framework [10]. According to the specification, potential threats can be categorised into into six types: Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information Disclosure, Denial of Service, and Elevation of Privilege. By adopting the STRIDE model, it is possible to model threats in an interoperable fashion across risk assessment methodologies. Specifically, this classification is essential for the CVSS-based methodology as it is required for the calculation of the IRL value as mentioned in Subsection 5.3. Finally, to further extend the knowledge base of vulnerabilities, the component enables security administrators to include more vulnerabilities from other sources, including zero-day vulnerabilities identified in their infrastructure.

5.4.5 Attack path calculator

The attack path calculator component is also critical for the enhancement of the risk overview in the context of the CVSS-based methodology through the calculation of the APRL value (Section 5.3). In scope of the OLISTIC artefact, it is possible to automate the attack path based on the vulnerability characteristics on neighbouring assets. Specifically, through the definition of a set of declarative rules, a security administrator defines the conditions under which an adversary can exploit a vulnerability on an asset that allows them to pivot to a neighbouring asset. These rules are then fed to the Drools engine [5], an expert system, designed for rule-based decision making and complex event processing.

Note: The automated identification of attack paths with pre-defined rules poses significant limitations. It requires that the cascading effects are described beforehand by security administrators, thus neglecting the necessity of capturing zero-day vulnerabilities. In scope of the attack path calculator, additional attack path identification approaches will be examined.

5.4.6 Risk quantification engine

The risk quantification engine is responsible for consuming the threat analysis performed either automatically or manually by the security administrators and compute a risk assessment risk values for the monitored asset cartography. This component is designed in a modular fashion to allow the inclusion of diverse risk assessment methodologies. It supports the CVSS-based methodology for both the calculation of IRL and APRL values. Having the results of multiple risk assessment methodologies, the risk quantification engine is also responsible for harmonising the results in order to provide a transparent output to the maximum possible extent. However, this introduces a challenge that the same attack vectors for a given trust property are not taken into consideration in multiple methodologies as this may lead to an increased required trust level that may be difficult - or even impossible - to be satisfied by the in-vehicle components during runtime.

Furthermore, the Risk Quantification Engine is in charge of managing the entire lifecycle of a risk assessment task, from initiation to completion. In parallel, this component provides the various risk reports to be consumed by the OLISTIC Frontend.

Finally, apart from its modular design (i.e., supporting various risk assessment methodologies), the risk quantification engine provides the functionality of converging the risk results to the maximum possible extent. This provides a seamless integration between the ENTRUST RA Engine and trust calculations as security administrators may evaluate how different risk methodologies impact the trust values both during design time (i.e., required/threshold trust value) and during runtime (i.e., actual trust value).

5.4.7 Mitigation strategy component

One of the ten functional requirements of the ENTRUST RA Engine, refers to the management of the various security controls and their impact on the risk level within the monitored topology. In the context of ENTRUST, there are three major types of security controls:

- *Controls for misbehaviour mitigation:* These controls are primarily focused on identifying and responding to anomalous or unauthorised behaviour within the edge topology. In the context of ENTRUST, this security control is offered by the AI-Based Misbehavior Detection component that leverages behavioural patterns and insights that trigger automated events when suspicious activity

is detected. In addition to these controls, security administrators may define other security controls to address misbehaviour of assets either in a proactive or a reactive fashion. This is achieved through the enforcement of mitigation actions stemming from well-known repositories - such as the Center for Internet Security (CIS) [1], as well as user-defined security controls.

- *Formal verification actions for controls:* This category includes security measures that stem from the assurance claims provided during the formal verification processes (Chapter 3). For example, the adoption of models such as ProVerif and Tamarin enables the generation of trust guarantees that the cryptographic protocols and schemes used in ENTRUST for specific security properties.
- *Attestation- and policy-based controls:* These controls not only include security measures that are implemented but also provide ongoing evidence of their execution and effectiveness during runtime. Examples include runtime attestation protocols, integrity measurement frameworks, and swarm attestation (these mechanisms are reported in [27]). These controls provide additional levels of assurance, allowing administrators to verify that security measures are actively enforced and responding as expected to potential threats.

The Mitigation Strategy Component supports the modelling of all types of controls. It also allows security administrators to signal the effectiveness of each security control by configuring the various parameters that contribute to the overall risk level for an asset or a trust relationship. By combining multiple security controls for various assets, security administrators can define specific profiles, namely Mitigation Strategies. The component enables the management of the various mitigation strategies and the evaluation of their impact on the overall risk.

5.4.8 RTL calculator

The internal components presented so far cover all the various aspects leading to the risk quantification and assessment over the monitored asset topology. The last - though equally important - internal component is responsible for materializing the required trust level (RTL) to be used in the context of the ENTRUST trust assessment framework. As explained in Chapter 7, RTL constitutes one of the two main aspects of the overall trust assessment framework. Along with the Actual Trust Level (ATL), the RTL enables the ENTRUST framework to assess the trustworthiness of a device and/or a service deployed in the CMD ecosystem. Hence, the main challenge that lies ahead is to express the RTL in a way that enables the comparison with the ATL value. In fact, this constitutes a timely challenge in modern Trust Assessment methodologies that shift from objective (e.g., fuzzy) techniques towards subjective logic. Such methodologies allow for the expression and quantification of trust levels in terms of belief, disbelief and uncertainty based on the available knowledge. In the current version of the ENTRUST framework, research is focused around the expression of RTL in terms of projected probabilities. Nevertheless, it is that in the next release of the ENTRUST Risk Assessment framework we plan to evaluate alternative approaches. The semantics and the detailed information for the realization of the RTL calculation is reported in D3.3.

5.5 Risk Assessment workflow

Figure 5.3 showcases how the ENTRUST Risk Assessment Engine internal components interact to conduct a risk assessment task. One key requirement for this component is that needs to run continuously across the different phases of the lifecycle of the CMD ecosystem. This is essential for ensuring a fresh,

up-to-date, overview of the risk and security posture of the topology so as to better evaluate the trustworthiness of the assets. At the same time, this allows for an accurate decision making with respect to the necessary security controls that need to be performed by the ENTRUST framework (e.g. patch management, software update) to ensure the secure and seamless operation of the domain services. In this workflow, we focus only on the execution of a risk assessment task, assuming that the threat analysis over the asset topology has been executed successfully both by the Domain Manager and, of course, the entire ENTRUST framework. As presented in 5.2, this involves the synchronization of the device-level eMUD profiles from the DLT, the fetching of attack scenario information from the Threat Modeling component as well as the acquisition of attack emulation details stemming from the Digital Twin.

The process starts with a new request for risk assessment sent by the Domain Manager either through the OLISTIC Frontend or using the respective OLISTIC Backend API calls (i.e., through a third-part tool). This request is redirected to the Risk Quantification Engine which is responsible for managing and performing a risk assessment task. First, it fetches the asset graph - i.e., asset catalogue and interdependencies - from the Asset Modeling and Visualization Engine. This information further enhances the related threat analysis as persisted in the Vulnerability and Threat Modeling and includes vulnerability impact attributes stemming from the CVSS specification, as well as the threat likelihood. Depending on the risk assessment methodology employed, it is possible to perform the calculation of the individual risk levels for the associated entities (i.e., assets, asset relationships). In the case of the CVSS-based methodology, this implies the calculation of the impact of each vulnerability on the related asset and the calculation of the Individual Risk Level (IRL) value for each asset. The details of the aforementioned calculations are presented in Subsection 5.3. The Risk Quantification Engine further invokes the Attack Path Calculator component to initiate an attack path discovery across the monitored edge topology. The identification of attack paths is based on the CVSS attributes characterizing a vulnerability, though, we envision to investigate additional strategies that are not based solely on pre-defined rules (e.g., attack emulations derived by the Digital Twin may result in the construction of concrete attack paths). The Risk Quantification Engine evaluates the discovered attack paths and computes the Attack Path Risk Level (APRL) for each one of them. Finally, all the computed information is shared with the RTL Calculator which contributes to the calculation of the RTL value for each asset. The risk results are persisted in the database and returned to the security administrator.

Figure 5.3: Risk assessment internal architecture

5.6 Definition of interfaces

This subsection presents the API specification of the ENTRUST RA Engine. The set of APIs can be depicted in two major categories. The first category, namely the internal APIs, specify the set of interfaces that the internal interfaces use to communicate within the ENTRUST RA framework. This category also, includes all the endpoints that Security Administrators can use to directly interact with the ENTRUST RA Engine. The second category refers to the interfaces with respect to the interaction with the rest of the ENTRUST architecture. These interfaces are reported in D6.1, as part of the overarching integrated framework.

Name: VULNERABILITY_THREAT_INTERFACE			
Description	Interface offered by the Vulnerability and Threat Modeling Component for managing threats, vulnerabilities. This is essential for enabling the threat analysis prior to any risk assessment task.		
Component providing the interface	Vulnerability and Threat modeling component		
Consumer components or External Entities	Risk Quantification Engine, OLISTIC Backend, OLISTIC Frontend		
Type of interface	REST		
Input /Output Data	Methods or endpoints of the interface	Parameters of the method	Return Object or Values of the method
	GET /api/v1/vulnerabilities /{id}	Vulnerability Identifier	Vulnerability Information
	POST /api/v1/vulnerabilities /{id}	Vulnerability Information	Vulnerability Identifier and name
	DELETE /api/v1/vulnerabilities /{id}	Vulnerability Identifier	HTTP OK
	GET /api/v1/threats /{id}	Threat Id	Threat information
	POST /api/v1/threats /{id}	Threat Information	Threat Identifier and name
	DELETE /api/v1/threats /{id}	Threat Identifier	HTTP OK

Table 5.3: Vulnerability and Threat Modeling component API

Name: ASSET_MODELING_INTERFACE			
Description	Interface offered by the Asset modeling and visualization component to enable security administrators to manage assets and asset topologies. This will enable the execution of fine grained risk analysis in pre-defined asset topologies corresponding to different trust models.		
Component providing the interface	Asset modeling and visualization component		
Consumer components or External Entities	Risk Quantification Engine, OLISTIC Backend, OLISTIC Frontend		
Type of interface	REST		
Input/Output Data	Methods or endpoints of the interface	Parameters of the method	Return Object or Values of the method
	GET /api/v1/assets /{id}	Asset Identifier	Asset information
	POST /api/v1/assets /{id}	Asset Information	Asset Identifier and name
	DELETE /api/v1/assets /{id}	Asset Identifier	HTTP OK
	GET /api/v1/processes /{id}	Process Id	Process information
	POST /api/v1/processes /{id}	Process Information	Process Identifier and name
	DELETE /api/v1/processes /{id}	Process Identifier	HTTP OK
GET /api/v1/processes /{id}/visualize	Process Id	Asset topology information	

Table 5.4: Asset Modeling and Visualization component API

Name: ATTACK_PATH_CALCULATOR_INTERFACE			
Description	Interface offered by the Attack Path Calculation component to manage attack path assessments as well as the update of the already identified attack paths with new ones by the security administrator.		
Component providing the interface	Attack Path Calculator		
Consumer components or External Entities	Risk Quantification Engine, OLISTIC Backend, OLISTIC Frontend		
Type of interface	REST		
Input/Output Data	Methods or endpoints of the interface	Parameters of the method	Return Object or Values of the method
	GET /api/v1/attack-path-assessment /{id}	Attack Path Assessment Identifier	Attack path assessment information
	POST /api/v1/attack-path-assessment /{id}	Attack path assessment information	Attack path assessment Identifier and name

	DELETE /api/v1/attack-path-assessment /{id}	Attack path assessment Identifier	HTTP OK
	POST /api/v1/attack-path-assessment /{id}/execute	Attack path assessment Id	HTTP OK
	POST /api/v1/attack-path-assessment /{id}/visualise	Attack path assessment Id	Attack paths in the format of a graph.

Table 5.5: Attack path calculator component API

Name: RISK_QUANTIFICATION_ENGINE_INTERFACE			
Description	Interface offered by the risk quantification engine that coordinates risk assessment tasks from the submission to their completion		
Component providing the interface	Mitigation Strategies component		
Consumer components or External Entities	Risk Quantification Engine, OLISTIC Backend, OLISTIC Frontend		
Type of interface	REST		
Input/Output Data	Methods or endpoints of the interface	Parameters of the method	Return Object or Values of the method
	GET /api/v1/risk-assessments /{id}	Risk Assessment Identifier	Risk Assessment information
	POST /api/v1/risk-assessments /{id}	Risk Assessment Information	Risk Assessment Identifier and name
	DELETE /api/v1/risk-assessments /{id}	Risk Assessment Identifier	HTTP OK

Table 5.6: Risk Assessment strategies component API

Chapter 6

Extending Protection Profiles for Trust Guidance

As advanced trust assessment mechanisms evolve, the use of Manufacturer Usage Description (MUD) profiles as protection profiles becomes crucial for bootstrapping trust in devices, particularly CMDs. MUD profiles include essential information about device characteristics and establish a baseline for its behavioral profile, helping to bootstrap trust by specifying the expected network traffic and behaviors. However, extending this trust to the runtime operation of devices requires additional information, which is where ENTRUST proposes the use of extended MUDs (eMUDs) with minimal changes to enable dynamic trust assessment.

The IETF specification introducing MUDs in RFC 8520 focuses on establishing the expected network behavior of a device when bootstrapped and connected to a network domain by defining ACLs. However, this lacks information needed for dynamic trust assessment at the execution layer of the device, as defined by the Common Criteria. MUD profiles fit into the overarching definition of a Target of Evaluation (ToE) as part of the functional specification of a Protection Profile. ENTRUST addresses this gap by proposing extensions to MUD profiles to enable runtime trust assessment capabilities for CMDs.

MUD profiles traditionally focus on network behavior, specifying the kinds of network traffic allowed or denied to prevent unauthorized access and attacks [57], [42]. However, **ENTRUST recommends enriching MUD profiles with more granular information on host behavior, known as eMUDs [55] to address advanced cyber threats and sophisticated attacks that target device misconfigurations at the edge**¹.

eMUDs include specific definitions of device behaviors, such as whitelists of expected binaries and control-flow graphs, and integrate dynamic trust policies. These profiles also use policy hashes to enforce behaviors in a zero-knowledge manner, preventing implementation disclosure attacks. eMUDs tailored at both the device and domain levels are essential for addressing unique operational and security needs within their respective scopes. **eMUDs define the trust boundaries of a device's operational profile**, helping to identify the Runtime Trust Level (RTL) against which the trust assessment will be conducted. This link to the trust assessment activities of ENTRUST ensures that each device operates within its intended trust level. Device-level eMUDs capture detailed information about potential security threats specific to the device and use key restriction usage policies for implicit attestation, verifying device integrity without accessing detailed evidence. Domain-level eMUDs extend these security measures to encompass broader domain-specific threats and operational contexts, adapting device-level protocols to the specific requirements of the domain and providing a cohesive security strategy across all devices.

¹<https://owasp.org/>

In ENTRUST, trust policies defined by the Domain Manager dictate the attestation process and trustworthiness evidence monitoring. Key restriction policies allow the initiation of the attestation process, elevating trust appraisals per device at the domain level. Domain-level eMUDs enable the provision of conformity certificates based on domain-specific policies, abstracting internal device details to appraise the domain's integrity comprehensively.

To illustrate the difference between device-level and domain-level eMUDs, we consider an ENTRUST use case involving the KardinBLU ECG device from UC1. In this scenario, a device-level eMUD for the KardinBLU ECG includes specific expected binaries of the device, expected executional behavior, and key restriction policies for implicit attestation, ensuring the device operates securely within its defined trust boundaries. The device-level eMUD captures detailed information about the expected software and operational behavior of the ECG device, such as the approved firmware versions and the control-flow integrity of the cardiac monitoring algorithms. Meanwhile, the domain-level eMUD for the healthcare network that integrates the KardinBLU ECG encompasses broader security measures, addressing domain-specific threats such as data privacy regulations, patient data interoperability, and secure cross-device communication protocols. This domain-level eMUD includes policies to ensure that all devices within the healthcare network, including the KardinBLU ECG, adhere to a unified security strategy. This strategy involves compliance with healthcare standards like HIPAA for data privacy and secure communication protocols for transmitting patient data across different medical devices and systems. This domain-level eMUD also ensures that conformity certificates are provided based on domain-specific policies, validating the integrity and trustworthiness of the entire healthcare domain. By linking the device-specific trust policies to the overarching domain-level trust policies, the ENTRUST framework can provide comprehensive trust appraisals that abstract the internal details of individual devices while ensuring overall domain integrity.

This multi-level approach ensures both the security of individual devices, like the KardinBLU ECG, and the overall integrity of the connected healthcare service chain, demonstrating the practical application and necessity of eMUDs in maintaining robust, adaptive security frameworks in complex IoT environments.

The MUD serves as the means for any device in a zero-trust ecosystem to use for bootstrapping.

Stored in the MUD server, which is part of the EAP-PSK [26], the manufacturer includes information as described by the standardized IETF on the expected network behavior and the threats that can affect a device, not considering the domain. It does not capture dependencies, new threats, and considerations that need to be addressed when a device is onboarded to the domain. This is why ENTRUST creates an enhanced MUD, which includes key restriction usage policy hashes for binding the use of a key to the specific software version. These key restriction usage policies are crucial for implicit attestation, based on which trustworthiness evidence is collected, encompassing various system aspects that inform the trust assessment process managed by the TAF. Based on this, a domain-level MUD is created, where essentially a service graph chain is established, comprising all the IDs of the devices in the connected medical service chain. Trust policies capture the relationships and dependencies between all devices in the domain, guiding the attestation process and trustworthiness evidence monitoring.

The trust policy dictates the attestation process and the trustworthiness evidence monitoring process, including the types of evidence to be collected and the methodology for assessing the device's state. The key restriction policy is established during device onboarding to bind the use of an attestation key to the correct state of a device, enabling implicit attestation once the device is onboarded into the domain. Trust policies encompass the trust model, which captures the relationships and dependencies between devices, and govern the continuous trust assessment process conducted by the TAF, which monitors and calculates the Actual Trust Level (ATL) based on runtime evidence. The domain-level trust policy elevates the trust appraisal per device at the domain level, enabling the provision of conformity certificates at the domain level and allowing trust appraisals based on the policy defined by the domain manager for

the target domain. This approach enables an appraisal of the domain’s integrity, abstracting all internal details about the devices. The attestation key and the key restriction policy hash allow for the monitoring and collection of trustworthiness evidence in a zero-knowledge manner. The key restriction regulates the use of the attestation key so we can verify the device’s state through this type of ENTRUST computing abstraction without having access to the detailed evidence. This ensures device integrity and compliance with security policies without exposing sensitive operational data.

It is important to note that the enhancements we are proposing for the MUDs do not change their functional purpose or specifications. The suggestions from ENTRUST are designed to be integrated seamlessly into the existing MUD framework without altering its fundamental functionality. This makes the enhancements easy for OEMs to potentially adopt, as they require minimal changes to the current MUD profiles. By making these minimal updates to the MUDs, we enable a very advanced trust assessment mechanism that facilitates the transition to zero-trust architectures. This allows trust to be established from the application, execution environment, and device hardware all the way to the backend system, as well as robust security measures and trust appraisals without the need for significant alterations to the established MUD specifications, providing a practical and efficient path towards enhanced IoT security.

In what follows, we delve into the specific enhancements made to MUDs both at the device- and domain-level, detailing the type of data/information involved in their construction. ENTRUST explores how eMUDs are implemented to provide robust security tailored to both individual devices and entire domains, ensuring that CMD deployments can effectively respond to evolving threats and maintain a high level of trustworthiness.

6.1 ENTRUST eMUD and Trust Policy: Preparing the Device for Trust Establishment

As aforementioned, the primary objective of integrating eMUDs and trust policies is to enable CMDs to safeguard their **trustworthiness** by both enabling them to establish the necessary cryptographic primitives (i.e. keys), for their runtime operational assurance (once securely enrolled into a domain) but also orchestrating the construction and maintenance of an up-to-date trust graph for the entire CMD service-graph-chain. These keys must be generated in a way so that they can allow a device to disclose information about its **state in a verifiable but zero-knowledge manner**: Essentially, a device should be able to produce **proof-of-ownership** of specific system attributes (e.g., access to a certified Trusted Computing Base (TCB), correct bootstrapping of the devices’ software stack, ec.) based on which the trust assessment process (conducted by TAF) can converge on a trust decision. As described in D4.2 [27], towards this direction, ENTRUST leverages a novel zero-knowledge, proof-of-conformance scheme that uses trusted computing abstractions to overcome the barriers of configuration privacy and scalability [20].

This is managed through the provision of a trusted computing abstraction, called **Policy-Restricted Attestation Key**, that dynamically restricts a device’s Attestation key (secured in the ENTRUST TCB [27]) to policies chosen by an authorizing entity (e.g., Manufacturer). By predicating its ability to use its attestation key for signing on its configuration correctness, we can verify a device’s conformance using a simple challenge-response protocol that neither requires nor reveals any configuration information. Moreover, to update a device’s “trusted configuration state” during runtime (e.g., in response to patches), the authorizing entity can reactively or proactively authorize new policies restricting the node’s attestation key to a new configuration state.

Such key restriction usage policies represent a device’s expected configuration and execution state and is usually constructed by the Manufacturer based on the whitelist of SW/FW binaries to be loaded onto

the device. This information is crucial to be accessible to any external entity authorized to process and enroll a device into a domain; i.e., Domain Manager. **This constitutes one core extension of the MUD profile that ENTRUST recommends towards the creation of device-level eMUDs enriched also with such policy structures capturing the expected state of a device (cf. Table 6.1).** The policy hash is crucial in this context as it defines the key restrictions used for implicit attestation, based on which evidence is collected.

This is part of the overarching key management system envisioned in ENTRUST for securing the entire lifecycle of CMDs: From the establishment of Attestation and Attribute-specific Keys established during device onboarding to the runtime generation of symmetric keys for secure communication. This management of keys is supported in a secure and transparent manner from the underlying trusted computing base that is instantiated in each entity of the CMD continuum. The system relies on the underlying Root-of-Trust [27] to verify the validity of trusted components, ensuring secure creation and storage of keys within the ENTRUST key hierarchy. The ability to dynamically update policies that govern the use of Attestation Keys without altering the keys or key hierarchy is vital, particularly during software or firmware updates. This prevents the exploitation of outdated policies and ensures that attestation assertions remain valid and secure.

During runtime, CMDs operate under established trust policies and perform local attestation to generate conformity certificates. Trust policies are essential as they include the necessary information for guiding the continuous trust assessment process through the entire lifecycle of a device (and subsequently a domain comprising multiple/heterogeneous devices): From the definition of the appropriate **trust model templates considering the most prominent types of risks and attacks against the entire CMD ecosystem**, dictating the type of trustworthiness evidence that need to be continuously monitored, from each resource, so as to quantify its trust level (Actual Trust Level-ATL) and compare it to the Required Trust Level (RTL), to the **deployment of all trust-related information and components as part of ENTRUST'S Trusted Computing Base** towards enforcing the circulated trust policies. A trust model is a graph-based model which is built on top of a system model which represents all components (both at the level of a device and its internal components but also at the domain level capturing the relationships that need to be established between the different devices) and data needed to perform a certain medical function. Components represented either create, transmit, process, relay, and receive the data used as input to a function. The vertices in a trust model correspond to an abstraction called trust objects, and the edges in a trust model correspond to trust relationships between a pair of trust objects. The trust model also encompasses a list of trust sources used to build up / quantify trust relationships by providing atomic trust opinions. The trust model is a main input to the TMM and the TLEE (Chapter 7). **Since trust is a directional relationship between two trust objects and it is always in relation to a concrete property or scope, then as part of the trust model, there can be multiple trust relationships between the same two trust objects, depending on different properties of the trust relationship, or the scope of the trust relationship.**

Besides the trust model, trust policies also include information outputted by the Risk Assessment Engine to enable the supervised calculation of the initial Required Trustworthiness Levels (RTLs) needed for bootstrapping the trust level of all actors considered in a trust model. This process is essentially a methodology that will be followed by the (for instance) Security Administrator so as to define the appropriate RTLs based on the considered threat model. As highlighted previously (Chapter 5), the RTL can be dynamically updated during runtime in case of any new vulnerabilities been identified. This RTL, in essence, represents a baseline for the accepted Trustworthiness Level while it further identifies the attributes that need to be attested during runtime for the Actual Trustworthiness Level (ATL), and will be used to form the security claims. In addition to the Trust Models and RTL the type of trustworthiness evidence that need to be monitored are further incorporated in the overall trust policy.

6.2 Device-level eMUD vs. Domain-level eMUD

In what follows, we proceed with the definition of the extensions that are recommended by ENTRUST so as to convert the MUD profile into a “state token” holding all necessary information about the expected state of a device - **been granular enough to cover both the network- but also the host-layer depicting such correct states through policy hashes**. Such device-level eMUDs are then also used to tackle the challenge of CMD-wide trust quantification by introducing adaptive-to-changes mechanisms for capturing the devices (HW and SW) trust scores, anchored to decentralized Roots-of-Trust, and subsequently elevated carefully at the domain-level.

Device-level eMUD: Device-level eMUDs are intricately aligned with the EAP, focusing specifically on the security and operational parameters of individual devices. These eMUDs incorporate a Manufacturer’s list of potential security threats tailored to the device’s unique vulnerabilities and operational contexts. Additionally, as aforementioned, they include “policy hashes” representing the expected configuration and execution state of a device for enabling the runtime implicit attestation so as to detect any configuration and/or control-flow integrity violations. Furthermore, device-level eMUDs specify the types of evidence required to support claims about the device’s security state and behavior. This evidence can range from logs and configuration data to real-time monitoring reports, all aimed at providing a verifiable trail of the device’s operational integrity and compliance with its designated security policies.

Domain-Level eMUD: On a broader scale, domain-level eMUDs take the foundational security measures outlined in the original MUDs provided by Manufacturers and extend them to encompass domain-specific information and threats. These eMUDs are essential for adapting the generic security protocols of device-level MUDs to the unique requirements and threats of a specific operational domain, such as a healthcare network or industrial control system. Domain-level eMUDs are crafted to include considerations for domain-specific threats, which may not have been within the purview of the original device-specific MUD. By extending the MUD to address these additional concerns, domain-level eMUDs ensure that all devices within the domain adhere to a cohesive and comprehensive security strategy that is both unified in its approach and specific in its application. The trust policy includes all the information necessary to capture the model of the domain, which is essential for assessing the trust level of the devices within that domain. The domain-level eMUD also includes a pointer to the device-specific trust policy, which by default connects to the domain-level trust policy due to the multi-level inheritance property structured through smart contracts (more details on how trust policies are managed through ENTRUST specially-crafted smart contracts can be found in D5.1 [28]). Essentially, a domain-level trust policy is a child of the device-level trust policy, providing a comprehensive trust appraisal for the entire domain.

The distinction between device-level and domain-level eMUDs highlights the layered approach to CMD-continuum security, where both individual devices and their operational environments are equipped with tailored security measures. Device-level eMUDs ensure that each device adheres to stringent security standards suitable for its operations, while domain-level eMUDs broaden these protections to account for the environmental and operational specifics of the domain in which the devices function. This dual approach facilitates a robust, adaptive security framework that is capable of addressing both inherent device vulnerabilities and broader, contextual threats within specific domains.

Device-Level eMUD Fields	Domain-Level eMUD Fields
OS (OS_name, OS_distro, OS_version)	OS (OS_name, OS_distro, OS_version)
CPU (type, cores)	CPU (type, cores)
RAM (size)	RAM (size)
Crypto (Alg, type, key_size)	Crypto (Alg, type, key_size)

Network (Open_port)	Network (Open_port)
Weaknesses (id, name, description, date, etc.)	Weaknesses (id, name, description, date, etc.)
Vulnerabilities (id, name, description, date, etc.)	Vulnerabilities (id, name, description, date, etc.)
Threat-mitigation (type, id, action, etc.)	Threat-mitigation (type, id, action, etc.)
Device-specific evidence requirements	List of trustworthiness evidence
Policy hashes for the key restriction usage policy	Pointer to the device-level trust policy
	Domain-specific threat considerations
	Unified security strategy across devices

Table 6.1: Fields included in the Extended MUDs

Table 6.1 outlines the different fields of the device-level and domain-level eMUDs, highlighting the distinct security and operational focuses for each context. Device-level eMUDs emphasize granular details specific to individual IoT devices, such as detailed operating system specifications (OS name, distro, version), hardware specifics (CPU type and cores, RAM size), cryptographic configurations (algorithm, type, key size), and open network ports. They also incorporate device-specific weaknesses and vulnerabilities, with detailed mitigation actions, evidence requirements, and trust policy hashes to ensure device integrity.

In contrast, domain-level eMUDs extend these foundational aspects to include broader considerations relevant to the entire operational domain. This includes domain-specific trust policies, which provide overarching security guidelines, and domain-specific threats that address potential risks unique to the operational environment, such as insider threats. Additionally, domain-level eMUDs include policies that ensure a unified security strategy across multiple devices within the domain, adapting device-specific security protocols to fit the broader network’s unique requirements and threats. This differentiation ensures that both individual devices and the larger domain are equipped with robust, contextually appropriate security measures.

Chapter 7

Trust Assessment Framework

In the previous chapter, we provided a detailed description of the Risk Assessment component of the ENTRUST framework, and its role in the calculation of the RTL of the CMD, which is essentially the baseline level of trustworthiness of the device so that it can be considered trusted. Considering this, here we describe the process for the calculation of the **ATL** of the device, which reflects the actual level of trustworthiness of the device during runtime, based on the collection of trust evidence during the execution of an attestation scheme, and will be used in order to determine whether the device is in a trustworthy state, or if further mitigation actions are needed.

As previously outlined, the purpose of the **TAF** in the context of ENTRUST is the evaluation of the **ATL** of the CMD based on a set of trust attributes, which have been selected in order to evaluate the fulfilment of the security requirements of the device. In other words, the ATL quantifies the extent to which a certain node or set of data can be considered trustworthy based on the available trust evidence (e.g., traces collected by the **Device Tracer**). The ATL is then compared with the RTL of the device, which has previously been calculated by the Risk Assessment component, and indicates the *baseline level of trust that needs to be achieved in order to determine whether the device can be considered trustworthy or not*.

This Chapter is dedicated to the description of the TAF in the context of ENTRUST. Specifically, we first provide an introduction to the notion of **trust and trustworthiness** through a core set of principles and definitions used throughout this Chapter. Next, we provide a state-of-the-art analysis of existing Trust Assessment methodologies and we outline the innovations brought forth by the ENTRUST solution. We then describe the ENTRUST TAF and its operation in the context of the ENTRUST framework in detail, and we outline the **Trust Models** based on which Trust Assessment will be performed in the context of each of the ENTRUST use case demonstrators.

7.1 General Principles of Trust and Trustworthiness

As previously outlined, throughout this chapter, we will provide a detailed description of the TAF component of ENTRUST, including the methodology employed in order to perform Trust Assessment. To this end, here we provide an overview of some core concepts and definitions that will be utilized extensively throughout the remainder of this chapter. In addition, while these properties are generic to the notion of Trust Assessment, we will position them within the context of ENTRUST in order to facilitate their correspondence with existing ENTRUST processes and artefacts.

Proposition. A proposition is a logical statement about a phenomenon of interest, such as a trust property or attribute, whose trustworthiness we are interested in assessing. For instance, recall that the **Trust**

Policy of the device dictates the types of **trust evidence** that needs to be collected for the assessment of the trustworthiness of a **trust property** of a device. This statement (i.e., that the trustworthiness of a specific property can be attested by the verification of the correctness of specific types of evidence) constitutes a Proposition. Note that Propositions can be categorized as follows:

- **Atomic propositions:** Propositions whose truth or trustworthiness can be directly assessed or verified through the the collection of a specified set of trust evidence, originating from one or more **trust sources**.
- **Composite propositions:** These consist of multiple atomic propositions, and can be assessed through the verification of all individual propositions.

Trust Source. The term **Trust Source** used in the above definitions refers to an entity from which trustworthiness evidence may originate, so that it can afterwards be sent to the TAF for the calculation of the ATL. In the context of ENTRUST, *the core elements used as Trust Sources are the **remote attestation enablers**, which rely on the collection of trust evidence using the Device Tracer of the CMD in order to verify the correctness of one or more trust properties.* The remote attestation enablers of ENTRUST are analyzed in further detail in D4.2 [27]. Another Trust Source used in the context of ENTRUST is the **AI-based Anomaly/Misbehaviour Detection** component, which is responsible for processing application data or network traces in order to detect any deviation from known and expected behaviors (e.g., significantly higher network traffic than usual). This can constitute a Trust Source, as it can provide information to the TAF regarding changes in the trustworthiness level of the system. The output of the **Digital Twin** can also be considered as a Trust Source, which is provided as harmonized threat intelligence data in STIX format.

Trust Object. The term Trust Object refers to any entity that assesses trust, or for which trust is assessed. In the context of ENTRUST, Trust Objects may be the following:

- **Entities or components** belonging to the Service Graph Chain of the (Medical) Domain under consideration. This may refer to any of the low-end devices (e.g., sensors or other devices aiming to collect patient data) or high-end devices (e.g., gateways) participating in the medical organization. Note that these are specific to the considered domain, and in the context of ENTRUST will be specified in the following for each use case demonstrator. These Trust Objects are also referred to as **nodes**.
- **Atomic propositions** related to the fulfilment of certain trust properties based on a set of trust evidence contained in the Trust Policy of the device. These are also specific to the type of device, as well as the details of the use case demonstrator.

Trust Relationship. The aforementioned Trust Objects are the core building blocks for the formulation of Trust Relationships. Specifically, a Trust Relationship refers to a directional connection between two Trust Objects, which are referred to as the **trustor** and the **trustee**. In addition, a Trust Relationship is always defined with regard to a specific Trust Property.

In this definition, the **trustor** is *the entity which wishes to assess and verify the trustworthiness level of the trustor*. Conversely, the **trustee** is *the entity whose trustworthiness level is assessed by the trustor depending on the fulfilment of the specified Trust Property, based on the collection of the required trust evidence*. Note that the trustor is always a **node** (i.e., a component or device), while the trustee may either be a node or an atomic proposition.

Trust Network. This term refers to a set of **Trust Objects**, as well as the existing **Trust Relationships** between those Objects. Note that, as outlined above, each node (component or device) may either be a trustor or a trustee, thus may be on either end of a Trust Relationship. Conversely, Atomic Propositions may only be trustees, meaning that they need to be assessed for their trustworthiness from the perspective of a node.

7.1.1 Taxonomy of Trust Relationships

In the previous section, we provided the definition of the concept of **Trust Relationships** in the context of Trust Assessment. In this regard, in order to facilitate the description and creation of Trust Models for a specific (Medical) Domain environment consisting of multiple Trust Objects, it is meaningful to make a categorization of Trust Relationships as follows:

- **Direct (Functional) Trust Relationships:** In this type of Trust Relationship, the trustor has a direct relationship with the trustee. A Direct Trust Relationship between trustor A and trustee C is denoted by $A \rightarrow C$. *Note that, while the trustor is always a node (component), this type of relationship can be categorized depending on the Trust Object type of the trustee as follows:*
 - ✓ **Node-centric Trust Relationships**, where the trustee is also a node. Thus, in this type of relationship, the trustor aims to verify the trustworthiness of one or more trust properties of the trustee.
 - ✓ **Data-centric Trust Relationships**, where the trustee is an atomic proposition on (a piece of) data. Thus, in this type of relationship, the trustor aims to verify the truth of this atomic proposition.
- **Referral Trust Relationships:** In this type of Trust Relationship, the trustor does not have a direct relationship with the trustee, but a relationship can be established using an intermediate node. For instance, in case three Trust Objects A , B , and C formulate the direct Trust Relationships $A \rightarrow B$ and $B \rightarrow C$, then A is considered to have a Referral Trust Relationship with C , with B acting as the intermediate (referral) node. *Note that this type of relationship can only be established between nodes and not atomic propositions.*

7.1.2 Trustworthiness

Trustworthiness can be defined as *the measure of the ability of a trustee to achieve a specific task as part of a trust relationship*. In other words, if the trustor expects the trustee to perform a specific task, Trustworthiness can be defined as the *likelihood of the trustee to fulfil the expectations of the trustor with regard to the specific task*.

In this context, expectations may be different depending on the characteristics of the considered application. For instance, they may refer to expectations regarding the **correctness of the data** provided by the trustee, or the ability of the trustor to **assess the correctness of the data**. Expectations may also refer to the **behavior of the trustee**, the **process followed by the trustee to carry out the task**, or the **purpose for which the task was chosen**. In addition, expectations depend on the type of the trustor, and different trustors may have different expectations from the trustee, or different ways to translate the behavior of the trustee. This may refer to the fulfilment of different trust property, or the correctness of different types of trust evidence.

Next, considering all the above, we provide a **formal mathematical definition of Trustworthiness**, which will be utilized in the analysis provided throughout this chapter. Given a trustor A and a trustee

B , and considering A 's expectations x regarding B 's behavior $R(x)$ (i.e., the behavior of the trustee is a function of its behavior) in a context C , the Trustworthiness $T_{w_{B,A}}$ of B from the perspective of A can be formally defined as follows:

$$T_{w_{B,A}}(C) : \text{The likelihood that } B \text{ will exhibit behavior } R(x) \text{ in context } C. \quad (7.1)$$

Furthermore, Trustworthiness can be also be defined in **degrees or levels**, depending on the **likelihood of B to fulfil A 's expectations**. Thus, we define this likelihood as L , which takes values between 0 and 1, where 0 represents no likelihood and 1 represents maximal likelihood for B to fulfil A 's expectations. Thus, the definition of Trustworthiness can be modified as follows:

$$T_{w_{B,A}}(C, L) : \text{The likelihood that } B \text{ will exhibit behavior } R(x) \text{ in context } C \text{ to a level } L. \quad (7.2)$$

Finally, Trustworthiness needs to be **verifiable**, meaning that Trustworthiness should be able to be assessed based on the trust evidence E provided by the trustee. Thus, the definition of Trustworthiness can be further modified as follows:

$$T_{w_{B,A}}(C, L, E) : \text{The likelihood that } B \text{ will exhibit behavior } R(x) \text{ in context } C \text{ to a level } L \text{ established by trust evidence } E. \quad (7.3)$$

Note that, while the evidence is objective, its verification is subjective, meaning that the same evidence may be interpreted by different trustors using following different procedures. Thus, even if a set of trust evidence E is sufficient from the perspective of a trustor for the verification of a Proposition, the same evidence may be insufficient from the perspective of a different trustor.

7.1.3 Trust

In the previous section we defined the notion of **Trustworthiness** in the context of trust establishment. Here, we define the notion of **Trust**. While these two terms are closely related, one key difference is that *Trustworthiness is defined from the perspective of the trustee, while Trust is defined from the perspective of the trustor*. In other words, Trustworthiness is a measure of the ability of the trustee to meet the expectations of the trustor. Conversely, Trust refers to the decision of the trustor on whether or not to consider that the trustee has fulfilled its expectations.

Another key difference is that *trust is binary, but trustworthiness is a spectrum*. Recall that **trustworthiness can be measured in levels** depending on the degree of likelihood that the expectations of the trustor are fulfilled, while **trust is a binary decision on whether the trustor believes that the trustworthiness level of the trustee is sufficient**. Thus, **when the trustworthiness of the trustee exceeds the minimum required level, then the trustor trusts the trustee**.

Zero Trust. The principle of Zero Trust refers to *the paradigm where no initial or implicit trust is assumed between the trustor and the trustee*. Thus, when the Zero Trust principle is followed, the **verifiability of the trust evidence** is a necessary part of establishing trustworthiness. Verifiability, in this context, verifiability refers to *the capability of the trustee to provide evidence that meets the expectations of the trustor in a measurable or demonstrable manner*. For instance, when a CMD aims to verify the correctness of a set of trust properties to a Verifier (trustor) based on evidence collected by its Device Tracer, there need to be verifiable guarantees on the correctness of the trust evidence (e.g., the traces are signed with the appropriate cryptographic keys).

7.1.4 Properties of Trustworthiness

As previously outlined, the evaluation of the trustworthiness of a device needs to be **measurable** and **verifiable**. Thus, the trustee needs to be able to exhibit the appropriate set of properties that enable the trustor to verify that the trustee is in a trustworthy state. For example, in the *Tellu Remote Patient Monitoring* use case of ENTRUST, the Tellu PHG gateway device may wish to verify the integrity of one or more of the medical sensor devices providing it with patient data, in order to ensure that the data provided is correct and reliable healthcare services can be provided. In general, properties of trustworthiness can be placed into three categories:

- **Performance-based:** Properties that can be used in order to evaluate whether the performance of the trustee is acceptable, such as *reliability* and *robustness*.
- **Based on ethical aspects:** Properties related to ethical aspects and implications of the expected behavior of the trustee in the context of the target application, such as *privacy protection* and *safety*.
- **Based on user acceptance:** Properties with implications on the acceptance of the trustee, as well as the overall system or domain it belongs to, by the users. Such properties include *transparency* and *usability*.

One property may belong to one or more of the aforementioned properties, and may be related to a different property. For instance, the *integrity* property relates to the correctness of the data exchanged between various devices in the (Medical) Domain and may have implications on the acceptance of users of the medical solution, as well as its performance. However, it may also be related to ethical concerns, as a loss of integrity may lead to the insufficient provision of healthcare services.

Considering all the above, in Table 7.1 we provide a set of trust properties that may be relevant for the evaluation of trustworthiness in the context of medical systems, based on the relevant international standards and regulations [7, 11, 8].

Property	Description
Accountability	Being responsible and answerable regarding the actions and decisions made by medical devices or components. For instance, in case of a malfunction that leads to an incorrect measurement of patient data, the Manufacturer needs to be accountable for a malfunction [8].
Functional Safety	Defined as the absence of unreasonable risk due to hazards caused by malfunctioning behavior of electric or electronic systems. Thus, in the medical domain, functional safety of the intended function implies (i) knowledge of the intended function, (ii) information on the required quality and accuracy of the outcome, and (iii) knowledge of the design, development, implementation, maintenance, and operation of the processes for the collection of the data provided by the CMD.
Privacy Protection	Safeguarding personally identifiable information and ensuring that it is appropriately collected, used, secured, removed when not needed, and accessible only to authorized parties. Mechanisms to ensure this include proper consent mechanisms or other measures related to data regulations in the medical domain. Note that privacy can be categorized into (i) identity privacy , i.e., privacy of the identity of the user or medical device, and (ii) attribute privacy , i.e., the inability of third parties to obtain information that may contain details about the properties of the device. In the context of ENTRUST we are mainly concerned with the latter category, as we aim to prevent threats such as implementation disclosure attacks.
Availability	The property of a system, service, or data to be accessible and operational when requested by authorized users. It ensures that the reliable resources are consistently and reliably available with no significant interruptions, attacks, or failures, thus enabling the effective execution of the intended tasks [7].

Integrity	The property of integrity can be categorized as follows: (i) Data integrity is achieved when data has not been altered in an unauthorized manner since their creation, transmission, or storage [ISO 29167], and (ii) Device (or system) integrity , which is a function of <i>accuracy</i> and <i>completeness</i> and measures the confidence an entity can place in the fact that the device has not been manipulated in an unauthorized manner [ISO 27000]. In general, integrity of a trustee can be proven through evidence provided to the trustor through the available Trust Sources [11, 8].
Authenticity	Ensures that the identity of an entity is the one that it claims to be. This can be proven, for instance, using the HW-based Root-of-Trust that the device is equipped with [8].
Confidentiality	Ensures the protection of sensitive information from unauthorized access or disclosure, such as data that may compromise the medical confidentiality of a patient [7].
Accuracy	The ability to provide outputs within the expected range of closeness between the measured/computed and the actual value of a medical variable (e.g., heart rate or heart pressure). Typically, a system demonstrates this ability by reporting the distribution of errors under the form of an error percentile representing the accuracy of its output [8].
Reliability	The ability of a system to demonstrate dependable behavior and performance under various conditions. For example, to make a correct medical decision, a medical system should be able to receive reliable data from various medical sensors or devices [11, 8].
Robustness	The ability of a device to operate at a sufficient level of performance and a high level of consistency in a variety of circumstances. In the context of the medical domain, robustness means the ability to provide results even if the operational conditions do not provide the ability to achieve high accuracy. This property also relates to the ability of the system to react in case the conditions have reached a critical point of uncertainty, such that it is not possible for the device to function safely given the quality and accuracy of available data [8].
Resilience	The ability to adapt, recover, and continue functioning effectively in case of disruptions, failures, or unexpected events. Such events in the medical domain may include message loss or invalid input provided by a subsystem. In addition, resilience may refer to the existence of deployed up-to-date security mechanisms capable of efficiently responding in cases of disruptions, failures, or unexpected events [8].
Stability	The ability of a system or device to maintain consistency and not change easily over time, or demonstrate limited fluctuations. Furthermore, if the input remains the same, the output of the device should not present significant fluctuations.
Completeness	The ability of a device to ensure that all necessary and relevant information is available without omission.
Consistency	The ability of a device to deliver coherent and reliable performance, outputs, and decision-making over time and across different scenarios. For example, a medical device should be able to provide results that are consistent with the values and ranges of the medical values that are expected from similar cases.
Explainability	The ability to provide understandable explanations or justifications for the decisions and actions taken by a healthcare provision system.
Usability	The ease of use and user-friendliness of a medical device, ensuring that it is accessible and understandable by the users it is intended for, promoting effective interaction and user acceptance.
User-centric	The ability to match the expected extent to which a healthcare provision system's decisions, actions, and behaviors align with and take into account the intended goals and objectives of the users or stakeholders.

Table 7.1: A list of indicative trust properties relevant to the medical domain.

Note that, in the context of ENTRUST, we are mainly focused on **integrity** as the core property to evaluate the trustworthiness of a CMD. Specifically, the properties defined in the Trust Policy of the device can be attested using the remote attestation enablers of ENTRUST, such as **Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV)** in order to verify that they have not been modified in an unauthorized manner by a potentially malicious third party. These remote attestation schemes are described in further detail in D4.2 [27]. However, the Trust Assessment mechanisms of ENTRUST are able to accommodate the assessment of other trust properties, if needed.

7.2 State of the Art in Trust Assessment

In D2.1 [25], we provided a state-of-the-art analysis on existing types of Trust Decision logic methodologies, outlining the advantages and disadvantages of each. These methodologies include **Probabilistic Logic**, **Fuzzy Logic** [63] (including **Mamdani's rule-based system** [54]), **Bayesian probability** [41], and **Dempster-Shafer Theory (DST)** [21, 69]. We also stated our decision to employ **Subjective Logic (SL)** [44] for performing Trust Assessment in the context of ENTRUST. Here, we provide a more comprehensive state-of-the-art analysis, better illustrating the reasoning behind the use of SL in ENTRUST, as well as some core concepts and definitions related to SL.

As outlined in D2.1, in Probabilistic Logic, the truth values of propositions are probabilities. However, in case of insufficient evidence, we are often not able to estimate probabilities with confidence. In addition, when the truth of a proposition is assessed, it is always performed by an individual and cannot be considered to represent a general and objective belief. Thus, to reflect the perceived world as faithfully as possible, a formalism for expressing **degrees of uncertainty** is needed, considering also **belief ownership** to reflect the subjective nature of beliefs [45].

In order to handle propositions with uncertain truth values, it is possible to employ **Bayesian probability and statistics** [41], which is essentially an interpretation of the notion of probability, where probability values are used as the fundamental measure of uncertainty. However, this type of logic *does not allow the seamless modeling of situations where different agents express their beliefs about the same proposition*. This is addressed by both DST and Subjective Logic, which are able to integrate the subjective nature of beliefs and their ownership in their formalism, thus allowing the combination of different beliefs about the same proposition.

DST is a Trust Modeling methodology where probability values are assigned to sets of possibilities rather than single events. In addition, DST's rule of combination is associative, commutative, and non-idempotent (i.e., unchanged in value when operated upon itself) [46], and the underlying functions are simple to implement and compute. While this makes DST appropriate for real-time applications by allowing the sequential application of trust sources at a random order, these results should be considered with caution, as it has been shown that the order of aggregation of Trust Sources may impact the results [22]. Another downside of DST is that it can lead to counterintuitive results when combining conflicting sources, as it cannot be used to combine sources which are in complete opposition [63]. Also, the original formalization of DST is not able to formalize the aspect of trust transitivity, which is needed for the types of use cases considered in ENTRUST. However, these concerns are addressed in Subjective Logic [45].

Next, we consider the use of **Fuzzy Logic**, which is closely related to probability-based theories, but presents a variety of essential differences. The most notable difference is that they address different types of uncertainty, as probability is usually associated with events that can either occur or not with a certain probability of occurrence, while Fuzzy Logic tries to capture the notion of vagueness, focusing on the notion of degrees of truth. Thus, probability logic works with probabilities that are precisely assigned, while Fuzzy Logic works with imprecise possibilities. Conversely, Subjective Logic consists of terms that are considered precise in nature, while subjective opinions contain belief mass and uncertainty mass that express uncertainty and vagueness. Thus, if we consider SL (or DST) and Fuzzy Logic, they are able to handle different aspects of uncertainty and vagueness. Potential combination of these reasoning frameworks is a subject of future research [15].

Considering all the above, we are able to justify the selection of Subjective Logic in ENTRUST. First, note that, apart from Binary Logic, all other methodologies at a high level deal with uncertainties and uncertain situations. However, each method handles this issue differently and with different expressiveness.

Specifically, except Binary Logic where propositions can be either True or False, and Fuzzy Logic which is a many-valued logic, all other methodologies express probabilistic truth values. In addition, in comparison with Probabilistic Logic, Bayesian Probability incorporates past evidence through the consideration of the prior probability of a proposition. Furthermore, although both DST and SL consider subjective beliefs from multiple agents on the same proposition, *only SL enables merging conflicting sources of evidence*. However, recall that *DST is not able to support Trust Sources which are in complete opposition and generates counterintuitive results in these cases, and DST does not support the notion of trust transitivity, which is necessary for modeling both referral and direct Trust Relationships in complex Trust Networks*. Thus, considering all the above, *Subjective Logic is the only Trust Assessment methodology which supports all required properties*.

7.2.1 Foundations of Subjective Logic

In recent years, Subjective Logic (SL) has gained prominence owing to its capability to deal with the notion of uncertainty in propositions by explicitly representing the amount of uncertainty on the degree of truth about a proposition. Specifically, SL inherently allows:

- The representation of uncertainty as part the fundamental building blocks of SL, referred to as **subjective opinions**.
- Reasoning about uncertainty through a process of **belief fusion**, which allows the aggregation of multiple subjective opinions based on the selected fusion operator.

In the following, we expand on these notions, and we provide details on their functionality within the operation of Subjective Logic.

Subjective Opinions. These are the fundamental building blocks of SL, which represent *the amount of certainty on the degree of truth about a proposition*. A Subjective Opinion is represented as a composite function consisting of **belief masses**, **uncertainty mass**, and **base rate**. Formally, a Subjective Opinion expresses a belief about the state of a variable X which takes its values from the domain (state space) \mathbf{X} , which consists of all possible states of X . Note that only one state value is possible at any moment in time (exclusive), and all possible state values are included in the domain (exhaustive). In addition, domains can contain any number n of values, where $n \geq 2$. A domain with $n = 2$ is referred to as **binary** and can be denoted as $\mathbf{X} = \{x, \bar{x}\}$, where \bar{x} is the complement of x .

In general, in the following, opinions in SL are denoted as ω_X^A , where X indicates the target variable or proposition the opinion applies to, and A denotes the Trust Source or agent who holds the opinion. Note that A can be omitted if the belief owner is implicit or irrelevant. Considering a binary domain $\mathbf{X} = \{x, \bar{x}\}$, a binomial random variable $X \in \mathbf{X}$ can be fixed to $X = x$. Note that opinions on a binomial variable are referred to as **binomial opinions**.

Belief Fusion. Belief Fusion, also referred to as Trust Fusion, is one of the core aspects of SL, and represents the capability to merge or aggregate multiple opinions regarding the same proposition into a single, collective opinion. The resulting opinion should be able to represent the truth more comprehensively and accurately compared to each individual opinion in isolation. Note that this approach enables the consideration of different Trust Sources, and different operators of Belief Fusion may be selected when different properties are required. A high-level representation of the Belief Fusion process is provided in Figure 7.1.

Figure 7.1: High-level representation of Belief Fusion in Subjective Logic.

Subjective Logic Operators. While some operators of SL originate from binary logic (e.g., the logical AND and OR) and set theory (e.g., union, difference, and Cartesian Product), there are other fusion operators that are unique to SL. Specifically, these are **constraint fusion, cumulative fusion, weighted fusion, consensus and compromise fusion, and trust discounting**. Each of these operators can be more appropriately applied in different scenarios, thus the choice of operator depends on the specific characteristics of the target application. More detailed definitions of these fusion operators are provided in [45].

Finally, we provide some information on two concepts that are extensively used within the SL methodology. A **Subjective Trust Network** is able to represent trust and belief relationships from agents via other agents to target entities, where each Trust Relationship is expressed as a Subjective Opinion. However, for the representation of *referral* and *functional Trust Relationships*, it is necessary to represent a Trust Network as a **Directed Series-Parallel Graph (DSPG)**, which is a graph that can be decomposed as a combination of series and parallel graphs, and only consists of directed edges that form paths without loops from the source to the target. Note that, by using *trust discounting* and *fusion operators*, it is possible to effectively transform a DSPG into an equivalent single edge, which encapsulates the entire trust flow, while also considering the various Trust Relationships and their corresponding Subjective Opinions. As will be detailed in the following sections, this approach is utilized in the context of ENTRUST for the final calculation of the ATL of a device.

7.3 Trust Assessment Framework - Architecture, Main Flow and Interfaces

Having provided definitions of the required core concepts of Trust Assessment, as well as the types of Properties of Trustworthiness to be considered, we proceed with the description of the actual TAF of ENTRUST. Thus, in this Section we first provide a high-level overview of the TAF and its internal components, and we then provide in-depth descriptions of the operational details of each of these components.

7.3.1 Conceptual Overview of the Trust Assessment Framework

Next, we provide a high-level overview of the ENTRUST TAF, including its internal components and interfaces. This will provide a conceptual overview of the process followed for the calculation of the ATL of a device based on a set of trust evidence. Note that the positioning of the TAF within the overall ENTRUST framework and its high-level functionality towards performing Trust Assessment in ENTRUST has already been outlined in Chapter 2.1. Here, we essentially zoom into these workflows, by analyzing the inner workings of the Trust Assessment process. A high-level depiction of the architecture of the TAF is provided in Figure 7.2, where the TAF receives a **Trust Assessment Request (TAR)**, as well as the appropriate **trust evidence** associated with the request, and makes a decision on the trustworthiness of the device.

Figure 7.2: High-level architecture of the ENTRUST Trust Assessment Framework (TAF).

Note that a detailed description of the internal components of the ENTRUST TAF, as depicted in Figure 7.2, will be provided in Section 7.3.2. However, here we provide initial high-level descriptions of all these components of the TAF in order to better illustrate their role in the calculation of ATL of the device:

- Trust Model Manager (TMM):** Recall that, as outlined in Section 7.1, the architecture and structural details of the domain where a Trust Assessment process needs to be executed are represented in the form of a *Trust Model (TM)*. In this regard, the TMM is the component of the TAF which is responsible for (i) selecting an appropriate, pre-stored TM based on the TAR received from the application, and (ii) creating and updating TMs during runtime. Thus, in case a new device is onboarded into the (Medical) Domain, the TMM is responsible for dynamically updating the corresponding TMs. Note that, since a TM is always matched to a specific function and requires specific types of evidence for the calculation of the ATL, the TMM is responsible for providing this information to the TAF (e.g., the appropriate trust sources for the collection of the trust evidence) so that the Trust Assessment process can be performed.
- Trust Source Manager (TSM):** As previously analyzed, the trust evidence required for the runtime calculation of the ATL may originate from different *Trust Sources (TSs)*. In this regard, the TSM is the component responsible for the storage and management of all available TSs. Specifically, when the Trust Assessment process needs specific types of evidence, the TSM is responsible for communicating with the appropriate external components and collecting the required evidence. Once all the evidence is collected, the TSM proceeds to quantify this evidence into *Atomic Trust Opinions (ATOs)* (one ATO per TS) following an appropriate quantification method, and afterwards

fusing all ATOs into a single opinion using a pre-defined fusion operator. Using this method, one ATO is calculated per Trust Relationship in the TM, and all calculated ATOs are forwarded to the TLEE for further calculations.

- **Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine (TLEE):** The TLEE receives input from both aforementioned components, i.e., the Trust Model from the TSM and the ATOs computed by the TSM, and uses Subjective Logic operators in order to compute the ATL of the device. Specifically, the TLEE is responsible for assessing the trustworthiness level of the specified Trust Model (i.e., the Trust Network) based on the aggregation of all the trust opinions calculated on all available Trust Sources into a single trust opinion, resulting in the ATL of the device. The operation of the TLEE will be analyzed in further detail in the following section.
- **Trust Decision Engine (TDE):** After the TLEE computes the ATL of the device based on the specified trust evidence, the TDE is responsible for making a Trust Decision (TD) on the device, i.e., a decision on if the device can be considered trustworthy or not. Thus, if $ATL > RTL$, then the device is considered trustworthy. However, it is also possible for other methods for extracting Trust Decisions can be implemented. For example, a different approach can be considered, where the projected probabilities of the ATL and RTL (P_{ATL} and P_{RTL} , respectively) are computed and compared. In any case, if the device is deemed untrustworthy, this signifies the need for mitigation actions to be performed. In the context of ENTRUST, the Digital Twin is responsible for emulating the attack path using the provided trust evidence in order to identify the point of intrusion.
- **Trust Assessment Manager (TAM):** The TAM is the central component of the TAF which is responsible for the coordination and orchestration of various tasks pertaining to the execution of the Trust Assessment process. Specifically, it is responsible for (i) providing Trust Assessment service functions to applications (including application session management), (ii) processing and incorporating changes of Trust Model instances when indicated by the TMM or TSM, (iii) scheduling of TLEE computations, and (iv) scheduling of TDE function calls.

In addition to the above, Figure 7.2 depicts the internal interfaces of the TAF, namely the **Trust Model Instance API (TMI_API)**, and the interfaces for the **TLEE invocation (TLEE_Invoke)** and the **TDE Invocation (TDE_Invoke)**. It also depicts the external set of interfaces and services which are responsible for providing and receiving information that is used in the context of Trust Assessment, namely the **Trust Assessment Service (TAS)**, the **Trust Assessment Query Interface (TAQI)**, the **Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT)**, the **Evidence Collection Interface (ECI)**, and the **Node Discovery Interface (NDI)**.

Considering all the above, we can now provide a high-level description of the action workflow of the ENTRUST TAF, outlining the process followed for the calculation of the ATL of the device, as shown in Figure 7.2.

1. First, an external application sends a **Trust Assessment Request (TAR)**, which is received by the **Request Manager** of the TAF.
2. The Request Manager processes the TAR, and extracts the following information:
 - **TM_ID:** The ID of the Trust Model which corresponds to the function the application wants to run.
 - **prop_data:** The Proposition which points to the data whose trustworthiness should be assessed.
 - **RTL_data:** The RTL corresponding to the ATL that needs to be assessed, so that the TAF is able to generate a **Trust Decision** when the ATL is eventually calculated.

3. TM_ID and prop_data are forwarded to the TMM. Conversely, the RTL_data is forwarded to the TDE, which then awaits input from the TLEE, when it eventually completes the calculation of the ATL.
4. The TMM uses the TM_ID to locate the matching **Trust Model**, which is then forwarded to the TLEE along with the prop_data.
5. Based on these two inputs, the TLEE identifies all **Trust Relationships** (TR) for which a **Trust Opinion** needs to be built based on a list of **Trust Sources** (TSL), which is also extracted from the Trust Model.
6. TR and TSL are then forwarded to the TSM, which then proceeds to collect all the necessary **trustworthiness evidence**. Once all this evidence has been collected of the evidence, the TSM uses a pre-defined method to quantify the evidence into a set of **Atomic Trust Opinions (ATOs)**. These ATOs are then fused to produce a **Trust Opinion (TO)** for each Trust Relationship that was requested by the TLEE.
7. These Trust Opinions are then forwarded to the TLEE, which uses them to produce the ATL for the data dictated by the received Propositions.
8. The ATL is forwarded to the TDE, which then compares it to the RTL received previously, in order to finally produce the **Trust Decision (TD)** that will be returned to the application.

Having provided a high-level overview of the action workflow of the ENTRUST TAF, in the following Section we provide further insight into the operation of each of the internal components of the TAF.

7.3.2 Detailed Architecture and Building Blocks of the Trust Assessment Framework

In the previous section, we provided a high-level overview of the execution of a Trust Assessment process in the context of ENTRUST, its positioning within the overall ENTRUST framework, as well as the internal components of the ENTRUST TAF participating in the execution of a Trust Assessment process. Here, we provide a detailed description of all the aforementioned internal components of the TAF, as well as their role in the generation of a Trust Decision.

7.3.2.1 Trust Model Manager (TMM)

As aforementioned, the TMM is the component of the TAF which is responsible for the *management of Trust Model Templates and Trust Model Instances*. The term **Trust Model Templates** refers to application-specific templates created at design-time, which specify all relevant information of the instantiation of the **Trust Model Instances**. A Trust Model Template always corresponds to a specific function or application and is intended to inform the TAF regarding *what types of trust evidence data is needed by the TAF in order to calculate the ATL of the specific function or application*. Moreover, the Trust Model Template contains the relevant **Trust Objects**, **Trust Relationships**, **Trust Sources**, and **Trust Methods** required for the creation of a Trust Instance based on the Model. Note that Trust Model Instances are created during runtime based on the Trust Model Templates, and are used in order to store **Atomic Trust Opinions**, **Trust Opinions**, as well as the **ATL calculated during runtime**.

A key aspect that needs to be addressed is the *storage and management of Trust Model Templates*. To this end, the ENTRUST TAF provides a local **Trust Model Template Database (TMT-DB)**, which is managed by the TMM. Specifically, each Trust Model Template in the TMT-DB is associated with a

unique identifier referred to as a **Trust Model Template ID (TMT-ID)**. Note that the TMT-ID values are agreed upon a priori and are known to both the TAF and the application requesting a Trustworthiness Assessment, and generally do not change over time.

Considering that the TMM is the first component of the TAF which is triggered when a Trustworthiness Assessment is initiated, here we are able to provide an overview of the process followed for the initialization of a session with the TAF, focused on the role of the TMM in the process:

1. During the initialization of a session with the TAF, the application sends the TMT-ID to the TAF as part of an **initialization message**.
2. The TMM then forwards the TMT-ID to the TMM which can either (i) **locate the corresponding Trust Model Template** in the local TMT-DB repository, or (ii) **query the DLT** where additional Trust Model Templates may be located for that specific TMT-ID.
3. If the specific TMT-ID is not found in neither the local TMT-DB nor the DLT, then the TMM returns a null value to the TAM. However, if a matching Template is found, the TMM will either (i) **create a Trust Model Instance** based on this Template and return a pointer to the instance to the TAM, or (ii) **return a pointer to the Trust Model Template** containing the corresponding TMT-ID to the TAM.
4. In the latter case, the TMM creates an Instance of the identified Template. Note that, during the initialization phase, the TMM is only able to instantiate **static Trust Model Instances**, as the structure of a static Instance is only based on the fixed structure inside its corresponding Template. However, the creation of a **dynamic Trust Model Instance** is also dependent on information that the TAF has not started receiving during the initialization phase.

Conversely, in case a **Trustworthiness Assessment Request (TAR)** is received from an application during runtime, the creation of a Trust Model Instance is formulated as follows:

1. The application sends a TAR to the TAF containing, among other pieces of information, a TMT-ID. This indicates that the application wants the TAF to perform Trust Assessment based on a specific Trust Model Template.
2. The TAM uses the TMT-ID in order to check whether there is already a Trust Model Instance associated with it.
3. If there is, and if the ATL has already been assessed and stored for this Instance, the TAM will return the corresponding ATL to the application.
4. If there is no Trust Model Instance for the corresponding TMT-ID yet, then the TAM forwards the TMT-ID to the TMM to start instantiating the required Instance.

Compounding all the above, the role of the TMM is to (i) **create appropriate Trust Model Instances** during runtime based on the input it receives from the TAM, (ii) **adding new Trust Object of existing Trust Model Instances** based on appropriate input, (iii) **deleting expired Trust Objects** such as Objects corresponding to inactive CMDs or ones that do not belong to the (Medical) Domain anymore, (iv) **deleting Trust Model Instances** when they are outdated or inactive, and (v) **managing and updating the Trust Model Template Database**.

7.3.2.2 Trust Source Manager (TSM)

As previously outlined, the TSM is responsible for managing the Trust Sources from which the required trust evidence is collected in order to perform the calculation of the ATL. For each Trust Source managed by the TSM, there exists a **Trust Source Quantifier Instances (TSQ-I)**, which is responsible for *processing the evidence received from the Trust Source and calculating an Atomic Trust Opinion based on the evidence*. However, note that the TSQ-I and the approach to calculate the Trust Opinion vary significantly depending on the Trust Source and the type of evidence it provides. In this regard, the TSM is a component of the TAF responsible for managing TSQ-Is.

TSQ-Is are created during runtime based on the corresponding **Trust Source Quantifier Template (TSQ-T)**, which is created at design time. Each TSQ-I corresponds to exactly one Trust Source, which is an external entity that resides outside the TAF and provides trust evidence on the trustworthiness of a node or data item. In order to determine how the TSQ-I calculates an Atomic Trust Opinion based on the trust evidence it receives from its assigned Trust Source, the corresponding TSQ-T describes **how the received trust evidence should be interpreted** and provides the **appropriate formulas and rules for calculating the belief, disbelief, and uncertainty of an Atomic Trust Opinion**. The TAF may obtain a TSQ-T from the following sources:

- The TSQ-T may already be stored in the TAF, if it is **created during design time and installed together with the TAF** when the corresponding node is set up by the Manufacturer. Updates of the TSQ-T may be possible via an update on the software of the TAF through the available secure update mechanisms (Chapter 10).
- If a TSQ-T required for the calculation of an Atomic Trust Opinion is not stored locally in the TAF, it may be stored **in the cloud or DLT**, in which case the TAF requests the template from the cloud/DLT and, upon reception, stores it in its local memory.

Figure 7.3: The Trust Source Manager (TSM) handling receiving trust evidence and calculating a Trust Opinion on a single Trust Relationship.

Considering the above, we next outline the process followed by the TSM for handling the received evidence and calculating a Trust Opinion on a single Trust Relationship. This process is depicted in Figure 7.3 and consists of the following steps:

1. A Trust Model Instance specifies which TSQ-T should be used in order to calculate the corresponding Trust Opinion, and TSQ-s have unique identifiers (TSQ-T IDs). As outlined in the previous section, an application sends the TMT-ID as part of an initialization message when a session is established between the application and the TAF. In this phase, the TSM will **extract the TSQ-T IDs for each Trust Relationships from the Trust Model Instance**, as well as further metadata for each Trust Source.
2. **A TSQ-I is created out of the TSQ-T** based on this metadata, which contains rules and formulas for the calculation of the Trust Opinions, representing the importance of each remote attestation scheme (e.g., Configuration Integrity Verification, Swarm Attestation) used as a Trust Source. Note that the remote attestation schemes of ENTRUST, which constitute the core elements used as Trust Sources, are analyzed in further detail in D4.2 [27]. This metadata also includes information on where the TSM should request the required trust evidence from.
3. Thus, as the TSM manages the TSQ-Is, it is aware of which instance needs evidence from which Trust Sources, and handles the **communication between the TAF and the Trust Sources**. Specifically, the TSM either requests evidence, or subscribes to the external entity corresponding to the Trust Source so that it is notified as soon as the trust evidence has changed.
4. The TSM also **manages received evidence and forwards it to the corresponding TSQ-I**. For this purpose, a **unique identifier** is necessary in each received piece of trust evidence, which can be used so that the TSM can map the evidence to the corresponding TSQ-I.
5. Based on the received evidence, the TSQ-I creates an **Atomic Trust Opinion (ATO)**, which is a subjective opinion calculated by a TSQ-I which has not been fused or discounted by other Trust Opinions provided by other TSQ-Is. Note that, *for one Trust Relationship in the Trust Model Instance, several Trust Sources can be specified, and the TSM is aware of which Trust Sources correspond to which Trust Relationships*.
6. After the TSQ-Is have calculated the corresponding Trust Opinions for the specified Trust Sources for a Trust Relationship, **the TSM fuses the ATOs into a Trust Opinion which is assigned to the Trust Relationship**. Various fusion operators may be available, but the appropriate one is specified in the Trust Model Instance for the Trust Relationship.

7.3.2.3 Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine (TLEE)

Here, we provide a detailed description of the **Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine (TLEE)**, which is responsible for the calculation of the ATL for the target device, based on the appropriate Trust Model and the collected trust evidence and the computations already performed by all other components of the TAF, as outlined in the previous sections. Note that the operation of the TLEE is based on **Subjective Logic**, which is able to support the workflow and types of inputs of ENTRUST. The architectural approach of the ENTRUST TLEE is also able to support a variety of features, specifically (i) **assessing the trust** of both atomic and composite propositions, (ii) handling **arbitrarily large Trust Models**, (iii) coping with **conditional relations between atomic propositions** (which fall outside the scope of ENTRUST), and (iv) allowing **future extensions** to work with other trust computation methodologies besides SL.

Next, in addition to the terminology provided in Section 7.1, here we provide some additional terms that will be useful in the following descriptions. The term **expression** refers to a sentence in *formal language*, and in this context refers to a *syntactic representation of a proposition inside the TLEE*. In addition, an **agent** is *an entity whose viewpoint on the trust of a proposition is relevant and needs to be assessed*. In

Figure 7.4: A simple example Trust Network.

general, the agent is the node that can be seen as the root of the Trust Model. In the context of ENTRUST, this may be a TelluPHG gateway device connected to a number of low-end medical devices.

The opinion of an agent A on a proposition p can be quantified into a **level of trust** and is denoted as ω_p^A . For instance, consider the simple example Trust Network depicted in Figure 7.4, where an agent A is connected to two Trust Objects, B and C , and needs to evaluate its level of trust on the composite proposition x AND y OR (NOT z), and x , y , and z are atomic propositions. In this case, the level of trust of agent A on the composite proposition is denoted as $\omega_{x \wedge y \vee (\neg z)}^A$.

Overview of the TLEE. Having provided all foundational concepts and definitions regarding the operation of the TLEE, here we provide a more detailed view of its capabilities and internal operations. First, in order to perform a trust calculation, the TLEE needs to receive as input the **proposition** and the **Trust Model** (as well as other inputs that will be elaborated in the following) based on which the evaluation will be performed. If a composite proposition is received as input, then the first step is its decomposition into atomic propositions, and the computation of opinions for each atomic component. Also, if an opinion cannot be derived on an atomic proposition z through the available Trust Model, the TLEE checks whether there is a different proposition that is related to z through a dependency relation. In addition, note that while SL is used to perform trust calculations in ENTRUST, the architecture of the TLEE has been designed to be agnostic to the type of trust computation theory employed, thus enabling the possibility to apply a different methodology if needed.

Considering all the above, the overall architecture of the ENTRUST TLEE is depicted in Figure 7.5. In the following, we will provide a detailed description of all the elements of the architecture depicted in the Figure, as well as their role in the computation of a final Trust Opinion on the Proposition provided by the Trust Model. First, we outline the **inputs of the TLEE**:

- **Proposition:** The proposition whose trustworthiness needs to be assessed by the TLEE so that the ATL of the device is calculated.
- **Trust Model:** A direct acyclic graph representing the Trust Model where the Trust Assessment needs to be performed. This contains the nodes corresponding to devices belonging to the (Medical) Domain, as well as the connections corresponding to Trust Relationships between the nodes.
- **List of Conditional Relationships:** A list that contains information on whether an atomic proposition logically implies or is implied by a different proposition. Thus, the Trust Network defined by the Trust Model represents the dependencies between atomic components.
- **Meta Operators:** Names of logical or conditional operators that are referred to when rewriting the proposition into an expression. Recall that the ENTRUST TLEE is agnostic to the type of Trust

Figure 7.5: The overall architecture of the ENTRUST Trustworthiness Level Expression Engine.

Assessment methodology used. In this regard, the Meta Operators are essentially placeholders that stand for operations transversal to several trust computational theories

- **Trust Theory Mapping:** A table that links each meta operator’s name to the function that implements the operators in a specific Trust Computing theory.
- **Trust Source Manager (Numerical Values of Opinions):** Recall that the Trust Source Manager is responsible for calculating numerical values for the trust opinions (ATOs) for all Trust Sources belonging to each Trust Relationship. These values are forwarded to the TLEE in the form of a table that stores the known numerical values of the opinions of all the atomic components, fetched in the final step of the evaluation, and is used in the final calculation of the ATL.

As shown in Figure 7.5, the ENTRUST TLEE is organized into four modules, namely (i) the **Subjective Proposition Processor**, (ii) the **Logic Conditionals Solver**, (iii) the **Subjective Trust Network (STN) Analyzer**, and (iv) the **Trust Evaluator**. Note that modules (i)-(iii) operate symbolically and their core functionality aims towards converting the received Proposition into an expression and appropriately rewriting the expression, while (iv) is responsible for the execution of the actual Trust Assessment logic. Specifically, the functionality of the four aforementioned modules is as follows:

- **Subjective Proposition Processor:** This component is responsible for receiving a Proposition

(such as the $\omega_{x \wedge y \vee (\neg z)}^A$ depicted in Figure 7.4) and transforming it into an expression of opinions (x AND y OR (NOT z)) for the aforementioned example), which entails the formation of the Subjective Logic opinion variables.

- **Logic Conditionals Solver:** If an opinion belonging to the expression from the Subjective Proposition Processor (e.g., ω_z^A) cannot be derived from the direct observation of proposition z or from the provided Trust Model, it is checked whether there is a different path to the proposition. If no such path is found, then this module tries to derive opinions from relationships with other atomic components that have a relation of dependence with z (e.g., $z|y$). This is possible if the dependence relation is known, and if an opinion is available on these atomic components, including other elements required to solve the dependence relation. As shown in Figure 7.5, this module receives as input the Trust Model, the List of Conditional Relationships, and the expression (from the Subjective Proposition Processor), and outputs the newly updated expression.
- **STN Analyzer:** This component is responsible for symbolically resolving an opinion on a concrete proposition using the provided Trust Model, for all opinions in the expression given as input from the Logic Conditionals Solver. In general, considering that the Trust Network for resolving a Trust Opinion on an expression is an acyclic directed graph, the purpose of the STN analyzer is to reduce the Network into a single-edged graph and to build up an expression that contains the history of all the steps performed to achieve this reduction. The result of this process is a modified expression, containing only opinions about atomic components unsolved.
- **Trust Evaluator:** This component is responsible for receiving the final, reduced expression from the STN analyzer and evaluating it into a final trust value, using the numerical values of the opinions given as input to the TLEE by the Trust Source Manager. This final, fused opinion contains numerical values for the *belief*, *disbelief*, and *uncertainties*, and is an aggregated/fused subjective opinion of the trustor for a concrete proposition. *This opinion is the final calculated ATL, which is then passed to the TDE component.*

7.3.2.4 Trust Decision Engine (TDE)

The **Trust Decision Engine (TDE)** is the final component in the action workflow of the ENTRUST TAF, which receives the ATL calculated by the TLEE as previously outlined, and is responsible for extracting a final decision on whether the device should be trusted or not. Specifically, as aforementioned, it receives the corresponding RTL as calculated by the **Risk Assessment** component based on the identified threats and vulnerabilities for the specific device (considering both device-level and domain-level vulnerabilities), and if $ATL > RTL$, then the device is considered trustworthy.

Note that an alternative approach to the operation of the TDE entails the calculation of the projected probabilities P_{ATL} and P_{RTL} of the ATL and the RTL, respectively. Specifically, these probabilities can be calculated using the formula for the **binomial opinion** on the truth of a binary variable x as follows:

$$P_x = b_x + a_x u_x \quad (7.4)$$

where b_x refers to the belief mass of x (i.e., the belief that x is TRUE), a_x refers to the base rate (i.e., the prior probability that x is TRUE in the absence of belief or disbelief), and u_x refers to the uncertainty mass (i.e., the amount of uncommitted belief on whether x is TRUE or FALSE). After these probabilities are calculated, if $P_{ATL} > P_{RTL}$ then the **Trust Decision (TD)** is positive and trust is awarded. Otherwise, the TD is negative and the device is not considered untrustworthy. In the context of ENTRUST, this constitutes an **indication of risk**, and signifies the need for further investigation on whether further mitigation actions

are needed. Recall that, as outlined in Chapter 2, this is performed by providing the **trust evidence** to the **Digital Twin (DT)**, which aims to emulate the attack path that led to the negative TD. This process is described in further detail in Chapter 9.

7.3.2.5 Trust Assessment Manager (TAM)

As aforementioned, the core functionality of the TAM entails the *management, orchestration, and scheduling of all tasks pertaining to the execution of the Trust Assessment process*. We also previously outlined the purpose of the TAM with regard to the management of Trust Assessment service functionalities to external applications, management of changes in Trust Model instances, and scheduling of various function calls and computations. Specifically, it can be considered that the purpose of the TAM is the **decoupling and compartmentalization of the independent functions of the TAF**, which entails:

- The separation of the observation of internal changes from the update of the corresponding internal representations (i.e., Trust Model instances).
- The separation of the update of internal representations from the (re-) calculation of the ATL (performed by the TLEE) and the generation of Trust Decisions (performed by the TDE).
- The separation of internal state handling from external requests (performed by the TAS).

Thus, the TAM is able to deliberately schedule TLEE and TDE executions depending on a number of factors, such as (i) the **number of Trust Model instance updates** not yet reflected in preceding calculations, (ii) the **number of pending change events** for the Trust Model instance, (iii) the **staleness of previous calculations** stored in the cache, (iv) the **demand for updated decisions** based on actual sessions or pending requests (i.e., non-cached TARs), and (v) the current **number of other concurrently issued executions** for other Trust Model instances. This approach enables the TAM to apply selective load-shedding in case of too many external updates, as well as a high level of flexibility in the configuration and scaling of the TAF to different load scenarios and runtime environments with varying degrees of parallelization, load-shedding, and caching.

Internal Trust Model Instance API: The TAF provides an **internal, event-based API** which enables the TMM and the TSM to create events concerning updates in their observations, which are afterwards observed by the TAM so that the corresponding Trust Model instances are updated. Thus, the TAM follows an **asynchronous event management approach** which decouples the components and follows the **single writer principle**, based on which *only the TAM has write access on all Trust Model instances*. This approach prevents write contention and concurrent writes between the TMM and the TSM, by offloading the responsibility for handling updates of the same Trust Model instance to the TAM. Note that updates on the same TM instance are performed sequentially, but they can be executed in parallel for different TM instances.

7.4 Interfaces of the Trust Assessment Framework

Here, we provide descriptions of the interfaces associated with the ENTRUST TAF, used in the context of the Trust Assessment process for communication and sharing relevant information between components. These can be split into two categories, (i) **External Interfaces**, which refer to the interfaces between the TAF and components that do not belong to the TAF, and (ii) **Internal Interfaces**, which refer to the

interfaces between internal components of the TAF. In Section 7.4.1 we elaborate on the former category, and in Section 7.4.2 we elaborate on the latter category.

In Table 7.2, we provide a list of all the Internal and External Interfaces that will be analyzed throughout this section, as well as the TAF components that utilize each of the listed interfaces.

Interface/Service	TAM	TMM	TSM	TLEE	TDE
<i>External</i>					
DLT		✓	✓		
Trust Assessment Query Interface	✓				
Evidence Collection Interface			✓		
Node Discovery Interface	✓		✓		
<i>Internal</i>					
Trust Model Instance API	✓	✓	✓		
TLEE Invocation	✓			✓	
TDE Invocation	✓				✓

Table 7.2: List of internal and external interfaces of the ENTRUST Trust Assessment Framework.

7.4.1 External Interfaces

Here, we expand on the types of External Interfaces implemented in the ENTRUST TAF. Note that, upon entry of a device into the domain during the Pre-deployment Phase (as outlined in Chapter 2), the Trust Assessment process is automatically initiated. During the Runtime Phase, Trust Assessment is performed following the execution of an attestation scheme, in order to evaluate whether the device is in a trustworthy state. Here, we provide the interfaces of the TAF present in order to enable the external interactions with other ENTRUST components for the execution of the Trust Assessment process.

7.4.1.1 DLT

The DLT in ENTRUST represents the main repository for **Trust Model Templates**. Note that, while it is also possible for such Templates to be stored locally on the TAF, the ENTRUST DLT represents a remote source for the retrieval of Templates, in case the required ones are not available locally. From the perspective of the TAF, the DLT is seen as a *distributed, read-only key-value store in which Trust Model Templates are stored by ID and version number*. Thus, the key for accessing a Template on the DLT consists of a tuple (trust model template identifier, trust model version), and the value of the Template stored in the DLT is a serialized representation of the actual Template.

In order to improve the performance of the TAF and alleviate the need to interact directly with the ledger, we assume a dedicated query interface (e.g., a HTTP-based web interface) on the DLT, which can be used in two possible scenarios: (i) *retrieving a specific Trust Model Template based on its ID*, and (ii) *retrieving a Trust Model Template based on its ID and referring to a specific version*. In both cases, the TAF receives a request for the establishment of a Trust Assessment session and, if a version is specified, that version is retrieved. Otherwise, the latest stored version is retrieved.

Compounding all the above, the DLT interfaces of the ENTRUST TAF are as follows:

- **Remote Resolution of a Trust Model Template (Figure 7.6):** This refers to the case where the TAF needs to retrieve the Trust Model Template using only its ID number. In this case, it retrieves the latest version stored on the DLT.

- **Remote Resolution of a Specific Version of a Trust Model Template (Figure 7.7):** This refers to the case where a version number is provided in addition to the ID number. In this case, this specific version is requested from the DLT.

Figure 7.6: Remote Resolution of a Trust Model Template.

Figure 7.7: Remote Resolution of a Specific Version of a Trust Model Template.

7.4.1.2 Trust Assessment Query Interface (TAQI)

The **Trust Assessment Query Interface (TAQI)** is a service of the TAF that enables other TAF instances to query Trust Assessment processes performed in that instance. Thus, the ENTRUST TAF provides an interface that enables TAF-to-TAF interaction and may be used by applications or application functions that are located in the same (Medical) Domain with the TAF. Therefore, the TAQI represents a stateless, pull-based, read-only query protocol with which the TAF can request trust values from a remote TAF. This interface is defined as follows:

- **Trust Assessment Query (TAQ) (Figure 7.8):** The TAQ interface enables a TAF instance to query a different TAF instance for a list of trust values. Thus, the TAQ needs to contain a selector to identify the values the querying TAF is interested in. This selector specifies a *Trust Model Template type*, as well as *potential paths with optional attributes* in corresponding Trust Model instance, in order to identify certain Trust Models and nodes. In addition, it is possible for such a query to use *wildcards*, which enable creating broader queries (e.g., queries for all Trust Models containing a node with a specific ID number). Note that, in case no corresponding trust values are identified, it is possible that the query returns an empty list.

Figure 7.8: Trust Assessment Query.

7.4.1.3 Evidence Collection Interface

As aforementioned, in order to perform Trust Assessment, the TAF of ENTRUST relies on the collection of trust evidence from various external **Trust Sources**. For instance, such trust evidence may originate from the Device Tracer during an attestation process, such as Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV) and Swarm Attestation. In this case, the remote attestation enabler is considered as a Trust Source. In general, as previously outlined, the **Trust Source Manager (TSM)** is responsible for receiving trust evidence through the **Evidence Collection Interface**, whose operational modes can be (i) *actively polling known nodes for evidence*, (ii) *subscribing for evidence notifications at specific nodes*, and (iii) *receiving evidence updates via one-way messages*. Thus, three external interfaces are defined for the Evidence Collection Interface based on these three operational modes:

- **Pull-based Evidence Collection (Figure 7.9):** In this case, the TAF is aware of a specific Trust Source (for example through the Node Discovery Interface, which will be detailed in Section 7.4.1.4, and queries the specific Trust Source for trust evidence.
- **Subscription-based Evidence Collection (Figure 7.10):** In contrast to pull-based evidence collection, which performs a one-time query for trust evidence to a Trust Source, the subscription-based interface requests evidence updates when changes are detected. Note that subscriptions time out after a certain time limit and need to be renewed in order to continue receiving updates.
- **One-way Evidence Collection (Figure 7.11):** In this type of interface, a Trust Source is able to send unsolicited trust evidence to the TAF, i.e., evidence that has not been specifically requested by the TAF. This evidence may be used by the TAF to perform Trust Assessment, if applicable.

Figure 7.9: Pull-based Evidence Collection.

Figure 7.10: Subscription-based Evidence Collection.

Figure 7.11: One-Way Evidence Notifications.

7.4.1.4 Node Discovery Interface

In order to collect the appropriate trust evidence to be able to make a decision regarding the trustworthiness of a device, the TAF needs to know what are the available Trust Sources that can be used to collect Trust Evidence. In this regard, the **Node Discovery Interface** enables the TAF to discover the presence of other entities in the network. The TAF uses this interface when it needs to query available communication partners and only acts as a client. Thus, the associated interface is formulated as follows:

- **Node Discovery Query (NDQ) (Figure 7.12):** The ENTRUST TAF may need to discover all nodes with specific characteristics (e.g., all nodes equipped with a PUF or all nodes using OP-TEE). Thus, an NDQ contains a potentially empty list of filters representing discoverable nodes that the TAF wants to query. These filters may include the identifier of the node or the type of the node, and returns a list of all matching nodes for which information is available.

Figure 7.12: Node Discovery Query.

7.4.2 Internal Interfaces

In the previous section, we provided a detailed overview of the external interfaces of the ENTRUST TAF, which enable the communication between the TAF and the outside world. Here, we focus on the **internal interfaces**, which define the types of communication between the internal components of the ENTRUST TAF, as described in Section 7.3.2.

7.4.2.1 Trust Assessment Manager

Recall that, as outlined in Section 7.3.2, the TAM is a central component of the TAF which is responsible for the management and orchestration of various tasks related to the Trust Assessment process. In this regard, one of the core purposes of **decoupling and compartmentalizing internal functions of the TAF**. For this purpose, the following internal interface has been defined:

- **Trust Model Instance:** The ENTRUST TAF provides an internal, event-based API, that enables the TMM and TSM to distribute events about updates in their observations. Thus, this is an *asynchronous* interface that decouples the components and follows the *single writer principle*, based on which only the TAM has write access to all Trust Model instances. This approach also prevents write contention and concurrent writes between TMM and TSM, while the TAM is able to handle updates to the Trust Models either sequentially (for the same Trust Model) or in parallel (for different Trust Models).

7.4.2.2 TLEE Invocation

As previously outlined, the TLEE is the component of ENTRUST which is responsible for the actual calculation of the ATL, after all other internal and external processing actions have been performed, and all the necessary information is available for the Trust Assessment logic to be applied. Thus, in order to invoke the TLEE for the Trust Assessment to be performed, the following internal interface is defined:

- **TLEE Invocation:** As part of the overall Trust Assessment process, the TLEE exposes a `runTLEE()` function that can be called by the TAM, which is responsible for the orchestration of Trust Assessment tasks, as previously outlined. Specifically, when the TAM detects that the computation of an ATL is needed, it invokes the `runTLEE()` function when a Trust Model instance has been initialized and needs to allow the expression engine to prepare internal models and structures. In this case, the function is called with `nil` as the value for the `values` parameter and is expected to return an empty list of ATLs.

Specifically, the `runTLEE()` function is defined as follows:

```
function runTLEE(trustmodelID, version, fingerprint, structure, values) (7.5)
```

Next, we provide information on each of the input fields of the `runTLEE()` function, corresponding to the information needed for the initiation of the Trust Assessment process:

- `trustmodelID`: A unique identifier for the Trust Model instance inside the TAF.
- `version`: A number corresponding to the version of the Trust Model instance to be used. Note that a new version is issued when an update is performed, either in the structure or in the values of the Trust Model instance.

- **fingerprint:** A numeric fingerprint of the structure of the Trust Model instance, computed as a hash of its graph topology. Thus, if the fingerprints of two Trust Model instances are identical, they have the same topological structure. Conversely, the values of the Trust Model instance do not affect the fingerprint.
- **structure:** An internal representation of the structure of the Trust Model Instance. This is presented in the form of an adjacency list, i.e., a keyed list of Trust Object identifiers (IDs). Thus, each Trust Object is depicted as a list of tuples (target Trust Object ID, Trust Relationship ID) representing the outgoing edges from the Trust Object. Note that, if there are no Trust Relationships for a Trust Object, the tuple list for that Object is empty.
- **values:** A list of key-value pairs associating Trust Relationship IDs with the Trust Opinions associated with each Relationship.

After `runTLEE()` is invoked and the Trust Assessment logic is performed, the function returns a list of ATLs, represented as a key-value pair list containing the IDs of all concerned nodes and their corresponding ATL values, as computed by the TLEE. Note that, if `nil` is used as the `values` parameter, the function will return `nil`.

7.4.2.3 TDE Invocation

As aforementioned, the purpose of the TDE is to make a final trust decision on whether a device is trusted or not, based on the trustworthiness level calculations performed by the TLEE. To this end, the following internal interface has been defined for the invocation of the TDE:

- **TDE Invocation:** The TDE exposes the `runTDE()` function, which signifies the need for a Trust Decision to be made, after all Trust Assessment computations have been performed. Recall that a Trust Decision is made based on the comparison of the computed ATL with the RTL, upon the relevant Trust Model instance. Recall that this may be performed either by directly comparing the ATL or the ATL, or by comparing their expected probability values. Therefore if $P(ATL) \geq P(RTL)$, the TDE outputs a positive Trust Decision, otherwise it outputs a negative Trust Decision.

Specifically, the `runTDE()` function is defined as follows:

```
function runTDE(values) (7.6)
```

The `values` input of the `runTDE()` function is essentially a key-value map, where the keys are Trust Object IDs and the values are tuples of corresponding ATLs and RTLs for for each Trust Object. Thus, for each Trust Object whose trustworthiness needs to be evaluated, this table contains both its ATL and its RTL. This function is expected to return a map with the same number of entries as the input value, each one of which has *the Trust Object ID as a key and the final Trust Decision for that Object as its value*.

7.5 Trust Models and Modeling Methodology

In the context of ENTRUST, we examine the notions of trust and trustworthiness in complex (Medical) Domains consisting of multiple interconnected CMDs, which need to perform various different types of operations, such as the execution of medical operations and the sharing of different types of operational data. In this regard, it is often necessary to establish Trust Relationships between the CMDs, considering

the different requirements and expectations of each, as well as the complex interdependencies between them. Thus, it is imperative to employ a methodology for the establishment of trust in such complex large-scale ecosystems.

This is achieved through the formulation and use of **Trust Models (TMs)**, as previously outlined in Section 6.1. These are defined as *graph-based constructions which represent all components and data needed to perform certain functions*. In general, a Trust Model consists of **Trust Objects** and the **directional Trust Relationships** between them, formulating a **Trust Network**. Note that these elements have been defined in Section 7.1, and are able to capture the various types of Objects and Relationships that may occur within the Trust Network. A Trust Model should also be able to capture and store **trust sources** used to quantify Trust Relationships.

Considering all the above, we are now able to provide the elements for the definition of a Trust Model. Specifically, the following information is needed in order to build a Trust Model for a specific use case:

- **Data Flow Diagram:** This diagram contains all components participating in the Trust Network, as well as all data exchanges performed between these components. Thus, this diagram depicts the paths followed by the data, starting from a data source and ending in their destination.
- **Additional knowledge about the function:** This typically includes knowledge of what component the function is executed on. For example, this may include Trust Sources that may be used for the formulation of Trust Opinions.

Figure 7.13: An example construction of a Data Flow Diagram.

Figure 7.14: An example construction of a Trust Model.

Having defined all the core components of a Trust Model, we are now able to provide an outline of the methodology followed for the construction of a function-specific Trust Model, which is provided in Table 7.3. Note that, in each step, the Data Flow Diagram and Trust Model are created in parallel, so the actions pertaining for each of these are provided for each step.

Step	Data Flow Diagram	Trust Model
1	Identify the component where the function will run, i.e., the component that the Trust Assessment Request (TAR) will originate from .	Instantiate a node Trust Object representing the component where the function will run.
2	Identify components acting as data sources and provide data as input to the function.	Instantiate Trust Objects for each one of these components.
3	Identify which components the data needs to go through in order to reach from the data source to the destination, as well as the paths formulated by the identified components.	Instantiate node Trust Objects for every one of these components.
4	N/A	Identify the exact routes and the direction of the data flow between sources and destination and create directed links between the node trust objects that match the data flow but point in the opposite direction. Each link represents a trust relationship and has a scope.
5	N/A	Instantiate a node trust object for the TAF and create directed links between the TAF and the component running the function, directional from the TAF to the component. The amount of links between the two should be equal to the number of data sources.
6	N/A	If the data source components are deemed capable of hosting a TAF, instantiate trust objects representing the data generated by each of those sources. Create directed links between the node trust objects representing the data sources and the data Trust Objects representing the data.

Table 7.3: Process for the creation of a Trust Model

Note that, in Step 6, it is possible that the data source is not capable of hosting a TAF for assessing the trustworthiness of the data. In this case, the trustworthiness of the data is equated to the trustworthiness of the data source itself, and the node trust object will be represented as a leaf in the Trust Model.

Considering all the above, we provide an example for the formulation of the Trust Model for a function corresponding to a simplified version of the Tellu use case outlined above. For instance, consider a medical Sensor device S that may collect different types of data, as well as a Gateway GW connected to one or more Sensors. Then, this data may be forwarded to the Backend BE for further manipulation. In addition, consider the possibility for a secure update to be deployed from BE to S . In this case, the GW will request an update from BE , which will then forward the update to S through the GW . In Figure 7.13 we provide the Data Flow Diagram for this example, containing the components and the data transactions between the components. Based on these, Figure 7.14 depicts the resulting Trust Model, including all the required Trust Objects (making the distinction between trustors and trustees) and Trust Relationships.

Next, we provide some details on the notations that will be used throughout the remainder of this Chapter with regard to the construction of the Trust Models. C_X denotes data of type X collected by Sensor S , while $C_{X|U}$ denotes that this data has been collected from patient U . Recall that, in general, a Trust Opinion is denoted by ω . Thus, $\omega_{C_X}^S$, $\omega_{C_X}^{GW}$, and $\omega_{C_X}^{BE}$ denote the Trust Opinions of the Sensor, the Gateway, and the Backend, respectively, on the data C_X . Note that the former is the only one of these formulated directly (as there is a direct connection between the data and the Sensor), while the latter two are formulated indirectly (as there is not a direct connection between the data and the Gateway or the

Backend). In addition, ω_S^{GW} denotes the Trust Opinion of the Gateway for the Sensor, and ω_{GW}^{BE} denotes the Trust Opinion of the Backend for the Gateway. The referral opinion ω_S^{BE} of the Backend of the Sensor is formulated indirectly, using the two aforementioned intermediate Opinions.

Note that, for all envisioned ENTRUST use case demonstrators, complete and detailed Trust Models will be provided in Chapter 8, considering the infrastructure and the functionalities that need to be carried out by each use case demonstrator.

Chapter 8

Trust Models for the ENTRUST Use Cases

Considering all the above, in this Chapter, we provide construction for the Trust Models corresponding to all use case demonstrators, considering the components participating in each demonstrator, the action workflows, and the types of data exchanged between components. These will essentially provide the basis for the evaluation of the ENTRUST framework in the context of D6.1 [29], by dictating the Trust Architecture of each use case demonstrator, as well as the types of components and Trust Relationships that the ENTRUST security enablers can be applied to, in order to provide operational security to the CMDs belonging to each use case architecture, as well as the system as a whole.

Specifically, the use cases considered in the context of ENTRUST are as follows: (i) **Dynamic Trust Assessment in ECG Monitoring Portable Devices and Complex Stationary Devices in a Hospital Setting**, (ii) **Remote Patient Monitoring Intelligent System for Supporting Independent and Safe Living**, (iii) **Digital Assistance Towards Enhancing the Health and Wellbeing of Patients and Carers**, which consists of two individual scenarios, specifically **Smart Ambulance** and **Ensuring Trust across Legacy Systems in an Emergency Care Unit**, and (iv) **Compliant Protection of Wearable Devices for Mental Health Monitoring and Integrity of Accompanying Data**. Throughout this Chapter, we provide details on the construction of the Trust Model for each of the aforementioned use cases, considering the Trust Relationships that need to be established, the and the challenges specific to each demonstrator.

8.1 UC1: Dynamic Trust Assessment in ECG Monitoring Portable Devices and Complex Stationary Devices in a Hospital Setting

As outlined in D2.1 [25], this use case entails the use of the **KardinBLU ECG and multi-parameter monitoring system**, which is a Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) acquisition device that is able to collect cardiological data for a patient. It is also possible to collect such information from sensors measuring SpO2 levels, temperature, and acceleration.

In this use case, the aforementioned sensors collect and send their respective patient medical measurements to the KardinBLU device. Afterwards, this data is forwarded to a Gateway (instantiated in the context of ENTRUST as a **TelluGate** device) in the form of a byte array with 231 bytes per package, in accordance with the BLE 5.0 specification. The purpose is for this data to be forwarded to the hospital backend so that it can be used for patient diagnosis purposes. To this end, this use case offers two alternatives:

- The Gateway sends the data to a desktop PC running the **Kardinero Desktop Software** suite, and provides the data to the Desktop PC as a byte array with 1155 bytes per package. Note that, if

there is not a Gateway device, the PC needs to be equipped with a **KardinBLU Dongle**, which acts as the data receiver.

- The KardinBlu device sends the data to a mobile device running the **Kardinero Mobile Software** suite, which then forwards the data to the hospital backend in the form of an array of integers.

Note that it is also possible to use the Kardinero Online DB Service in order to store the data originating from the KardinBLU device. These data exchanges are also outlined in Tables 8.1 and 8.2, and depicted in Figure 8.1.

From (Component)	To (Component)	Type of Data Exchanged
ECG Data (Data Trust Obj.)	Sensor 1	Raw Sensor Data (Digital ECG)
Sensor 1	KardinBLU Device	Raw Sensor Data (Digital ECG)
KardinBLU Device	Gateway	Byte Array (231 Bytes per package) (BLE 5.0)
Gateway	Kardinero Desktop SW	Byte Array (1155 Bytes per package)
Kardinero Desktop SW	Hospital Network	Array of Integers

Table 8.1: List of components and data exchanged for UC1, Scenario 1

From (Component)	To (Component)	Type of Data Exchanged
ECG Data (Data Trust Obj.)	Sensor 1	Raw Sensor Data (Digital ECG)
Sensor 1	KardinBLU Device	Raw Sensor Data (Digital ECG)
KardinBLU Device	Kardinero Mobile SW	Byte Array (231 Bytes per package) (BLE 5.0)
Kardinero Online DB Service	Hospital Network	Array of Integers

Table 8.2: List of components and data exchanged for UC1, Scenario 2

Figure 8.1: Data Flow Diagram construction for UC1.

Considering all the above, we are able to formulate the Trust Model for the ECG Monitoring use case, depicted in Figure 8.2. Note that **the end goal of this Trust Model is the calculation of the Trust Opinion of the Backend on the data collected by the KardinBLU device**. As will be demonstrated in the following, this is essentially achieved by calculating ω_{PC}^{BE} or ω_{Mob}^{BE} , which are the final Trust Opinions in the trust chain beginning from the data themselves until their final destination. These Trust Opinions are calculated in a cascading manner, where each Trust Opinion builds upon the previous one along the trust chain, up until the final destination (i.e., the Backend).

At a high level, this Model aims to define the process for the formulation of **Trust Opinions** by devices acting as trustors towards devices acting as trustees. Note that these opinions are formulated based on the data collected by the available **Trust Sources**. In the following, we go into further detail regarding the **semantics of Trust Opinions** in this Trust Model instance, in the context of the process followed to achieve trust establishment between entities.

- C_X denotes the data collected from sensor X , and may refer to any type of sensor used in the context of this use case (EKG, SpO2, temperature, etc.). Considering a patient U , $C_{X|U}$ and $C_{Y|U}$ denote data collected for this patient from two different types of sensors, X and Y .
- Recall that Trust Opinions are denoted as ω . Thus, considering the C_X set of data, $\omega_{C_X}^{KBlu}$, $\omega_{C_X}^{GW}$, and $\omega_{C_X}^{BE}$ denote the opinions formulated on C_X by the KardinBLU device, the Gateway, and the Backend, respectively. Note that, in the Figure, only the connection between the KardinBLU device and the data is depicted as a solid line, representing a direct connection. The other two are depicted with dashed lines, representing a referral Trust Relationship, as these entities do not receive the data directly, but through other components in the data flow.
- ω_{GW}^{KBlu} denotes the Trust Opinion of Gateway for the KardinBLU device. This Opinion is formulated based on the data sent by the KardinBLU device to the Gateway.
- In the case where communication goes through the Desktop PC, ω_{GW}^{BE} denotes the Trust Opinion of the Backend for the Gateway. However, as these two components are not directly connected, the Backend needs to follow the trust chain of intermediate components in order to formulate this Opinion. Specifically, ω_{GW}^{PC} denotes the opinion of the PC on the Gateway, and ω_{PC}^{BE} denotes the opinion of the Backend on the PC.
- In the case where communication goes through the Mobile device, recall that the KardinBlu device communicates directly with the Mobile device, which then communicates with the Backend Server. Thus, ω_{KBlu}^{Mob} denotes the opinion of the Mobile device on the KardinBlu device, and ω_{Mob}^{BE} denotes the opinion of the Backend on the Mobile device. Then, the referral Trust Opinion ω_{KBlu}^{BE} of the Backend on the KardinBlu device is formulated using the two aforementioned intermediate Trust Opinions.
- As previously outlined, in the context of ENTRUST, it is possible to construct **Digital Twins (DTs)** of CMDs acting as additional Trust Sources, which can provide data that participates in the formulation of Trust Opinions on these devices. For instance, consider a **Misbehaviour Detection** operation performed on both the Gateway and the KardinBLU Device, using their respective DTs. In this case, TR_i denotes the Trust Relationships between the Gateway and its DT, while TR_j denotes the Trust Relationship between the KardinBlu device and its DT. The output of the Digital Twin component is the Misbehaviour Report $MR_{i,j}$ containing the results on the individual Misbehaviour Detection processes on both components, which is forwarded to the Backend so that it can be used in the formulation of its Trust Opinion on the Gateway and the KardinBLU device.

8.2 UC2: Remote Patient Monitoring Intelligent System for Supporting Independent and Safe Living

The focus of the Tellu Remote Patient Monitoring use case is on facilitating remote assistance for patient suffering from chronic diseases, such as diabetes and COPD. Thus, it enables patients to stay at home during the treatment and care process, facilitates any self-care actions that need to be taken, and enables healthcare providers utilize their medical personnel in a more efficient manner.

The core component of this use case is the **Tellu Personal Health Gateway (PHG)**, which is responsible for collecting data from various medical sensors and sending them to the **TelluCare cloud platform** for medical processing. Then, the TelluCare service enables medical personnel to access the collected data in order to perform remote patient monitoring, and to record the data and events in the patient's

Figure 8.2: Trust Model construction for UC1.

electronic health journal. Note that, in the context of ENTRUST, the PHG is utilized as a Gateway component in all four envisioned use cases. Specifically, a Tellu Software Stack is available, which can be installed by each use case demonstrator on a Raspberry Pi device that meets the appropriate requirements (as outlined in D2.1 [25]).

The data exchange workflow for the Tellu use case is depicted in Figure 8.3, and the types of components and data exchanges are outlined in Table 8.3. In order to collect patient medical measurements, we consider the use of a **KardinBLU** device for the collection of patient medical measurements. Recall that this device enables the collection of data from various different sensors (ECG, temperature, SpO2 levels). This data is then forwarded to the Gateway, from where it is afterwards sent to the TelluCare platform. Note that the communication between the Gateway and the TelluCare platform requires a Bluetooth pairing process as a prerequisite, and the TelluCare platform is able to communicate with the **Tellu Cloud** at the Manufacturer side in order to receive support information about the Gateway. However, these two aforementioned actions are not considered in the construction of the Trust Model, since they do not refer to the runtime operation of the system.

From (Component)	To (Component)	Type of Data Exchanged
Tellucare platform (Azure)	Gateway	MAC-adress for bluetooth pairing
Gateway	KardinBLU device	Bluetooth pairing request Binaries for software updates(assumed)
Sensor 1	KardinBLU device	Sensor data for a patient Trust metrics
KardinBLU device	Gateway	Sensor data for a patient Trust metrics

Tellu ENTRUST cloud (AWS)	Tellucare platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information about gateways/devices to be onboarded Audit support information
---------------------------	--------------------	---

Table 8.3: List of components and data exchanged for UC2

Figure 8.3: Data Flow Diagram construction for UC2.

Considering all the above, we are able to construct the Trust Model for the Remote Patient Monitoring System, which is depicted in Figure 8.4. Note that **the end goal of this Trust Model is the calculation of the Trust Opinion of the TelluCare Platform on the data collected by the KardinBLU device**. As will be demonstrated in the following, this is essentially achieved by calculating ω_{GW}^{TC} , which is the final Trust Opinion in the trust chain beginning from the data until their final destination, and is calculated in a cascading manner along the trust chain starting from the collection of the data.

As in the previous Use Case, here we provide details in the semantics of Trust Opinions as depicted in the Model, towards defining the process followed for the trust establishment between entities:

- C_X denotes the data collected from sensor X , and may refer to any type of sensor used in the context of this use case. As in the previous use case, $C_{X|U}$ and $C_{Y|U}$ denote data collected on patient U by sensors X and Y , respectively.
- $\omega_{C_X}^{KBlu}$, $\omega_{C_X}^{GW}$, and $\omega_{C_X}^{TC}$ denote the Trust Opinions on the set of data C_X by the KardinBLU device, the Gateway, and the TelluCare platform, respectively. As previously, only the KardinBLU device formulates direct Trust Opinions on the data, while the other components form indirect Trust Opinions based on the referral Trust Relationship.
- ω_{KBlu}^{GW} denotes the Trust Opinion of the Gateway on the KardinBLU device, while ω_{GW}^{TC} denotes the Trust Opinion of the TelluCare platform on the Gateway. Furthermore, ω_{KBlu}^{TC} denotes the Trust Opinion of the TelluCare Platform on the KardinBLU device, but since there is no direct connection between them, it is formulated indirectly through the referral Trust Relationship, using the two aforementioned intermediate Trust Opinions.
- Recall that the information collected at the TelluCare platform can be used by medical personnel in order to perform a medical diagnosis on the health of the patient. This diagnosis needs to be associated with trustworthiness evidence for the correctness and integrity of the infrastructure where the TelluCare Platform is running. While this goes beyond the attestation capabilities of ENTRUST as we focus on the edge devices, we need to be able to consider **attestation enablers for virtualized environments** in the context of a Trust Assessment Framework for such a use case (such as the TelluCare platform, in this instance). Such trustworthiness evidence TE_i may be provided by a Trust Source TS_i , in order to evaluate the trustworthiness of the medical diagnosis.

Figure 8.4: Trust Model construction for UC2.

8.3 UC3: Digital Assistance Towards Enhancing the Health and Wellbeing of Patients and Carers

The purpose of this use case is to address the cybersecurity challenges associated with the increasing prevalence in the use of digital health solutions (e.g., connected devices, digitalized information systems, healthcare data repositories) in healthcare delivery systems, which need to operate in tandem with older devices running outdated or legacy software and/or firmware with different operating systems. Such systems may present a high number of vulnerabilities or risks, which need to be addressed by the ENTRUST framework. In this context, two different scenarios have been identified: (i) **Smart Ambulance** and (ii) **Ensuring trust across legacy systems in an Emergency Care Unit**. In the following, we provide details on the construction of the Trust Models for both aforementioned scenarios.

8.3.1 Scenario 1 (UC3-S1): Smart Ambulance

This use case entails the transportation of patient in critical status to a healthcare institution (hospital). During transportation, several CMDs are used in order to monitor the condition of the patient until the patient is safely transported to the hospital. In addition, the **Emergency Medical Technicians (EMTs)** present on the ambulance collect medically relevant information on the condition of the patient. This demonstrator enables the creation of a **connected smart ambulance** system, allowing all aforementioned types of data to be sent to the hospital, thus making them instantly available to hospital doctors and staff, in order to facilitate the timely and efficient remote provision of healthcare services. It is also possible for this network to support multiple ambulances through the establishment of a **dynamic network topology**, as outlined in D2.1 [25].

The data exchange workflow in this use case is depicted in Figure 8.5, and the types of components and data exchanges are outlined in Table 8.4. The components present in the architectural setup of this use

case are as follows:

- **PARTICLE Cloud Server (server node):** backend and frontend services with API to receive, store and manage data from CMDs.
- **PARTICLE Gateway (proxy CMD):** Component deployed at the ambulance that provides connectivity between local CMDs and PARTICLE server. It will be used to run local ENTRUST components.
- **Benevision N1 MD (medical device from third party):** Medical device deployed at the ambulance that gathers vitals data from patients.
- **Kardinero ECG Bluetooth (KardinBLU) MD (medical device from ENTRUST Partner):** Medical device deployed at the ambulance that gathers ECG from patients.
- **PARTICLE SW Update Server (server node):** backend services to provide SW updates to PARTICLE gateway.

In this case, we consider the capability to support various types of devices in the ambulance. Specifically, as outlined above, the demonstration scenario includes a **KardinBLU device**, as previously outlined in the context of UC1, and a **Benevision N1 MD device**, which is a third-party medical data collection device. The medical data originating from these devices is sent to the **PARTICLE Gateway** (to be instantiated in the context of ENTRUST using the **Tellu Gateway** software stack), from where it is sent to the **PARTICLE Cloud Server** where it can be retrieved by medical personnel in order to provide the required medical services. It is also possible to fetch software updates for any of the aforementioned devices through the **Update Server**, which communicates with the medical data collection devices through the Gateway.

From (Component)	To (Component)	Type of Data Exchanged
Benevision N1 MD	PARTICLE Gateway	Device identification information. Vitals data in HL7 format. Includes BP, HR, SpO2, RR, etc.
KardinBLU	PARTICLE Gateway	Device identification information. ECG data.
PARTICLE Gateway	PARTICLE Cloud Server	Authentication credentials and auditing information. Patient data from connected devices (using PARTICLE API)
PARTICLE Gateway	PARTICLE SW Update Server	Authentication credentials, Fetch software components
PARTICLE Gateway	Update server	Fetch software components

Table 8.4: List of components and data exchanged for UC3, Scenario 1

Figure 8.5: Data Flow Diagram construction for UC3 (Scenario 1).

Figure 8.6: Trust Model construction for UC3 (Scenario 1).

Considering all the above, we are able to construct the Trust Model for the Smart Ambulance use case, which is depicted in Figure 8.6. Note that **the end goal of this Trust Model is the calculation of the Trust Opinion of the Cloud Server on the data collected by the devices collecting data from the patient in the ambulance**. As will be demonstrated in the following, this is essentially achieved by calculating $\omega_{GW_i}^{CS}$, which is the final Trust Opinion in the trust chain beginning from the data until their final destination, and is calculated in a cascading manner along the trust chain starting from the collection of the data.

In the following, we also consider the possibility for multiple ambulances denoted by different indices (i and j in this case). As in the previous Use Cases, here we provide details in the semantics of Trust Opinions as depicted in the Model, towards defining the process followed for the trust establishment between entities:

- C_X and C_Y denote the data collected from the KardinBlu and Benevision devices, respectively. In this case, considering a patient U being transported by Ambulance i , $C_{X|U}$ denotes data collected by the KardinBLU device from patient U , while $C_{Y|U}$ denotes data collected by the Benevision device from patient U .
- $\omega_{C_X}^{KBlu}$, $\omega_{C_X}^{BV}$, $\omega_{C_X}^{GW_i}$, and $\omega_{C_X}^{CS}$ denote the Trust Opinions on the set of data C_X by the KardinBLU device, the Benevision device, the Gateway, and the Cloud Server, respectively. Note that only the KardinBLU and Benevision devices formulate direct Trust Opinions on the data they collect, while the other components form indirect Trust Opinions on the data through the referral Trust Relationship.
- $\omega_{KBlu}^{GW_i}$ and $\omega_{BV}^{GW_i}$ denotes the Trust Opinion of the Gateway of ambulance i on the KardinBLU and Benevision devices, respectively. Conversely, $\omega_{GW_i}^{CS}$ denotes the Trust Opinion of the Cloud Server on the Gateway. Furthermore, ω_{KBlu}^{CS} and ω_{BV}^{CS} denotes the Trust Opinion of the Cloud Server on the KardinBLU and the Benevision devices, respectively. However, since there is no direct connection

between the Cloud Server and these devices, the Trust Opinions are formulated indirectly through the referral Trust Relationship using the intermediate Trust Opinions.

- As aforementioned, in this use case, we also consider the presence of an Update Server in order to be able to deploy updates to the CMDs in a secure manner. Recall that this process is performed through the Digital Twin (DT) module, which is responsible for emulating potential attacks on the devices running in the ambulance. Thus, TR_i and TR_j denote the Trust Relationships between the DT and the KardinBLU and Benevision devices, respectively, and $MR_{i,j}$ denotes the Misbehavior Detection report sent to the Update Server in order to determine if a secure update is needed. In addition, ω_{US}^{DT} denotes the Trust Opinion of the DT on the Update Server, which is used to determine if the Server is in a trustworthy state for the deployment of secure updates.
- Recall that the information collected at the Cloud Server can be used by medical personnel in order to perform a medical diagnosis on the health of the patient during their transportation to the hospital. Similarly to the Tellu use case, the diagnosis needs to be associated with trustworthiness evidence for the correctness and integrity of Cloud Server infrastructure. Such trustworthiness evidence TE_i may be provided by a Trust Source TS_i , in order to evaluate the trustworthiness of the medical diagnosis.
- As aforementioned, it is possible to consider multiple ambulances in the context of this use case. Thus, the Cloud Server and Update Server are able to communicate with the Gateway of each connected ambulance in order to receive its corresponding medical sensor information, and all aforementioned types of Trust Relationships and Trust Opinions can be applied to the internal components of each connected ambulance (such as ambulance j depicted in Figure 8.6).

8.3.2 Scenario 2 (UC3-S2): Ensuring Trust across Legacy Systems in an Emergency Care Unit

The purpose of this use case is the development of an environment that enables ensuring trust in situations where legacy CMDs are used for monitoring patients in a hospital environment. In general, the lifecycle of a CMD may reach 10 years or more. However, unless they can receive the latest security updates, CMDs become outdated, thus constituting a potential source of vulnerabilities. Before reaching the end of their lifecycle, most CMDs stop receiving updates, either due to lack of support from manufacturers or due to hardware limitations. This use case will build a trusted secure environment in a hospital setting even when legacy outdated CMDs are deployed. In this setting, a secure gateway running ENTRUST components is deployed, in order to protect the unsecure legacy CMDs, while also ensuring that the legacy CMDs and the server component can exchange data in a secure manner. Thus, the components belonging to the architecture of this use case are as follows:

- **Econet Compact 7 (legacy CMD):** outdated and vulnerable CMD deployed at the hospital that collects data from patients.
- **BMC server (server node):** server component that receives data from the legacy CMD. The server runs Windows 10.
- **ENTRUST Gateway:** Component deployed at the hospital that provides connectivity between legacy CMDs and the BMC server. It will be used to build a secure network and run local ENTRUST components. In the context of ENTRUST, this is instantiated using the Tellu Gateway software stack.

The data flow diagram for this use case is depicted in Figure 8.5, and the types of data exchanged between components are outlined in Table 8.5. Specifically, we consider the **Econet Compact 7** medical sensor device, which corresponds to an outdated or legacy CMD. This is connected to the **ENTRUST Gateway**, which is responsible for forwarding the collected sensor data to the **BMC Server**, where this data may be used depending on the needs of the medical organization. There is also a **Windows Update Server**, which is responsible for deploying updates to the Gateway component.

From (Component)	To (Component)	Type of Data Exchanged
Econet Compact 7	BMC Server	Authentication credentials. Patient medical measurements: NIBP, ECG, Pulse Rate, Respiration, SpO2, Temperature, IBP (optional), CO2 (optional). This interface is mediated and controlled by the ENTRUST Gateway.
Econet Compact 7	ENTRUST Gateway	Profile and network data to be used by ENTRUST components.
ENTRUST Gateway	BMC Server	Profile and network data to be used by ENTRUST components.
BMC Server	Windows Update Server	Fetch software updates from Microsoft servers.

Table 8.5: List of components and data exchanged for UC3, Scenario 2

Figure 8.7: Data Flow Diagram construction for UC3 (Scenario 2).

Considering all the above, we are able to construct the Trust Model for the Smart Ambulance use case, which is depicted in Figure 8.8. Note that **the end goal of this Trust Model is the calculation of the Trust Opinion of the BMC Server on the data collected by the Econet Compact 7 device**. As will be demonstrated in the following, this is essentially achieved by calculating ω_{GW}^{BMC} , which is the final Trust Opinion in the trust chain beginning from the data until their final destination, and is calculated in a cascading manner along the trust chain starting from the collection of the data.

As in the previous Use Cases, here we provide details in the semantics of Trust Opinions as depicted in the Model, towards defining the process followed for the trust establishment between entities:

- C_X denotes the data collected from sensor X , and may refer to any type of legacy medical device used in the context of this use case. As, aforementioned, in this case, this is represented with an Econet Compact 7 device. Thus, $C_{X|U}$ and $C_{Y|U}$ denote data different types of data collected from the Econet Compact 7 device from Patient U . The types of collected data may include NIBP, ECG, Pulse Rate, Respiration, SpO2, temperature, IBP, or CO2.
- $\omega_{C_X}^{EC7}$, $\omega_{C_X}^{GW}$, and $\omega_{C_X}^{BMC}$ denote the Trust Opinions on the set of data C_X by the Econet Compact 7 device, the Gateway, and the BMC Server, respectively. Note that only the Econet Compact 7

Figure 8.8: Trust Model construction for UC3 (Scenario 2).

device formulates a direct Trust Opinion on the data it collects, while the other components form indirect Trust Opinions on the data through the referral Trust Relationship.

- ω_{EC7}^{GW} denotes the Trust Opinion of the Gateway on the Econet Compact 7 device, while ω_{GW}^{BMC} denotes the Trust Opinion of the BMC Server on the Gateway. Furthermore, ω_{EC7}^{BMC} denotes the Trust Opinion of the BMC Server on the Econet Compact 7 device. However, since there is no direct connection between the BMC Server and the Econet Compact 7, this Trust Opinion is formulated indirectly using the intermediate Trust Opinions through the referral Trust Relationship.
- As aforementioned, in this use case, we also consider the presence of an Update Server in order to be able to deploy updates to the software running on the BMC server in a secure manner. Thus, we need to consider the Trust Opinion of the BMC Server on the Update Server on the Gateway and BMC Server, denoted by ω_{US}^{BMC} , which is used in order to determine if the Update Server is in a trustworthy state, and is thus able to deploy updates in a secure manner.

8.4 UC4: Compliant Protection of Wearable Devices for Mental Health Monitoring and Integrity of Accompanying Data

This use case entails the development of precision biomarkers and digital therapeutics in order to facilitate the provision of healthcare services pertaining to the Mental Health of patients, thus facilitating the enhancement of their emotional intelligence and the development of appropriate coping mechanisms and behavioral techniques. To this end, the core components participating in the architecture of this use case demonstrator are as follows:

- **Feel Emotion Sensor (FES):** This is essentially the core component of this use case, which is a wearable device with the capability to collect various types of medical evidence from the patient, specifically (i) **Sweat**, (ii) **Heartbeat**, and (iii) **Skin temperature**.
- **Mobile device:** The mobile phone of the patient, equipped with the **Feel mobile application**, which is able to analyze the aforementioned collected data using proprietary algorithms in order to detect

events and phenomena related to the Mental Health of the patient. Thus, through this application, the patient is able to receive relevant real-time notifications, track their sleep, log their emotions, and enhance their emotional awareness.

- **Gateway:** As outlined in D2.1 [25], a Gateway device has been added to the action workflow of this use case demonstrator in the context of ENTRUST, in order to enable the provision of the security services provided by the ENTRUST framework. As in the previous use cases, this is instantiated through the use of the **Tellu Gateway software stack** on a Raspberry Pi device.
- **Update Server:** In order to securely install software or firmware updates on the FES (e.g., after a threat or vulnerability has been identified through the Digital Twin), the relevant patches are deployed through an Update Server.

The data flow between components in this use case is depicted in Figure 8.9, and the types of data exchanged between components are listed in Table 8.6. Specifically, the FES device is connected to the Gateway through Bluetooth using the BLE protocol, and connection is established via a pairing process. As outlined in the Table, various types of data are exchanged between the FES and the Gateway, such as the sensor data packets collected by the FES. This data is then forwarded to the Mobile Device. The Gateway is also connected to the Update Server, and is able to request an update for the FES, so that it can afterwards be securely deployed and installed on the FES.

From (Component)	To (Component)	Type of Data Exchanged
Feel Emotion Sensor	ENTRUST Gateway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bluetooth Advertising/Scan response data (while disconnected - see BLE standards) • BLE Connection parameters and Pairing data (see BLE standard) • Live Sensor Data packets - 341 bytes/packet (in 25 separate chunks/messages sent every second) • Offline Sensor Data packets - 12 packets x 341 bytes/packet every second • Command responses (e.g. FW Version - 6 bytes, echo command responses - variable length max 4 bytes per response)
ENTRUST Gateway	Feel Emotion Sensor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BLE Connection parameters and Pairing data (see BLE standard) • FES Commands (3 -10 bytes per command) • Device FW Update (FW image approx. 250-350kB)

Table 8.6: List of components and data exchanged for UC4

Considering all the above, we are able to construct the Trust Model for the Smart Ambulance use case, which is depicted in Figure 8.10. Note that **the end goal of this Trust Model is the calculation of the Trust Opinion of the Feel mobile application on the data collected by the FES wearable device**. As will be demonstrated in the following, this is essentially achieved by calculating ω_{GW}^{Mob} , which is the final Trust Opinion in the trust chain beginning from the data until their final destination, and is calculated in a cascading manner along the trust chain starting from the collection of the data.

As in the previous Use Cases, here we provide details in the semantics of Trust Opinions as depicted in the Model, towards defining the process followed for the trust establishment between entities:

Figure 8.9: Data Flow Diagram construction for UC4.

Figure 8.10: Trust Model construction for UC4.

- C_X denotes the data collected from sensor X , and may refer to any type of data collected by the FES wearable device (sweat, heartbeat, or skin temperature). Thus, $C_{X|U}$ and $C_{Y|U}$ denote data different types of data collected by the FES from Patient U .
- $\omega_{C_X}^{FES}$, $\omega_{C_X}^{GW}$, and $\omega_{C_X}^{Mob}$ denote the Trust Opinions on the set of data C_X by the FES, the Gateway, and the Mobile Device, respectively. Note that only the FES formulates a direct Trust Opinion on the data it collects, while the other components form referral Trust Relationships and form referral Trust Opinions on the data.
- ω_{FES}^{GW} denotes the Trust Opinion of the Gateway on the FES, while ω_{GW}^{Mob} denotes the Trust Opinion of the Mobile device on the Gateway. Furthermore, ω_{FES}^{Mob} denotes the Trust Opinion of the Mobile device on the FES. However, since there is no direct connection between these two components is indirect through the Gateway, this referral Trust Opinion is formulated indirectly through the intermediate Trust Opinions. Note that the connection of the FES with the Gateway is instantiated with a Bluetooth (BLE) connection. Thus, in the evaluation of this use case in the context of D6.1, this relationship will be considered as trusted with a high level of belief, because attesting Bluetooth operations goes beyond the scope of the Trusted Computing enablers offered by the project.
- As aforementioned, in this use case, we also consider the presence of an Update Server in order to be able to deploy updates to the FES in a secure manner. Thus, we need to consider the Trust Opin-

ions of the Update Server on the Gateway and FES, denoted by ω_{GW}^{US} and ω_{FES}^{US} , respectively. Note that, as the Update Server is only connected to the BMC Server and not directly to the Gateway, the former (referral) Trust Opinion is formulated indirectly through the intermediate Trust Opinions, while the latter is formulated directly.

- In this use case, in the context of ENTRUST, we employ the **Digital Twins (DT)** component in order to emulate potential attacks detected at the FES or the Gateway. Thus, in case a secure update needs to be deployed, the DT determines if there is an Indication of Compromise that necessitates the deployment of an update through the DT. In this case, TR_i denotes the Trust Relationships between the Gateway and its DT, while TR_j denotes the Trust Relationship between the FES and its DT. The output of the Digital Twin component is the Misbehaviour Report $MR_{i,j}$ containing the results on the individual Misbehaviour Detection processes on both components, which is forwarded to the Update Server in order to determine whether an update is needed or not. In addition, ω_{US}^{DT} denotes the Trust Opinion of the DT on the Update Server, which is used in order to determine if the Update Server is in a trustworthy state and is thus able to deploy a secure update.

Chapter 9

ENTRUST Digital Twinning for CMD Sustainability

The ENTRUST Digital Twin employs state-of-the-art digital twin technology to enhance the cybersecurity and operational assurance (e.g., resilience, safety, and robustness) of connected medical devices. It utilizes a **sophisticated architecture that mirrors the real-time dynamics of connected medical devices within a controlled digital environment, enabling continuous monitoring, predictive analytics, and proactive system management.**

The ENTRUST Digital Twinning technology aims to enhance the trustworthiness of CMDs through two core functionalities: AI-based Anomaly Detection and a controlled environment for emulating attack paths identified by the Threat Modelling component. The AI-based Anomaly Detection serves as an additional trust source by continuously monitoring and identifying unusual behaviors. The controlled environment for attack emulation, which will be investigated in the next release of the framework, enables the simulation of potential attack scenarios based on vulnerabilities identified by Threat Modelling. This simulation helps determine the appropriate security controls and attestation tasks to be deployed, thereby strengthening the overall security posture of CMDs.

Recall that, in D3.1 [26], we outlined a series of high-level user stories (as functional specifications) that demonstrated our strategic vision for utilizing digital twin technology to enhance the cybersecurity framework of connected medical systems. Each narrative underscored a distinct facet of the proposed solution, illustrating how digital twins can effectively secure and manage connected medical infrastructure. In this chapter, we delve deeper into the design and implementation aspects of these technologies, providing a detailed exploration of the architectural and operational advancements proposed in the earlier narratives.

This chapter delves into the intricate architecture and functional mechanics of the ENTRUST Digital Twin, providing a comprehensive overview of its components, data flow processes, and interactions with other ENTRUST framework components (e.g., the Threat Modeling and Risk Assessment components). The interactions between the ENTRUST digital twin and other ENTRUST components facilitate its envisioned functionalities. These interactions are primarily driven by runtime trust enablers, such as attestation extensions, which enable real-time monitoring of events and the detection of changes in a device's trust level following a failed attestation. The digital twin mainly interacts with the ENTRUST Threat Modelling and Risk Assessment components, further enhancing its capability to identify and respond to potential security threats and vulnerabilities. By outlining the project's core elements—ranging from the IoT gateway to advanced data processing, visualization tools, and interactions with other ENTRUST components—we aim to showcase how digital twin technology can be leveraged to foster a more secure and efficient healthcare infrastructure.

The subsequent sections will explore each component of the digital twin architecture in detail, highlight the data flows and mechanisms that facilitate seamless system integration, and discuss the practical applications of this technology in enhancing **device security and predictive maintenance**. Through this analysis, we aim to contribute to the **broader discourse on digital twin technology towards healthcare sustainability**, highlighting its potential to transform the management and security of CMDs.

9.1 Overall Vision & Set of Exposed Functionalities

The overarching vision for the ENTRUST Digital Twin is to establish a **sophisticated, multifaceted simulation and analysis platform that enhances the security posture of connected medical systems**. Central to this vision is the implementation of an experimental sandbox environment, which serves as a controlled testing ground for detailed system analysis and configuration experimentation. Within this sandbox, we deploy a representative system of connected medical devices, allowing for comprehensive monitoring and manipulation of system properties under various scenarios.

Synchronizing physical medical devices with their virtual representations poses a significant challenge. In ENTRUST, we address this by continuously consuming runtime-monitored system measurements to maintain an up-to-date view of device configurations rather than relying on strict synchronization. This approach allows the digital twin to dynamically reflect the current state of the devices, accommodating changes and updates in real-time. By leveraging ongoing data streams from system metrics, we ensure that the digital twin remains a reliable and accurate representation of the physical devices, facilitating effective monitoring, anomaly detection, and risk assessment without rigid synchronization protocols. This method enhances the resilience and flexibility of the digital twin and ensures that the system can adapt to the evolving operational conditions of the medical devices. The key components of such an architecture are the following:

- **Experimental Setup (Sandbox):** The sandbox environment is designed to simulate real-world operations of medical systems, facilitating the execution of controlled attack simulations. This setup enables the exploration of system behaviors under different configurations (e.g., system behaviors are monitored through traces collected from physical devices, which can then be tested and evaluated under different configurations), thereby identifying potential vulnerabilities and response mechanisms under simulated cyber threats. System configuration involves the software and firmware stack of a medical device, which is fine-tuned with various parameters and potentially includes connections and communication channels with other devices in the same domain. It is essential for evaluating and predicting the behavior of the interconnected devices.
- **Attack Simulation:** By simulating various attack scenarios (obtained from the Threat Modeling component) within the sandbox, we can assess the resilience of different system configurations. This proactive approach helps in refining the system's defenses, ensuring that each configuration is robust against a wide range of potential threats.
- **Anomaly Detection:** An advanced anomaly detection framework is integrated within the sandbox, analyzing measurements and data flows to pinpoint irregular patterns that may indicate vulnerabilities or ongoing attacks. This tool is crucial for preemptive security measures, as it allows for the early detection of potential threats before they manifest in the operational environment.
- **Predictive Intelligence:** Leveraging data from attack simulations and anomaly detections, the vision includes developing predictive models that can foresee vulnerabilities based on specific system designs. Although not yet implemented, this future research goal aims to transform reactive security

measures into a predictive framework, thereby enhancing the preemptive capabilities of healthcare cybersecurity. Such a predictive analysis can support us to better identify the trust boundaries of a device's/domain's behavior which means what type of system properties can be affected by a threat. Consequently, this allows for targeted attestation of only those critical properties, rather than the entire software stack. This approach addresses a core limitation of traditional attestation processes by focusing on the safety-critical properties that have been identified as potential vulnerabilities in the device's overall behavior.

- **Integration with Real System Traces:** Beyond the sandbox, the digital twin is designed to interface seamlessly with the ENTRUST Attestation Agent, which monitors real-time operations of the deployed medical systems. By analyzing system traces collected from the operational environment, the anomaly detection algorithms can identify deviations from normal behavior, suggesting potential security breaches or system malfunctions.
- **Continuous Learning and Adaptation:** The data and insights gained from both the sandbox simulations and real-time system monitoring contribute to a continuous learning loop. This iterative process ensures that the digital twin remains updated with the latest threat intelligence and adapts its predictive models to evolving cybersecurity challenges.

9.2 Digital Twin Infrastructure

This section provides a comprehensive overview of the digital twin framework, illustrating how it integrates with, enhances, and supports the cybersecurity measures for connected medical devices. This section is structured into several subsections, each detailing a critical aspect of the development, implementation, and functionality of the ENTRUST Digital Twinning component. Initially, we briefly summarize the DT's connectivity and collaborative interactions with other components of the ENTRUST ecosystem (see Section 9.2.1). Next, we present the high-level architecture of the digital twin, providing a broad perspective on how the digital twin operates within the larger context of connected medical devices (see Section 9.2.2). This overview sets the stage for a deeper exploration of the digital twin's role in simulation and analysis. We delve into a more granular illustration of the digital twin's architecture, outlining specific components, their functionalities, and how they are engineered to work together to simulate, monitor, and analyze device behavior and system integrity (see Section 9.2.3). We further break down the individual components of the digital twin, describing their roles, the technology stack behind them, and their contribution to the overall effectiveness of the digital twin in identifying and mitigating security risks (see Section 9.2.4). Finally, we describe the installation of the digital twin infrastructure (see Section 9.2.5). The current focus in the first release is to enable AI-based Anomaly Detection based on the integration of real-time traces. Therefore, we detail the anomaly detection method employed by the digital twin, explaining the algorithms, data processing techniques, and operational logic used to detect irregular patterns and potential threats from vast datasets collected from medical devices (see Section 9.3). The other core functionalities of predictive maintenance will be provided as part of the second release of the framework.

9.2.1 System Context

This section details the potential interactions between the ENTRUST Digital Twin components and other integral components within the ENTRUST framework. This holistic perspective is crucial to understanding how the digital twin integrates seamlessly with broader system operations to enhance the trust (including

security and efficiency) of connected medical devices. The ENTRUST Digital Twin relies on continuous data exchange and functional interoperability with various other components within the ENTRUST ecosystem. These interactions are essential for the digital twin to receive real-time data and apply machine intelligence effectively.

- **Data Acquisition and Integration:** The Device Data and Execution Tracer component (as part of the ENTRUST Trusted Computing Base deployed as the trust anchor of all devices comprising a medical-service-graph-chain [27]) is designed to capture detailed operational data from connected medical devices. It continuously monitors and records data from medical systems, ensuring a comprehensive capture of all relevant operational aspects. Note that, with regard to the tracing capabilities of ENTRUST, we consider two components: (i) the **Monitoring Agent**, which is responsible for the collection of information that enables the synchronization of the Digital Twin component with the Secure Software Update component (this process is described in detail in Chapter 10), and (ii) the **Tracer**, which is responsible for collecting trustworthiness evidence to be used in the context of the attestation schemes of ENTRUST. While these two components conceptually run together, here we make this distinction in order to highlight the different types of information that can be collected in ENTRUST.

In this Chapter, we consider the Tracer component, which facilitates real-time monitoring of both a device's static properties (e.g., secure boot outcomes, configuration integrity) and runtime properties (e.g., memory usage, control-flow integrity, CPU usage) according to defined trust policies. This monitoring focuses on data identified as trust sources, which are essential for runtime trust assessment. The nature of this data, which pertains to key system properties that define trust, allows the digital twin to be invoked when a change in the device's trust level is detected. Specifically, traces are transmitted to the digital twin in the event of an attestation failure, indicating a potential risk. This data is essential for the digital twin to perform real-time analytics and monitoring. The digital twin uses the tracer's data to detect anomalies and unusual patterns that could indicate malfunctions or security threats. By integrating this data, the digital twin enhances its capability to identify and react to issues promptly.

- **Threat Modeling:** The digital twin is designed to collaborate with the threat modeling components to simulate different threat scenarios and test the effectiveness of security measures in a controlled setting. These ENTRUST components provide information required in order to simulate the attacks. Insights from these simulations inform the development of more robust security strategies and system updates, enhancing the overall resilience of the connected medical systems.
- **Software Verification:** The digital twin outputs to the Software Verification component, enabling the construction of more precisely formulated fuzzing test cases. By analyzing the device's behavior and identifying potential vulnerabilities, the digital twin generates detailed insights into system weaknesses. These insights inform the Software Verification component, allowing it to create targeted fuzzing tests that effectively probe and assess the identified weak points. This collaborative process can enhance the thoroughness and effectiveness of software verification, ultimately improving the security and reliability of the system.
- **Dynamic Risk Assessment:** The digital twin receives detailed operational data from the Tracer component, which continuously monitors the actual medical devices in deployment. It is also designed to obtain data generated from controlled attack simulations within an experimental setup. This setup should support testing the system resilience under different attack scenarios, providing valuable insights into potential security vulnerabilities. The digital twin analyzes the data from both the Tracer and the experimental simulations to detect anomalies and unusual patterns that could indicate potential vulnerabilities or system malfunctions. Upon detecting anomalies and identifying

vulnerabilities, the digital twin can forward this critical information to the Risk Assessment component. This proactive information sharing enables a dynamic reassessment of risks based on current data and recent experimental outcomes and enables the calculation of RTL.

- **Threat Knowledge Sharing:** The digital twin can populate or update the content of the Threat Intelligence Database. It does not identify new vulnerabilities; instead, it establishes connections between monitored deviations and vulnerabilities per threat. This process enriches the threat intelligence database, supported by our ENTRUST Blockchain infrastructure, by providing detailed information. This comprehensive threat intelligence can then be utilized by other stakeholders to devise and implement optimal mitigation strategies.
- **Digital Twin Operator:** The ENTRUST digital twin can be operated by human entities who wish to harness the features provided by the digital twin but also oversee the simulation process. This includes leveraging the digital twin’s capabilities to obtain various artifacts that aid in visualizing the flow of data, access information regarding anomaly detection, but also maintain the properties and network topology of the monitored assets.

9.2.2 Conceptual Architecture of the ENTRUST Digital Twinning

Figure 9.1 outlines the high-level architecture of the ENTRUST Digital Twin, a sophisticated system designed to integrate and analyze data from connected medical devices within the medical computing continuum. This architecture is constructed upon a robust digital twin model that utilizes a suite of Docker-installed services to process, store, and visualize data, enabling proactive monitoring and management of medical IoT systems.

The blue section of the figure, designated as the "Experimental Setup," represents a controlled environment where the example system is isolated, or 'sandboxed,' to monitor various system properties. Within this setup, the IoT Gateway (high-end device) plays a pivotal role. It is equipped with two elements: the Telegraf Agent, which employs multiple input plugins to capture data concerning system performance metrics, and a MQTT Broker, a communication medium which enables the monitoring of the messages which are published by actual or emulated medical devices to the gateway. The digital twin ingests data collected by the Telegraf Agent through specialized output plugins, which forward the metrics through HTTP requests to the InfluxDB database. In fact, all database components pertaining to the digital twin are accessible through APIs, allowing other ENTRUST components or external entities to populate and interact with the collected data. This sandbox environment is instrumental in evaluating the performance and security of the system under controlled conditions. Simulating different operational scenarios and potential threat models allows for detailed observation and analysis of how system modifications or updates impact device functionality and security. The data collected through the Telegraf plugins is critical as it provides a continuous stream of performance metrics transmitted to the InfluxDB within the Digital Twin. This setup helps in refining the operational efficiency of the system and ensures that any potential vulnerabilities can be identified and mitigated before deployment in a real-world setting.

Once the data is transmitted into the digital twin environment, it undergoes rigorous processing and analysis facilitated by a suite of interconnected services: first by being stored in InfluxDB, which manages time-series data, and later by a sophisticated modeling service that utilizes this data to analyze system behaviors, enhancing the predictive capabilities of the digital twin. The resulting model outputs are then stored and can be visualized in Neo4j, a graph database optimized for handling complex data relationships. Visualizing these outputs is accomplished using NeoDash, which offers an interactive interface for user interaction and engagement. Additionally, MinIO provides robust data lake functionalities and the necessary means to store object files such as larger datasets, metadata, and configuration files

Figure 9.1: High-level Architecture of the ENTRUST Digital Twin. This diagram focuses on illustrating the main subcomponents of the digital twin for clarity and better understanding. It does not depict the connections with other ENTRUST components, which are detailed in the comprehensive architecture diagram in Figure 9.2.

used in setting up the experimental grounds. This cohesive and integrated methodology is strategically engineered to enhance the security and reliability of connected medical devices, enabling continuous monitoring and facilitating predictive maintenance to preempt potential issues.

The Telegraf Agent utilizes various input plugins (memory, disk, system, CPU, processes, network, MQTT topic subscriptions, and more) to collect data from and through the IoT gateway. These data are not primarily intended for trust assessment; they primarily focus on performance metrics for evaluation. However, certain metrics, such as memory and CPU usage, can also be utilized to inform trust decisions, as they may indicate events like an unauthorized software update. This data is sent via HTTP to the InfluxDB database in the Digital Twin.

MQTT Broker manages messaging between IoT devices and the gateway. This allows for efficient, real-time data transmission and management. A prerequisite to data streaming is the creation of topics, as real-time streaming events are stored in these topics. A Telegraf Agent input plugin is then used to

monitor these message streams.

InfluxDB receives and stores time-series data from the Telegraf Agent. It serves as the primary database for analytics and storage. InfluxDB offers high query performance and integrated data visualization tools. Other features are allowing the selection of event points within a specified time range and the possibility of adjusting data retention policies for memory-efficient storage.

MinIO serves as the storage solution for object files used in modeling asset topology and threat simulations within the digital twin framework. It also functions as a data lake, managing historical datasets essential for modeling and analysis. As an open-source, Kubernetes-native object database, MinIO is renowned for its high performance and scalability. Its S3 compatibility enables seamless migration to AWS S3 applications, which motivates its use in the project. MinIO stores binary large objects (BLOBs), each comprising an ID, data, and metadata, within containers known as buckets. These buckets, which can be organized using prefixes similar to directories, are essential for managing storage volumes. Each network element or asset is mapped to its respective bucket via its ID. Additionally, MinIO offers the MinIO Console, a tool that facilitates S3 operations and administrative tasks, enhancing the overall management capabilities within the digital twin framework.

Neo4j is a graph data storage platform used to create, store, and visualize the underlying knowledge graph that reflects the network topology. Other data, such as model outputs, can also be included as additional properties of nodes. Operators use Cypher queries to populate and interact with this database by quickly querying data points (i.e., nodes) and connections (i.e., relations). Neo4J data can be retrieved or inserted through RESTful API and the developer interface browser. Neo4J is known and utilized due to its scalability, availability, and cost reduction due to its distributed cluster architecture and query-processing enhancements.

NeoDash represents the dashboard tool that pulls data from Neo4j to visualize and present insights, allowing users to interact with the digital twin data and outcomes effectively. NeoDash supports the creation of several collections of reports, also called pages. A report is defined as the smallest building unit in NeoDash and builds around a Cypher query. This makes it possible to visually represent the query data in a more structured way and lets the user gain insightful information about the data at hand by customizing the dashboard to specific needs.

User Interaction: The user interacts with the Digital Twin primarily through NeoDash for visualization and updates. This interaction enables the user to receive insights from the digital twin and make informed decisions or adjustments.

Data Flow: Data is initially captured from the experimental setup by the input plugins adhering to the Telegraf Agent, including the monitored MQTT subscriptions. This agent processes the data, subsequently forwarding it to InfluxDB, a specialized time-series database adept at handling high-frequency data inputs and queries. From InfluxDB, the data may be archived in MinIO, an object storage solution for larger datasets, or employed directly by analytical models to produce actionable outputs. These outputs are then stored in Neo4j, a graph database that excels in managing and visualizing complex relationships between data entities. Insights derived from these outputs are finally visualized through NeoDash, providing an intuitive graphical interface for user interaction and data interpretation.

Overall Functionality: This high-level architecture integrates multiple Docker-installed components that work together to facilitate the data flow from the experimental setup through the gateway, processed and modeled within the digital twin, and ultimately visualized for user interaction. It highlights a robust setup designed for scalability, real-time data handling, and complex data interactions.

9.2.3 Detailed Architectural Model & Internal Building Blocks

Figure 9.2 depicts the detailed architecture diagram of the ENTRUST Digital Twin. This diagram offers a systematic illustration of the interplay among various components within the digital twin framework and their interactions with other elements of the ENTRUST ecosystem.

The operator in the ENTRUST Digital Twin architecture is a human role that oversees the operation and effectiveness of the digital twin system. This role involves interacting with and managing various components within the digital twin to ensure that it accurately reflects the connected medical devices it represents and operates efficiently and securely. The operator interprets the analysis results produced by the digital twin. This role is vital for translating complex data and model outputs into actionable insights and strategic decisions for the enforcement of appropriate mitigation strategies. The operator role can be taken by other ENTRUST roles, e.g. the Security Administrator that manages the Risk Assessment process, who also makes informed decisions regarding the operation and management of the connected medical devices. These decisions could involve adjusting operational parameters, deploying preventative maintenance strategies, or initiating responses to emerging threats. Part of the security administrator's role in interpreting analysis results involves assessing potential risks identified by the digital twin. The operator evaluates these risks in the context of their impact on system operation and patient safety and develops strategies to mitigate them.

The WebUI is the primary interface for human operators. It is represented by a dashboard where connected medical devices are digitally represented, allowing users to view and manage the state of these devices easily. Within the dashboard, the operator can inspect individual devices to view properties and current state, or examine the network of devices to gain insights into their collective behavior. It is designed to integrate seamlessly with other components of the digital twin system, and can display information from external components. This integration facilitates data exchange and coordination across different platforms, enhancing the overall functionality.

Knowledge Graph (Container: Neo4j) stores the knowledge graph which represents assets and relationships in a graphical format, making it easier to perform complex queries and modify or analyze relationships between different entities and their attributes within the system. These assets and relationships for the knowledge graph can be obtained from the trust policies in the TAF.

Time-Series Database (Container: InfluxDB) is responsible for storing time-series data such as device metrics and operational parameters. This database is optimized for high write and query speeds which are essential for handling real-time data streaming from medical devices.

Object Database (Container: Minio) acts as an object storage solution where larger datasets, such as logs and binary files, are stored. Additionally, one may also store data regarding threat modeling and simulation and other configuration files. Minio provides scalable and efficient storage for various types of data that do not fit the typical relational database model.

API Layer (Component: Flask, HTTP) facilitates communication between different software components and external systems through well-defined HTTP APIs. This layer is crucial for integrating the digital twin with other healthcare IT systems and for allowing external applications or components to access data and functionalities.

Attack Simulator The digital twin includes an attack simulator module which takes in attack data and information about targeted devices from other ENTRUST components, emulates the devices in a virtual environment and runs attacks in order to identify additional vulnerabilities.

Analysis Models (Container: Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning) utilize advanced AI/ML algorithms to analyze the data collected and detect anomalies. Models may also use monitored data and

Figure 9.2: Detailed Architecture of the ENTRUST Digital Twin. The digital twin is a pictured as a central component, interfaced with multiple external components through the API layer. Requests to and from the digital twin are represented by incoming and outgoing arrows, respectively.

configuration files to predict potential failures. These models can also learn from new data to continuously improve their accuracy and effectiveness. Our anomaly detection method is one analysis model we utilize in the context of the ENTRUST digital twin infrastructure (see Section 9.3).

Introspection Agent (Component: Telegraf) monitors additional device properties through various plugins, enhancing the capability of the digital twin to provide real-time monitoring and predictive maintenance.

Attestation Agent is the external ENTRUST component (not part of the ENTRUST digital twin) that tracks and monitors operational data from devices during runtime, assessing their performance and reliability. This component is essential for ensuring that devices are functioning during runtime as expected and for identifying any deviations that might indicate a security or operational issue.

Subfleet Controller An ENTRUST component (not part of the digital twin) running on the Domain Manager and enabling the interaction with the Secure Software Update Engine. Once received from the

engine, the digital twin sends the necessary software update commands to the controller, which further propagates the updates to the targeted devices (for more details, see Section 10).

Software Assignment Engine Represents a functional building block of the Secure Software Update ENTRUST component (not part of the digital twin). The digital twin provides information about the digitally represented devices which are then used by the assignment engine to create a mapping between devices and their respective software updates. This assignment is forwarded to the digital twin (for more details, see Section 10).

Threat Intelligence Database is an external ENTRUST database (not part of the digital twin) that stores information about potential threats and is used to enhance security measures. It processes outputs from the digital twin to continually update the threat landscape and responses, expanding the threat knowledge of manufacturers and other relevant entities.

Blockchain Infrastructure External, off-chain storage component to the Trust Assessment Framework. Through interaction with this component, the digital twin is able to retrieve trust relationships, used in determining the array of related assets that are to be assessed or closely examined.

System Administrator External ENTRUST entity providing additional domain-specific threat and attack information at pre-deployment time.

Threat Modeling An external ENTRUST component responsible for collecting device-specific vulnerability information and using this to generate attack data which can be used by the digital twin attack emulation modules. If found, additional vulnerabilities identified within the digital twin are forwarded to the threat modeling component in order to update the threat and vulnerability landscape for the devices (for more details, see Section 4).

Risk Assessment An interacting external ENTRUST component (not part of the digital twin) performing various risk assessment related tasks, such as risk calculation based on risk indicators. Relevant information can be acquired from various sources, including the digital twin (for more details, see Section 5).

Software Verification External ENTRUST component entrusted with assessing the safety of software and libraries running on the medical devices by malware scanning and fuzz testing. After scanning and testing, verification results are sent to the digital twin (for more details, see Section 4).

Domain Manager ENTRUST external server tasked with managing the authentication, enrollment and onboarding processes of medical devices into the domain. Once a device is enrolled at pre-deployment time, the domain manager can trigger a topology update inside the digital twin.

In the sandbox environment, **the Pool of Emulated Critical Medical Devices** is used to test and validate the digital twin's functionalities. This setup supports the simulation of various scenarios, including potential failures, attack vectors, and operational inefficiencies, without risking the integrity or functionality of the actual medical devices. It provides a safe environment where we can test software updates, security patches, and system configurations thoroughly before being applied to the live system.

The Pool of Critical Medical Devices in the real system deployment is continuously monitored via **Attestation Agent** for performance and security. For instance, if $ATL < RTL$, the Device Data and Execution Tracer component sends the system traces to the ENTRUST digital twin for anomaly detection. The **Analysis Model** component of the digital twin runs the ML technique to detect any anomalies in the system traces.

There is a continuous feedback loop between the sandbox and the real system. Insights gained from the real system's data analysis can lead to refinements in the digital twin model within the sandbox.

Conversely, improvements and updates tested in the sandbox are rolled out to enhance the real system’s functionality and security.

9.2.3.1 Interfaces

Figure 9.3 illustrates the API layer of the ENTRUST Digital Twin, detailing how both external and internal components within the digital twin infrastructure communicate through the API layer via API calls.

Figure 9.3: Digital Twin API layer showing API calls from external and internal components to the databases provided by the digital twin. We also depict API calls triggered by the nodes in the knowledge graph.

The API layer consists of specific APIs that connect the frontend components with the backend databases. Each API is responsible for fetching or sending data to its respective database:

- **InfluxDB API** ("influxdb_api.py" on "localhost:5000") handles data interactions with the InfluxDB, which stores time-series data from various sensors and devices.
- **MinIO API** ("minio_api.py" on "localhost:5002") manages requests to MinIO, an object storage database for handling larger datasets that might include logs, images, or other binary data.
- **Neo4j API** ("neo4j_api.py" on "localhost:5001") interfaces with Neo4j, a graph database that manages complex relationships between data points stored within the digital twin.

External Components are not explicitly shown in this diagram but typically include other systems or platforms (**Risk Assessment, Threat Modeling, etc.**) that interact with the digital twin via the API layer.

Figure 9.3 shows various API calls (indicated by arrows) between the components. These calls allow data to flow between frontend components and the backend through the APIs:

- Calls from the nodes to each API indicate data being sent or queried from the respective databases.
- The nature of calls (GET, POST, etc.) might differ based on the operation, such as retrieving data, updating records, or inserting new data.

Our architecture facilitates a modular and scalable approach to managing a digital twin’s data interactions. By separating data handling into distinct APIs and databases, the system can efficiently manage different types of data flows — from real-time analytics to large-scale data storage — while maintaining robust security and performance. This setup is crucial for ensuring that the digital twin can process and analyze data effectively. Note that the array of nodes presented (i.e., Platform, Device, Gateway, TelegrafDS) reflects the current state of implementation but may change due to an increase in granularity in future development.

ENTRUST Component	Interface Needed	Type of Information Exchanged
Threat Modelling	API Interface	Updated attack data necessary for emulation
Threat Intelligence Database	Database Connection	Threat intelligence data
Risk Assessment	API Interface	Information necessary to quantify risk
Domain Manager	API Interface / Server Communication	Information on device enrollments
Software Assignment Engine	API Interface	Information on the assignment and management of software updates
Software Verification	API Interface	Software Verification information as resulting from testing and scanning binaries
Blockchain Infrastructure	Database Connection	Information about targeted devices as trust relationships.
Subfleet Controller	API Interface	Commands for performing software updates on devices
Introspection Agent	HTTP request	Monitor data, as collected by various Telegraf plugins
Attestation Agent	API Interface	Collected traces

Table 9.1: Interfaces needed between the digital twin and other ENTRUST components in Figure 9.2, highlighting the type of information exchanged.

Table 9.1 summarizes the necessary interfaces between the ENTRUST digital twin and other ENTRUST components, detailing the type of information exchanged. For example, the digital twin interacts with the Threat Modeling component via an API interface to receive updated attack data necessary for emulation.

It connects to the Threat Intelligence Database through a database connection to access comprehensive threat intelligence data. An API interface links the digital twin to the Risk Assessment component, which provides calculation results of IRL and RTL based on current threat knowledge. Communication with the Domain Manager is facilitated by an API interface and server communication to coordinate device operations and mediate data. The digital twin interfaces with the Software Assignment Engine through an API interface to manage and assign software updates effectively. Other components interact in a similar manner. These interfaces ensure seamless data flow and integration, enhancing the monitoring, assessment, and security of connected medical devices within the ENTRUST framework.

9.2.4 Digital Twin Components

9.2.4.1 Embedded Introspection Agent

The Telegraf Agent plays a critical role in seamlessly collecting and transmitting data from medical devices to the digital twin framework. Telegraf is an open-source server agent designed for collecting metrics and data from various sources, processing them, and writing them into several storage mediums, e.g., InfluxDB of our digital twin setup. Key functions and features of the Telegraf agent are the following:

- **Data Collection:** Telegraf is equipped with a wide range of input plugins that enable it to gather metrics from a diverse array of sources. In the context of the ENTRUST Digital Twin, these sources primarily include the IoT ecosystem, such as the connected medical devices and the network elements connecting these. The data collected can vary broadly from operational metrics like memory usage, disk space, and CPU load to more specific health-monitoring data such as device status, environmental conditions, and usage statistics.
- **Real-Time Processing:** Once data is collected, the Telegraf Agent processes it in real-time. This processing may involve aggregating, filtering, or transforming data to ensure its optimization for further analysis. The real-time processing capability is crucial for maintaining up-to-date system analytics and enabling immediate response to detected anomalies or emerging issues.
- **Modular and Extensible:** One of the strengths of Telegraf is its modularity and extensibility. It supports a plug-and-play architecture where new plugins (both input and output) can be easily added. This flexibility allows the Telegraf Agent within the ENTRUST architecture to be adapted and scaled according to evolving needs and technological advancements in medical IoT.
- **Data Transmission:** After processing the data, Telegraf sends it to InfluxDB via HTTP. This transmission is secure and efficient, ensuring that data integrity and confidentiality are maintained, which is paramount in medical applications. The use of HTTP for data transmission simplifies integration with web-based technologies and services, enhancing the interoperability of the digital twin environment.
- **Scalability and Efficiency:** Telegraf is designed to handle vast amounts of data without significant resource consumption, making it highly scalable and efficient. This is particularly important in medical IoT settings where the number of devices and the volume of data can grow exponentially.
- **Configuration and Maintenance:** Telegraf offers easy configuration and maintenance, which is vital for ensuring that the digital twin remains robust and responsive over time. Administrators can configure Telegraf to meet specific data collection requirements and can maintain its operation with minimal downtime, ensuring continuous data flow to the digital twin.

The Telegraf Agent is a fundamental component in the ENTRUST Digital Twin architecture, tasked with the critical functions of data collection, real-time processing, and secure transmission, all of which are essential for the dynamic and responsive monitoring of connected medical devices.

Agent Plugins: As detailed above, Telegraf utilizes plugin-driven agents to collect metrics not only from the device on which it is installed but also from connected IoT devices and other network equipment. This feature is achieved by listening to the message queue and verifying availability through specialized plugins. Table 9.2 lists the Telegraf input plugins relevant for monitoring the behavior and properties of the installed device. Table 9.3 enumerates the plugins used for monitoring connected IoT elements, such as critical medical devices. It is important to note that these lists are suggestive and may vary in length based on the experimental setup, deprecated features, and specific contextual requirements.

Plugin Name	Description	Fields
mem	System memory usage	active, available, available_percent, buffered, cached, commit_limit, committed_as, dirty, free, high_free, high_total, huge_pages_free, huge_page_size, huge_pages_total, inactive, laundry, low_free, low_total, mapped, page_tables, shared, slab, sreclaimable, sunreclaim, swap_cached, swap_free, swap_total, total, used, used_percent, vmalloc_chunk, vmalloc_total, vmalloc_used, wired, write_back, write_back_tmp
disk	Disk usage metrics	free, total, used, used_percent, inodes_free, inodes_total, inodes_used, inodes_used_percent
diskio	Disk traffic and timing	reads, writes, read_bytes, write_bytes, read_time, write_time, io_time, weighted_io_time, iops_in_progress, merged_reads, merged_writes
system	System metrics	load1, load15, load5, n_users, n_unique_users, n_cpus, uptime, uptime_format
cpu	System CPU metrics	time_user, time_system, time_idle, time_active, time_nice, time_iowait, time_irq, time_softirq, time_steal, time_guest, time_guest_nice, usage_user, usage_system, usage_idle, usage_active, usage_nice, usage_iowait, usage_irq, usage_softirq, usage_steal, usage_guest, usage_guest_nice
processes	Number of processes and status	blocked, running, sleeping, stopped, total, zombie, dead, wait, idle, paging, parked, total_threads
kernel	Kernel and pressure stall	boot_time, context_switches, disk_pages_in, disk_pages_out, interrupts, processes_forked, entropy_avail, ksm_full_scans, ksm_max_page_sharing, ksm_merge_across_nodes, ksm_pages_shared, ksm_pages_sharing, ksm_pages_to_scan, ksm_pages_unshared, ksm_pages_volatile, ksm_run, ksm_sleep_millisecs, ksm_stable_node_chains, ksm_stable_node_chains_prune_millisecs, ksm_stable_node_dups, ksm_use_zero_pages
exec	Executes custom scripts	Custom script output
swap	Swap memory	free, total, used, used_percent, in, out
temp	System temperature	temp
filecount	Number and size of files in directories	count, size_bytes, oldest_file_timestamp, newest_file_timestamp
linux_cpu	CPU metrics exposed on Linux systems	scaling_cur_freq, scaling_min_freq, scaling_max_freq, cpuinfo_cur_freq, cpuinfo_min_freq, cpuinfo_max_freq, throttle_count, throttle_max_time, throttle_total_time
net	Network interface and protocol usage	bytes_sent, bytes_recv, packets_sent, packets_recv, err_in, err_out, drop_in, drop_out, speed
net_response	Test UDP/TCP connections response time	response_time, result_code
sensors	Collects sensor data	Depends on sensor availability

Table 9.2: Overview of agent plugins for monitoring device hosting Telegraf.

Plugin Name	Description	Fields
mqtt_consumer	Consume messages published to list of topics	Messages per topic
http_response	HTTP/HTTPS requests for checking connections	response_time, content_length, response_string_match, response_status_code_match, http_response_code, result_type, result_code
exec	Executes custom scripts	Custom script output
ping	Execute ping command	packets_transmitted, packets_received, percent_packet_loss, ttl, average_response_ms, minimum_response_ms, maximum_response_ms, standard_deviation_ms, percentile<N>_ms (where N is the percentile), result_code

Table 9.3: Overview of agent plugins for monitoring devices connected to the one hosting Telegraf.

Tracer Information Comparison: The Device Data and Execution Tracer component in ENTRUST facilitates the tracking and monitoring of operational data during runtime. The metrics it collects complement those gathered by the Telegraf introspection agent, though some overlap exists. The Tracer monitors performance, security, and network aspects of the device at runtime, potentially using different methods than the Telegraf agent plugins. For instance, Telegraf can monitor process execution through the `processes` input plugin, and system information via the `CPU`, `mem`, and `exec` plugins. Disk I/O latency and size are measured by the `diskio` plugin, while the `net` and `net_response` plugins assess UDP/TCP connection usage. However, unlike Telegraf, the Tracer can differentiate between active and passive TCP connections and obtain additional information such as security capability checks, signal tracing, function calls, and power consumption. Consequently, the combined outputs of the Telegraf agent and the Tracer provide a more comprehensive view of the properties and behavior of the device.

9.2.4.2 Digital Twin Graphical Dashboard

In the ENTRUST Digital Twin, **NeoDash** is a pivotal component for data visualization and user interaction. It is a dashboarding tool designed for use with the Neo4j graph database, enabling users to create informative and interactive visualizations based on the graph data stored within Neo4j. Its role within the digital twin framework is critical, as it provides an intuitive interface for end-users to monitor, analyze, and interact with complex datasets and model outputs derived from the digital twin system. Key features and functionalities of NeoDash are the following.

- **Customizable Dashboards:** NeoDash allows users to build custom dashboards tailored to specific monitoring or analytical needs. It supports a wide range of widgets and visualization options, such as graphs, charts, and tables, which can be configured to display different aspects of the data stored in Neo4j.
- **Real-Time Data Visualization:** The tool is designed to handle real-time data, enabling dynamic updates and visualizations that reflect the current state of the system. This is particularly valuable in a digital twin environment where timely data is crucial for making informed decisions.
- **Interactive Interface:** NeoDash offers an interactive user interface that enables users to drill down into specific data points, explore relationships, and retrieve detailed information on demand. This interactivity enhances user engagement and allows for deeper exploration of the data, facilitating better understanding and insights.

- **Integration with Neo4j:** Being designed specifically for Neo4j, NeoDash seamlessly integrates with the graph database, leveraging its powerful querying capabilities to fetch, display, and manipulate data efficiently. This integration ensures that users can exploit the full potential of Neo4j’s rich data relationships and complex querying features.
- **Accessibility and Ease of Use:** NeoDash is designed with a focus on usability, making it accessible to users who may not have deep technical expertise in database management or data science. This user-friendly approach democratizes data access, allowing a broader range of stakeholders to benefit from the insights offered by the digital twin.
- **Scalability and Flexibility:** The dashboarding tool is scalable and flexible, capable of handling large datasets and complex visualizations without significant performance degradation. This scalability is crucial where data volumes and system complexity can grow rapidly.

Role in the Digital Twin Architecture: In the ENTRUST Digital Twin system, NeoDash acts as the visual front end that presents processed data, analytics results, and model simulations in a clear and actionable format. By providing powerful visualization capabilities, it aids users in understanding complex data patterns, detecting anomalies, and assessing the effectiveness of potential interventions. The tool’s ability to present sophisticated graph-based data in an intuitive manner makes it an indispensable part of the digital twin environment, bridging the gap between complex data management technologies and practical, actionable user interfaces.

Figure 9.4: Preliminary Digital Twin Dashboard version.

Figure 9.4 presents the preliminary digital twin dashboard designed for monitoring and analyzing data from the experimental setup for the eHealth platform of Tellu, called "TelluCare eHealth." The dashboard is organized into three distinct sections: Graph Overview, Telegraf Data Selection (DS) panel, and Console and Data Output.

- **Graph Overview Section:** The left part of the dashboard displays a graphical overview showing the relationships between different nodes in the network. It prominently features one Platform node called "TelluCare eHealth," multiple "Gateway" nodes that connect to the Platform, and one "TelegrafDS" node per Gateway, which are nodes managing data collected by Telegraf in InfluxDB. The nodes are interconnected by relations, illustrating the flow of data or the network topology. This is an example of an underlying knowledge graph showcasing a simple star topology.
- **Telegraf Data Selection Panel:** The "Telegraf Data Selection" section on the right side allows users to specify which data (i.e., plugins) to monitor. This section includes options to select Gateway properties such as Execution Time, Temperature, and Memory, as well as Device Properties like Ping. Users can define a specific time frame for data analysis by entering start and end dates and times, enabling flexibility in analyzing historical data or monitoring data in real-time. For testing purposes, the list of plugins is kept concise. In the rightmost part of the dashboard, selected data is logged into the console for inspection. The console displays structured, time-stamped entries for temperature data ("temp") recorded by the Telegraf agent within the specified time frame. Each entry includes a field name, measurement type, time stamp, and actual value, providing detailed insights into the monitored data.

9.2.4.3 Time-series Data Collection

In the architecture of the ENTRUST Digital Twin, **InfluxDB** is utilized to manage time-series data sourced from the experimental setup, ensuring efficient storage and retrieval of temporal metrics. Concurrently, data obtained from the Tracer component is securely stored within the ENTRUST Blockchain infrastructure, providing a tamper-proof record of device activities. The digital twin can access and leverage this blockchain-stored data either through its integrated databases or bypass them and directly access the blockchain data. This synergy between InfluxDB and the blockchain ensures robust data management and enhances the digital twin's ability to monitor and assess the performance and security of connected medical devices. Time-series data, characterized by its sequential time-stamped entries, is particularly prevalent in systems monitoring real-time operational parameters from medical devices. InfluxDB's role is to capture, store, and ensure the rapid retrieval of this data, supporting both real-time analysis and historical data queries necessary for comprehensive system monitoring and anomaly detection. Key features and functionalities of InfluxDB in the ENTRUST digital twin are the following:

- **High Performance:** InfluxDB is optimized for high write and query speeds, which are essential for handling large volumes of data generated continuously by numerous devices. This capability is crucial for maintaining real-time responsiveness in the digital twin environment.
- **Scalability:** Designed for scalability, InfluxDB can accommodate the increasing influx of data as more devices are connected within the healthcare system. Its architecture supports horizontal scalability, which is effective for expanding data volume management without a loss in performance.
- **Data Integrity and Precision:** Each piece of data stored in InfluxDB includes a precise timestamp. This precision is vital for accurate monitoring and analysis, ensuring that data from various sources can be synchronized and analyzed coherently.
- **Powerful Query Language:** InfluxDB utilizes InfluxQL, a query language that allows for complex queries across time-stamped data. This feature is particularly useful for generating specific insights needed for system optimization and anomaly detection.
- **Real-Time Analysis:** InfluxDB supports continuous queries to process data in real time as it streams into the database. This feature allows for setting up real-time alerts based on specific data patterns or thresholds, enabling proactive system management.

- **Data Downsampling:** InfluxDB supports implementing data retention policies, which are crucial for managing how long data is stored and when it is archived or deleted. Downsampling data—reducing the resolution of older data while preserving its overall trends—is also supported to optimize storage efficiency.
- **Integration Capabilities:** InfluxDB can be seamlessly integrated into the digital twin architecture through its RESTful API and client libraries available in multiple programming languages. This integration facilitates data exchange between InfluxDB and other components of the digital twin system, such as analysis models and visualization tools.

Role in the Digital Twin Architecture: In the ENTRUST Digital Twin, InfluxDB acts as the backbone for all time-series data analytics. It stores operational data from medical devices, which can be used to perform real-time analytics, simulate potential system changes, and detect anomalies. The data stored in InfluxDB provides a historical record that can be invaluable for long-term system analysis.

Figure 9.5: View of InfluxDB database content for one field of the memory property of device.

Figure 9.5 shows a user interface from InfluxDB’s Data Explorer, a tool used for visualizing and querying time-series data stored within the InfluxDB database. It displays a graphical view and the query setup for monitoring the memory property of a device. The main part of the graphical display shows a line graph, which tracks “free” memory over time for a particular device. The graph shows a timeline from “2024-05-31 17:00:00” to “2024-05-31 17:15:00”, depicting a decrease in free memory during this period, which could indicate increasing memory usage or a potential issue if the free memory drops too low.

The query configuration area below the graph in Figure 9.5 details the setup for retrieving this data. The data originates from a designated bucket in InfluxDB, specified to measure mem focusing on the ‘free’ memory field. The dataset is filtered by host IP addresses, highlighting that multiple devices are being monitored, with the current view possibly filtered to display data from a specific host.

Additional user interface elements include options to view raw data, export the data in CSV format, and access a script editor for more advanced query customization using InfluxDB’s Flux language. The query

execution is initiated by the `Submit` button. Adjustable settings for handling data aggregation and missing values, such as window period and fill methods, are set to `Auto`, allowing the system to automatically optimize the data display and query handling.

This user interface from InfluxDB's Data Explorer is a powerful tool for monitoring and analyzing time-series data related to device performance, in this case, memory usage. It allows users to visually inspect data trends, drill down into specifics with custom queries, and export data for further analysis, which can be useful for system performance monitoring and troubleshooting.

9.2.4.4 Experimental Setup

The hardware part of the experimental setup utilizes a Raspberry Pi 400, a compact single-board computer powered by a quad-core ARM Cortex-A72 processor clocked at 1.8 GHz. The system boasts 4GB of LPDDR4-3200 DRAM, facilitating efficient data processing capabilities for sustaining the experiments. The Raspberry Pi 400 is equipped with a 32GB MicroSD card as its primary storage, running the Raspbian GNU/Linux 11 operating system. The modular nature of the Raspberry Pi 400 makes it an ideal choice for the experimental setup, reflecting the behaviour of a gateway to several medical devices or sensors, which can be connected by various means (i.e. Bluetooth, USB, GPIO, Wi-fi). The Raspberry hosts both the Telegraf agent and the message broker by running the Docker compose file of both services. The Telegraf configuration file is then modified and updated with the relevant plugins. A ZTE 4G wireless router is then used to host a network between the Raspberry Pi and the computer hosting the Digital Twin.

9.2.5 Installation

The full source code of the ENTRUST Digital Twin can be obtained from GitHub: <https://github.com/SINTEF-9012/entrust-dt>. Currently, the installation of the platform is mainly for development purposes.

9.3 Unsupervised Learning System for Anomaly Detection

In this section, we explore the development and implementation of advanced machine learning techniques designed to identify and analyze anomalies within the operational data of connected medical devices. This section delves into the specifics of the unsupervised learning algorithms that have been employed to autonomously detect unusual patterns and potential threats without the need for labeled training data. These techniques help understand and preempt irregularities that could indicate cybersecurity risks or faults in device operations. By leveraging statistical feature analysis and machine learning methodologies, this system sifts through vast datasets to highlight discrepancies that deviate from established normal behavior, providing an essential layer of intelligence and security to the ENTRUST Digital Twin infrastructure.

The unsupervised learning technique employed for anomaly detection represents a critical instance of the analysis model component within the digital twin architecture (see Figures 9.1 and 9.2). Leveraging vast amounts of unlabelled operational data, these models analyze and learn from the system's inherent patterns to identify deviations that could signal potential issues or threats. In the following subsections, we detail how this component of the digital twin architecture enhances its capability to autonomously monitor

and secure connected medical devices, providing crucial insights into system health and preempting possible malfunctions or security breaches.

Deep learning methods (e.g., LSTM, CNN, autoencoders) have been used in anomaly detection (with a focus on residual error-based detection) [52]. While they are effective at anomaly detection, we did not implement these methods in our current framework due to constraints in computational resources and the complexity of model training and interpretation. Instead, our **approach leverages more traditional machine learning techniques that are computationally less intensive while not requiring massive amounts of labeled training data and offer greater transparency in terms of feature importance and decision-making processes. These unsupervised techniques are highly efficient, though they do impose certain limitations on the scope of analysis due to the constraints of a virtualized environment, despite the ample resources available. Nonetheless, this serves as a proof of concept that can be readily expanded with additional algorithms in the future.** This decision of employing an unsupervised learning technique aligns with our need for real-time processing and the requirement for not using huge amounts of labeled data, where the ability to rapidly adapt and respond to new and evolving threats without extensive retraining is paramount.

The output of anomaly detection as part of the ENTRUST digital twin framework can serve as an additional trust source in the context of the ENTRUST use cases, such as the TELLU case. In the TELLU system, clients (patients) use connected medical devices to continuously monitor vital signs such as heart rate and blood pressure. These devices transmit data to a central system where healthcare providers can monitor patient health in real-time.

Anomaly Detection as an Additional Trust Source: The digital twin of the TELLU system obtains measurements of the performance and behavior of these connected medical devices. By applying the anomaly detection technique, we can identify unusual patterns and deviations that may not be captured by traditional attestation methods.

TELLU Example: You imagine a scenario where a patient's heart rate monitor, typically operating within a specific range of CPU and memory usage, suddenly exhibits a spike in CPU usage and an increase in memory consumption. This anomaly could indicate several potential issues, such as:

- A malfunction in the device firmware causing it to run unnecessary processes.
- Unauthorized software running on the device, potentially indicating a security breach.
- Network latency issues affecting the device's data transmission efficiency.

How Anomaly Detection Provides Additional Trust: For each potential issue, the anomaly detection may give different diagnosis or warnings for further checks.

- **Early Detection of Malfunctions:** The anomaly detection system flags the unusual CPU and memory usage. This early warning allows healthcare providers to investigate the device before it completely fails, ensuring continuous patient monitoring and safety.
- **Security Breach Identification:** Traditional attestation methods might not detect unauthorized software if it does not alter the device's integrity measurements. However, the anomaly detection system can identify unusual behavior patterns, prompting further security checks and mitigating potential data breaches. These further security checks could involve checking correlations between CPU usage, memory usage, and other measurements to detect potential security issues. Some example checks are CPU usage and network traffic (to detect unauthorized data exfiltration or DDoS

attacks), memory usage and Disk I/O operations (to identify potential malware activity or memory leaks), CPU usage and process execution (to detect unauthorized processes or resource hogging), and power consumption and device temperature readings (to detect excessive computational load).

- **Network Issue Identification:** The system could identify patterns correlating device performance with network latency, providing insights that attestation enablers focused on device integrity alone would miss. This helps in diagnosing and rectifying network issues to ensure reliable data transmission.

As described in potential scenarios for the TELLU system, the anomaly detection output has the potential to be an additional trust source, while providing valuable evidence that complements traditional attestation methods.

Figure 9.6: Overview of the unsupervised learning pipeline for anomaly detection.

9.3.1 Overview of the Approach

Figure 9.6 provides a schematic overview of the unsupervised learning pipeline used for anomaly detection. This pipeline is divided into three main stages (i.e., *data preprocessing*, *unsupervised learning of clusters*, and *labeling and validating new data*), each critical for processing and analyzing data to identify potential anomalies effectively.

Step 1 (Data preprocessing) involves preparing the training data for analysis. The data is first divided into subsequences, which helps manage and analyze the data in smaller, more manageable batches. Statistical features are extracted from the subsequences. Each feature vector represents a subsequence. The training dataset should ideally consist of data from normal execution of the system without any

anomalies because it serves as the baseline for comparison with data coming from system execution under potential anomalous conditions.

Step 2 (Training the model) is the core of this pipeline, where the unsupervised learning model is trained with the vectorized data. Unsupervised learning algorithms are used here because they do not require labeled input data to learn patterns or detect outliers. These algorithms can identify patterns and statistical anomalies in data based on the input vectors. The extracted feature vectors undergo a sophisticated cluster analysis. Each vector is assigned to a specific cluster or category. The output model is composed of multiple cluster centers, effectively categorizing the data into distinct groups that represent the underlying patterns or behaviors observed in the dataset. This structured approach facilitates the identification and analysis of similar data points, enhancing the model's utility in predictive and analytical applications.

The pipeline has a semi-supervised learning mode. It optionally takes manual labels created by annotating a small set of training data, i.e., assigning labels to periods/regions of the data. It computes feature vectors from the manual labels and calculates cluster centers corresponding to each unique label. We use the cluster centers as initial centers when running the clustering algorithm in Step 2.

Upon completion of training and validation, the model proceeds to evaluate the feature vectors in **Step 3 (Labeling and validating new data)**, where its capacity for generalization and anomaly detection is assessed. During this phase, each data subsequence is labeled according to the cluster it has been allocated to within the model. The pipeline then quantitatively assesses the deviation of each feature vector by calculating a metric that indicates the distance of the vector from the cluster centers in the feature space. This metric is crucial for determining the degree to which each vector conforms to or diverges from the established norms of the existing clusters, thereby facilitating the effective identification of anomalies.

The final output of this pipeline is new data that has been processed through the model, with anomalies identified and labeled. This labeled data is crucial for monitoring and maintaining the health of the system being analyzed, allowing for proactive measures to be taken in response to detected anomalies.

This unsupervised learning pipeline is a systematic approach that transforms raw data into actionable insights by detecting anomalies without the need for labeled training datasets. It is particularly useful in environments where obtaining labeled data is costly or impractical, such as monitoring complex connected systems or when dealing with new types of data or conditions not previously encountered. Below, we explain each step of the pipeline in detail.

9.3.2 Data preprocessing (Step 1)

Raw time series data inherently contains relationships between consecutive data points, but clustering extensive time series is computationally intensive. To mitigate this, we utilize feature extraction on subsequences derived using the sliding window technique [39, 17], effectively reducing the temporal dimension. This process generates feature vectors from each subsequence, capturing critical information from the time series, thereby simplifying the data for more efficient analysis and clustering.

Feature Name	Mathematical Definition
Mean	$\mu = \frac{1}{w} (\sum_{i=1}^w x_i)$
Range	$r = \max(x) - \min(x)$
Gradient	$\nabla x = \frac{x_{i+1} - x_{i-1}}{2d}$
Variance	$v = \frac{1}{w} \sum_{i=1}^w (x_i - \mu)^2$
Frequency strength	$\nu = \text{DFT}(w) _2$

Related quantities	Symbol
Rolling window size	w
Time step between each data point	d

Table 9.4: List of engineered features in the pipeline.

Following the extraction of subsequences, feature vectors are generated by aggregating summary statistics. The pipeline utilizes six fundamental features that provide essential insights into the characteristics of these subsequences. These include measures of central tendency (mean and median), gradient indicating change, variance showing data spread, range detailing the span between the minimum and maximum values, and frequency strength representing the magnitude of frequency components. Table 9.4 details the calculations for these features. The frequency strength is calculated using the L2-norm of the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), and the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) is used to obtain the frequency domain representation, with the magnitude of each frequency component determined by the Euclidean norm.

In the clustering process, each feature is scaled in order to be assigned equal weight during clustering. This ensures uniform contribution from all features, facilitating a balanced and methodologically sound clustering analysis. We use the following equation to scale the features:

$$f = \frac{f' - \mu}{\sigma}, \tag{9.1}$$

where μ and σ are the mean and standard deviation of the feature f' before scaling and f is the scaled feature.

In this step of the pipeline, we can integrate annotated data as supplementary input, where annotations represent labels for specific segments of the time series. We generate feature vectors from this labeled data, assigning corresponding labels to all vectors. This method allows for calculating average feature vectors for each label, which then serve as initial cluster centers in constructing the model in Step 2.

9.3.3 Unsupervised learning of clusters (Step 2)

During the model creation step (training the model), the pipeline employs unsupervised clustering algorithms to categorize feature vectors into clusters, thereby uncovering latent patterns within the pre-processed time series data. This step is pivotal for detecting anomalies and deviations in new data utilizing the model. To enhance adaptability, our system supports a range of clustering algorithms available from Scikit-learn [67] in Python, providing versatile options to best fit the analysis needs.

The selection of a clustering algorithm is critical for the efficacy of this step and involves evaluating factors such as high-dimensional data compatibility, cluster diversity, noise resilience, and resource availability. Various algorithms like K-Means [53, 70], mini-batch K-means [68], DBSCAN [30], OPTICS [14], Affinity Propagation [38], and Mean Shift [40, 16] each present distinct advantages and limitations. The choice of algorithm depends on the specific attributes of the dataset, the complexities of the industrial process, and the computational resources at hand. For example, K-Means is appropriate for scenarios with a predefined number of clusters, whereas Mean Shift, DBSCAN, OPTICS, or Affinity Propagation are better suited for scenarios where cluster counts are determined based on the data itself, ensuring alignment with specific manufacturing data requirements and attributes.

Figure 9.7: Sample clusters identified by the unsupervised learning pipeline within a 2D feature space. Individual observations (or feature vectors) within the data set are depicted as colored dots, with distinct colors (red, orange, blue, and green) signifying four different clusters as per the model. The diamond markers signify the centers of the clusters. The annotations provide a step-by-step explanation of the calculation of the deviation metric D_l for a particular feature vector, F_l , which is illustrated as a black dot.

Figure 9.7 demonstrates the clustering process on data points, simplifying the visualization by using only two features from the multidimensional data space for clarity. This allows the clusters to be observed within a two-dimensional context. The plot uses color-coding to show how observations are grouped, with data points from the same cluster share the same color. Additionally, diamond-shaped markers distinctly indicate the cluster centers of the four identified clusters in the dataset.

9.3.4 Labeling and validating new data (Step 3)

The cluster model, produced in Step 2, is crucial for inference tasks, where it categorizes and assesses new, unlabeled data from connected medical devices (either in the experimental setup through Telegraf plugins or in the deployed system during runtime through the tracer component). This model applies the same data preprocessing methods used on the training data to new data, ensuring consistency and enhancing model performance. The model assigns appropriate cluster labels to each feature vector derived from the new data. Figure 9.8 illustrates this process: a multicolored line represents time-dependent sensor data, with color shifts indicating transitions between clusters. The assigned labels are then plotted onto the corresponding subsequences within the timeline.

The training data serves as a benchmark, representing the expected behavior of connected medical devices. To calculate the deviation metric, we compute the Euclidean distance between each feature vector in the new data and each cluster center within a multidimensional feature space. This calculation enables us to measure the proximity or divergence of a new observation (feature vector) relative to the predefined cluster centers. It is critical to note that these cluster centers are defined based on the average values of the features of all feature vectors within a specific cluster.

Figure 9.8: Visualization of raw data from the anomaly dataset (multicolored line) alongside the deviation metric D (black line) for both the normal (upper panel) and anomaly (lower panel) scenarios. Subsequences are distinguished by the color of the cluster they are assigned to. The peak value of the deviation metric for the training data is 33.8, while the anomaly data has a peak of 41.9.

Let the total number of clusters be N with each cluster c indexed by $i \in 1, \dots, N$. The cluster center c_i is as follows:

$$c_i = [\mu_{i,1}, \mu_{i,2}, \dots, \mu_{i,j}, \dots, \mu_{i,M-1}, \mu_{i,M}], \tag{9.2}$$

where $\mu_{i,j}$ is the mean of the j^{th} feature of all feature vectors in cluster i . The index j runs from 1 to M , where M is the total number of features each feature vector comprises. To calculate the Euclidean distance (denoted as $d_{i,l}$) between each feature vector F_l and cluster center c_i , we use the following equation:

$$d_{i,l} = \sqrt{(f_1 - \mu_{i,1})^2 + \dots + (f_j - \mu_{i,2})^2 + \dots + (f_M - \mu_{i,M})^2}, \tag{9.3}$$

where f_j is the feature of the given feature vector F_l and $l \in 1, \dots, L$ is the index of the feature vector in the data set. The sum of distances is computed as follows:

$$D_l = \sum_{i=1}^N d_{i,l}. \tag{9.4}$$

Our understanding of deviation is based on the principle that the anomalousness of a feature vector increases as its distance from all cluster centers exceeds a certain threshold. While a feature vector's distance from a single cluster center may not definitively indicate a deviation, a notable increase in distance from all centers suggests potential anomalies. Figure 9.7 illustrates the calculation of this deviation metric, represented by a black dot for a specific feature vector. Observations located at or beyond the boundaries of the plotted area are indicative of deviations. It is crucial to note that the deviation metric

is never zero for any feature vector from either the reference or production datasets. Therefore, its interpretation requires a contextual comparison—either within the same production dataset or against the reference dataset. Significant spikes or a consistently high deviation metric compared to the reference may indicate substantial deviations or changes within the production data.

9.3.5 Deployment of the Pipeline as a Docker Container

The output model from the unsupervised learning pipeline is an example model in the high-level digital twin architecture (See Figure 9.1). This section details the deployment of both the pipeline and its resultant model as a Docker container, a key component of the ENTRUST digital twin framework. This containerization strategy ensures that the model and its associated processes are seamlessly integrated, maintained, and executed within the digital twin's operational environment, facilitating consistent performance and scalability across different deployment scenarios.

The unsupervised learning pipeline, encapsulated within a Docker container, includes both training and inference processes as illustrated in Figure 9.9. It operates by fetching necessary assets from a Docker volume mounted on the host file system and stores the resultant models in the cache. Users can access the inference pipeline either through a browser-based GUI or programmatically via a REST API. Constructed using Flask, this REST API facilitates smooth integration with other applications and enhances user interaction with its Flask-RESTful extension, which simplifies the management of endpoints. The API, implemented in a single Python script (`api.py`), encompasses all essential functions including API configuration, route definitions, and request handling, and integrates various Python modules for data handling, machine learning, and visualization to meet diverse user requirements.

The pipeline employs a suite of Python libraries to enhance its functionality: NumPy and Pandas for managing and manipulating large datasets, Plotly for interactive data visualization, and Scikit-learn for clustering and other data analysis techniques. Additionally, the API uses the YAML library for configuration management and the UUID library to generate unique model identifiers, streamlining operations and ensuring robustness in data handling and analysis.

The API features several endpoints to streamline model creation, management, and inference. Key endpoints include `create`, `infer GUI`, and `infer`. The `create` endpoint allows users to establish a new model by defining parameters and training data, supporting GET requests to list existing models and POST requests to initiate model creation. The `infer GUI` endpoint facilitates dataset inference via a graphical user interface, while the `infer` endpoint caters to REST API clients for programmatic inference. Both endpoints handle GET requests (which return status codes) and POST requests (which trigger the inference process).

The pipeline utilizes file-based storage and Data Version Control (DVC) to manage data and model assets. It organizes raw data, models, and metadata into dedicated directories, simplifying access and retrieval. DVC monitors changes to these assets, providing a version-controlled history that enhances manageability. This setup allows the API to efficiently handle storage, retrieval, and versioning of models and data, with DVC ensuring a clear separation between the API's core functionalities and its storage mechanisms.

We containerized the pipeline's REST API using Docker to streamline deployment and maintain a consistent runtime environment. Docker encapsulates the API and its dependencies into a portable container, facilitating deployment across various platforms. It uses Docker volumes for persistent storage of assets and data files, ensuring that data remains accessible and modifiable on the host machine even after the container is terminated. This approach allows for efficient and consistent API deployment, enhancing the user experience across different environments.

Figure 9.9: Pipeline Deployment as a Docker Container.

9.3.6 Initial Experiments with ENTRUST Data

We conducted an initial evaluation of our system using a select dataset of time series data (memory usage of a high-end device) obtained from a high-end device. Figure 9.10 displays the outcomes of the initial evaluation, showcasing the time series of memory usage for a high-end device. This data has been analyzed using the unsupervised learning method to identify anomalies, demonstrating the effectiveness of this method in monitoring and detecting unusual patterns in memory consumption.

Memory usage is represented by the multi-colored line in Figure 9.10, showing the amount of memory used over time. The different colors on this line correspond to different labels assigned by the anomaly detection algorithm, indicating various states or behaviors of the device memory usage. The black line indicates the deviation metric, which quantifies the degree of deviation of memory usage from what is considered normal or typical behavior. This metric is crucial for identifying significant changes or anomalies in memory usage.

The red points, appearing at the beginning of the timeline, indicate stable and low memory usage, which suggests normal operating conditions without significant fluctuations. **The blue points** show a rapid increase in memory usage, indicating a potential anomaly or a shift in the device’s operational state.

Figure 9.10: Time series of memory usage for a high end device, processed using our approach for anomaly detection using unsupervised learning.

Following the peak, **the green points** indicate a stabilization of memory usage at a new higher level compared to the initial baseline. Although stable, the deviation metric remains elevated.

The deviation metric (black line) remains low during the red point phase, suggesting that the memory usage is within expected norms. As the memory usage increases (blue points), the deviation metric spikes, reflecting a significant divergence from the baseline. This spike is a critical indicator of an anomaly or a notable change in device behavior. Even as the memory usage stabilizes at a new higher level (green points), the deviation metric reduces but does not return to the initial baseline levels, indicating that while the anomaly has passed, the system may be operating under a new normal condition that differs from the original state.

The initial testing of our unsupervised learning approach for anomaly detection in memory usage has yielded promising results, demonstrating the capability of the method to effectively analyze time series data and identify potential anomalies. The success in detecting irregular patterns and significant deviations in memory consumption suggests that this methodology is robust and can be applied more broadly.

Encouraged by these findings, there is a strong rationale to extend this anomaly detection technique to other system measurements within the ENTRUST framework. This expansion could include analyzing different types of operational data, such as CPU usage, network traffic, and power consumption, among others. By applying the same unsupervised learning techniques to these varied data streams, we can potentially uncover a wider range of anomalies that might indicate security threats within the system.

Building on these promising initial results, we will continue refining and expanding our anomaly detection approach. Our next steps will involve applying this unsupervised learning technique to other system measurements and much more extensive datasets within the ENTRUST framework. Extending the anomaly detection approach to multiple system measurements would not only enhance the overall monitoring capabilities but also improve the system’s resilience by enabling early detection of anomalies across different aspects of the operational environment. This proactive detection is critical for maintaining system integrity and ensuring the reliability and safety of connected medical devices within ENTRUST. Such comprehensive monitoring is integral to developing a robust digital twin model that accurately reflects

real-world conditions and provides actionable insights for system improvement and risk management.

Our current unsupervised learning technique is applicable to numerical time series data, effectively monitoring variables like temperature, energy usage, and network load. However, extending this methodology to handle categorical data, such as event logs, presents a challenge. Categorical data, with its non-numeric, discrete values, requires different analytical approaches to identify patterns and anomalies. Enhancing our anomaly detection capabilities to address categorical data is a research question we will explore to improve the analysis and monitoring of system logs and activities.

Type of Data	Anomaly Type	Indicators
CPU Usage	Unusual Spikes/Drops	A sudden increase or decrease in CPU utilization, e.g., unexpected spikes in CPU usage which might indicate the execution of a resource-intensive process. If there is a sudden spike in CPU utilization without a corresponding expected activity, it could be an indicator of an unauthenticated software update being performed, potentially compromising the system's security. Or this could be an attempt of a SW Downgrade so as to lead the device to a vulnerable state with an unpatched SW stack that can allow for further, more devastating type of attacks.
Memory Usage	Memory Leaks, unexpected changes in memory profile, or exceeding predefined memory boundaries	Gradual increase in memory usage over time. For instance, by monitoring the memory profile and specific memory regions for cases where there is gradual increase in memory usage over time, we can perform integrity checks related to loaded libraries and application states. Sudden or unexplained variations in these regions may indicate unauthorized modifications or the presence of malicious code. This could help identify anomalies such as unauthorized library loading or unexpected changes in application state that compromise system integrity.
Disk I/O	High Latency or Errors	Increased read/write times, I/O error rates
Network Traffic	Bandwidth Abuse, DDoS Attacks	Sudden spikes in traffic, unusual traffic patterns
System Load	Overload Conditions	High system load average over extended periods
Process Execution	Unauthorized Processes	Execution of unknown or unauthorized processes. This can affect both the integrity but also secrecy of the target device operational profile. For instance, in case of a device where locality-protected process execution mechanisms are employed, then such localities can be used in order to determine security policies: For instance, Locality 0 processes indicate commands that originate from a Static OS and, thus, have less privileges in reading/writing to specific memory regions - unlike to Locality 4 processes which depict commands and signals originating from the CPU memory controller with the highest privileges. A possible elevation of a process locality that may have been exploited by an adversary can lead to the compromise of the device's entire trusted computing base.
Control-Flow Integrity	Execution Anomalies	Divergence from expected control flow paths through the efficient extraction of device's execution features from only one execution trace. This can allow the identification of dependencies between execution embeddings so as to identify any attempt to exploit memory vulnerabilities including control- and non-control data attacks.
Signal Tracing	Unexpected Signal Activity	Unusual or unexpected signals sent or received
Power Consumption	Abnormal Power Usage	Sudden changes in power usage patterns

Table 9.5: Behavioural profiles for anomaly detection in Connected Medical Devices.

9.3.7 Definition of Misbehavior/Plausibility Checks in CMDs

In this section, we define the types of **misbehavior and plausibility checks applicable to Connected Medical Devices**. These checks are crucial for maintaining trust and have been compiled to demonstrate the capabilities of an advanced AI-based Anomaly Detection system (as the one envisioned in ENTRUST) based on the availability and richness of system traces monitored by the Digital Twins.

In this context, Table 9.5 presents a comprehensive overview of the types of data collected in ENTRUST (more details on the tracing capabilities leveraging ENTRUST advanced Tracer can be found in D5.1 [28]), the anomalies that could be detected within this data, and their corresponding indicators. It includes critical system metrics such as CPU usage, memory usage, disk I/O, network traffic, and system load, highlighting potential anomalies like unusual spikes, memory leaks, high latency, bandwidth abuse, and overload conditions. Additionally, it covers the type of trustworthiness evidence that can be collected as a trust indicator that can be processed by the TAF to assess the device's trustworthiness level against such attack vectors. For instance, evidence on control-flow integrity, configuration integrity verification, power consumption, etc., can enable domain-wide trust quantification based on comprised devices' individual trust scores. Each anomaly type is associated with specific indicators, enabling precise and effective monitoring of connected medical devices to ensure their trustworthiness, integrity in remote attestation, and secure software updates.

We must highlight that Table 9.5 constitutes a rather exhaustive list of plausibility checks based on a superset of types of traces that can become available in a collection of commodity devices prominently used in the CMD domain. As described in detail in D5.1 [28], continuously monitoring and extracting such data is highly dependent on their resource profile, dictating the type of tracing capabilities that can be instantiated. For instance, dynamic traces on the execution flow of the running SW stack are relatively difficult to monitor in low-end devices due to scarce resources. Therefore, the focus is mainly on static properties, availing the underlying hardware characteristics, such as secure boot. In the second half of the project, we plan to investigate and map the feasibility of such plausibility checks to the types of devices currently available in the context of the envisioned use cases. We will give special attention to those checks that can enable the assessment of various aspects of the functional correctness of a device: all checks related to the integrity of the execution correctness and accuracy of a device (e.g., Control-Flow Attestation) are of interest since they can help the decision-making process based on monitored data that have been extracted and processed by service workloads with the Required Trust Level. The efforts will involve a deeper analysis of specific indicators such as memory usage and profile alterations (evidence that can allow the AI-based Anomaly Detection to identify deviations in the sequence of memory addresses allocated to capture the normal execution flow of a program); CPU usage spikes (as an indicator of possibly unauthorized SW Updates), unauthorized processes running and trying to get access to sensitive data stored in isolated environments, etc.

By concentrating on these areas, we aim to develop more robust and precise methods for detecting unauthorized activities, such as unauthenticated software updates and unauthorized library loading. This targeted investigation will enhance our understanding of how these indicators correlate with potential security breaches, ultimately leading to more effective anomaly detection and mitigation strategies within the Digital Twin framework.

9.3.8 Installation

The unsupervised learning system is available on GitHub, with detailed instructions on how to install and run it: <https://github.com/SINTEF-9012/udava>.

9.4 Risks and Challenges

In this section, we evaluate potential hurdles and obstacles associated with the implementation and ongoing development of the digital twin within the ENTRUST project. This assessment is crucial for proactively identifying areas that might impact the project's success and developing strategies to mitigate these risks.

- **Scalability and Performance:** As the volume of data and the complexity of network environments increase, ensuring the scalability and performance of the digital twin becomes crucial. Failure to scale effectively could result in system slowdowns or failures, impacting real-time monitoring and decision-making processes.
- **Accuracy and Reliability:** The effectiveness of the digital twin relies heavily on the accuracy and reliability of its simulations. Developing models that accurately reflect real-world conditions and predict future states with high reliability is a challenging task. Inaccurate simulations could lead to incorrect assessments and decisions, potentially compromising device safety and system integrity.
- **Technical Expertise:** The development and maintenance of the digital twin require highly specialized knowledge in several areas such as machine learning, system integration, and cybersecurity. A shortage of skilled personnel could slow down the development and affect the overall quality of the digital twin.
- **Data Requirements for Advanced Techniques:** We plan to investigate and use cutting-edge techniques like causal AI for predictions. While these advanced techniques offer significant potential, they require extensive and high-quality data to produce useful outcomes. Acquiring sufficient data and ensuring its quality can be challenging, and inadequate data can limit the effectiveness of these advanced analytical methods.
- **Experimental Nature of Advanced Techniques:** Incorporating experimental techniques for predictions introduces an additional layer of risk. These methods, while promising, are still in the experimental phase and may not perform as expected. There is a possibility that these techniques might not yield the anticipated results, leading to unreliable predictions or failure to detect critical anomalies. This uncertainty can impact the trust and reliability of the digital twin, necessitating contingency plans and alternative strategies to ensure robust and dependable system performance.

Addressing these challenges requires a comprehensive risk management strategy that includes regular reviews of the system's performance and security, continuous training for all users, and ongoing development to improve the digital twin's accuracy and functionality. By acknowledging and preparing for these risks, the project can enhance its resilience and ensure that the digital twin is a robust tool to advance connected medical device security within the healthcare sector.

Chapter 10

ENTRUST Securing & Authenticating SW/FW Updates

In the rapidly advancing domain of CMDs, the significance of Secure Software Updates cannot be overstated. These CMDs, ranging from wearable health monitors to sophisticated diagnostic tools, as well as intermediate network gateways, are integral to patient care and medical research. Ensuring the security and reliability of the software that governs these devices is paramount for patient safety, data integrity, and overall system functionality. To this end, in the remaining of this chapter, we outline the current **design and preliminary implementation of the Secure Software Update functionality**, highlighting its critical role in maintaining the integrity and efficacy of CMDs. The Secure Software Update process is a part of the secure lifecycle management of CMDs, drawing upon the principles established in the 'Guidance for Secure Update of Software and Firmware on Embedded Systems' by the Trusted Computing Group (TCG) [49]. Although there exist several relevant reference architectures and guidances for software updated (e.g., by European Union Agency for Network and Information Security (ENISA) [51] or Medical Device Coordination Group (MDCG) [56]), the TCG has established itself as the main standardisation body capturing the definition of those trusted computing abstractions for safeguarding device integrity and robustness. Thus, they are considering systems with the same type of requirements as we have in ENTRUST.

ENTRUST's vision is to build a robust and secure ecosystem for CMDs, ensuring that each device operates reliably and securely throughout its lifecycle. In this vision, the Secure Software Update process is a core building block of an overarching trust management framework. One important dimension when devices try to establish trust relationships as well as for building trust in the data extracted from edge devices, is to have the necessary guarantees that an always up-to-date SW/FW has been instantiated within the system. Thus, whenever there is a need (e.g., there is a change in the trust level of a device), this might necessitate the deployment of a new software version with the necessary patches. This envisioned system aims to safeguard patient data, ensure the uninterrupted provisioning of healthcare services, and maintain compliance with stringent regulatory requirements, such as [33] and [32]. **Secure Software Updates are essential for implementing of this vision, enabling the seamless and safe evolution of device capabilities while protecting against emerging cyber-threats.** To this end, the Secure Software Update mechanism is part of the overall Trust Assessment pipeline of ENTRUST for ensuring the trustworthiness of the device and the CMD ecosystem as a whole.

The primary concern in the medical field is patient safety. CMDs often monitor and manage critical health functions, where any compromise in their software could lead to incorrect diagnoses, treatment errors, or even life-threatening situations. Secure Software Updates ensure that vulnerabilities are patched promptly, reducing the risk of malicious interference or malfunction, thus aligning with the TCG's emphasis on **maintaining device integrity through timely and trustworthy updates** in response to a change

in the trust level of a device. More specifically, the implementation of the Secure Software Update mechanism will offer the following: (i) mechanisms for the **verification of the provenance of the update** and safeguarding the **integrity of the update** itself, (ii) **robustness of the update distribution system** and mechanisms to ensure the authenticity of exchanges, (iii) **secure installation of the software update** by providing verifiable evidence on the integrity of the updated software stack deployed on the device, and (iv) **post-installation verification of the correctness of the deployed update**.

10.1 Positioning Within the Overall ENTRUST Architecture

In the context of ENTRUST, a core pillar is the use of Secure Software Updates as a reaction strategy in response to identified vulnerabilities or cyber-attacks, i.e., as an answer to an event that changes the trust level of a CMD. This is essentially an indication of a risk, which can lead to the need for a Secure Software Update.

Therefore, the scope of the Secure Software Update task encompasses the development and implementation of a comprehensive framework for Secure Software Updates across all CMDs within the ENTRUST network. This includes conducting thorough security assessments of existing devices, integrating secure update mechanisms, and establishing an automated and secure delivery system for Secure Software Updates. A trigger for a Secure Software Update process will come as a result of the TAF's calculation of a trust opinion about a device that is less than the required level identified as part of the trust policy deployed (i.e. $ATL < RTL$). This can be the result of a failed attestation task which will enable the provision of the detailed raw traces (i.e., system traces capturing the behaviour of the target system) to be shared with the Digital Twin-based simulation component, where further processing can be conducted in an attempt to identify the exact attack execution path that resulted in this failed attestation. In this case, this attack path will be shared with the Software Verification component where additional fuzzing will be conducted towards compiling an updated version of the software with the necessary patches to be deployed. It is expected that after a successful software update, the identified vulnerability will be patched, thus bringing the device back to a trustworthy state (i.e., $ATL \geq RTL$).

10.2 Conceptual Architecture of the ENTRUST Secure SW/FW Update Functionality

We now proceed with the design of the Secure Software Update functionality, as depicted in Figure 10.1. The main elements of this architecture are the following:

- **Device Manufacturer** plays a crucial role in the ENTRUST ecosystem, not only producing the hardware but also often developing the associated software. The expected version of the software/-firmware stack to be deployed for each CMD model is specified as part of the Device-level MUD profile. The manufacturers may either create the software themselves or subcontract trusted third parties to ensure specialised expertise and security. Regardless of the development approach, the integrity and security of the software updates are paramount. Manufacturers sign the software updates with a private key, ensuring that each update can further be authenticated and verified. The corresponding public key is embedded in the manufactured devices, enabling the high-end devices to verify the authenticity of updates upon receipt.¹ This cryptographic method ensures that only

¹ Please note that this approach primarily applies to high-end devices that have the capabilities for asymmetric cryptography. We discuss the further extension of this approach to low-end devices in Chapter 11, where the core idea is to employ high-end devices as proxies capable of performing the required complex operations on behalf of their coupled low-end devices.

Figure 10.1: High-level Secure Software Update architecture in ENTRUST.

verified, untampered updates are installed, maintaining the security and reliability of the CMDs. The run-time check of the correct SW/FW version running on a device is also achieved through the establishment of the appropriate key restriction usage policies for safeguarding the use of the Attestation Key if and only if the device is at a correct configuration state.

- **System Administrator** in the context of ENTRUST possesses in-depth knowledge of the medical domain and its specific requirements, and is thus responsible for providing information on domain-specific threats and vulnerabilities to the Risk Assessment component. In addition to these responsibilities, the System Administrator also oversees the Secure Software Update process and ensures that software updates are applied correctly and securely across all devices. Using the Digital Twin platform, the System Administrator can manually trigger updates if needed, to provide timely response to emerging threats or vulnerabilities.
- **ENTRUST Ecosystem** collectively represents the rest of the ENTRUST components which may trigger the Secure Software Update process. More specifically, the main reason for automatic

software updates envisioned by ENTRUST is a change in the trust state of a device. For example, it could be a failed attestation process, when the TAF indicates that the ATL is lower than the RTL, thus signifying the need to identify potential vulnerabilities and apply necessary mitigation measures. Additionally, another common trigger for Secure Software Updates is the results of attack simulations based on the Digital Twin. These simulations may reveal the need for proactive Secure Software Update actions to address potential security threats. Technically, this triggering can be implemented using HTTP API or MQTT listeners. HTTP API can provide a straightforward and robust mechanism for initiating updates by sending HTTP requests to the update engine, while MQTT listeners can offer a lightweight and efficient solution for real-time monitoring and triggering updates through publish-subscribe messaging patterns. Noteworthy, while the triggering of updates can be fully automatic, in ENTRUST we assume that the Secure Software Update process is not completely automated and relies on the involvement of the System Administrator who oversees this whole process.

10.2.1 Main Functional Elements

- **Digital Twin Platform** maintains a live view of the managed CMD fleet, i.e., a collection of continuously updated Digital Twins for each managed CMD. The Digital Twin platform is the central element of the whole Secure Software Update functionality, as it maintains an up-to-date representation of managed devices. This enables secure and timely software updates by providing a comprehensive view of each device's configuration and operational state. This has been extensively described in Chapter 9, and the same Digital Twin platform is employed for the purposes of the Secure Software Update functionality. For the automatic triggering of software updates, the Digital Twin platform is equipped with APIs (e.g., HTTP entry-points and MQTT listeners), so that the rest of the ENTRUST components can interact with it.
- **Assignment Engine** takes as input the current contextual information about CMDs and software assignment constraints; produces device-software assignment as an output, i.e., what software should be deployed on which CMD. Targeted, context-aware assignment of software updates in the IoT using Digital Twins is essential for ensuring that each device receives updates tailored to its specific configuration and operational environment. This approach minimises the risk of incompatibility and maximises the effectiveness of updates, enhancing device performance and security. By leveraging Digital Twins, updates can be precisely managed and deployed, reducing downtime and ensuring a seamless integration into the existing IoT infrastructure.
- **Subfleet Controller** is deployed and runs on the Domain Manager (i.e., close to CMDs in the secure domain) and is responsible for interaction with the ENTRUST Secure Software Update engine on behalf of a subfleet (e.g., Tellu's subfleet of connected healthcare gateways). It receives software update commands from the central Digital Twin platform through its northbound interface and propagates them to the downstream IoT devices via its southbound interface using device- or platform-specific adapters. This setup ensures efficient and secure dissemination of updates, tailored to the specific needs of local devices, while maintaining synchronisation with the central management system.
- **Software Repository** serves as a central distribution point for Secure Software Updates for CMDs. This repository can be a private server managed by the manufacturer or a public cloud-based service, such as Docker Hub,² which is widely used for distributing containerised applications. Acting as a central hub, the repository ensures that updates are securely stored and can be accessed programmatically by the devices. Secure protocols like HTTPS are employed to protect the integrity

²<https://hub.docker.com/>

of the data in transit, and access control mechanisms are in place to restrict update uploads and modifications to authorised personnel only.

- **Adapters** are device- or platform-specific software components responsible for interacting with CMDs and enacting the actual software updates on CMDs. They are instantiated and run alongside the subfleet controller on the Domain Manager, and depending on the type of devices in its sub-fleet, the subfleet controller will instantiate a corresponding adapter. These adapters are tailored to the unique characteristics and protocols of each device type or platform within the IoT ecosystem. By interfacing directly with the devices through standardised or proprietary APIs, they ensure that updates are deployed efficiently and securely. This approach guarantees compatibility and reliability across diverse CMD types, enhancing overall system resilience and performance.
- **Devices** are diverse CMDs that ENTRUST deals with, ranging from wearable and portable devices, to healthcare gateways for telemedicine, to intelligent patient transportation infrastructure. Devices expose some APIs specific to their hardware platform, network interfaces, OS, software stack, etc., which are used by the Adapters to enact the software update process. In ENTRUST, we distinguish between **high-end devices** and **low-end devices**. The distinction is primarily based on the available hardware capabilities. Low-end devices having scarce capabilities (e.g., network bandwidth, CPU, storage), and thus, their operation is limited to collecting and relaying monitored patient data to the backend system through their parent node – a high-end device.
- **Monitoring Agents:** these run on the devices and act as essential components for collecting real-time contextual information. These agents gather data on device status (based on the tracing capabilities as documented in the context of D5.1 [28]), operational parameters, environmental conditions, and other relevant metrics. This information is then transmitted back to the central Digital Twin platform where it is represented as reported properties. By continuously updating these properties, the platform maintains an accurate and dynamic Digital Twin model of each device, facilitating informed decision-making for the following Secure Software Updates.

10.2.2 Triggering Software Updates with the Desired-Reported Property Pattern

The **desired-reported property** pattern in Digital Twins is a key mechanism for managing and synchronising the state of physical assets and their virtual counterparts, as depicted in Figure 10.2. This pattern involves two primary components: the **desired properties** and the **reported properties**.

- **Desired Properties:** These are the target states or configurations that the System Administrator wants the physical asset to achieve. They are set within the Digital Twin and serve as directives for how the asset should be configured or operated. For instance, in the context of Secure Software Updates, the desired property might be the target software version to be deployed.
- **Reported Properties:** These reflect the current state or configuration of the physical asset as detected and communicated by sensors or monitoring systems. The reported properties are continuously updated to provide a run-time status of the asset's condition. Continuing with the Secure Software Update example, the reported property would be the current software version that the device is running. Reported properties, and especially evidence on the correct device configuration (which entailed evidence on the device's correct software version running), is achieved through the trusted computing enablers of ENTRUST. Such evidences are monitored/provided in a verifiable manner through the Configuration Integrity Verification (CIV) scheme as described in [27].

The interplay between these two components allows for effective monitoring and control. When a discrepancy is detected between the desired properties and the reported properties, the Digital Twin platform can

Figure 10.2: Desired-reported property pattern in Digital Twins.

trigger actions to align the physical asset with the desired state. This might involve sending commands to the asset to adjust its configuration (e.g., upgrade the software version), or it might involve alerting operators to take corrective actions. This pattern is particularly valuable in the ENTRUST use case scenarios requiring precise control and automation, such as telemedicine using remote patient monitoring, wearables and portable health monitors, and intelligent patient transportation services. It ensures that the Digital Twin remains an accurate and actionable representation of the physical asset, enabling proactive maintenance, optimisation, and fault detection.

10.2.3 Context-Aware Software Assignment

Software assignment using Digital Twins in CMDs leverages detailed digital representations of physical devices, incorporating multi-dimensional contextual properties, to assign software updates efficiently. More specifically, the cyber-physical-social context of monitored CMDs encompasses several dimensions [19]. The cyber aspects include the traditional hardware and software properties of the devices. Physical aspects refer to environmental conditions such as the device’s location, surrounding temperature, and time of day, which can also affect device performance and patient safety. Social aspects involve the actual human user, considering factors like specific medical conditions, usage patterns, and service subscription types, all of which influence how the device is used and monitored. The assignment engine uses these context-aware Digital Twin representations to match target software requirements with the appropriate devices. This can be implemented in various scenarios: **one-to-one**, **one-to-many**, and **one-to-all**.

1. **One-to-One Scenario:** In the one-to-one scenario, the assignment engine assigns a specific software update to a single CMD based on its unique contextual properties. For example, if a Digital Twin of a particular device indicates that it requires a firmware update to fix a known vulnerability, the Assignment Engine will push the update directly to that specific device (e.g., using its unique ID as the target condition). In this context, the one-to-one software assignment can be connected to the CIV scheme [27], which is a single prover-single verifier attestation scheme, so a failure will lead to the update of a specific individual device. The desired-reported property pattern is used to confirm the device reaches the desired state after the update, ensuring the CMD operates securely and effectively after the installation.
2. **One-to-Many Scenario:** In the one-to-many scenario, the assignment engine assigns software updates to a group of CMDs sharing certain contextual properties. For instance, a hospital might have several patient monitoring systems that require an update to enhance data encryption protocols. The Digital Twins of these monitors, which may include similar models or devices within the same

department, will indicate they all need the update. The assignment engine identifies these commonalities and distributes the update to all relevant devices, ensuring consistency and efficiency. In the context of ENTRUST, the one-to-many software assignment may be connected with the Swarm Attestation scheme [27]. In contrast with CIV, this attests to the correctness of multiple devices simultaneously. So if a vulnerability is identified in more than one device, a patch can be applied to all of them at once. This approach facilitates the update process across multiple CMDs, leveraging batch processing capabilities to maintain high standards of patient data security.

- 3. One-to-All Scenario:** In the one-to-all scenario, the assignment engine broadcasts a software update to all CMDs within the network. This is typically done for critical updates, such as a security patch addressing a widespread vulnerability. For example, if a new regulation mandates enhanced cyber-security measures across all medical devices, the Digital Twins provide the necessary contextual properties to ensure each device is eligible and capable of receiving the update. In the context of ENTRUST, this type of software assignment may further support both aforementioned types of attestation. For example, if a vulnerability is identified for a single device of a specific model, a patch can be applied to all other devices of this type in a scalable and timely manner. Also this could apply if the Swarm Attestation detects a vulnerability in more than one device. The assignment engine then ensures that this update is deployed across the entire fleet of CMDs, leveraging the Digital Twins to monitor and validate the update process.

Noteworthy, in each of these scenarios, apart from the plain assignment, the fundamental security requirements are addressed. For instance, integrity and authenticity of an update are achieved by signing the update by the Device Manufacturer (or Software Provider). Confidentiality, if needed, is achieved by equipping the devices with the appropriate software update keys. In this case, for the one-to-one or one-to-many assignments, each device will need to have its own software update key.

10.3 Implementing Software Management Lifecycle

The described conceptual architecture for Secure Software Updates in ENTRUST is aligned with the TCG Guidance for Secure Update of Software and Firmware on Embedded Systems [49]. The software update lifecycle is part of the Runtime Phase of the ENTRUST architecture, as depicted in Figure 2.4. It is expected that the secure CMD domain is already established, with the medical device enrolled and the Domain Manager up and running.

The Secure Software Update lifecycle begins with the development step, which employs secure coding practices. Updates are cryptographically signed to verify their authenticity and integrity, ensuring that only verified updates can be installed on the device. The distribution step ensures updates are assigned and delivered securely, using encrypted communication channels (see [27]) and secure servers to prevent interception or tampering. In the deployment phase, devices must authenticate the updates before installation. This involves verifying the cryptographic signatures to confirm the update is from a trusted source and has not been altered. Post-deployment, the verification and attestation step involves validating the update's integrity and functionality, monitoring for any issues or anomalies that might arise. All these lifecycle steps are also included in Figure 2.4 as gray boxes in the background.

By adhering to these steps, we can ensure that CMDs remain secure throughout their operational lifecycle, proactively addressing potential vulnerabilities. In the following sub-sections, we will look into each of these steps in more detail, describing how the proposed ENTRUST Secure Software Update functionality implements them.

Figure 10.3: Step 2: Secure Update Signing.

10.3.1 Step 1: Secure Development

Implementing secure development for CMDs goes beyond the official scope of ENTRUST, thus, we assume that developers and service providers follow best practices based on TCG Guidance [49]. Essential practices include: incorporating secure coding practices throughout the software development lifecycle to avoid vulnerabilities like buffer overflows and SQL injection; regular code reviews and the use of static analysis tools are essential for early detection of vulnerabilities; conducting extensive security testing, including penetration testing, to identify and mitigate potential issues before deployment; employing robust cryptographic measures to protect data, and ensure that software updates are signed and verified to maintain integrity.

10.3.2 Step 2: Secure Update Signing

In the first place, implementing secure update signing for CMDs requires robust key management and thorough signing of software updates (as depicted in Figure 10.3). In ENTRUST, we assume that device manufacturers generate and manage a pair of cryptographic keys: a private key for signing updates and a corresponding public key for verifying them. The private key, crucial for the integrity of the signing process, is stored securely (safeguarded by the underlying Root-of-Trust as part of ENTRUST’s TCB) to prevent unauthorised access and potential misuse. On the other hand, the public key is embedded within the medical devices during the manufacturing process, enabling these devices to verify the authenticity of received updates. This asymmetric Secure Software Update key pair can potentially be the same as the asymmetric Root Device ID key pair. For the devices capable of symmetric cryptography, it can be the case that a symmetric Secure Software Update key is established in each device during the manufacturing process.

When a software update, such as a Docker container or a binary executable file, is prepared for deployment following the secure development phase, the manufacturer uses their private key to create a digital signature. This process involves generating a hash of the update file and encrypting this hash with the private key. The resultant digital signature is then attached to the software update package. For updates involving Docker containers, the process is similar. The entire container image is signed by hashing its content and creating a digital signature. Devices that run Docker can verify the container signature before deploying it, ensuring that the container has not been altered. This cryptographic measure ensures that any alteration of the update file post-signing will be detectable. After generating a digital signature using

Figure 10.4: Step 3: Robust Distribution.

the private key, the signed software updates are pushed to a secure repository, either private or public, from where they can be accessed by the devices. This process starts with securely uploading the signed update package to the designated Software Repository, which can be a private server managed by the Device Manufacturer or a public cloud-based service.

At this point, the signed software update, coupled with its signature, is then ready for secure distribution to the CMDs. This method ensures that only verified and authentic software is installed, maintaining the integrity and security of the medical devices.

10.3.3 Step 3: Robust Distribution

To implement robust distribution of software updates for CMDs (Figure 10.4), leveraging Digital Twins and the desired-reported property pattern is essential. As previously explained, Digital Twins provide real-time virtual representations of each device, capturing their current status, including operating system, software version, execution traces, and other critical data. The update distribution process begins with the Assignment Engine, which uses the detailed information from Digital Twins to determine which devices need updates. By comparing the desired state (i.e., the latest software version) with the reported state (i.e., the current software version on the device), the engine can identify discrepancies and target the necessary updates. This is also an example of an update safeguard of how to efficiently monitor when an update process needs to be triggered. This can be enabled by other trust assessment controls and, for instance, directly from the TAF.

For a single device (i.e., one-to-one scenario), the assignment engine checks the Digital Twins’s reported properties and pushes the update if the device is not up-to-date. For a subset of devices (i.e., one-to-many scenario), the engine filters devices based on specific criteria, such as those running an outdated version or those with a particular operating system. It then pushes the update to this group, ensuring all selected devices meet the desired state. For fleet-wide updates (i.e., one-to-all scenario), the engine initiates a broad distribution to all devices. This ensures uniformity across the entire network, with each device’s Digital Twin confirming receipt and installation of the update, maintaining consistent software versions across the fleet.

The distribution itself takes place over secure channels, ensuring data integrity and preventing unauthorised access. The process includes continuous monitoring of the update status, using the Digital Twins

Figure 10.5: Step 4: Secure Update Installation.

to track progress and verify successful installations.

10.3.4 Step 4: Secure Update Installation

Secure installation of software updates on CMDs (Figure 10.5) requires addressing the diversity in hardware architectures, operating systems, execution environments, network interfaces, and APIs. This implementation relies on specific software adapters developed for each CMD type, ensuring a seamless installation process tailored to the unique requirements of each device.

In addition to the adapters, the Subfleet Manager is another important software component installed within the same secure domain as the CMDs. It plays a vital role in coordinating and managing the update process across a diverse range of devices, ensuring that each device receives the appropriate updates securely and efficiently. The Subfleet Manager acts as intermediary between the central Secure Software Update server and the medical devices, ensuring compatibility and proper communication. Its main task is to receive software update commands from the Digital Twin platform on the northbound interface and routing to the assigned device on its southbound interface. Upon receiving a command, the Subfleet Manager identifies the specific adapter required for the target device type and instantiates it accordingly. It then forwards the software update command to the designated adapter, ensuring the correct and secure execution of the update process.

The installation process varies depending on the CMD type but generally involves securely transferring the update package to the device and initiating the installation process via the corresponding API. The adapter handles specific commands and procedures required for installation on different operating systems and execution environments. It monitors the installation process in real-time to ensure it completes successfully without interruptions or errors.

10.3.5 Step 5: Post-Update Verification and Attestation

This is the last step in the Secure Software Update cycle (Figure 10.6). Local attestation involves verifying the integrity of software updates directly on the device. Each CMD is equipped with a public key from the manufacturer. These keys are essential for verifying the authenticity and integrity of installed software updates, which are signed with the manufacturer's private key. After a software update is installed, the

Figure 10.6: Step 5: Post-Update Verification and Attestation.

device uses this public key to verify the digital signature of the update. This verification ensures that the update has not been tampered with and is indeed from a trusted source. This process can be automated and performed periodically, ensuring the software’s continuous integrity.

To further enhance security, continuous monitoring is implemented using device-side monitoring agents. These agents run on each CMD, collecting run-time information such as current software versions, execution traces, and other relevant metrics. This data is sent to the Digital Twin platform at regular intervals. The platform uses this information to maintain an up-to-date virtual representation of each device, enabling real-time monitoring and detection of anomalies or discrepancies.

The continuous monitoring system allows for proactive security measures, as any deviations from expected behaviour can be quickly identified and addressed. By leveraging local attestation supported by continuous monitoring, a robust framework is established to ensure the security and integrity of software updates in CMDs, thereby safeguarding patient data and device functionality.

10.4 Current Implementation Status

As this development iteration, focus has been given on adoptability and integrability, and therefore we have taken an architectural design approach to improve aspects of coupling to application-specific details and separation of concerns. Given the cyber-physical nature of managed CMDs within the distributed fleet, three main design decisions underpin the design and implementation of the Secure Software Update mechanism:

- **Decoupled architecture:** Managed devices may unexpectedly crash, unpredictably lose network connection, and then reappear online. To accommodate such ad-hoc behaviour and prevent bottlenecks, communication between software components is implemented using pub-sub messaging based on MQTT.
- **Asynchronous communication:** For the same reason, it is important that any software updates initiated are guaranteed to be delivered to target devices regardless of how long they stay offline. This also means that the status of each device is continuously monitored and stored to apply the required changes when it gets back online. This can be implemented using the described desired-reported property pattern, which enables real-time monitoring of devices and comparison of reported properties against desired ones.

- **Hierarchical architecture and extensibility:** To prevent single points of failure and distribute the workload within the managed fleet of heterogeneous CMDs, devices with similar interfaces are grouped together. This introduces an extra layer of filtering and load-balancing functionality between the centralised Secure Software Update engine and numerous devices within the managed fleet. Thanks to this hierarchical architecture, where generic functionality is separated from device-specific implementations, the Secure Software Update engine will be able to accommodate new types of devices in the future.

In addition to these main requirements, the design and implementation of the Secure Software Update mechanism were driven by several non-functional requirements, such as the availability of a graphical user interface (GUI), user friendliness, and the intention to re-use existing software libraries.

To implement the conceptual architecture of the ENTRUST Secure Software Update functionality depicted in Figure 10.1, several software components were developed. These elements correspond to the main building blocks of the conceptual architecture, which we describe in more detail in the following subsections.

10.4.1 Digital Twin Platform: Eclipse Ditto

As the technological baseline on top of which we developed the Secure Software Update functionality, we used Eclipse Ditto³ – an open-source framework for building Digital Twins of Internet-connected devices with extensible modeling and built-in querying languages.

As already explained, by using a device management platform, edge application providers can remotely provision, monitor, and maintain their devices, as well as push software updates either manually or in an automated manner whenever a new version is released. In recent years, all these tasks have been underpinned by the prominent concept of Digital Twins. Simply put, Digital Twins are virtual models designed to accurately reflect physical objects equipped with various sensors related to certain aspects of their functionality. They enable the creation of rich digital models of anything physical or logical, from simple assets or products to complex cyber-physical environments. The collected sensor data is relayed to a processing system and applied to the Digital Twin.

Furthermore, Ditto acts as middleware, providing an abstraction layer for IoT solutions interacting with physical devices via the Digital Twin pattern. It can be seen as a toolkit, providing core functionality (e.g., meta-model, database, different messaging protocols and connectors, REST APIs, etc.), while some other features must be developed by users on top of it (e.g., domain-specific Digital Twin models, graphical user interfaces, device-side monitoring agents, etc.). Being part of a larger open-source ecosystem, it can be relatively easily integrated with other technologies from the Eclipse stack, including various communication protocols, pub-sub messaging, and load balancing. Some of these extensibility capabilities are demonstrated in Figure 10.7, which includes the GUI of the extended Digital Twin platform in the context of ENTRUST. More specifically, the screenshot includes the basic Secure Software Update functionality accessible to the System Administrator via a Digital Twin representation in the context of Tellu's use case on connected healthcare gateways.

10.4.1.1 Software Assignment Engine: Ditto Meta-Model + Resource Query Language

Ditto offers developers an extensible meta-model [19] (depicted in Figure 10.8) that, in its simplest form, enables modeling physical entities, referring to them as **Things**, using a JSON schema with the following

³<https://eclipse.dev/ditto/>

Figure 10.7: Front-end interface of the Digital Twin platform for Secure Software Updates.

key concepts:

- **Thing** is the top-level modeling concept for describing physical assets.
- **Definition** is included in every **Thing** (and optionally in **Features**) and essentially represents a URI linking to an external Web of Things (WoT) model.⁴ It describes how a **Thing** is structured and what behaviour/capabilities can be expected in an interoperable and standard manner.
- **Policy** enables fine-grained access control configuration. A specific policy defines who and how someone can access a specific resource.
- **Metadata** is Ditto’s internal field to store technical information, e.g., version or creation/modification timestamps.
- **Attributes** are used to model rather static properties of a **Thing**, i.e., values that do not change as frequently as **Features**. They can be of any type and can be used to search for **Things**.
- **Features** are the central modeling concept to capture all run-time data and functionality of a **Thing** in a given application system. Users are allowed to define their own Features or extend existing WoT definitions. This is a key enabler for modeling the multi-dimensional context through more fine-grained **Properties**.

⁴<https://www.w3.org/TR/wot-thing-description/>

- **Properties** are used within Features to model individual run-time indicators of a **Thing**, e.g., to manage the status, the configuration, or any fault information. Each **Property** can be either a simple scalar value or a complex JSON object. By using **Properties**, it is possible to implement the prominent desired-reported pattern widely adopted in DTs, wherein sensor measurements are reported upstream while desired configuration updates are pushed downstream until eventually **Properties** and **DesiredProperties** are in sync. As explained, this is the main mechanism for monitoring the state of the deployed software and managing the deployment.

Figure 10.8: Digital Twin meta-model capturing the multi-dimensional device context (an extension to Eclipse Ditto) [19].

A simplified example of a Digital Twin definition (i.e., a Tellu healthcare gateway) used by the Secure Software Update mechanism is depicted in Figure 10.1. The Digital Twin includes all main elements, including the multi-dimensional features. Note the **properties** and **desired_properties** fields, which are used for twin synchronisation and trigger the update procedure of the outdated **software_component_01**, as explained in more detail in Section 10.2.2.

```

1  "thingId": "no.tellu.rpm:rpm_gateway_01",
2  "policyId": "no.sintef.sct.giot:rpm_policy",
3  "definition": "no.sintef.sct.giot:rpm_gateway:1.0.0",
4  "attributes": {
5      "manufacturer": "RPM Inc.",
6      "cpu_model": "Broadcom BCM2711"
7      "cpu_arch": "arm_v8",
8      "os": {
9          "name": "Raspberry Pi OS 11 (Bullseye)",
10         "kernel_version": "5.15.84"
11     }
12 },
13 "features": {
14     "cyber": {
15         "properties": {
16             "software_component_01": {
17                 "status": "stopped",

```



```

18         "version": "1.0.0"
19     },
20     "docker_engine": {
21         "enabled": true,
22         "version": "containerd.io_1.2.0-1_arm64.deb"
23     }
24 },
25     "desired_properties": {
26         "software_component_01": {
27             "status": "running",
28             "version": "1.0.1"
29         }
30     }
31 },
32     "physical": {...},
33     "social": {...}
34 }
35 }

```

Listing 10.1: A simplified example of a Tellu RPM gateway Digital Twin.

Eclipse Ditto also offers its users the Resource Query Language (RQL) to search for and manage these Digital Twins efficiently. Using RQL's logical operators, we can perform precise assignments of software updates to medical devices based on their Digital Twin data. One-to-one assignment involves updating a specific device by querying its unique ID. For instance, if a critical update is needed for a particular device identified by its ID, RQL allows us to target and update just that device:

```
eq(thingId,"no.sintef.sct.giot:rpm_gateway_01")
```

One-to-many assignment leverages RQL to identify and update multiple devices that meet certain contextual requirements. This might include updating all devices running an outdated software version, devices deployed in a particular location, or devices used by patients with a premium subscription:

```
lt(features/cyber/properties/software_version,"11.0")
```

```
eq(features/physical/properties/location,"hospital")
```

```
eq(features/social/properties/subscription,"premium"))
```

One-to-all assignment involves updating an entire class of devices. By querying devices that share common characteristics, such as model type or firmware version, we can efficiently distribute the update to ensure all relevant devices are up to date:

```
eq(attributes/cpu_arch,"arm_v8")
```

This way, Eclipse Ditto's meta-model and RQL enable accurate and efficient assignment of software updates, enhancing the reliability and security of CMDs.

10.4.1.2 Subfleet Controller and Adapters

We now discuss the actual installation of software updates onto the managed devices. The design emphasises generality and extensibility, ensuring compatibility with diverse device types and allowing effortless introduction of new device categories. Currently, the system supports three different types of high-end CMDs (all based on Tellu's use case on remote patient monitoring):

- **Docker:** This type involves any device equipped with a Docker Engine, hosting a software component as a Docker container.
- **Linux SSH:** This category encompasses devices operating on a Linux operating system with open SSH access, wherein the software components operate as basic shell scripts.
- **Device-specific HTTP API (Axis Camera):** Specifically for Axis cameras,⁵ the software components run as apps within the camera, utilising the camera's REST API for deployment and lifecycle management.

For each of these three, there is an **Adapter**, which oversees the device, handling connection, status checking, basic device info collection related to Secure Software Updates, and the actual installation of the updates. Each device is paired with a single adapter, which can operate on the device itself (provided the device has an independent Internet connection) or externally on another computational unit with a secure connection to the target device. All the adapters inherit from the main abstract *Adapter* class, which defines the basic methods (such as pinging the device, deploying software components, launching the components, etc.), as well as some common utility functions. Once active, all the adapters will regularly ping the devices, report the status to the Digital Twin platform, and subscribe to any possible downstream commands. Whenever there is a software update that requires actions on one of the devices, the adapter will launch the action on the corresponding device through the device-specific APIs and then report the status back to the Digital Twin platform.

We use the adapter for Docker as an example. For devices that support a Docker environment, a software component operates as a Docker container. The essential requirement is for the device to enable the Docker Engine, which provides a REST API for communication. This adapter operates both on the device itself and externally. It utilises the REST API to remotely communicate with the Docker Engine on the device. The device Digital Twin holds key information such as the device's IP and the Docker Engine API port. This information allows the adapter to call the info method of the Docker Engine to retrieve additional metadata about the device, including CPU architecture, OS distribution, and Docker version. This method also serves as a ping operation, ensuring the device is connected.

For installing a software update, the adapter performs several sequential steps. It begins by downloading the Docker image using the URL provided in the device twin. Following this, it invokes the *loadImage* method of the Docker Engine to upload the image package into the device. To start the software, the adapter calls *runContainer*, launching a Docker container from the loaded image. Given that loading an image and initialising a container may be time-consuming, the adapter maintains continuous communication with the Docker Engine.

10.4.1.3 Device-side Monitoring Agents

As previously explained, Monitoring Agents are deployed on CMDs to collect contextual information, which is then sent to the Digital Twin platform. This information includes hardware and software status, environmental conditions, and user interactions, creating a comprehensive overview of each device's state and performance. By providing real-time data, Monitoring Agents close the monitoring loop, enabling continuous oversight and proactive management of the device fleet.

One of the key functionalities of the Monitoring Agents is to track the successful installation and execution of software updates. They verify that updates have been applied correctly and that the updated software operates as intended. This may involve checking for any installation errors, verifying the integrity of the

⁵<https://www.axis.com/products/network-cameras>

installed software, and monitoring the device's performance post-update. By doing so, they will ensure that updates do not disrupt device functionality or compromise patient safety.

Currently, these Monitoring Agents are implemented using Influx Telegraf⁶ and are installed as Docker containers. Influx Telegraf is a highly versatile data collection agent that can gather a wide range of metrics and events from the host devices. Running these agents as Docker containers provides a consistent and isolated environment, simplifying deployment and management across diverse hardware and software configurations.

Looking ahead, the goal is to develop more lightweight Monitoring Agents that can perform the same functions with reduced resource consumption. Future implementations may also rely on the ENTRUST Tracers, which can provide detailed insights into software execution with minimal overhead. These tracers can capture precise execution paths, identify performance bottlenecks, and detect anomalies, further enhancing the monitoring capabilities.

⁶<https://www.influxdata.com/time-series-platform/telegraf/>

Chapter 11

Conclusions

Throughout this deliverable, we have provided detailed descriptions of all the components participating in the Trust Assessment process of ENTRUST, throughout all three operational phases of the ENTRUST framework (Manufacturing (Design) Phase, Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase, Runtime Phase). Specifically, we described the process for the calculation (and recalculation) of the RTL of the device based on the identified types of threats and vulnerabilities, as well as the process for the calculation of the ATL of the device during runtime based on the collection of trustworthiness evidence on the specified set of trust properties. Thus, in the context of ENTRUST, we provide a detailed and comprehensive Trust Assessment methodology that is able to ensure that the trustworthiness of medical devices remains at an acceptable level throughout their operational lifecycle.

Component	Research Roadmap and Next Steps
Threat Modeling and Software Verification	<p>Regarding the Software Verification component, in this deliverable, we identified the methodologies for the use of the AFL for the identification of bugs and vulnerabilities on the software components installed on the CMDs of a medical organization. However, the identification and the definition of the actual fuzzing test cases, as well as the evaluation of the Software Verification component in the context of the use cases will be performed during the second release. This essentially entails the establishment of the appropriate fuzzing test cases for a subset of the software running on the entities belonging to the infrastructure of each use case demonstrator. Thus, we aim to perform an evaluation and benchmarking of the AFL method against emulated attack vectors, particularly related to memory-related vulnerabilities which we are able to hardcode and introduce into a binary.</p> <p>With regard to the Threat Modeling component, we aim to investigate the possible use of LLMs in order to identify the narrative for the generation of attack scenarios, based on which attack vectors will be created.</p>
Formal Verification	<p>In this deliverable, We outlined the envisaged roadmap that aims at modeling and verifying the most important ENTRUST protocols and crypto schemes. The current focus is on capturing the overall flow of events among the protocol participants while abstracting from their internal implementations. The latter will be addressed in a follow up step.</p> <p>The next steps include refining the current models to include internal details of the participating components, modeling other critical ENTRUST protocols, addressing more challenging security properties such as anonymity and working towards a tool-neutral domain specific language for expressing security protocols and their properties accompanied with automatic and transparent generation of tool-specific representations.</p>

<p>Digital Twin</p>	<p>As we continue to develop the ENTRUST Digital Twin infrastructure, several critical research challenges remain at the forefront of our efforts. These challenges are integral to realizing the full potential of the digital twin in enhancing the security framework for connected medical devices. Here, we outline these challenges and the specific research questions we still need to address:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simulation of Cyber Attacks on Connected Medical Devices: One of the primary research endeavors involves determining the types of cyber-attacks that are both relevant and feasible to simulate within the context of connected medical devices. This involves a comprehensive analysis of potential threats specific to medical devices, including but not limited to, network-based attacks, data integrity attacks, and denial-of-service attacks. Understanding the nature of these attacks will guide the development of simulation models that effectively emulate potential security breaches in a controlled environment. • Integration of Fuzz Testing in Attack Simulation: Related to the simulation of attacks is the exploration of integrating fuzz testing techniques into our attack simulation protocols. Fuzz testing, a method traditionally used in software testing to discover coding errors and security loopholes, is being considered for its applicability in this broader context. The challenge lies in adapting fuzz testing methods developed under the "Software Verification and Threat Modelling" component of ENTRUST to suit the specific requirements and constraints of medical device simulations. • Architectural Formation of the Digital Twin: A significant aspect of our research revolves around the conceptualization and architecture of the digital twin itself. The question here is whether to construct individual digital twins for each medical device and then aggregate these into a cohesive system model based on their connectivity topology. This approach raises complex questions about the granularity of simulation and the interactions between individual device twins, particularly how to effectively simulate network-wide attacks within such an aggregated model. • Enhancement of Anomaly Detection Technique: Currently, our anomaly detection is based on an unsupervised learning technique applied to numerical data in time series (see Section 9.3), effective for monitoring variables like temperature, energy usage, and network load. However, the need to extend this methodology to handle categorical data such as event logs presents a challenge. Categorical data, which often includes non-numeric, discrete values, requires different analytical approaches to identify patterns and anomalies effectively. Enhancing our anomaly detection capabilities to address this type of data is a research question we will investigate in the context of analyzing and monitoring system logs and activities. • Prioritization and Impact on Monitoring Accuracy: In the ENTRUST project, while extensive data monitoring is essential, doing so continuously can affect device performance. To mitigate this, we can prioritize monitoring: trust-related data is collected asynchronously during trust state changes, while performance metrics are gathered when resources allow. This approach ensures critical security monitoring without overwhelming the devices but may result in gaps in performance data and missed subtle anomalies. In the rest of the project, we will investigate strategies for optimal data collection times and enhanced triggers for trust state changes for the balance between monitoring accuracy and operational efficiency. <p>As we progress with implementing the overall vision of the ENTRUST Digital Twin in the second part of the project, we will investigate the extent to which we can address the aforementioned research challenges. This exploration will focus on methodologies and technologies that enhance the effectiveness and reliability of the digital twin as a critical tool for securing connected medical devices.</p>
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<p>Secure Software Update</p>	<p>Currently, our focus has been on high-end CMDs that are immediately connected to the Internet and capable of directly receiving Secure Software Updates. However, to ensure comprehensive coverage and security across all devices as envisioned by ENTRUST, our future research roadmap will include exploring solutions for low-end devices that are not immediately connected to the Internet. These low-end devices often lack the computational power and connectivity features of their high-end counterparts, presenting additional challenges for Secure Software Updates.</p> <p>One promising solution is leveraging high-end devices as proxies for low-end devices. In this scenario, high-end devices, which are already connected to the Internet, will act as intermediaries. They will receive Secure Software Updates and then relay these updates to the low-end devices. This approach necessitates a robust communication protocol between high-end and low-end devices for secure and efficient update delivery.</p> <p>Implementing high-end devices as proxies will require thorough redesign of the Digital Twins. The Digital Twin models must reflect a systems-of-systems approach [62], where low-end devices are modeled as integral components of high-end devices. This hierarchical systems-of-systems approach ensures that the Digital Twin platform maintains an up-to-date and comprehensive view of both high-end and low-end devices. This holistic view is critical for planning and executing Secure Software Updates, monitoring device health, and ensuring compliance with security protocols.</p> <p>Adopting this proxy-based update mechanism will necessitate revisiting several steps in the secure software update lifecycle as defined by the TCG. Specifically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation: The update packages must be prepared to accommodate the proxy relay mechanism. This includes ensuring compatibility with both high-end and low-end device architectures and providing secure communication protocols. • Distribution: The distribution strategy must be adapted to account for the two-step process: first delivering updates to high-end devices and then relaying them to low-end devices. This might involve additional security measures to protect the integrity of updates during the relay process. • Verification and Installation: The verification process must now include an additional layer where high-end devices verify updates before relaying them to low-end devices. Both local and remote attestation mechanisms must be adapted to ensure that the updates remain secure throughout the entire relay process. • Monitoring and Maintenance: Continuous monitoring must be extended to include both high-end and low-end devices. Monitoring Agents on high-end devices will also need to track the status of connected low-end devices, ensuring that updates are successfully installed and operational. <p>In addition to supporting low-end devices, future research will also explore other use case scenarios in ENTRUST, such as supporting different types of CMDs and environments. This involves developing device- or platform-specific adapters to ensure compatibility and security across a diverse range of devices. Device-specific adapters will cater to the unique requirements of different hardware and software environments, enabling secure updates for devices with varying capabilities and constraints. This modular approach will contribute to flexibility and scalability, allowing the Secure Software Update mechanism to be tailored to the specific needs of each CMD type.</p> <p>Finally, in future deliverables, we will provide a comprehensive alignment of the software distribution and update enforcement process with the ENTRUST TCB, highlighting how the ENTRUST TCB can support the software update process as part of the overall ENTRUST architecture.</p>
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<p>Risk Assessment</p>	<p>In the first release of the ENTRUST risk assessment engine we focus on the execution of risk assessment processes in their entirety. This involves from maintaining an up-to-date knowledge base, but also ensuring the risk management and quantification. Moving from the standalone implementation, the plan is to finalize the integration with other ENTRUST tools, namely the Threat Modeling and the AI-based Anomaly Detection in the Digital Twin. Release B provides new enhancements in the risk assessment methodology. Through the support of the latest CVSS v4.0 methodology, the ENTRUST RA Engine shall be able to determine the impact of the identified vulnerabilities based on the up-to-date best practices. In parallel, enhancements will be explored in the area of the attack path calculation methodologies. Finally, a key enabler in the context of the ENTRUST Trust Assessment Framework is to carry out the realization of the Required Trust Level (RTL) based on the risk results.</p>
<p>Trust Assessment Framework</p>	<p>In Chapter 8, we provided a detailed description of the Trust Models to be used in order to perform the Trust Assessment process in the context of all envisioned use cases. In the second release, we aim to perform the instantiation of these Trust Models in the actual TAF. We also aim to perform the connection of the TAF with the attestation enablers described in D4.2 [27], as well as the documentation and implementation of the interfaces for the connection of the TAF with the other components of the ENTRUST Framework.</p> <p>Also, in this deliverable, we presented the design of a Standalone TAF, meaning a TAF component running in the backend infrastructure, outside of the devices themselves. During the next reporting period, we will consider the expansion of the Standalone TAF to a Federated TAF from a research perspective. Essentially, we aim to investigate whether it is meaningful to add TAF modules to the high-end devices themselves, and if it may be beneficial to do so in terms of performance.</p>

Table 11.1: Research roadmap and next steps for components presented in this deliverable.

With regard to the **Formal Verification** component, we provided a detailed description of the action workflow followed for the verification process. This essentially consists of two core phases, (i) the **modeling of the interactions** among the participating entities by following a black-box approach through the simplification and representation of their internal functions, and (ii) the **full modeling of the internal components** following a white-box approach. We also provided details on the verification of the **Device Authentication and Credential Issuance** process of ENTRUST, while setting the scene for the formal verification of all other security processes of ENTRUST. Specifically, we discussed the models of the device authentication and credential issuance protocol and the first step in the device onboarding: the delegated authentication mechanism following the EAP-PSK standard. These protocols are modeled in two state-of-the-art security protocol verifiers: ProVerif and Tamarin. All formulated security properties (secrecy of keys and authentication) are verified successfully within a few seconds.

With regard to the **Threat Modeling and Software Verification** component of ENTRUST, we detailed the motivation behind the usage of LLMs for processing the identified threats towards the generation of unified and efficiently organized attack vectors. We also provided detailed action workflows for the Threat Modeling and Software Verification processes, as well as their interaction with other components of ENTRUST, namely the **Digital Twin** and the **Risk Assessment** process. With regard to the latter, we described in detail the mathematical methodology for the calculation of the risk level affecting a device, both in isolation and considering interdependencies with other components of ENTRUST, and we detailed the methodology for the calculation of the RTL of the device based on the threat landscape identified by the Threat Modeling component. We also described the construction of device-level and domain-level eMUDs, which are used for the mapping of identified threats with the appropriate mitigation measures. We also provide a comprehensive list of the fields included in each type of eMUD, as well as example implementations of those eMUDs.

We then provide a comprehensive description of the **Trust Assessment Framework (TAF)** of ENTRUST, as well as its role in the extraction of a decision on whether a device can be considered trusted or not.

Specifically, we listed the set of **trust properties** based on which the trustworthiness of a device can be assessed, and we provided a detailed description of the Trust Assessment methodology based on **Subjective Logic**. Then, we described all internal components of the TAF in detail and positioned them within the Trust Assessment action workflow, including the management of Trust Models by the TMM, the management of trust sources by the TSS, the execution of the actual Trust Assessment logic by the TLEE, and the final decision by the TDE. We also constructed the **Trust Models for each of the envisioned use case demonstrators of ENTRUST**, which provide the basis for the application of the entire ENTRUST workflow within each use case infrastructure.

Next, we focused on the description of the emulation process for potential attacks by the **Digital Twin** component. We provided a detailed description of the internal architecture of the Digital Twin, including all internal components and interfaces, as well as the available APIs for interfacing between internal components, or between the Digital Twin and external entities. Then, we provided a detailed description of the emulation process through. Next, we focused on the **Unsupervised Learning System for Anomaly Detection** system of ENTRUST, which leverages statistical feature analysis and Machine Learning methodologies in order to identify deviations from known and established behaviors, thus adding a layer of security and intelligence to the Digital Twin infrastructure. Finally, we described in detail the **Secure Software Update** component, which operates through the Digital Twin and is capable of deploying secure updates to devices in order to address identified vulnerabilities. We also outlined the various possible approaches that can be followed regarding the action workflow of the update process (one-to-one, one-to-many, one-to-all).

From all the above, it follows that we have provided a complete set of tools, methodologies, and components, which are able to operate in tandem throughout the operational lifecycle of a medical device in order to ensure that it is in a trustworthy state. This process is **dynamic**, meaning that it is able to detect, identify, and mitigate threats and vulnerabilities in real-time, while continuously updating the instantiations of the utilized models in order to address the ever-changing threat landscape. In Table 11.1, we provide detailed research roadmaps for the components presented in the context of this deliverable, including plans for future work.

Appendix A

Glossary

(Medical) Domain Refers to the entirety of the infrastructure of the medical organization where a CMD is deployed, including the backend infrastructure (servers), medical devices operating within the organization, and interconnectivity between all aforementioned entities.

AI-based Intrusion/Misbehavior Detection This component applies AI-based methods on the emulation performed on the Digital Twin, as well as information collected during the runtime of the operation of the device using probes, in order to determine whether the behavior of the device deviates from the normal behavior of the device.

ATL The Actual Trust Level (ATL) reflects the result of an evaluation of a trust proposition, for a specific CMD, as defined in a trust model managed by the ENTRUST TAF. It quantifies the extent to which a certain node or data can be considered trustworthy based on the available evidence.

Attestation Agent The component of the CMD which is responsible for the execution of the attestation logic of an attestation enabler, as well as communicating with external entities in order to share attestation-related information.

Authentication The process which aims to verify the authenticity of a device, prior to its Onboarding and Enrolment into the (Medical) Domain. This process is performed by the Authentication Server of the Manufacturing domain through the Domain Manager, using the Root ID Key of the device.

Authentication Server The Authentication Server is responsible for authenticating the device using its Root ID Key, in order to enable its enrolment and onboarding into the (Medical) Domain.

CMD A medical device that has been deployed, enrolled, and onboarded into a (Medical) Domain. Note that this term cannot be used during the Manufacturing (Design) Phase of the ENTRUST action workflow, since this phase considers the device in isolation, and can only be applied during the Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase and the Runtime Phase of the ENTRUST action workflow.

Conformity Certificate A certificate which is created after a successful attestation process on a device and is stored on the ledger, so that an external entity is able to audit the correctness of the attested set of attributes of the device. The Conformity Certificate utilizes Privacy Attribute-Based Credentials (PABCs) in order to share those attributes in a privacy-preserving manner.

Device Tracer The capabilities of the device (e.g., eBPFs) to collect types of trust evidence or attestation evidence specified by the Trust Policy of the device in order to prove the correctness of the required trust attributes of the device.

Device-level MUD Defines the foundational security requirements of a device, outlining the necessary operational characteristics to mitigate threats and vulnerabilities, considering the device in isolation (i.e., before it is deployed to the actual medical domain).

Digital Twin The Digital Twin refers to a digital representation of a device, which is used in order to perform an emulation of the identified types of attacks and can provide the basis for the detection of deviations from the known and expected behavior of the device. It may also be used in the context of secure software updates, where an up-to-date contextual information of a device is required to perform the targeted assignment of software updates.

Domain Manager The Domain Manager is a centralized server deployed at the infrastructure level of a (Medical) Domain, responsible for the Authentication, Enrolment, and Onboarding of medical devices into the domain. It also acts as an orchestrator for the operation of all ENTRUST components between the medical domain, as well as the mediator between the device, the Blockchain infrastructure, and the MUD Server.

Domain-level eMUD Extends the Device-level MUD in order to include device characteristics, threats, and vulnerabilities that considering its positioning within the medical domain, and specifies security enablers for mitigating domain-level threats and vulnerabilities.

Enrolment Entails the issuance of the set of Verifiable Credentials (VCs) of a device through the Privacy CA, after it has been successfully authenticated.

Formal Verification The Formal Verification component is the component of the ENTRUST framework which is responsible for checking whether the design of the device satisfies the security requirements identified for the particular device, by specifying and using models of the critical security protocols and schemes of ENTRUST and checking whether the security properties hold for the specific model.

Key Restriction Usage Policy A local attestation policy dictating that a specific cryptographic key cannot be used by a device, unless it is known to be in a correct and trustworthy state, based on the characteristics contained in the Policy Hash of the device.

LLM In the context of ENTRUST, this refers to a model used by the Threat Modeling component in order to create attack scenarios in natural language to set forth expectations regarding what types of attacks could occur in a specific infrastructure.

Manufacturing (Design) Phase The Manufacturing phase of the ENTRUST framework includes all actions taken from the construction of the actual device until it leaves the manufacturing domain and is deployed to the medical domain where it will be enrolled and onboarded. This phase includes the identification of threats and vulnerabilities by the Manufacturer and the Threat Modeling component, the Formal Verification of the source code and binaries on the device, the emulation of identified threats using the Digital Twin of the device, and an initial Risk Assessment of the device in isolation (i.e., before it is actually deployed to the medical domain).

MUD Server The MUD Server is responsible for the storage of the Device-level MUD and the Domain-level eMUD of the CMDs. They can be retrieved based on the MUD URL provided by the Manufacturer and contained within the device, so that the specified security controls can be applied by the device.

Onboarding Entails the integration of a medical device into the (Medical) Domain, after its successful Authentication and Enrolment. In this context, the device needs to provide a Verifiable Presentation (VP) to the Domain Manager containing the set of attributes that the device needs to verifiably prove ownership of in order to be enrolled into the domain.

Policy Hash Values that can be used in order to verify the operational correctness of the device based on specific characteristics of the device (e.g., secure boot output, type of Secure Element, TCB specification).

Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) Phase The Pre-deployment (Domain-specific) phase of the ENTRUST framework includes the actions taken from the moment the device is deployed from the Manufacturer to the medical domain, until it begins its actual operation in the context of the domain. It includes two core phases: (i) The device authentication, enrolment, and onboarding, and (ii) the re-evaluation of the recalculation of the RTL of the device based on domain-specific threats and vulnerabilities identified by the System Administrator, the Threat Modeling, the Digital Twin, and the Formal Verification component.

Privacy CA The entity responsible for the issuance of the Verifiable Credentials (VCs) of the CMD containing the device attributes or characteristics based on which Trust Assessment is performed, after it has been successfully authenticated through the Authentication Server.

Protection Profile The Protection Profile of the device is the part of the Device-level MUD or Domain-level eMUD which contains the identified threats and vulnerabilities for the device, as well as the mitigation measures which can be employed for their mitigation during runtime.

Remote Attestation A secure mechanism where a Verifier entity aims to verify the correctness of one or more attributes of a Prover device (e.g., configuration integrity or control flow). This is typically performed by the Verifier issuing an attestation challenge to the Prover, who needs to collect the appropriate data as attestation evidence (using its Device Tracer) and construct the appropriate response in order to prove the correctness of the specified attributes.

Risk Assessment The Risk Assessment component of ENTRUST is responsible for performing risk quantification on the device based on all the identified threats and vulnerabilities, both at the manufacturing domain considering the device in isolation, and at the medical domain considering the interdependencies of the device with other entities of the service graph chain. It is also responsible for the calculation of the RTL of the device based on the identified threats and vulnerabilities, as well as its recalculation in case new threats or zero-day exploits are detected during runtime.

RoT The (Hardware) Root of Trust (RoT) is the minimal set of security guarantees usually provided by the hardware that is sufficient to guarantee the security of a larger TCB.

RTL The RTL reflects the amount of trustworthiness a device considers required in order to characterize it as trusted, based on the identified threats and vulnerabilities for the particular type of device.

Runtime Phase The Runtime phase includes all actions in order to ensure the trustworthiness of the CMD during runtime. This entails the execution of security controls, such as Remote Attestation schemes and the runtime calculation of the ATL of the CMD. In case $ATL < RTL$, the device is determined to be in an untrustworthy state and additional mitigation measures may need to be applied, such as the deployment of a Secure Software Update.

Secure Software Update This process refers to the secure deployment of a software or firmware patch through the Digital Twin of the device, in case a vulnerability has been detected and needs to be addressed.

Software Verification The Software Verification component is responsible for checking the safety of software applications running on the medical device, as well as libraries running on the device, using Indices of Compromise from multiple intelligence sources based on the identified threat landscape.

System Administrator The person or entity who has in-depth knowledge of the (Medical) Domain and its specific requirements, is responsible for providing information on domain-specific threats and vulnerabilities to the Risk Assessment component, and is able to re-assess the risks identified by the ENTRUST component and the mitigation measures required in order to address them.

TAF A software framework which, given a trust model for a specific function running inside a CMD, is able to evaluate trust sources for trustworthiness evidence, as well as evaluate propositions within the trust model to obtain their ATLS. An RTL can also be evaluated and trust decisions can be taken and communicated to the application.

TCB The Trusted Computing Base (TCB) of a computer system is the set of all hardware, firmware, and/or software components that are critical to its security, in the sense that bugs or vulnerabilities occurring inside the TCB might jeopardize the security properties of the entire system. By contrast, parts of a computer system that lie outside the TCB must not be able to misbehave in a way that would leak any more privileges than are granted to them in accordance to the system’s security policy.

Threat Intelligence Database A common database which contains the threats and vulnerabilities identified for a medical device by the ENTRUST framework, and can be accessed by other device manufacturers as threat intelligence knowledge towards increasing the security posture of devices operating within the medical domain.

Threat Modeling The Threat Modeling component is responsible for identifying known threats and vulnerabilities for a specific type of device based on existing threat intelligence databases, and aggregating them into an attack vector using an Large Language Model (LLM).

Trust Policy A smart contract deployed to the private ledger, which specifies the RTL of the device, as well as the types of trust evidence that needs to be collected in order to verify the correctness of the trust attributes of the device.

Appendix B

Formal Verification Models

B.1 Device Authentication and Verifiable Credential Issuance

B.1.1 ProVerif Model

```
1 type skey.
2 type pkey.
3 type attribute.
4
5 free c1: channel.
6 free c2: channel.
7 free sk_R: skey [private].
8
9 (* Function for creating a HMAC using a secret key and a message *)
10 fun hmac(bitstring, skey): bitstring.
11 (* Function for deriving a public key from a given secret key *)
12 fun pk(skey): pkey.
13
14 (* Function for signing a message with a secret key *)
15 fun sign(bitstring, skey): bitstring.
16
17 (* Function for converting a variable of type attribute to bitstring
18 *)
19 fun attributeToBitstring(attribute): bitstring.
20
21 (* Function for computing the attribute key *)
22 fun kdf(bitstring, skey): bitstring.
23
24 (* Reduction rule that the original message can be recovered from its
25 signature *)
26 reduc forall m: bitstring, sk: skey; getmess(sign(m, sk)) = m.
27 (* Reduction rule that a signature can be verified with the
28 corresponding
29 public key *)
30 reduc forall m: bitstring, sk: skey; checksign(sign(m, sk), pk(sk)) =
31 m.
```



```

29 (* Reduction rule that a signature can be verified with the
    corresponding
30 public key *)
31 reduc forall m: bitstring, sk: skey; checksignhmac(hmac(m, sk), sk) =
    m.
32
33 (* Verify the secrecy of the variables *)
34 query secret sk_R.
35 query secret sk_VC.
36 query secret sk_CA.
37 query secret sk_M.
38
39 (* Verify the attacker cannot compute keys using from free names *)
40 query attacker(sk_R).
41
42 event beginAuth(bitstring).
43 event endAuth(bitstring).
44 event beginChallengeCA(bitstring).
45 event endChallengeCA(bitstring).
46 event check_reachability().
47
48 (* Query that the endAuth event follows the beginAuth event *)
49 query x: bitstring; inj-event(endAuth(x)) ==> inj-event(beginAuth(x)).
50 query x: bitstring; inj-event(endChallengeCA(x)) ==> inj-event(
    beginChallengeCA(x)).
51 query event(check_reachability()).
52
53 let processDevice(sk_R: skey, pk_CA: pkey) =
54     new a_i: attribute;
55     (* Step 1 *)
56     out(c1, a_i);
57     (* Step 2 *)
58     in(c1, c: bitstring);
59     new sk_VC: skey;
60     let pk_VC = pk(sk_VC) in
61     (* Step 3*)
62     out(c2, (c, pk_VC));
63     (* Step 4 *)
64     in(c2, c': bitstring);
65     event beginAuth(c');
66     let sig_R_D = hmac((c, c'), sk_R) in
67     let sig_VC_D = sign((c, c'), sk_VC) in
68     (* Step 5 *)
69     out(c2, (sig_R_D, sig_VC_D));
70     (* Step 6 *)
71     in(c2, sig_M: bitstring);
72     (* Step 7 *)
73     out(c1, sig_M);
74     (* Step 8 *)
75     in(c1, a_i_selected: attribute);

```



```

76 let sign_a_i = sign(attributeToBitstring(a_i_selected), sk_VC) in
77 (* Step 9 *)
78 out (c1, (sign_a_i));
79 (* Step 10 *)
80 in(c1, attr_key_signed: bitstring);
81 (* Verify the signature *)
82 let (attr_key: bitstring, =pk_CA) = checksign(attr_key_signed,
83 pk_CA) in
84 event check_reachability().
85
86 let processCA(sk_CA: skey, pk_CA: pkey, pk_M: pkey) =
87 (* Step 1 *)
88 in(c1, a_i: attribute);
89 new c: bitstring;
90 event beginChallengeCA(c);
91 (* Step 2 *)
92 out(c1, c);
93 (* Step 7 *)
94 in(c1, sig_M: bitstring);
95 let ((=c, pk_VC: pkey)) = checksign(sig_M, pk_M) in
96 (* Step 8 *)
97 out(c1, a_i);
98 (* Step 9 *)
99 in(c1, sign_a_i: bitstring);
100 let (=attributeToBitstring(a_i)) = checksign(sign_a_i, pk_VC) in
101 let attr_key = kdf(attributeToBitstring(a_i), sk_CA) in
102 (* Replace this with kdf *)
103 let attr_key_signed = sign((attr_key, pk(sk_CA)), sk_CA) in
104 (* sign attribute key with sk_CA *)
105 event endChallengeCA(c);
106 (* Step 10 *)
107 out(c1, attr_key_signed).
108
109 (* pk_M is not used here *)
110 let processManufacturer(sk_M: skey, pk_M: pkey, sk_R: skey) =
111 (* Step 3 *)
112 in(c2, (c: bitstring, pk_VC: pkey));
113 new c': bitstring;
114 (* Step 4 *)
115 out(c2, c');
116 (* Step 5 *)
117 in(c2, (sig_R_D: bitstring, sig_VC_D: bitstring));
118 (* Verify signature sig_R_D with sk_R *)
119 let ((=c, =c')) = checksignhmac(sig_R_D, sk_R) in
120 (* Verify signature sig_VC_D with pk_VC *)
121 let ((=c, =c')) = checksign(sig_VC_D, pk_VC) in
122 event endAuth(c');
123 (* Sign the message with sk_M *)
124 let sig_M = sign((c, pk_VC), sk_M) in

```



```

125   (* Step 6 *)
126   out(c2, sig_M).
127
128 process
129 new sk_CA: skey;
130 new pk_CA: pkey;
131 new sk_M: skey;
132
133 (!processDevice(sk_R, pk(sk_CA)))
134 | (!processCA(sk_CA, pk_CA, pk(sk_M)))
135 | (!processManufacturer(sk_M, pk(sk_M), sk_R))

```

Listing B.1: Verifiable Credential Issuance - ProVerif Model

B.1.2 ProVerif Model - EAP-PSK

```

1
2 type key.
3 type nonce.
4 type mac.
5 type id.
6 type message.
7
8 free c1: channel.
9 free c2: channel.
10
11 (* Cryptographic primitives *)
12 fun nonce_to_bitstring(nonce): bitstring [data,typeConverter].
13 fun key_to_bitstring(key): bitstring [data,typeConverter].
14 fun MAC(bitstring, key): mac.
15
16 (* Encryption *)
17 fun senc(bitstring,key): bitstring.
18 reduc forall x:bitstring,y:key; sdec(senc(x,y),y) = x.
19
20 (* Hash function *)
21 fun h(bitstring, key): key.
22
23 free msk_aaa: key [private].
24 free eap_session_key_cmd: key [private].
25 free eap_session_key_aaa: key [private].
26
27 (* Verify the attacker cannot compute keys using from free names *)
28 query attacker(msk_aaa).
29 query attacker(eap_session_key_cmd).
30 query attacker(eap_session_key_aaa).
31
32 (* Verify the secrecy of the variables *)
33 query secret msk_aaa.

```



```

34 query secret eap_session_key_cmd.
35 query secret eap_session_key_aaa.
36 query secret kdk.
37 query secret ak.
38 query secret k.
39
40 event beginAuthAaa(mac).
41 event endAuthAaa(mac).
42 event beginAuthCmd(mac).
43 event endAuthCmd(mac).
44
45 event beginMskProvisioning(bitstring).
46 event endMskProvisioning(bitstring).
47
48 (* Authenticate AAA to CMD using MAC_P*)
49 query x: mac; inj-event(endAuthAaa(x)) ==> inj-event(beginAuthAaa(x)).
50 (* Authenticate CMD to AAA using MAC_S *)
51 query x: mac; inj-event(endAuthCmd(x)) ==> inj-event(beginAuthCmd(x)).
52 (* For every decrypted MSK key by the DM there is a provisioning phase
    for the MSK *)
53 query x: bitstring; event(endMskProvisioning(x)) ==> event(
    beginMskProvisioning(x)).
54
55
56 let processDM(k: key) =
57     (*Step 5*)
58     in(c1, (id_s: id, rand_s: nonce));
59     (*Step 6*)
60     out(c2, (id_s, rand_s));
61     (*Step 7*)
62     in(c2, (rand_p: nonce, id_p: id, mac_p: mac));
63     (*Step 8*)
64     out(c1, (rand_p, id_p, mac_p));
65     (*Step 9*)
66     in(c1, (mac_s: mac, m: message, tag1: bitstring));
67     (*Step 10*)
68     out(c2, (mac_s, m, tag1));
69     (*Step 11*)
70     in(c2, (m1: message, tag2: bitstring));
71     (*Step 12*)
72     out(c1, (m1, tag2));
73     (*Step 13*)
74     in(c1, msk_enc: bitstring);
75     (* Decrypt MSK *)
76     let(msk: bitstring) = sdec(msk_enc, k) in
77     event endMskProvisioning(msk);
78     0.
79
80 let procesAAA(id_s: id, kdk: key, ak: key, k: key) =
81     new rand_s: nonce;

```



```

82  (*Step 5*)
83  out (c1, (id_s, rand_s));
84  (*Step 8*)
85  in(c1, (id_p: id, rand_p: nonce, mac_p: mac));
86  (* Verify MAC_P *)
87  if mac_p = MAC((id_p, rand_p, id_s, rand_s), ak) then
88  (
89      event endAuthCmd(mac_p);
90      (* Derive MSK and transient key for the protected channel *)
91      let msk_aaa = h(nonce_to_bitstring(rand_p), kdk) in
92      let eap_session_key_aaa = h(nonce_to_bitstring(rand_p), kdk)
93          in
94          (* Compute MAC_S *)
95          let mac_s = MAC((id_s, rand_p), ak) in
96          event beginAuthAaa(mac_s);
97          (* Protected channel tag *)
98          new m: message;
99          let tag1 = MAC((m, rand_s), eap_session_key_aaa) in
100         (*Step 9*)
101         out(c1, (mac_s, m, tag1));
102         (*Step 12*)
103         in(c1, (m1: message, tag2: mac));
104         (* Verify tag *)
105         if tag2 = MAC((m1, rand_s), eap_session_key_aaa) then
106             let msk_aaa_bitstring = key_to_bitstring(msk_aaa) in
107             event beginMskProvisioning(msk_aaa_bitstring);
108             (* Encrypt MSK *)
109             let msk_enc = senc(msk_aaa_bitstring, k) in
110             (*Step 13*)
111             out(c1, msk_enc)
112         )
113     else 0.
114 let processCMD(id_p: id, kdk: key, ak: key) =
115     (*Step 6*)
116     in(c2, (id_s: id, rand_s: nonce));
117     new rand_p: nonce;
118     (* Compute MAC_P *)
119     let mac_p = MAC((id_p, rand_p, id_s, rand_s), ak) in
120     event beginAuthCmd(mac_p);
121     (*Step 7*)
122     out(c2, (rand_p, id_p, mac_p));
123     (*Step 10*)
124     in(c2, (mac_s: mac, m: message, tag1: mac));
125     (* Verify MAC_S *)
126     if mac_s = MAC((id_s, rand_p), ak) then
127     (
128         event endAuthAaa(mac_s);
129         (* Derive MSK and transient key for the protected channel *)
130         let msk_cmd = h(nonce_to_bitstring(rand_p), kdk) in

```



```

131     let eap_session_key_cmd = h(nonce_to_bitstring(rand_p), kdk)
132         in
133     (* Verify tag *)
134     if(tag1 = MAC((m, rand_s), eap_session_key_cmd)) then
135     (
136         (* Protected Channel *)
137         new m1: message;
138         let tag2 = MAC((m1, rand_s), eap_session_key_cmd) in
139         (*Step 11*)
140         out(c2, (m1, tag2))
141     )
142     else 0
143 )
144 else 0.
145 process
146 new id_s: id;
147 new id_p: id;
148 new kdk: key;
149 new ak: key;
150 new k: key;
151
152 (!processDM(k)) | (!procesAAA(id_s, kdk, ak, k)) | (!processCMD(id_p,
    kdk, ak))

```

Listing B.2: EAP-PSK - ProVerif Model

B.1.3 Tamarin Model

```

1 theory VCI
2 begin
3
4 builtins: symmetric-encryption, signing
5 functions: hmac/2, vc/1, kdf/2
6
7 //pre-shared keys infra
8 rule Register_psk:
9     [Fr(~skr)]
10 -->
11     [!Psk_skr('d', 'm', ~skr)]
12
13 //public keys infra
14 rule Register_pk:
15     [Fr(~skCA)]
16 -->
17     [!Ltk('ca', ~skCA), !Pk('ca', pk(~skCA)), Out(pk(~skCA))]
18
19 rule Register_pk1:
20     [Fr(~skM)]

```



```

21 -->
22   [!Ltk('m', ~skM), !Pk('m', pk(~skM)), Out(pk(~skM))]
23
24 //step1
25 rule D_1:
26   [Fr(~a)]
27 -->
28   [Out(<'ca', ~a>), D_1(~a)]
29
30 //step2
31 rule CA_1:
32   [In(<'ca', a>), Fr(~c)]
33 -->
34   [Out(<'d', ~c>), CA_1(a, ~c)]
35
36 //step3
37 rule D_2:
38   [In(<'d', c>), D_1(a), Fr(~skVC)]
39 -->
40   [!Ltk('d', ~skVC), !Pk('d', pk(~skVC)), Out(<'m', c, pk(~skVC)>),
41     D_2(a, c)]
42
43 //step4
44 rule M_1:
45   [In(<'m', c, pkVC>), Fr(~c1)]
46 -->
47   [Out(<'d', ~c1>), M_1(c, pkVC, ~c1)]
48
49 //step5
50 rule D_3:
51   [In(<'d', c1>), D_2(a, c), !Psk_skr('d', 'm', skr), !Ltk('d', skVC)]
52 --[Initiate('d', 'm', <c, c1>)]->
53   [Out(<'m', hmac(<c, c1>, skr), sign(<c, c1>, skVC)>), D_3(a, c, c1)]
54
55 //step6
56 rule M_2:
57   [In(<'m', hmac(<c, c1>, skr), sig>), M_1(c, pkVC, c1), !Psk_skr('d',
58     'm', skr), !Ltk('m', skM)]
59 --[Eq(verify(sig, <c, c1>, pkVC), true), Auth('d', 'm', <c, c1>),
60   Initiate_M('m', 'ca', <c, pkVC>)]->
61   [Out(<'d', sign(<c, pkVC>, skM)>)]
62
63 //step7
64 rule D_4:
65   [In(<'d', sig>), D_3(a, c, c1), !Pk('d', pkVC)]
66 -->
67   [Out(<'ca', sig, pkVC>), D_4(a, c, c1)]
68
69 //step8
70 rule CA_2:

```



```

68 [In(<'ca', sig, pkVC>), CA_1(a, c), !Pk('m', pkM)]
69 --[Eq(verify(sig, <c, pkVC>, pkM), true), Auth_M('m', 'ca', <c, pkVC>
70 ]->
71 [Out(<'d', vc(a)>), CA_2(a, vc(a), pkVC)]
72
73 //step9
74 rule D_5:
75 [In(<'d', vca>), D_4(a, c, c1), !Ltk('d', skVC)]
76 -->
77 [Out(<'ca', sign(a, skVC)>), D_5(a, vca)]
78
79 //step10
80 rule CA_3:
81 [In(<'ca', sig>), CA_2(a, vc, pkVC), !Ltk('ca', skCA)]
82 --[Eq(verify(sig, a, pkVC), true)]->
83 [Out(<'d', kdf(a, skCA), sign(kdf(a, skCA), skCA)>), CA_3(a, vc,
84 pkVC, kdf(a, skCA))]
85
86 //step11
87 rule D_6:
88 [In(<'d', ak, sig>), !Psk_skr('d', 'm', skr), !Pk('ca', pkCA)]
89 --[Eq(verify(sig, ak, pkCA), true), Success(skr)]->
90 []
91
92 restriction Equality:
93 'All x y #i. Eq(x, y) @#i ==> x = y'
94
95 lemma shared_key_secret: // shared secret between device and
96 manufacturer is not revealed during protocol execution
97 'not(Ex k #i #j. Success(k) @ #i & K(k) @ #j)'
98
99 lemma device_auth: // device is authenticated by the manufacturer
100 '(All d m data #i. Auth(d, m, data) @ #i ==> (Ex #j. Initiate(d, m,
101 data) @ #j & (#j < #i)))'
102
103 lemma man_auth: // manufacturer is authenticated by the ca
104 '(All m ca data #i. Auth_M(m, ca, data) @ #i ==> (Ex #j. Initiate_M(m,
105 ca, data) @ #j & (#j < #i)))'
106
107 lemma honest: // the protocol can run to the end
108 exists-trace 'Ex k #i. Success(k) @ #i'
109
110 end

```

Listing B.3: Verifiable Credential Issuance - Tamarin Model

B.2 Device Onboarding - Device Authentication with EAP-PSK

B.2.1 Tamarin Model

```

1 theory Onboarding
2 begin
3
4 builtins: symmetric-encryption
5 functions: mac/2, hkdf1/2, hkdf2/2
6
7 //pre-shared keys infra
8 rule Register_psk:
9   [Fr(~ak), Fr(~kdk), Fr(~k)]
10 -->
11   [!Psk_ak('id_s', 'id_p', ~ak), !Psk_kdk('id_s', 'id_p', ~kdk), !
12     Psk_k('id_s', 'dm', ~k)]
13
14 //step1
15 rule Aaa_1:
16   [Fr(~rand_s)]
17 -->
18   [Aaa_1(~rand_s), Out(<'dm', 'id_s', ~rand_s>)]
19
20 //step2
21 rule Dm_1:
22   [In(<'dm', id_s, rand_s>)]
23 -->
24   [Out(<'cmd', id_s, rand_s>)]
25
26 //step3
27 rule Cmd_1:
28   [In(<'cmd', id_s, rand_s>), Fr(~rand_p), !Psk_ak(id_s, 'id_p', ak)]
29 --[CmdAuthReq('id_p', ak)]->
30   [Cmd_1(~rand_p, id_s, rand_s), Out(<'dm', ~rand_p, 'id_p', mac(ak,
31     <'id_p', ~rand_p, id_s, rand_s>))]
32
33 //step4
34 rule Dm_2:
35   [In(<'dm', rand_p, id_p, mac_p>)]
36 -->
37   [Out(<'aaa', rand_p, id_p, mac_p>)]
38
39 //step5
40 rule Aaa_2:
41   [Aaa_1(rand_s), !Psk_ak('id_s', id_p, ak), !Psk_kdk('id_s', id_p,
42     kdk), Fr(~payload), In(<'aaa', rand_p, id_p, mac(ak, <id_p, rand_p,
43     'id_s', rand_s>))] //pattern match checks the mac
44 --[AuthAaa(id_p, ak)]->
45   [Aaa_2(rand_s, hkdf1(rand_p, kdk), hkdf2(rand_p, kdk)), Out(<'dm',
46     mac(ak, <'id_s', rand_p>), ~payload, mac(hkdf1(rand_p, kdk), <~
47     payload, rand_s>))] //computes session and msk keys, stores them

```



```

43 //step6
44 rule Dm_3:
45   [In(<'dm', mac_s, payload, tag>)]
46 -->
47   [Out(<'cmd', mac_s, payload, tag>)]
48
49 //step7
50 rule Cmd_2:
51   [Cmd_1(rand_p, id_s, rand_s), Fr(~payload1), !Psk_ak(id_s, 'id_p',
52     ak), !Psk_kdk(id_s, 'id_p', kdk), In(<'cmd', mac(ak, <id_s, rand_p
53     >), payload, mac(hkdf1(rand_p, kdk), <payload, rand_s>>))]
54 --[AuthCmd(id_s, ak)]->
55   [Out(<'dm', ~payload1, mac(hkdf1(rand_p, kdk), <~payload1, rand_s>
56     >), Cmd_2(rand_p, id_s, rand_s, hkdf1(rand_p, kdk), hkdf2(rand_p,
57     kdk))]
58
59 //step8
60 rule Dm_4:
61   [In(<'dm', payload, tag>)]
62 -->
63   [Out(<'aaa', payload, tag>)]
64
65 //step9
66 rule Aaa_3:
67   [In(<'aaa', payload, mac(eap_sk, <payload, rand_s>>)), Aaa_2(rand_s,
68     eap_sk, msk), !Psk_k('id_s', 'dm', k)]
69 --[Msk_Aaa(msk)]->
70   [Out(<'dm', senc(msk, k)>)]
71
72 //step10
73 rule Dm_5:
74   [In(<'dm', msk_en>), !Psk_k('id_s', 'dm', k)]
75 --[Msk_Dm(sdec(msk_en, k))]->
76   []
77
78 lemma secrecy1:
79 'not(Ex Id k #i #j. AuthAaa(Id, k) @ #i & K(k) @ #j)''
80
81 lemma secrecy2:
82 'not(Ex Id k #i #j. AuthCmd(Id, k) @ #i & K(k) @ #j)''
83
84 lemma secrecy3:
85 'not(Ex k #i #j. Msk_Dm(k) @ #i & K(k) @ #j)''
86
87 lemma secrecy4:
88 'not(Ex k #i #j. Msk_Aaa(k) @ #i & K(k) @ #j)''
89
90 lemma cmd_auth:
91 '(All id k #i. AuthAaa(id, k) @ #i ==> (Ex #j. CmdAuthReq(id, k) @ #j)
92 )'

```



```
87  
88 lemma honest:  
89 exists-trace 'Ex k #i. Msk_Dm(k) @ #i'  
90  
91 end
```

Listing B.4: Device Authentication with EAP-PSK

Appendix C

CVSS attributes

Value		Description	Score	
Base Metric	Attack Vector	Physical (P)	The susceptible system must be physically accessible to the attacker (e.g., firewire attacks).	0.20
		Local (L)	The attacker needs a local account on the target system (e.g., privilege escalation attack).	0.55
		Adjacent (A)	The attacker must have access to the same broadcast or collision domain as the vulnerable system (e.g., ARP spoofing, Bluetooth attacks).	0.62
		Network (N)	The vulnerable interface operates at layer 3 or higher in the OSI network stack, making it remotely exploitable (e.g., remote buffer overflow in a network service).	0.85
	Attack Complexity	High (H)	There are specialized conditions, such a race condition with a small window or a need for social engineering techniques that would be obvious to experienced people.	0.44
		Low (L)	No unique circumstances, such as when the system is accessible to a large number of users or the susceptible configuration is common, exist for exploiting the vulnerability.	0.77
	Privileges Required	High (H)	The exploit involves specialized conditions or social engineering techniques that would be evident to experienced individuals.	0.27
		Low (L)	The vulnerability can be exploited under common circumstances without the need for specialized conditions or user interaction.	0.62
		None (N)	The attacker can initiate the attack without first authenticating.	0.85
	User Interaction	None (N)	The attacker does not need to authenticate in order to initiate the attack.	0.85
		Required (L)	The user must take action in order to successfully exploit this vulnerability before it can be used against them.	0.62

Temporal Metric	Exploit Code Maturity	Not Defined (X)	This value is assigned when there is not enough information to select one of the other values. It has the same scoring impact as assigning the value High and has no effect on the total Temporal Score.	0.0
		Unproven (U)	Either an exploit is hypothetical or there is no exploit code accessible.	0.91
		Proof-Of-Concept (P)	For the majority of systems, an attack demonstration is not feasible even when proof-of-concept exploit code is available. The code or technique may need to be significantly modified by a knowledgeable attacker because it is not always effective.	0.94
		Functional (F)	There is working exploit code available. In most cases when the vulnerability exists, the code functions.	0.97
		High (H)	There is functional autonomous code, no need for an exploit (manual trigger), and information is readily available. Exploit code operates under all circumstances or is actively disseminated by an autonomous agent (such as a worm or virus). Systems linked to the network are susceptible to scanning or exploitation efforts. Exploit development has advanced to the point that automated tools are trustworthy, accessible, and simple to use.	1.0
	Remediation Level	Not Defined (X)	This value is assigned when there is insufficient information to select one of the other values. It has the same scoring impact as assigning Unavailable and has no effect on the overall Temporal Score.	0.0
		Official Fix (O)	There is a full vendor solution available. Either an official fix has been released by the vendor, or an upgrade is available.	0.95
		Temporary Fix (T)	There is a legitimate, short-term treatment available. Instances where the vendor releases a temporary patch, tool, or workaround are included in this.	0.96
		Workaround (W)	Unofficial, non-vendor solutions are accessible. Some users of the impacted technology will develop their own patches, offer solutions to get around the issue, or take other actions to minimize it.	0.97
		Unavailable (U)	Either there isn't a solution, or applying it is impossible.	1.0
	Report Confidence	Not Defined (X)	This value is assigned when there is not enough information to select one of the other values. It has the same scoring impact as Confirmed and has no effect on the total Temporal Score.	0.0
		Unknown (U)	Impacts have been reported, which suggests a vulnerability exists. The reports claim that the vulnerability's cause is unknown, or that the cause or effects of the vulnerability may vary between studies.	0.92

		Reasonable (R)	Substantial information is made public, but researchers lack complete confidence in the underlying cause or lack access to the source code necessary to thoroughly verify all of the interactions that may have contributed to the outcome. Yet, there is a reasonable level of confidence that the defect can be reproduced and that at least one impact can be validated (proof-of-concept exploits may provide this).	0.96
		Confirmed (C)	There are detailed reports available, or a working reproduction is feasible (functional exploits may provide this). The researcher’s claims can be independently verified with access to the source code, or the vulnerability has been confirmed by the creator or vendor of the affected code.	1.0
Environmental Metric	C.I.A. Triad	Not Defined (X)	This value is assigned when there is not enough information to select one of the other values. Assigning this value has the same scoring impact as applying the value Medium and has no effect on the overall Environmental Score.	0.0
		Low (L)	The organisation or those connected to the organization will certainly suffer catastrophic consequences if [Confidentiality — Integrity — Availability] are lost (e.g., employees, customers).	0.5
		Medium (M)	The organisation or those connected to the organization will certainly suffer catastrophic consequences if [Confidentiality — Integrity — Availability] are lost (e.g., employees, customers).	0.5
		High (H)	The organisation or those connected to the organization are likely to experience just a little negative impact from the loss of [Confidentiality — Integrity — Availability] (e.g., employees, customers).	1.5

Table C.1: CVSS v3.1 characteristics

Appendix D

Examples of eMUD profiles

Device-Level eMUD

```
{
  "ietf-mud:mud": {
    "mud-version": 1,
    "mud-url": "http://localhost/device_eMud_Entrust.json",
    "mud-hash-url": "Hash of device MUD file to check the integrity of the file",
    "last-update": "2024-06-20T12:00:00Z",
    "cache-validity": 48,
    "is-supported": true,
    "systeminfo": "IoT device - temperature sensor",
    "mfg-name": "Device Manufacturer",
    "documentation": "http://localhost/device_documentation",
    "model-name": "TempSensorX",
    "software-rev": "1.0.0",
    "firmware-rev": "1.0.0",
    "Security-Properties": {
      "OS": {
        "OS_name": "Linux",
        "OS_distro": "Debian",
        "OS_version": "10"
      },
      "CPU": {
        "type": "ARM Cortex-A53",
        "cores": 4
      },
      "RAM": {
        "size": "512MB"
      },
      "Crypto": {
        "Alg": "AES",
        "type": "Symmetric",
        "key_size": "256"
      },
      "Network": {
        "Open_port": [80, 443]
      }
    }
  }
}
```



```

},
"weaknesses": [
  {
    "id": "weakness-1",
    "name": "Hardcoded Credentials",
    "description": "The device uses hardcoded credentials for initial setup.",
    "date": "2024-06-19",
    "likelihood": "High",
    "risk": "Critical",
    "cvss": 9.8
  }
],
"vulnerabilities": [
  {
    "id": "vuln-1",
    "name": "Buffer Overflow",
    "description": "The device firmware is susceptible to a buffer overflow vulnerability.",
    "date": "2024-06-18",
    "likelihood": "Medium",
    "risk": "High",
    "cvss": 7.5
  }
],
"Threat-mitigation": [
  {
    "type": "course-of-action",
    "id": "coa--device-1",
    "action": "Apply Vendor-Supplied Patch for vuln-1",
    "description": "Apply the vendor-supplied patch or update for vuln-1 to mitigate the buffer overflow vulnerability.",
    "objective": "Mitigate the risk of exploitation and unauthorized access",
    "target_ref": "vuln-1"
  }
],
"evidence-requirements": [
  {
    "type": "log",
    "description": "Device operation logs for last 24 hours"
  },
  {
    "type": "configuration",
    "description": "Current device configuration"
  }
],
"trust-policy-hashes": [
  {
    "type": "SHA-256",
    "hash": "abc123...xyz"
  }
],
"from-device-policy": {
  "access-lists": {

```



```

    "access-list": [
      {
        "name": "mud-id-device-fr"
      }
    ]
  },
  "to-device-policy": {
    "access-lists": {
      "access-list": [
        {
          "name": "mud-id-device-to"
        }
      ]
    }
  },
  "ietf-access-control-list:acls": {
    "acl": [
      {
        "name": "mud-id-device-fr",
        "type": "ipv4-acl-type",
        "aces": {
          "ace": [
            {
              "name": "device-to-internet",
              "matches": {
                "13": {
                  "ipv4": {
                    "protocol": "tcp",
                    "src-port": "any",
                    "dst-port": [80, 443]
                  }
                }
              },
              "actions": {
                "forwarding": "accept"
              }
            }
          ]
        }
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "name": "mud-id-device-to",
    "type": "ipv4-acl-type",
    "aces": {
      "ace": [
        {
          "name": "internet-to-device",
          "matches": {
            "13": {
              "ipv4": {
                "protocol": "tcp",
                "src-port": "any",

```



```
        "dst-port": [80, 443]
      }
    }
  },
  "actions": {
    "forwarding": "accept"
  }
}
]
}
]
}
}
}
```


Domain-Level eMUD

```
{
  "ietf-mud:mud": {
    "mud-version": 1,
    "mud-url": "http://localhost/domain_eMud_Entrust.json",
    "mud-hash-url": "Hash of domain MUD file to check the integrity of the file",
    "last-update": "2024-06-20T12:00:00Z",
    "cache-validity": 48,
    "is-supported": true,
    "systeminfo": "Healthcare network devices",
    "mfg-name": "Domain Manufacturer",
    "documentation": "http://localhost/domain_documentation",
    "model-name": "HealthcareNetwork",
    "software-rev": "1.0.0",
    "firmware-rev": "1.0.0",
    "Security-Properties": {
      "OS": {
        "OS_name": "Linux",
        "OS_distro": "Ubuntu",
        "OS_version": "20.04"
      },
      "CPU": {
        "type": "Intel Xeon",
        "cores": 8
      },
      "RAM": {
        "size": "16GB"
      },
      "Crypto": {
        "Alg": "RSA",
        "type": "Asymmetric",
        "key_size": "2048"
      },
      "Network": {
        "Open_port": [22, 443]
      }
    },
    "weaknesses": [
      {
        "id": "weakness-1",
        "name": "Weak Encryption Protocols",
        "description": "The network uses outdated encryption protocols.",
        "date": "2024-06-19",
        "likelihood": "Medium",
        "risk": "High",
        "cvss": 6.8
      }
    ],
    "vulnerabilities": [
      {
        "id": "vuln-1",
        "name": "SQL Injection",
```



```

    "description": "The web application is vulnerable to SQL injection.",
    "date": "2024-06-18",
    "likelihood": "High",
    "risk": "Critical",
    "cvss": 9.0
  }
],
"Threat-mitigation": [
  {
    "type": "course-of-action",
    "id": "coa--domain-1",
    "action": "Apply Vendor-Supplied Patch for vuln-1",
    "description": "Apply the vendor-supplied patch or update for vuln-1 to mitigate the SQL i
    "objective": "Mitigate the risk of exploitation and unauthorized access",
    "target_ref": "vuln-1"
  }
],
"evidence-requirements": [
  {
    "type": "log",
    "description": "Network operation logs for last 24 hours"
  },
  {
    "type": "configuration",
    "description": "Current network configuration"
  }
],
"trust-policies": [
  {
    "policy": "Network devices must use strong encryption protocols."
  }
],
"domain-specific-threats": [
  {
    "threat": "Insider Threats",
    "description": "Potential threats originating from within the organization."
  }
],
"from-device-policy": {
  "access-lists": {
    "access-list": [
      {
        "name": "mud-id-domain-fr"
      }
    ]
  }
},
"to-device-policy": {
  "access-lists": {
    "access-list": [
      {
        "name": "mud-id-domain-to"
      }
    ]
  }
}

```


}
}

Appendix E

Threat Modeling and Software Verification

Threat Modeling

```

1 {
2   "cpe": "cpe:2.3:o:cisco:ios_xe:16.12:*:*:*:*:*:*:*:*:*:*",
3   "id": "Device-1",
4   "name": "Device-name",
5   "vulnerabilities": [
6     {
7       "cpes": [
8         "cpe:2.3:o:cisco:ios_xe:*:*:*:*:*:*:*:*:*",
9         "cpe:2.3:o:cisco:ios_xe:*:*:*:*:*:*:*:*:*",
10        "cpe:2.3:o:cisco:ios_xe:*:*:*:*:*:*:*:**"
11      ],
12      "cvss_vector": [
13        "CVSS:3.1/AV:N/AC:L/PR:H/UI:N/S:U/C:H/I:H/A:H"
14      ],
15      "description": "A vulnerability in the web UI feature of Cisco
16        IOS XE Software could allow an authenticated, remote
17        attacker to inject commands with the privileges of root.
18        This vulnerability is due to insufficient input validation.
19        An attacker could exploit this vulnerability by sending
20        crafted input to the web UI. A successful exploit could
21        allow the attacker to inject commands to the underlying
22        operating system with root privileges.",
23      "id": "CVE-2023-20273",
24      "name": "Threat-name",
25      "threats": [
26        {
27          "attributes": [
28            {
29              "key": "capec",
30              "value": [
31                "108",
32                "15",
33                "43",

```



```
27         "6",
28         "88"
29     ]
30 },
31 {
32     "key": "mitigations",
33     "value": [
34         "If at all possible, use library calls rather than
35         external processes to recreate the desired
36         functionality.",
37         "For any data that will be used to generate a
38         command to be executed, keep as much of that data
39         out of external control as possible. For example,
40         in web applications, this may require storing the
41         data locally in the session's state instead of
42         sending it out to the client in a hidden form
43         field.",
44         "For any security checks that are performed on the
45         client side, ensure that these checks are
46         duplicated on the server side, in order to avoid
47         CWE-602. Attackers can bypass the client-side
48         checks by modifying values after the checks have
49         been performed, or by changing the client to
50         remove the client-side checks entirely. Then,
51         these modified values would be submitted to the
52         server.",
53         "While it is risky to use dynamically-generated
54         query strings, code, or commands that mix control
55         and data together, sometimes it may be unavoidable
56         . Properly quote arguments and escape any special
57         characters within those arguments. The most
58         conservative approach is to escape or filter all
59         characters that do not pass an extremely strict
60         allowlist (such as everything that is not
61         alphanumeric or white space). If some special
62         characters are still needed, such as white space,
63         wrap each argument in quotes after the escaping/
64         filtering step. Be careful of argument injection (
65         CWE-88).",
66         "If the program to be executed allows arguments to
67         be specified within an input file or from standard
68         input, then consider using that mode to pass
69         arguments instead of the command line.",
70         "When the set of acceptable objects, such as
71         filenames or URLs, is limited or known, create a
72         mapping from a set of fixed input values (such as
73         numeric IDs) to the actual filenames or URLs, and
74         reject all other inputs.",
75         "Run the code in an environment that performs
76         automatic taint propagation and prevents any
```



```

command execution that uses tainted variables ,
such as Perl's \"-T\" switch. This will force the
program to perform validation steps that remove
the taint, although you must be careful to
correctly validate your inputs so that you do not
accidentally mark dangerous inputs as untainted (
see CWE-183 and CWE-184).",
41 "Run the code in an environment that performs
automatic taint propagation and prevents any
command execution that uses tainted variables ,
such as Perl's \"-T\" switch. This will force the
program to perform validation steps that remove
the taint, although you must be careful to
correctly validate your inputs so that you do not
accidentally mark dangerous inputs as untainted (
see CWE-183 and CWE-184).",
42 "Use runtime policy enforcement to create an
allowlist of allowable commands, then prevent use
of any command that does not appear in the
allowlist. Technologies such as AppArmor are
available to do this.",
43 "Use an application firewall that can detect attacks
against this weakness. It can be beneficial in
cases in which the code cannot be fixed (because
it is controlled by a third party), as an
emergency prevention measure while more
comprehensive software assurance measures are
applied, or to provide defense in depth.",
44 "Run your code using the lowest privileges that are
required to accomplish the necessary tasks [REF
-76]. If possible, create isolated accounts with
limited privileges that are only used for a single
task. That way, a successful attack will not
immediately give the attacker access to the rest
of the software or its environment. For example,
database applications rarely need to run as the
database administrator, especially in day-to-day
operations.",
45 "When using PHP, configure the application so that
it does not use register_globals. During
implementation, develop the application so that it
does not rely on this feature, but be wary of
implementing a register_globals emulation that is
subject to weaknesses such as CWE-95, CWE-621, and
similar issues."
46 ]
47 }
48 ],
49 "description": [
50 " ",

```



```

51     "1. Remote Authenticated Attack: An attacker could
        exploit this vulnerability by sending crafted input to
        the web UI, potentially leading to injection of
        malicious commands with root privileges. This could
        allow the attacker to gain unauthorized access to
        sensitive information or disrupt system operations.",
52     "2. Local Privilege Escalation: An attacker with low-
        privileged access to the system could exploit this
        vulnerability to inject malicious commands,
        potentially leading to elevation of their privileges
        to root level. This could allow the attacker to
        perform malicious actions with increased access and
        control over the system.",
53     "3. Denial of Service (DoS): An attacker could exploit
        this vulnerability to inject malicious commands that
        consume excessive system resources, potentially
        leading to a denial of service attack. This could
        cause the system to become unavailable or slow,
        disrupting critical operations and services.",
54     "4. Command Injection with Persistence: An attacker
        could exploit this vulnerability to inject malicious
        commands with persistence, allowing them to maintain
        access to the system even after a reboot or system
        update. This could provide the attacker with long-term
        access and control over the system.",
55     "5. Combination with Other Vulnerabilities: An attacker
        could combine this vulnerability with other known
        vulnerabilities in the system, potentially leading to
        more severe attacks and exploitation. For example, an
        attacker could use this vulnerability in conjunction
        with a command injection vulnerability in another
        component of the system, allowing them to inject
        malicious commands with increased effectiveness."
56 ],
57 "id": "Threat-1",
58 "name": "Improper Neutralization of Special Elements used
        in an OS Command ('OS Command Injection')"
59 }
60 ]
61 }
62 ]
63 }

```

Listing E.1: Threat model of a Cisco router

Software Verification

```

1  {
2    "yara_results": {
3      "glassrat": [
4        {
5          "rule_description": "Detects win.glassrat.",
6          "rule_name": "glassrat"
7        }
8      ]
9    }
10 }

```

Listing E.2: Detection of glassRAT using Software Verification

```

1  {
2    "afl_results": {
3      "crashes": [
4        "aP8AAAAAZH9mAAD/AGQA/0w="
5      ],
6      "total_crashes": 1
7    }
8 }

```

Listing E.3: AFL results with input encoded using base64

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